

MEN4DEM

EUROPEAN CONTEXTS OF SOCIALIZATION INTO (ANTI-)DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES

AUTHORS

FRANCESCA TOMATIS, UNIVERSITY OF BERGAMO

VERA LOMAZZI, UNIVERSITY OF BERGAMO

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- Authors:** Francesca Tomatis is post-doc researcher in sociology at the University of Bergamo (IT)
Vera Lomazzi is associate professor of sociology at the University of Bergamo (IT)
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MEN4DEM

ABOUT MEN4DEM

MEN4DEM (2025-2027) is an innovative collaborative co-creation project that involves six partner universities as well as a theatre group and a gender justice organization. The consortium studies various manifestations of masculinities in politics. Based on mixture of academic, activist and artistic knowledge MEN4DEM will develop concrete tools to support democratic masculinities in Europe. The project was funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant number 101177356). The project website is: www.men4dem.eu.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czechia
DE	Germany
DK	Denmark
EE	Estonia
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EL	Greece
ES	Spain
ESS	European Social Survey
EU	European Union
FI	Finland
FR	France
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
ILGA	International Lesbian and Gay Association
IT	Italy
LGBTQI+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer and Intersex people (the “+” includes other sexual orientations and gender identities not explicitly listed)
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
MEN4DEM	Masculinities for the Future of European Democracy
MIPEX	Migrant Integration Policy Index
MPs	Members of Parliament
MT	Malta
NL	Netherlands
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PL	Poland
PPS	Purchasing power standards
PT	Portugal

RO	Romania
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SIGI	Social Institutions and Gender Index
SK	Slovakia
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report focuses on the macro-level factors that can potentially explain adherence to (anti-) democratic gender norms, particularly anti-democratic masculinity, as the result of socialization processes. It provides an overview of the social, cultural, and legal norms in Europe, useful for understanding how they relate to gender roles.

Our framework identifies seven dimensions influencing these processes: (1) socioeconomic structure and inequalities; (2) adherence to European values and attitudes towards Europe; (3) gender norms; (4) gender-based violence and institutional response; (5) political dimension; (6) digitalization and online behaviour; and (7) youth agency. Together, these dimensions capture how structural conditions, political climates, and cultural practices interact to (re)produce either inclusive or exclusionary masculine repertoires defining prevailing cultural norms in the EU27 contexts of socialization.

Building on detailed descriptions of country profiles, the report shows how contexts of socialization vary within Europe but also highlights commonalities across national contexts. By mapping support for gender equality and liberal democracy, the report identifies three clusters of countries that suggest different lines of intervention. In contexts marked by hierarchical gender norms, authoritarian preferences, and socioeconomic vulnerabilities such as Hungary, Poland, or Cyprus, measures to reduce economic, educational, territorial, and digital divides, alongside strengthened civic education, are crucial to foster more democratic masculinities. In countries where democratic institutions and egalitarian norms coexist with tensions or slower change, like Italy, Greece, or Slovakia, interventions should focus on reducing internal disparities, bolstering institutional trust, and reinforcing inclusive public discourses to counter polarization. In the most egalitarian and democratic countries, such among which Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany, the challenge lies in sustaining achievements—ensuring welfare systems, education, and gender-equality infrastructures remain resilient, while preventing backlash or disinformation from undermining progress.

By providing both national specificities and broader European patterns, the report offers comparative scholars a framework for explanatory and causal studies, practitioners guidance for culturally and structurally sensitive interventions, and policymakers a theory- and data-driven account of social and political dimensions vital to advancing democratic societies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bjarnegård and Mügge (2025) point out that understanding how authoritarian masculinity ideals spread within mainstream political leadership, political party youth wings, and broader public attitudes is crucial for counteracting these trends and intervening to promote democratic models of masculinity. But how do (anti-)democratic masculinities develop as socially accepted models? And how are individuals socialized into anti-democratic masculinities? What societal factors and mechanisms help to explain the conditions under which democratic models of masculinity can instead be fostered? In this respect, are European contexts all the same, or do they present different challenges?

With these fundamental questions in mind, the report provides crucial information on the European contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. We use the term “anti-democratic masculinities” to refer to those forms of masculinity that legitimize unequal gender relations and justify, or even amplify, anti-democratic behaviours such as hostile sexism, homophobia, and support for violence or authoritarianism (Blake and Denson 2017; Mahalik et al. 2003; Kennedy-Kollar 2024; Bjarnegård and Mügge 2025). As these forms of masculinity have often been identified in the ideologies of far-right movements and in the manosphere¹ with negative implication for democracy (Holm 2024; Kennedy-Kollar 2024; Botto and Gottzén 2024; Linders et al. 2023), it is relevant to reflect on the societal context in which these masculine norms, also beyond these specific environments, can be transmitted and spread.

The report provides a collection of country profiles aimed at describing, from a multidimensional perspective, the societal context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities in the 27 European Union member countries (EU27). In addition, it underlines differences and commonalities among the analyzed national contexts, to identify common paths across European countries. It provides readers with tools for understanding the specificity of each national context and the general patterns in Europe.

¹ The “manosphere” consist of a constellation of online groups that share a common core ideology that predicates the rejection of feminist paradigms and a reaffirmation of essentialist gender binaries, wherein masculinity is framed as both embattled and inherently dominant (Kennedy-Kollar 2024)

The report is relevant for policy-makers, academics, and practitioners. Policymakers can count on a theory- and data-driven description to identify, at the national and European level, social and political dimensions that appear to be crucial for the development of more democratic societies. The report comprises critical information for scholars interested in comparative studies, who can refer to the framework here proposed to design explanatory and causal studies, and for practitioners who need to consider the cultural and structural contexts for their interventions.

The report is articulated in six sections. Following the introductory section, we introduce the concept of socialization. In particular, we refer to the constructivist approach to socialization, according to which gender and masculinities are socially constructed through social interactions among individuals and between individuals and social structures (Berger and Luckmann 1966; Giddens 1984; 1991; Wharton 2005). The social interactions take place at multiple levels, from the micro-level of interaction among individuals and intergroup dynamics, to the meso-levels of institutions, to the macro-level of societal context. The macro-level is of specific interest to this report. The third section addresses the theoretical framework used to disentangle the roles of the social opportunity structure and the cultural dimension in socialization processes and explains the multidimensional perspective used to describe the EU27 national contexts of socialization. It makes explicit the multidimensional nature of the societal context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. In this section, we outline aspects belonging to the culture and to the structure of society, two intertwined dimensions that concur in the provision of opportunities for individual self-realization, and in the legitimation of social norms, including masculine gender norms (Giddens 1984; 1991; Wharton 2005).

The fourth section presents the methodological approach and strategy. After introducing the key contextual dimensions examined, we detail the desk-research strategy we used to develop country profiles of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities in the EU27. This section explains how we identified, selected, and reviewed indicators and presents the approach we used to detect cross-national patterns. Building on our multidimensional framework and on the detailed overview of the country profiles of the EU27² in which socialization into (anti-)

² The detailed overview of the EU27 country profiles is available in Annex I

democratic masculinities takes place, the fifth section illustrates how European countries differ by contextual dimensions.

The sixth section explores possible common paths of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities, focusing on European patterns. Indicators of gender equality and support for liberal democracy were used to identify potential groups of countries. For these potential groups of countries, other relevant indicators were scrutinized to underline cultural and structural convergencies in contributing to the context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. Finally, although this report does not address a specific policy area, it provides remarks on the contextual aspects that require more attention in specific regional and/or national contexts to be able to intervene and counteract, also with policy interventions, to support socialization into more democratic masculinities.

2. SOCIALIZATION INTO (ANTI-)DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES: A CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH

Socialization is a never-ending process in which individuals negotiate, internalize and interpret social norms, including masculine gender norms. These norms shape how individuals behave in public and private life, hence influencing whether democratic or anti-democratic attitudes take hold. These norms are reinforced or challenged through daily interactions, as such, the construction of (anti-) democratic masculinities is not fixed but shaped by the environments individuals move through. Daily interactions do not only concern interindividual dynamics. Policies, for example, can shape everyday socialization by embedding democratic values and inclusive gender norms into schools, workplaces, families, and public spaces. They can do this through education reforms, inclusive parenting programs and policies, workplace equality measures, and community initiatives that challenge discriminatory and exclusionary social norms. In this section, we define the process of socialization and why it is relevant for understanding how (anti-)democratic masculinities develop.

Socialization is the link between the social world of norms, values, and relationships between roles and the individual world of identity construction. Through socialization processes, individuals learn norms, values, and behaviors that are considered appropriate in the social context of belonging. They also develop the ability to function as members of larger social groups and become active actors in transmitting social norms themselves. In other words, they participate in the process of cultural (re)production (Berger and Luckmann 1966).

Socialization has two main forms: primary and secondary. Primary socialization refers to the very first socialization that individuals face during childhood and through which they become members of society. Secondary socialization refers to any other process that introduces already socialized individuals into new sectors of their societies (Berger and Luckmann 1966). They are both crucial processes in the transmission of democratic social norms. While primary socialization mainly involves the family, the key players in secondary socialization processes are peer groups, schools, and workplaces. In both cases, socialization processes take place in a specific sociohistorical context that shapes social norms with regard to

masculinity and democratic behavior. Policies and institutional framework are therefore paramount for defining contexts promoting democratic masculinities.

But how do these mechanisms work? How can children learn democratic gender norms and how adults can challenge or perpetuate norms interiorized during childhood? Primary socialization is crucial to learn social norms and values. Conformity dynamics are important in the transmission and interiorization of social norms. Social expectations and social control mechanisms implemented by parents (or other adults of reference) play a key role in the regulation of expected and desirable behaviors—also concerning gender aspects. If in a family the distribution of tasks, as for example the division of paid work and unpaid care work, is strongly marked by a traditional gendered separation, this gender norm influences what children of that family perceive as the expected role for a man and for a woman. Gender socialization is a relevant part of socialization, and it consists of processes related to the transmission of gender norms and the expected conformity to them.

“Gender norms” refer to the norms and values guiding people in their behavior about gender relations and providing gender role expectations (Lomazzi 2023a). Since their first period of life, children tend to conform in order to assume those qualities and characteristics that their parents (and, more generally, society) expect from them as girls or boys (Wharton 2005). Through the process of gender socialization, gender expectations transmitted during childhood and adolescence assume a strong normative power, influencing the individual’s development of gender identity and the identification and interiorization of socially approved forms of femininity and masculinity. Harmful or exclusionary expectations regarding gender roles, especially men’s role, can therefore solidify at very early stage of life.

To the child, the norms and values transmitted by parents appear to be the expression of the only existing world and not just one of the possible ways of interpreting the world. According to Berger and Luckmann (1966), this is why norms internalized during primary socialization tend to be firmly rooted in people’s value systems. Hence, models of masculinity and gender roles transmitted and internalized during the formative years tend to be quite stable (Adler et al. 1992; Cunningham 2001). However, they can be challenged, or crystallized, through secondary socialization. Typical agents of secondary socialization include peer groups, educational institutions, religious institutions, workplaces, mass media, government, and legal systems.

One of the main functions of secondary socialization is to allow individuals to become more specialized social actors. At the same time, entering into contact with multiple social worlds can introduce ideals, norms, and values that can reinforce those already internalized or challenge them because of the different phases of individuals' cognitive development and critical thinking (Brim 1966). Coming into contact with different gender norms and models of relationships between masculinity and femininity stimulates a process of interaction between the individual and society that results in a (re)interpretation and (re)production of the gender norms learned in primary socialization (Thébaud and Pedulla 2016).

From this perspective, (anti-)democratic masculinities are socially constructed and result from a continuous and interactive process of socialization. This is precisely what makes masculinities malleable and open to policy intervention, or that they can be transformed. Secondary socialization as well as “resocialization”, a deeper process that involves renouncing former behavioral patterns and adopting new ones, can substantially challenge anti-democratic masculinities and contribute to transforming anti-democratic masculinities into more democratic forms of masculinity. In this perspective, interventions that reframe masculinity by fostering models of masculinity based on empathy, emotional expression, and mutual respect, as those documented in the MEN4DEM reports (Schaaf and Mars 2025; Besta et al. 2025), can be therefore very effective.

A constructivist perspective on socialization emphasizes its dynamic nature and the active role of individuals in engaging with social structures (Giddens 1984; Risman 2004; Ridgeway and Smith-Lovin 1999). Identity formation and integration into society emerge through multidimensional daily interactions with social actors, institutions, and broader contexts, in which individuals both interpret and reshape cultural meanings. The relationship between individual and society is reciprocal: our actions are shaped by structural features of the societies in which we live, while simultaneously re-creating and, to some extent, transforming those structures through our behavior (Giddens 1984). Understanding this dynamic is essential for understanding how masculinities develop as part of the broader social construction of gender. As West and Zimmerman (1987) describe in their notion of “Doing gender,” masculinity is a routine accomplishment produced and reproduced through everyday practices and institutional settings. Gender, therefore, is not a fixed identity but a

plurality of socially constructed forms continuously enacted and negotiated in social interaction.

Socialization processes operate simultaneously at multiple levels:

- Micro-level: daily interactions among individuals;
- Meso-level: groups and institutions (e.g., family, schools, workplaces, religious communities, and peer groups);
- Macro level: laws, societal structure, and prevailing cultural orientation.

At the aggregate level, these processes ensure social continuity and social change. By transmitting values, ideals, and behavioral models to new members of society, socialization allows for reproduction, even though its composition changes continuously with the death and birth of individuals. At the same time, the dynamics of fertility and mortality result in cohort replacement through which each society can renew itself, generation by generation, because new individuals, socialized in different sociohistorical periods, interact with the contemporary cultural heritage and interpret and reproduce it in a new way (Ryder 1965).

As societies develop through unique sociohistorical pathways, the contexts in which socialization occurs differ across Europe. The next section presents a multi-dimensional framework for analyzing macro-level factors that shape how (anti-)democratic masculinities develop in the EU27.

3. A MULTIDIMENSIONAL PERSPECTIVE TO DESCRIBE THE EU27 NATIONAL CONTEXTS OF SOCIALIZATION INTO (ANTI-)DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES

Daily interactions driving socialization do not happen in a vacuum: the societal context shapes the content of norms, values, and models transmitted. A multidimensional perspective that includes both structural and cultural elements is relevant to reading the national contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities.

The context in which primary and secondary socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities occur plays a crucial role in defining cultural orientation to masculinity and democracy. For example, people's beliefs regarding the role of men as caregivers depend not only on their interpretation of male roles in society but also on the family and gender norms in their families of origin and on the social acceptance of caring masculinity among the group of peers. In addition, policies that favor the caring role of men, for example, by providing statutory paternity and parental leaves, contribute both to providing structural opportunities for men to act on their caring role and to culturally legitimate it, transmitting therefore a caring masculine gender norm (Sjöberg 2004; Doucet 2017; Hipp and Bünning 2021). In this report, we focus on the macro-level context as it provides structural and cultural coordinates for understanding the dynamics taking place at lower levels of social contexts. It is also where the content of gender norms, masculinities, and democratic stands that are transmitted to individuals through primary and secondary socialization can best be understood/found/examined. When referring to the macro-level context of socialization, we need to consider that each society consists of structural and cultural components that are intertwined in a circular process and interact with individuals' agencies (Lomazzi 2023a; 2016; Wharton 2005).

The cultural dimension refers to the norms and values that guide the actions of social actors. For example, it includes the prevailing cultural orientation toward democracy and gender equality in a certain society. Scholars use the term "gender culture" to indicate the system of values and models that people use as an orientation for their behavior in relation to gender dynamics (Aboim 2010; Pfau-Effinger 1998).

The structural component of society concerns aspects such as the systems of education, economy, and demography, which shape the structure of living conditions in that specific society. In addition, policies and welfare systems are crucial elements of the opportunity structure, which is the organized system of opportunities that makes it possible for social actors to pursue their goals (Latorre-Catalán 2017). The term “gender regime” specifically refers to the system of rules, legal norms, and institutions that structures how gender operates in a certain society (Walby 2020; Pascall and Lewis 2004).

Cultural and structural dimensions reciprocally influence each other. Values and norms define political priorities when developing policies, but at the same time, policies have a normative effect, as they legitimate social roles and behaviors. For example, family and work policies supporting the dual role of worker and caregiver of both parents are inspired by the principle of gender equality; at the same time, by making the dual role for men and women possible through an opportunity structure, they legitimate that social role (Wharton 2005; Lomazzi 2016). The interplay between gender culture and the gender regime defines the specific gender order that exists in a certain society in a given historical moment (Connell 2002). Similarly, social norms and values supporting democracy, as well as structural components of society expressing (or challenging) it, contribute to the definition of the broader structural and cultural system in which individuals are socialized into (anti-)democratic masculinities. Understanding how European contexts of socialization shape these processes is therefore crucial for interventions aiming at fostering more democratic societies.

As European societies express different social structures and cultures concerning gender and democracy, this report focuses on the national contexts of socialization and describes them from a multidimensional perspective. In particular, as displayed in

Figure 1 Multidimensional perspective to describe the contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities, it considers seven dimensions that we expect to be relevant in shaping the context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities: 1) socioeconomic structure, 2) institutional adherence to European values and prevailing orientations towards European institutions, 3) prevailing gender norms and attitudes, 4) gender-based violence and institutional response, 5) political dimension, 6) digitalization and online behavior, and 7) youth inclusion and agency. In the following sections, we describe our approach to the analysis of the context of socialization.

Figure 1 Multidimensional perspective to describe the contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities

4. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH AND STRATEGY USED IN THIS REPORT

Using secondary data from international sources, this report adopts a descriptive approach to provide an overview of country profiles and to identify patterns across European countries. To achieve this, we followed an analytical strategy organized into three main steps. (1) In the first step, we operationalized the concepts into measurable indicators, reviewed and selected existing indicators, and organized the selected information. (2) In the second step, we used the retrieved secondary data to describe the national context of socialization into (anti-) democratic masculinities following a standardized structure. (3) In the third step, we tried to identify patterns within Europe by exploring differences and commonalities. Table 1 outlines the strategy undertaken.

Table 1 Strategy used to design the report

Step 1: Conceptual definition of the main contextual dimensions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of seven dimensions of the societal contexts that can be relevant to socialization into (anti-) democratic masculinities. - Discussion of a preliminary list of indicators with the MEN4DEM partners to finalize the selection with their suggestions. - Conceptual definition of the dimensions, including the identification of subdimensions to guide the empirical operationalization in indicators. 	
Step 2: From concept to indicators	
2.1 Review of existing indicators to cover each dimension	<p>Review of existing indicators to cover each dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review of indicators to conceptually cover each of the seven dimensions and the related subdimensions. <p>Consulted sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For information on structural components of the societal contexts: OECD and Eurostat population databases, reports from the Freedom House, World Justice Project, European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), ILGA-Europe, Varieties of Democracy, and Migrant Integration Policy Index. - For information on prevailing cultural orientations: Eurobarometer, European Social Survey, the European Values Study, the International Social Survey Programme, and the World Values Survey.
2.2 Selection of indicators	<p>All the sources reviewed potentially provide multiple indicators to describing the topics of our interest. To reduce complexity, we selected a subset of indicators for each dimension following three main criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Conceptual relevance: we prioritized indicators closer to the key concepts identified in the definition of the dimension. b) Country coverage: we selected indicators available for all the EU27 or for most of them. c) Time relevance: we selected the most recent data available for each country/indicator. <p>The final number of indicators for each dimension resulting from this process is as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socioeconomic structure and inequalities: 21 • European values and attitudes toward Europe: 10 • Gender norms: 20 • Gender-based violence and institutional response: 7 • Political dimension: 12 • Digitalization and online behavior: 7 • Youth agency: 5

	The complete list and country coverage are available in Appendix I.
2.3 Data organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data retrieval and download of the related databases. - Organization of the selected information into a new dataset to facilitate descriptive analysis and comparison. - Data processing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o data from statistical offices or indexes provided by international agencies we used the same information as provided (no further processing). o information from population surveys: we recoded the variables with several response categories to obtain more compact figures. For example, for agreement questions with answer categories such as “Agree strongly”, “Agree”, “Disagree”, and “Strongly Disagree”, we recoded them in the dichotomy Agree/Disagree and used the percentages of respondents to one of the categories as indicators. Annex I provides details of the indicators used in each case.
Step 3: Draft of country profiles	
<p>Design of country profiles to describing the context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each profile follows the same standardized structure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o It builds on the secondary data retrieved to describe the contextual dimensions separately. o A conclusive paragraph summarizes the more salient information that characterizes the specific context of socialization. <p>To ease the reading of the report, the detailed country profiles are available in Annex I, at the end of the report.</p>	
Step 4: Differences and Commonalities Identification of potential patterns within Europe	
<p>Based on the analysis of the national contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities (Annex I), we provide two synthetic overviews:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Differences across European contexts by dimension <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of key indicators from step 2.2 for each dimension. Criteria selection to reduce complexity: indicator’s ability to perform as a proxy for broader contextual configuration. - Visualization countries’ figures through graphs to describe contextual differences by subdimensions - Provision of a short overview by dimension to show outliers and specific distributions. b) Common pattern within Europe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific goal: Focus on two crucial aspects of democracy and gender equality to analyze whether European cultural contexts cluster consistently - The mapping is based on the analysis of correlations between: 1) the structural indicators of the Quality of Democracy and the Gender Equality Index; 2) sexist orientations in public opinion and the share of respondents who self-positioned themselves at the far-right extreme of the left-right scale (source: European Social Survey); 3) gender norms and the preference for an authoritarian political leader (source: European Values Study). - Use scatter plots to visualize the correlations and clustering. - Connecting the resulting clusters with crucial features of the contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities that emerged in the national profiles. 	

In our strategy, the identification of subdimensions and their related indicators was crucial (Step 2 in Table 1). In

Table 2 we summarize the subdimensions for each one of the seven dimensions that belong to our multidimensional approach and report the number of indicators selected to observe each dimension. Annex I displays details for each indicator used in this report. In 4.1 we then

describe in a more detailed way each dimension and explain its relevance for socialization context into (anti)-democratic masculinities.

Table 2 Summary of subdimensions considered and number of indicators used by dimensions

Dimension	Subdimensions	Total number of indicators
Socioeconomic structure and inequalities	Economic structure and inequality Access to welfare and paternity leave schemes Education Demographic and spatial distribution	21
European values and attitudes toward Europe	Democracy and governance Gender equality and institutional discrimination Pluralism and inclusion Trust in European institutions and democratic legitimacy Attitudes toward European integration	10
Gender norms	Gender role attitudes in the domestic and in the private sphere Hostile sexism and benevolent sexism Opinion about women in leadership position Masculine gender norms Anti-gender equality views	20
Gender-based violence and institutional response	Prevalence of gender-based violence Awareness of gender-based violence Institutional responsiveness Legal framework	7
Political dimension	Electoral participation and behavior Trust in political institutions Interest and attitudes toward politics Polarization Political violence	12
Digitalization and online behavior	Internet use Trust in digital media Misinformation Spread of the manosphere	7
Youth agency	Structural dimension Youth perception and evaluation of their environment	5

4.1 CONCEPTUAL AND EMPIRICAL DEFINITION OF THE CONTEXTUAL DIMENSIONS AND INDICATORS

4.1.1 Socioeconomic structure and inequalities

Observing the socioeconomic structure of a society is crucial for understanding the opportunities provided through economic conditions, education, and welfare systems. Unequal

access to these opportunities can fuel relative deprivation and sentiments of resentment, which may mobilize anti-democratic stances. Furthermore, the socioeconomic structure is a key lens through which to examine gender socialization.

In other terms, the socioeconomic structure of a society refers to the organized set of social and economic institutions, relationships, and hierarchies that determine how resources, opportunities, and power are produced, distributed, and accessed. In addition to the organization of economic activity, it includes forms of social stratification, such as class, education, gender, and other determinants of status. Together, these elements shape the conditions under which individuals and groups participate in social and economic life and influence broader outcomes related to equity, development, and social cohesion.

Socioeconomic structures shape gender socialization by organizing access to resources, defining divisions of labor, and embedding gendered expectations into key institutions. As Bourdieu (1984) argued, social structures produce “habitus”, which are internalized dispositions that guide how individuals learn gender-appropriate roles. Economic arrangements, such as the gendered division of paid and unpaid labor, reinforce these dispositions by associating women with caregiving and men with waged work. Institutions, including schools, workplaces, and families, transmit these norms. Additionally, inequalities in economic power shape who holds authority in households and public life. Together, these mechanisms ensure that gender norms are not merely cultural expectations but are reinforced, or challenged, by the material and institutional arrangements of society, as explained earlier. Crucial elements of socioeconomic structures are those shaping welfare access but also those providing insights into economic and gender inequality, education, demographic and spatial distribution, and rule of law and rights.

Income inequality is captured through measures such as the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in purchasing power standards (PPSs) and the Gini coefficient, while the risk of exclusion is illustrated by the proportion of individuals vulnerable to poverty and the employment/activity rates differentiated by gender. The Gender Equality Index developed by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), specifically in the domains of money and work, further elucidates economic disparities from a gendered perspective.

Economic precarity and unequal access to work opportunities may reinforce traditional, competitive masculinities rooted in dominance and economic provision. On the one hand, female participation in paid work may challenge dominant gender norms, yet it is often coupled with job insecurity, double burdens, and occupational segregation (EIGE 2024). On the other hand, men who struggle to fulfill the traditional breadwinner role may experience frustration, leading to reactive attitudes or withdrawal from public and familial responsibilities (Nixon 2018; Robertson et al. 2018).

Conversely, welfare regimes that provide economic security and redistribute resources may enable men to engage in caregiver roles without a perceived loss of standing. Well-designed policies, when complemented by broader cultural reforms, may strengthen men's motivations to proactively advance gender equality (Goossen 2023; Connell 2005). For example, welfare models that support work-life balance, promote paternal leave, and reduce gender gaps in care responsibilities directly challenge rigid masculinity norms by legitimizing men's caregiving and emotional roles (Doucet 2017; Almqvist and Duvander 2014). General access to welfare is measured by total social expenditure as a proportion of GDP, along with indicators in connection with family policies, such as paternal leave duration and pay rate. These dimensions are complemented by the subdimension "Health" of the EIGE Gender Equality Index, which reflects disparities in terms of both access to and outcomes from the provision of health.

Educational structure not only determines skill formation but also identity formation, as well as gendered experiences of varying gender norms. Overrepresentation of men in specific disciplines and underrepresentation in others signal larger socialization processes about what is "proper" for men and women. In this report, education is measured in terms of tertiary graduation rates, disaggregated by field and sex (e.g., underrepresentation of women in disciplines such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) or overrepresentation in humanities), and the proportion of early school leavers. Additionally, the sub-index "Knowledge" of the EIGE Gender Equality Index offers a composite view of gender parity in educational outcomes.

Demographic and spatial indicators, such as urban-rural groups, old-age dependency ratio, and foreign-born percentage, highlight how socialization contexts vary across settings. Urban environments tend to foster more pluralistic, inclusive, and less traditional gender norms, whereas rural contexts tend to reinforce the continuity of traditional gender roles and

masculinities because of tighter kinship networks, lower demographic diversity, and more traditional labor markets (Giddens 1991; Lichter and Brown 2011).

4.1.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Monitoring how European values are implemented at the institutional level helps assess how conducive national contexts are to the formation of democratic and egalitarian masculinities. With reference to Article 2 of the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, this section focuses in particular on the EU values of democracy, gender equality, pluralism, and human rights. In addition, we pay attention to public opinion regarding trust in European institutions and integration.

Indicators of governance, such as the Democracy Index, Rule of Law Index, Freedom in the World, and Civil Liberties Index, reflect the extent to which individuals live in open, rights-respecting societies. These institutional contexts influence not only the protection of gender rights but also the normative legitimacy of nontraditional masculinities. In democratic countries, masculinities may be shaped by civic values, such as pluralism, mutual respect, and emotional self-awareness, while in more authoritarian systems, masculinities may be modeled on hierarchy, discipline, and control. The evaluation of governance occurs through indices pertaining to freedom, democracy, rule of law, and civil liberties.

The overall EIGE Gender Equality Index and its subdimensions, which cover aspects of inequality related to time and power, allow us to describe progress on gender equality in Europe and serve as a general proxy for the environment in which boys and men are socialized. The Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI), designed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), provides insights into institutional discrimination that may undermine gender-equal norms from early childhood.

To investigate the institutional position regarding the European values of pluralism, integration policies and anti-discrimination laws related to sexual orientation and gender identity are considered key markers of inclusive societies. As demonstrated by Anderson and McCormak (2018), law reforms have been essential to decreasing levels of homophobia and have opened a space for wider inclusive forms of expressions of masculinity. Within environments of effective social inclusion and welfare policy, such frameworks disrupt the classical association

between breadwinning and masculinity and, as such, create space for novel forms of masculine identity to coexist (Goossen 2023).

Lastly, trust in European institutions and attitudes toward European integration provide important insight into broader orientations toward Europe and the legitimation of its cultural values. Higher levels of trust and pro-integration attitudes are consistently associated with openness, pluralism, and support for democratic values (Inglehart and Norris 2003; Delhey 2007). These cultural attitudes tend to encourage the acceptability of nontraditional gender beliefs and egalitarian familial arrangements, whereas settings marked by Euroscepticism and institutional distrust tend to be linked to traditional gender role preservation, along with resistance toward gender equality initiatives (Kuhar and Paternotte 2017; Lomazzi and Crespi 2019).

4.1.3 Gender norms

The prevailing gender norms in a society capture the normative and symbolic climate within which processes of socialization take place and gender relations and masculinities are reproduced.

Gender norms define what behaviors are seen as common (descriptive norms) and what behaviors are considered acceptable (injunctive norms) for members of a group, such as men and boys. From this perspective, gender norms and, more generally, public opinion on gender roles and gender relations play a relevant role in gender socialization (Lomazzi and Crespi 2019). Gender norms are acquired in early childhood and continually reinforced across the life course; however, they remain open to reinterpretation, negotiation, and individual agency. Historically, patriarchal traditions have cast politics and the economy as male-dominated spheres, promoting an image of the “ideal man” as a public figure wielding both political and economic power. This has played a central role in shaping restrictive masculinities, characterized by authority and dominance over women as well as over other men (Connell 1995).

This dimension focuses on the shared beliefs, expectations, and stereotypes that shape the meanings and performances of masculinity in the public and private spheres. In the economic sphere, gender norms reinforce the idea that certain jobs are “appropriate” for men and others for women. This sustains occupational segregation by classifying tasks as either masculine or

feminine (Simpson 2004; Cataldi and Tomatis 2024) according to the physical strength required, as well as cultural elements, such as power and prestige. Individuals who cross these boundaries may face stigma and loss of status, even when they benefit from gendered advantages compared to members of the opposite sex in the same role.

In the private sphere, gender norms also shape social expectations about women's and men's roles and responsibilities. More traditionally, men are expected to take authority in domestic decisions, control resources for families, act as guardians of female relatives, and not take part in unpaid domestic work and caregiving, whereas women are held to fulfill caregiving and housework chores (Bittman et al., 2003; Thébaud, 2010). European countries display different levels of support for traditional gender roles in the public and domestic domains, with signs of polarization between genders and generations (Lomazzi and Soboleva 2024). In addition to gender role attitudes, beliefs of hostility toward women and resistance to gender equality, for example, sexism and anti-gender equality views, contribute to describing the gender culture of a given society. Contexts characterized by prevailing traditional gender norms alongside emerging resistance or opposition to gender equality among the public opinion contribute to creating a context that tends to perpetuate rigid expectations toward gender roles, supporting patriarchal and sexist forms of masculinity.

4.1.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

As discussed in other MEN4DEM reports (Schaaf and Mars 2025; Besta et al. 2025), gender-based violence is a critical lens through which to examine how masculinities are constructed, sanctioned, or challenged. This dimension includes both prevalence data and institutional responses, thereby capturing the degree to which violent behavior is normalized or contested within society.

The structural and cultural environments in which individuals are situated guide and influence their behaviors, offering a shared framework of what is perceived as desirable, acceptable, or tolerated within society. Understanding the prevailing gender cultures of a given context is essential for uncovering the underlying dynamics that legitimize violence against women (Lomazzi 2023b).

Despite the growing recognition that empowering women has social benefits, it is sometimes seen as a loss of men's authority. Violence is often seen as a reaction against changes in the

status quo that have privileged males and supported male dominance in the past. When men see female empowerment as a threat to their masculine identity, they may respond by adopting behavior designed to reestablish their supposed superiority, and this can manifest as violence against women. In workplaces and public arenas, this can take the form of sexual harassment or overtly aggressive behavior (McLaughlin et al. 2012). Within the household, domestic violence can similarly be used as a means of reestablishing gender hierarchies, contributing to the persistence and prevalence of intimate partner violence (IPV).

To grasp information on the national context of socialization regarding this specific dimension, we map experiences of gender-based violence, awareness of the phenomenon, and institutional responses. The prevalence of gender violence, as defined by the rate of women who have ever been in a partnership and have experienced IPV, is an important indicator of how violent masculinities are present in the personal and public spheres. However, prevalence alone does not tell the full story; awareness indicators, such as knowledge of legal help and support services among victims as well as nonvictims, reflect whether societies have the appropriate instruments to comprehend and fight such violence.

Institutional responsiveness is measured through registries of intentional homicides disaggregated by sex and relationship to the offender. This aids in understanding the gendered character of violence and how justice mechanisms document and respond to violence. The ratification of the Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence, also known as “the Istanbul Convention”, further signals a formal commitment to combatting gender-based violence and promoting gender-sensitive legal standards.

Taken together, the indicators in this dimension can shed light on how societies problematize or ignore violent masculinities. Where institutional responses are weak and awareness is low, traditional and harmful masculinities are more likely to remain unchallenged.

4.1.5 Political dimension

Understanding whether a certain context supports, in its structural and cultural components, democracy is pivotal to reading the processes of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. Among the many aspects to observe the quality and support for democracy, we explore how masculinity intersects with political life through patterns of participation, trust in

institutions, political orientation, and the potential for violence or polarization. Indicators related to these subdimensions can help assess whether democratic citizenship is experienced inclusively or is associated with authoritarianism, disaffection, extremism radicalization, and anti-equality backlash (Mudde 2019; Dietze and Roth 2020).

Studies have reported that supporters of radical right beliefs are often found to have high levels of political discontent and mistrust of official institutions and the political system (Knigge 1998; Lubbers et al. 2002). Indicators such as voter turnout, women's representation in parliament, and the electoral strength of far-right parties can help assess the inclusiveness of political arenas and the extent to which traditional gender hierarchies are reinforced or challenged. Attention to the share of far-right supporters is relevant because in far-right narratives, conventional gender roles and the promotion of masculinist values firmly based in hierarchical and command-oriented structures remain central reference points (Holm 2024; Messerschmidt 2024). Political disengagement, as well as the rejection of pluralistic values, may then be framed as responses to sociopolitical uncertainty, in which traditional masculine ideals are reasserted as a form of stability.

Finally, political violence and polarization indicators highlight the extent to which democratic contestation is managed peacefully or devolves into antagonism. Individuals who display hostile sexist attitudes tend to be more inclined to accept and legitimize the use of political violence. Furthermore, hostile sexism and support for such violence are closely intertwined, mediated by a social dominance orientation and broader patterns of political illiberalism (Piazza and O'Rourke 2025). Consequently, such indicators offer clarity as to how political spaces' construction, expression, and usage of masculinities are developed, alongside how such may strengthen or violate democratic principles.

4.1.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The internet has become a key arena of socialization, particularly for adolescents and young adults. Digital environments not only shape everyday media consumption but also provide fertile ground for the circulation of masculinist discourses. If digitalization and trust in media are key elements to this process, aspects related to online exposure to fake news and misogynistic content are relevant to grasp information on the online context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. Scholars use the term "manosphere" to indicate the

constellation of online groups that share a common core ideology that predicates the rejection of feminist paradigms and the reaffirmation of essentialist gender binaries, wherein masculinity is framed as both embattled and inherently dominant (Kennedy-Kollar 2024).

In the manosphere ideology, violence against women, seen as an understandable consequence of the unnatural and emasculating situation, pairs with the dynamics of victimization of men and aggrieved entitlement (Dickel and Evolvi 2023; Nicholas et al. 2024; Gotell and Dutton 2016). Men of the manosphere have been socialized to feel entitled to achieve everything that patriarchal masculinity promises. The delusion of this unmet promise (aggrieved entitlement) fuels anger and anxiety, preparing the path to radicalization and violence, which are seen as the only way to restore masculinity when traditional methods (such as sexual success) are not available (Messerschmidt and Tomsen 2018). Specific indicators to quantitatively monitor the manosphere cross-nationally are still not available. However, we use the number of men who declared to be members of a manosphere platform as a proxy to grasp the presence of the manosphere in the EU27 countries. Furthermore, research evidences an expanding overlap between communities of incels and right-wing politics in expression, in a similar belief system, and reciprocal participation in digital discourse (Cottee 2020; Dickel and Evolvi 2023). With this in view, indicators concerning internet use, digital media trust, and misinformation are essential in terms of capturing how people are exposed to and interpret information, as media mistrust and misinformation often nurture polarized and anti-democratic discourses articulated in gendered terms.

4.1.7 Youth agency

According to the socialization approach proposed in this report, individual agency is crucial in the internalization and reproduction of gender norms and masculinity models. At the collective level, the demographic process of cohort replacement, with the new generation socialized in structural and cultural contexts different from those of the older generation, can potentially lead to social change (Ryder 1965). Young people are therefore at a critical junction where socialization solidifies or transforms, making their experiences essential for understanding evolving masculinities. One of the key insights emerging from sociological research on youth is that gender constitutes a central social order that shapes young people's lives. Masculinities and femininities are not fixed attributes but are constructed over time through encounters with systems of gender relations that differ across societies and historical moments (Connell 2002).

This means that young people's experiences of identity, belonging, and exclusion are profoundly shaped by the gender order they inhabit. Institutions such as schools play a pivotal role in this process. As Connell (2002) suggested, they are characterized by specific "gender regimes" that structure opportunities, expectations, and divisions of labor, embedding gender norms into the everyday trajectories of youth.

Generational analyses suggest that youth often construct themselves as agents of social progress, contrasting their attitudes with those of older cohorts perceived as less tolerant (Allen et al. 2022). At the same time, the apparent openness of young people toward gender diversity is not without limits. This reveals that inclusive attitudes coexist with persistent attachments to traditional frameworks of gender intelligibility. Thus, youth orientations toward inclusivity should not be interpreted as a wholesale rejection of restrictive gender norms but rather as an ongoing process of negotiation. On the one hand, young people help destabilize binary and exclusionary models of masculinity and femininity; on the other hand, their attitudes often reproduce subtle hierarchies of legitimacy among different gender identities. In this sense, youth perspectives reflect the contradictions of broader cultural transformations, in which inclusivity is both expanded and contested.

To consider youth agency, this final dimension focuses on how structural conditions and young people's perceptions shape the intergenerational transmission, or disruption, of gender norms. From this perspective, structural subdimensions are tools used to clarify links between socialization processes and broader opportunity structures. Indicators such as the share of young women aged 25–29 attaining upper secondary or higher education not only signal educational access but also reflect the contexts in which gender roles are negotiated. Further elements to complement youth's potential agency in changing the current gender order concern, for example, their sense of belonging and opportunity in their local environment. In addition, how welcoming they perceive their city or region toward immigrants and toward LGBTQI+ people, as well as whether they are satisfied with social connectedness opportunities, provides great insight into whether young people reside in inclusive, pluralistic settings. Such environments are more likely to foster egalitarian and open forms of masculinity and suppress impulses toward exclusionary or hypermasculine forms of identity. Taken together, these perspectives underline that understanding how young people experience inclusion and imagine their future is key to analyzing the social construction of masculinity, whether it

continues to rest on competition and control or is reshaped around empathy, diversity, and democratic engagement.

5. ANALYTICAL DIMENSIONS AND COMPARATIVE INDICATORS ACROSS EU27 COUNTRIES

In this section we offer a comparative overview of the national contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities. For this, we provide comparisons of countries following the logic of our multidimensional perspective. For each one of the seven dimensions that concur with shaping the socialization context, we selected set of indicators for each subdimension, rather than a comprehensive list of all available measures. This choice is guided by the aim of capturing the most relevant contextual features for cross-national comparison, while ensuring clarity and comparability across countries and data sources. Also, indicators do not have an inherent or self-evident meaning when taken in isolation, but their interpretation depends on how they interact with other structural, normative, and political dimensions of the national context. In other words, within each subdimension, several measures are considered together, since single indicators provide only a partial and potentially misleading picture of complex social, institutional, and normative contexts. Detailed description of each national profile, based on the richer set of indicators that we described in Section 4, is available in Annex I.

5.1 SOCIOECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND INEQUALITIES

Across EU countries, pronounced cross-national differences emerge in socio-economic inequalities. Northern and Western European countries generally combine higher GDP per capita, lower income inequality, stronger gender equality in work and knowledge, lower early school leaving, and more urbanized contexts with higher shares of foreign-born populations (Figure 2). These settings are also characterized by higher levels of social protection expenditure, although this does not consistently translate into longer paternal leave. By contrast, many Southern and Eastern European countries display lower economic resources, higher inequality, weaker gender equality outcomes (

Figure 3), higher rural population shares, more limited immigration, and stronger ageing pressures (

Figure 4). These contexts also tend to combine lower levels of social expenditure with shorter or more limited paternal leave arrangements, pointing to less supportive welfare frameworks for reconciling work and family life

Figure 5. Overall, the patterns point to persistent and cumulative socio-economic inequalities across European contexts, shaped by the interaction of economic development, demographic structures, and welfare institutions.

Figure 2 Socioeconomic Structure and Inequalities – Economic Structure

Overall, the data reveal substantial cross country economic heterogeneity within the EU. Higher levels of GDP per capita are concentrated in Northern and Western European countries and in some small, highly specialized economies (such as Luxembourg, Ireland, the Netherlands, and Denmark), which also tend to display lower income inequality and higher scores on the Gender Equality Index in the domain of work.

In contrast, many Southern and Eastern European countries record GDP per capita below the EU27 average, higher levels of income inequality, and lower performance in gender equality in work. However, the relationship between economic development, inequality, and gender equality is not strictly linear, as illustrated by cases such as Italy, which combine intermediate income levels with relatively weaker outcomes in the work dimension of gender equality.

Source: GDP per capita (Eurostat 2024c); Gini coefficient (Eurostat 2024d); Gender Equality Index – Work (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Figure 3 Socioeconomic Structure and Inequalities – Education

Source: Early leavers from education and training by sex – Females (Eurostat 2024a); Gender Equality Index – Knowledge (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Figure 4 Socioeconomic Structure and Inequalities – Demography and Spatial Distribution

Settlement patterns, demographic ageing, and migration shape very different social contexts within Europe. Higher shares of rural population are mainly observed in Eastern and some Southern European countries, while Western and Northern countries tend to be more urbanized and host larger foreign-born populations.

Ageing pressures, as measured by the old-age dependency ratio, are widespread across the EU but are particularly pronounced in Southern Europe, whereas countries with very low shares of foreign-born residents (e.g. Poland, Bulgaria, Romania) combine more limited migration with comparatively younger population structures.

Source: Population by urban-rural typology - Rural (Eurostat 2024a); Old-age dependency ratio (Eurostat 2024e); Foreign-born population (Eurostat 2022)

Figure 5 Socioeconomic Structure and Inequalities – Welfare and Access to Social Services

European countries strongly differ by their welfare system. While higher social spending is more common in Northern and Western European countries, this does not systematically translate into longer paternal leave.

In most EU countries, paternal leave remains short, with a few notable exceptions such as Spain, Portugal, and the Netherlands, highlighting strong cross-country disparities in institutional support for fathers' involvement in childcare, with potential implication for social norms regarding fatherhood.

Source: Social protection expenditure % of GDP (OECD 2024b); Paternal leave, length (OECD 2024a).

5.2 EUROPEAN VALUES AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS EUROPE

Across EU countries, cross-national differences emerge in democratic quality, institutional inclusion, and European orientations. Northern and Western European countries generally combine higher scores on the Freedom in the World Index, Democracy Index, Rule of Law, and Civil Liberties (Figure 6) with lower levels of institutional gender discrimination (SIGI), more inclusive migrant integration policies (MIPEX), stronger protection of LGBTIQ+ rights (Rainbow Europe Index) (Figure 7), higher trust in the European Parliament, and more positive attitudes toward further European integration (Figure 8). These contexts are characterized by more consolidated democratic and inclusive institutional environments.

By contrast, many Central and Eastern European countries display weaker performance on democratic and rule-of-law indicators (Figure 6), higher levels of institutional gender discrimination, more restrictive frameworks for migrant integration and minority rights

(Figure 7), lower trust in EU institutions, and more skeptical attitudes toward European unification (Figure 8). Southern European countries often occupy intermediate positions, combining relatively strong civil liberties (Figure 6) with weaker institutional effectiveness and more ambivalent orientations toward European integration (Figure 7 and Figure 8).

Figure 6 European Values – Governance, Rights, and Freedoms

Source: Freedom in the World Index (Freedom House 2025); Democracy Index (EIU) (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024); Rule of Law Index (World Justice Project 2024); Civil Liberties (Varieties of Democracy 2024)

Figure 7 European Values - Pluralism and Inclusion

stronger legal protections for LGBTIQ+ rights, as reflected in the Rainbow Europe Index.

By contrast, several Central and Eastern European countries, including Poland, Hungary, Bulgaria, and Romania, combine higher levels of institutional gender discrimination with more restrictive migrant integration frameworks and weaker protections for sexual minorities. Southern European countries such as Italy, Greece, and Cyprus typically occupy intermediate positions, showing moderate performance across these dimensions but remaining below the levels observed in Northern Europe.

Source: Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) (OECD 2023b); Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX 2023) (MIPEX); Rainbow Europe Index (ILGA-Europe 2025)

Figure 8 European Values – Trust in European Institutions and Democratic Legitimacy

Levels of trust in the European Parliament vary substantially across EU countries. Higher levels of trust are generally observed in Northern and Western European countries, such as Spain, the Netherlands, and Ireland, while lower trust is more common in several Central and Eastern European contexts, including Germany, Slovakia, Romania, and the Czech Republic.

Attitudes toward European unification are, on average, moderately positive across

the EU, but important cross-country differences persist. Support for further integration tends to be stronger in countries such as Portugal, Spain, and Lithuania, whereas more skeptical positions are more prevalent in countries like Austria, Italy, and Slovakia, highlighting that institutional trust and support for European integration do not always fully overlap.

Source: Trust in the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c); European unification - go further vs gone too far (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.

5.3 GENDER NORMS

Across EU countries, pronounced cross-national differences emerge in gender norms and beliefs related to work, family roles, leadership, care, and feminist claims. Northern European countries generally combine lower endorsement of traditional gender roles (

Figure 9), weaker support for male authority in family decision-making (**Figure 10**), greater acceptance of men’s emotional expression (**Figure 11**), and lower agreement with narratives delegitimizing feminism or women’s experiences of harassment (**Figure 10**). These contexts are characterized by more egalitarian normative environments, in which gender equality is more widely normalized.

By contrast, many Southern and Central and Eastern European countries display higher support for traditional expectations around women’s family responsibilities, stronger endorsement of male dominance in leadership and household decisions, greater stigma toward men’s involvement in care, and more widespread agreement with anti-feminist and backlash-oriented statements. Overall, the patterns point to persistent and cumulative inequalities in gender norms across European contexts, shaped by historically rooted cultural expectations and broader institutional and social configurations.

Figure 9 Gender norms – Domestic sphere

Source: Women should prioritize family over career - agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024); Family life suffers when mother has a full-time job - agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Figure 10 Gender norms – Public sphere

Source: Women exaggerate claims of sexual harassment (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025) Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.; Feminism has gone too far – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024); Men make better leaders than women – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024); Unattractive for women to express strong opinions in public – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 11 Gender norms – Masculine gender norms/beliefs

The indicators reveal marked cross-country differences in gender stereotypes related to masculinity, authority within the family, and men’s involvement in care. Agreement with the statement that it is acceptable for men to cry is high across most EU countries, particularly in Nordic and Western European countries such as Denmark, Sweden, Finland, and Luxembourg, suggesting a broader acceptance of emotional expression among men. By contrast, more traditional views—such as the belief that men should have the final say in important family decisions or that men taking parental leave lack career ambition—remain more prevalent in several Southern and Central and Eastern European countries, including Romania, Croatia, Portugal, Bulgaria, and the Netherlands. Overall, the EU27 average masks substantial heterogeneity in how masculine norms around authority, care, and emotional expression are socially constructed across national contexts.

Source: It is acceptable for men to cry – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024); For important family decisions men should have final say – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024); Men taking parental leave show lack of ambition – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

5.4 GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AND INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSE

Across EU countries, pronounced cross-national differences emerge in gender-based violence and institutional responses. Several countries combine high levels of intimate partner violence with comparatively stronger institutional frameworks for prevention and protection, as reflected in the Gender Equality Index (Violence) (

Figure 12) and earlier ratification of the Istanbul Convention (Figure 13). In these contexts, violence against women appears more visible and systematically addressed through policy and legal instruments.

By contrast, other countries display weaker institutional responses, delayed or absent ratification of the Istanbul Convention (Figure 13), and less comprehensive policy frameworks, alongside varying patterns of violence prevalence and lethal outcomes (

Figure 12). Overall, the patterns point to persistent and cumulative inequalities in how gender-based violence is prevented, recognized, and addressed across European contexts, shaped by the interaction between social prevalence, severity of violence, and the timing and strength of institutional commitment.

Figure 12 Gender-Based Violence and Institutional Response – Gender-Based Violence (Experience & Awareness)

The prevalence of intimate partner violence among ever-partnered women varies widely across EU countries. Particularly high levels are observed in Croatia, Greece, Romania, Portugal, Slovakia, and Denmark, while comparatively lower levels are reported in countries such as the Netherlands, Bulgaria, Poland, and Ireland.

Female homicide committed by intimate partners or family members is a relatively rare event overall but shows marked cross-country differences. Italy and Lithuania stand out for comparatively higher rates, whereas very low levels are observed in Romania, the Czech Republic, Bulgaria, and Latvia. Importantly, this lack of a linear association between the prevalence of violence and lethal outcomes is also reflected in the Gender Equality Index (Violence), which highlights substantial cross-national variation in exposure to gender-based violence across Europe.

Taken together, these indicators suggest that gender-based violence operates along multiple and partly independent dimensions, shaped not only by prevalence but also by institutional capacity, prevention policies, and broader gender regimes.

Source: Gender Equality Index – Violence (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024); Female homicide rate by intimate partner/family member; Ever-partnered women experiencing IPV (psychological/physical/sexual) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 13 Gender-Based Violence and Institutional Response – Institutional Legal Framework

Source: Ratification of the Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe 2025)

5.5 POLITICAL DIMENSION

Across EU countries, pronounced cross-national differences emerge in democratic attitudes, political climates, and exposure to disinformation. Northern and Western European countries generally tend to combine higher levels of electoral democracy (Figure 14), lower support for strong non-parliamentary leadership (Figure 15), weaker far-right self-placement (Source: Strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections – agree (Haerpfer et al. 2024). Information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 16), and comparatively lower levels of political polarization and violence (Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 17). In these contexts, awareness of disinformation as a threat to democracy is high, while reported personal exposure to fake news tends to be more limited. By contrast, many Southern and Central and Eastern European countries tend to display stronger political polarization (Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 17), greater openness to strong leaders who bypass democratic institutions (Figure 15), and higher shares of respondents positioning themselves on the far right of the political spectrum (. Information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 16), alongside weaker electoral democratic performance (Figure 14). Overall, the patterns point to persistent and cumulative differences in democratic strain across European contexts, shaped by the interaction between information environments, political conflict, and institutional quality.

Figure 14 Political Dimension – Electoral Participation and Behavior

Source: Electoral democracy index (Varieties of Democracy 2024)

Figure 15 Political Dimension – Trust in Political Institutions

By contrast, most Western and Northern European countries—including Austria, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Sweden, and France—show comparatively lower levels of endorsement. Overall, the EU27 average conceals cross-national differences in attitudes toward authoritarian leadership within Europe.

Source: Strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections – agree (Haerpfer et al. 2024). Information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 16 Political Dimension – Interest and Attitudes toward Politics

Higher proportions of respondents placing themselves on the far right of the left–right scale are observed in the Netherlands, Croatia, Italy, and the Czech Republic, indicating a comparatively stronger far-right self-identification in these contexts.

Conversely, very low or negligible shares are found in countries such as Luxembourg, Latvia, Austria, Finland, and Malta, while most other countries cluster around intermediate levels. Overall, the EU27 average masks notable cross-national differences in far-right positioning across European societies.

Source: Placement on left-right scale (self-placement) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Note: The information is available only for the displayed countries.

Figure 17 Political Dimension – Polarization and Political Violence

Source: Political violence (Varieties of Democracy 2024); Political polarization (Varieties of Democracy 2024)

5.6 DIGITALIZATION AND ONLINE BEHAVIOR

Across EU countries, agreement that disinformation constitutes a serious problem for democracy is high in all regions, indicating a broad and shared normative concern. This consensus is particularly strong in Central and Eastern European countries (such as Slovakia, Romania, and the Czech Republic), as well as in several Southern European countries, while remaining high also in Northern and Western Europe (Figure 18).

Conversely, self-reported exposure to disinformation over the past seven days shows marked regional variation. Higher levels of exposure are more frequently reported in Central and Eastern and Southern European countries (including Bulgaria, Croatia, Portugal, and the Czech Republic), whereas lower exposure tends to be observed in Northern European countries (such as Denmark, Finland, and Sweden) and in parts of Western Europe (Figure 18). Overall, the patterns point to a common recognition of the democratic risks of disinformation alongside uneven experiences of exposure across European regions.

Figure 18 Digitalization and Online Behavior – Internet Use, Trust in Digital Media, and Disinformation

Perceived exposure to disinformation and fake news varies substantially across EU countries. Respondents in Bulgaria, Croatia, Portugal, the Czech Republic, Slovenia, and France report higher levels of self-reported exposure, while lower exposure is reported in countries such as Malta, Denmark, Finland, Slovakia, and Belgium. This suggests uneven informational environments and differences in media consumption or awareness across national contexts. At the same time, agreement that disinformation represents a problem for democracy is consistently high across all countries, with particularly strong consensus in Slovakia, Romania, the Czech Republic, Spain, Luxembourg, and Malta.

Overall, while perceived personal exposure to disinformation varies widely, there is broad cross-national agreement that fake news constitutes a serious democratic challenge throughout the EU.

Source: Disinformation is a problem for democracy – agree (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022); Self-reported exposure to disinformation (last 7 days) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022)

5.7 YOUTH AGENCY

Across EU countries, marked cross-national differences emerge in youth inclusion, reflecting the interplay between structural opportunities and normative contexts. Northern and several Western European countries such as Denmark, Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and Germany tend to cluster together, combining high Youth Index scores (Figure 20), high educational attainment among young women (

Figure 19), and greater openness toward immigrants and sexual diversity among youth (Figure 20).

By contrast, many Southern and Central and Eastern European countries including Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Portugal, Italy, and Latvia display more uneven youth outcomes. In these contexts, opportunities for social interaction may be relatively widespread (

Figure 20), but educational attainment among young women is more polarized and attitudinal openness is weaker (

Figure 19), resulting in lower Youth Index scores (Figure 20).

Figure 19 Youth Agency – Structural Dimension

The share of young women aged 25–29 with upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education is generally high across the EU, but notable cross-national differences remain. Very high levels of educational attainment are observed in Northern and several Central European countries, including Lithuania, Romania, Sweden, Germany, Estonia, Italy, Denmark, and the Netherlands, indicating strong gender parity in basic educational outcomes for younger cohorts.

By contrast, lower attainment levels are found in Latvia, Slovenia, Poland, Portugal, Bulgaria, Cyprus, and Ireland, pointing to more uneven educational trajectories for young women in these contexts. Overall, while the EU27 average reflects broad progress in women’s educational attainment, the variation across countries highlights persistent territorial inequalities in the educational foundations of gender equality.

Source: Young women 25-29 with 12-18 years of education (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)

Figure 20 Youth Agency – Perceptual Dimension

The four indicators highlight meaningful cross-national variation in youth social openness, inclusion, and opportunities. While perceived opportunities to make friends are relatively high and fairly homogeneous across countries, attitudes toward immigrants and sexual minorities show much stronger differentiation.

Openness toward immigrants and acceptance of gays and lesbians vary substantially across contexts, suggesting that social connectedness does not automatically translate into broader inclusionary attitudes. These patterns are consistent with differences observed in the Youth Index, pointing to unequal institutional and social environments shaping young people’s attitudes.

Source: Youth Index (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022); Openness towards immigrants (youth 15-29) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022); Opportunity to make friends (youth 15-29) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022); Acceptance of gays and lesbians (youth 15-29) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)

6. PATTERNS OF SOCIALIZATION INTO (ANTI-) DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES IN EUROPE

Despite the specific national contexts of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities described so far, common patterns can be retrieved across EU27. Building on the previous parts of the report, this section aims to explore whether consistent cross-national clusters exist within Europe.

As introduced in Section 4, we do this by considering two aspects that are crucial for the context of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities: democracy and gender equality. To assess whether the potential clustering is consistent, we use different sets of indicators to map countries' information on the distribution of power and opportunities and the normative expectations surrounding gender roles.

First, we examine the correlation between structural indicators of the Quality of Democracy and the Gender Equality Index. Second, we shift our attention to cultural indicators. We show the association between sexist orientations and the share of respondents who self-position themselves in the far right extreme, and the correlation between gender norms and preference for an authoritarian political leader. To visualize the correlation between these dimensions, we provide scatter plots.

Figure 21 plots the Gender Equality Index (EIGE) and the Democracy Index (EIU)—two indicators already used in the report to describe countries' institutional and normative settings. These two indicators are positively and strongly correlated. In other words, gender equality and democratic quality are two dimensions that tend to evolve together, as both reflect how rights, opportunities, and forms of participation are distributed within a society. Countries that invest in equal access to resources and decision-making for women and men are often also those in which civil liberties, accountability, and political participation are more firmly established.

Looking at both dimensions together, therefore, offers a synthetic view of the conditions that shape everyday experiences of inclusion—and of the values that boys and men learn as they grow up in different national contexts.

Figure 21 Gender Equality and Democracy Across EU Countries

Source: European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Gender Equality Index 2022, Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU), Democracy Index 2022. The correlation between the Gender Equality Index and the Democracy Index is strong and positive ($r = 0.75$).

The joint distribution of the Democracy Index and the Gender Equality Index reveals three broadly recognizable clusters, although the boundaries between them are gradual rather than rigid. At the upper end of both scales, we find Sweden, Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, Ireland, Luxembourg, and Germany. These countries combine very high democratic quality—mostly above 8.7—with high to very high gender equality scores. Their position in the top-right area of the scatter reflects institutional environments in which democratic performance and gender equality reinforce one another and in which egalitarian norms have been deeply embedded in both political and social life.

A second group occupies the middle of the distribution, showing solid but not exceptional democratic scores and moderate levels of gender equality. This includes Austria, France, Spain, Portugal, Slovenia, Italy, and Malta, as well as several Central and Eastern European countries such as Czechia, Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia. These countries cluster around democracy scores between roughly 7.5 and 8.1, and gender equality levels range from the low 60s to the low 70s. Their intermediate positioning reflects contexts in which democratic

institutions are in place and broadly trusted but where social and gender inequalities remain more persistent, creating more uneven environments for everyday experiences of equality.

The lower-left area of the plot is composed mainly of Bulgaria, Romania, and Hungary, with Cyprus and Croatia also positioned toward the lower end of gender equality. These countries combine more modest democratic scores with the lowest gender-equality levels in the EU.

Their position signals contexts in which institutional constraints on democracy, socioeconomic vulnerabilities, and entrenched gender norms coexist, shaping environments in which the alignment between democratic values and gender-equality principles is less consolidated. Overall, the correlation between the two indicators is strong and positive, but the plot also shows variation within each band of democracy and gender equality. Some countries—such as France, Belgium, and Portugal—perform more strongly on gender equality than their democracy score alone would suggest. Others—such as Czechia and Estonia—have comparatively higher democratic scores but remain closer to the middle range of gender equality.

Building on this, the next figures provide two sets of graphs to examine how specific cultural attitudes map onto political orientations across the EU. The first set explores the associations between support for authoritarian leadership and gender-egalitarian views in both the private and public spheres (Figure 22), while the second focuses on how far-right positioning relates to hostile and modern forms of sexism (

Figure 23).

Figure 22 displays the association between the individual's support for authoritarian leaders and the gender role expectations in the public and domestic domains. Considered jointly, they capture complementary aspects of the cultural environment: Acceptance of authority without democratic limits reflects a preference for hierarchy, while egalitarian gender norms reveal how individuals value equality in relationships and institutions. Together, they help identify whether people grow up in contexts that normalize shared power and equal participation or in settings in which political and gender hierarchies appear more legitimate.

These visualizations help clarify the wider attitudinal environments in which gender norms—and, ultimately, masculinities—are shaped. Importantly, viewing these indicators side by side also makes it possible to identify recurring clusters of countries, showing how different dimensions of gender norms and political orientations tend to align. This reinforces, rather than replaces, the broader analysis developed earlier in the report. The scatter plots offer a synthetic way of visualizing patterns that emerge from a much wider set of structural, institutional, and cultural factors. The two scatter plots compare egalitarian gender role attitudes—in the family sphere and in public life—with support for authoritarian leadership, offering a view of how political orientations and gender norms intersect within each national context.

Figure 22 Associations Between Support for Authoritarian Leadership and Gender Egalitarian Views in Private and Public Spheres

Source: European Values Study (EVS), 2017. Egalitarian views on women’s family roles are derived from agreement with the statements “When a mother works for pay, the children suffer”, “A job is alright but what most women really want is a home and children”, and “All in all, family life suffers when the woman has a full-time job”. Egalitarian views on women’s public and leadership roles use responses to “On the whole, men make better political leaders than women do”, “A university education is more important for a boy than for a girl”, and “On the whole, men make better business executives than women do”. Support for authoritarian leadership is based on an agreement with “Having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections”. Correlations are moderately negative, both for family-related gender norms ($r = -0.47$) and for public-sphere gender norms ($r = -0.50$).

Across both plots displayed in Figure 22, which relate support for authoritarian leadership to egalitarian views in the family and in public life, the overall pattern is clear—the more egalitarian the gender norms, the lower the acceptance of strong-leader politics. In both domains, the association is negative and of comparable strength, as also reflected in the country-level correlations, indicating that neither family-role norms nor public-role norms diverge substantially in how they relate to authoritarian preferences. Countries cluster in similar ways across the two dimensions. Nordic and Northwestern European countries consistently lie in the high-egalitarian, low-authoritarian area; several Central and Southern European countries form an intermediate zone; and a group of Eastern and Southeastern European countries appear where egalitarian views are weaker and authoritarian acceptance is higher. The similarity of these patterns suggests that attitudes toward gender roles in private and public spheres are closely interconnected and form part of the same broader cultural environment in which boys and men learn to interpret authority, hierarchy, and gender relations. The analysis focuses here on two complementary dimensions—hostile and

modern sexism—which reflect different expressions of gender resentment and far-right positioning, signaling broader political orientations tied to hierarchy and exclusion.

The two scatter plots in

Figure 23 relate hostile and modern sexism to support far-right positions, allowing us to see whether explicit and more subtle forms of gender resentment align with broader political orientations.

Figure 23 Hostile and Modern Sexism in Relation to Far-Right Support

Source: European Social Survey (ESS) Round 11, 2023; national election results (far-right vote share). Hostile sexism is measured through agreement with the statement that “Women seek power over men”, while modern sexism reflects the belief that “Women exaggerate harassment claims”. Far-right support refers to the share of respondents placing themselves on far-right party positions (on a scale of 0–10). Correlations show a modest positive association between hostile sexism and far-right support ($r = 0.38$) and a slightly weaker association between modern sexism and far-right support ($r = 0.29$).

Despite the different items used, the two plots display very similar configurations. Poland and Hungary lie clearly at the high-sexism, high-far-right end, with Latvia, Lithuania, and Cyprus also positioned toward the upper right of both figures. At the opposite end, Sweden, Ireland, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Germany consistently cluster where sexist attitudes and far-right support are both low. A number of countries—including Slovenia, Croatia, France, Italy, Spain, and Austria—fall in intermediate positions across both indicators.

The correlations, while not particularly high, are positive in both cases, reinforcing the idea that skepticism toward gender equality tends to move together with greater openness to far-right political messages. The fact that the same countries regroup in similar ways across the two plots suggests that explicit and modern forms of sexism are embedded within a shared cultural environment, shaping how gender relations and political authority are interpreted across Europe.

Taken together, the three sets of scatter plots (Figure 21, Figure 22, and

Figure 23) reveal striking regularity. Despite relying on different indicators—gender equality, democratic quality, authoritarian attitudes, gender norms in private and public life, hostile and modern sexism, and far-right positioning—the countries tend to cluster in remarkably consistent ways. The patterns are not identical across all figures, but the overall structure often reappears enough to indicate that the socialization of boys and men takes place within broader cultural, institutional, and socioeconomic environments that are both coherent and self-reinforcing.

A first group of countries consistently appears in the least egalitarian parts of the plots. Hungary, Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania, Cyprus, and Malta tend to cluster where support for authoritarian leadership, lower gender-egalitarian views, and higher levels of sexist attitudes converge. Although each country has its own trajectory, they generally share features such as higher income inequality, lower levels of disposable income, weaker welfare provisions, less comprehensive gender-equality policies, slower digital transformation, and more constrained political or civic environments. They also tend to display lower trust in institutions, weaker protection against hate speech or discrimination, and more traditional gender norms in both family and public life. These factors contribute to socialization contexts in which hierarchical gender expectations and skepticism toward egalitarian change are more strongly embedded. In such settings, boys and men are more likely to encounter models of masculinity that normalize unequal power relations and place less emphasis on democratic norms, such as inclusion, accountability, and shared authority—even if countervailing influences remain present.

A second set of countries—France, Austria, Spain, Slovenia, Croatia, Italy, Czechia, Greece, Slovakia, Estonia, and Portugal—tends to occupy intermediate positions across most scatter plots. They display broadly democratic institutional frameworks and moderately egalitarian gender norms but also greater internal variation, stronger political polarization, or slower diffusion of egalitarian attitudes compared to the most advanced countries. Some of these states combine strong educational systems with persistent regional or rural–urban divides; others show higher inequality or more constrained welfare capacity. Digitalization and trust in institutions also vary considerably. These conditions create environments in which young

people are more frequently exposed to norms of shared power, institutional trust, and gender equality as part of everyday life. While this does not imply that tendencies toward hierarchical or exclusionary masculinities are absent, it suggests that such environments are generally more conducive to the development of democratic forms of masculinity and make defensive or anti-egalitarian models less socially reinforced.

A thirds group includes Sweden, Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, Ireland, Belgium, Germany, and Luxembourg. Across nearly all indicators, these countries occupy the most egalitarian and democratic parts of each distribution. They combine strong gender-equality outcomes with robust democratic institutions, very low support for authoritarian leadership, low acceptance of sexist beliefs, and limited resonance of far-right political messages. As described in detail in the individual country profiles, these attitudinal patterns align with national structural features, such as high educational attainment, well-funded welfare states, relatively low-income inequality, strong labor market participation for both women and men, advanced digitalization, and more comprehensive protections for minority groups, including LGBTQ+ communities. These conditions create environments in which young people grow up encountering norms of shared power, institutional trust, and gender equality as part of everyday life.

Across all three clusters, the recurrence of similar country groupings across conceptually different indicators is notable. The associations displayed in this section suggest that gender norms, political attitudes, and broader institutional conditions are not isolated phenomena but elements of a larger ecosystem shaping how boys and men learn to interpret authority, fairness, rights, and gender relations. The consistency of these patterns underscores that socialization into more democratic or more hierarchical masculinities reflects deep structural and cultural configurations—rooted in education systems, labor market opportunities, inequality levels, media environments, welfare institutions, and democratic quality. The cross-cutting alignments help explain why the same groups of countries repeatedly appear together across the figures; they represent systems in which material conditions, political structures, and cultural norms reinforce one another, producing stable and distinctive environments of socialization across Europe.

7. MAJOR CONCLUSIONS & KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

Socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities involves processes at multiple levels. It does not concern only individual preferences or dispositions; rather, masculine gender norms and democratic values are transmitted through primary and secondary socialization processes in daily social interactions among individuals and between individuals and institutions. From a constructivist perspective, individuals act as crucial agents in this process. In fact, they contribute to the production and reproduction of gender norms, masculinity ideals, and democratic cultures. These interactions occur within broader societal contexts, where cultural and structural elements jointly shape the conditions of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities.

By adopting a multidimensional approach, the report identified key elements for understanding how cultural and structural elements of the EU27 societal contexts can influence socialization processes. Each European country displays its unique gender and democratic culture, as a result of the specific historical pathway involving cultural, political, and economic development. The country profiles presented in the report illustrate how social, cultural, economic, and legal norms within national contexts relate to gender roles and masculine norms. Furthermore, the report highlights common patterns of socialization into (anti-)democratic masculinities and classifies countries into three clusters based on their combined support for gender equality and liberal democracy.

The report relies on secondary data. While structural dimensions of European societies are well documented, information on cultural dimensions—particularly masculinities—remains limited, outdated, or restricted to a subset of countries. The choice of indicators reflects these constraints, and interpretations of socialization contexts depend directly on the indicators employed. In some cases, adequate proxies for target concepts were available; however, several dimensions remain underexplored due to the absence of cross-national data (e.g., the spread of the manosphere, support for patriarchal masculinity, rates of hate crimes).

Despite these limitations, the overview provided in the report allows us to contribute to a greater understanding of the roots of anti-democratic masculinities by situating them within their societal contexts and identifying elements that risk normalizing them. Also, it points to

directions for social and policy interventions that can foster democratic masculinities by reshaping the conditions of socialization.

The cross-national patterns suggest several areas that merit particular attention. Although clustering depends on the indicators used, results remain consistent across different variable sets analyzed in the report. Countries in the first cluster (Hungary, Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania, Cyprus, and Malta) display a convergence of hierarchical gender norms, authoritarian preferences, and socioeconomic vulnerabilities. These countries may benefit from targeted initiatives that strengthen civic education, expand access to quality schooling, and support young people's opportunities in rural and urban areas. Addressing inequalities—whether economic, territorial, or digital—appears particularly relevant, as these divides often intersect with the cultural environments in which gender norms take shape.

The more intermediate cluster includes France, Austria, Spain, Slovenia, Croatia, Italy, Czechia, Greece, Slovakia, Estonia, and Portugal. In these countries, democratic institutions and egalitarian norms coexist with areas of tension or slower diffusion of change. Effective interventions may focus on reducing internal disparities, supporting institutional trust, and reinforcing inclusive public discourses that counter polarization.

The third cluster refers to the most egalitarian and democratic contexts, which includes Sweden, Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, Ireland, Belgium, Germany, and Luxembourg. For these countries, the key challenge is sustaining existing achievements. Policymakers must ensure that welfare systems, education, and gender-equality infrastructures remain robust and that emerging forms of backlash or disinformation do not erode the conditions that currently support more democratic forms of masculinity. More broadly, reinforcing trust in institutions, supporting independent media, and increasing the visibility of diverse role models can help create more inclusive climates for the socialization of boys and men.

While the pathways differ across countries, the recurring clusters observed in the data point to the importance of coordinated long-term strategies that address structural conditions and cultural norms together rather than isolated interventions.

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ANNEX I. THE NATIONAL CONTEXTS OF SOCIALIZATION INTO (ANTI-)DEMOCRATIC MASCULINITIES: THE EU27 COUNTRY PROFILES

I.1 AUSTRIA

I.1.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Austria’s socioeconomic landscape is characterized by a level of economic development above the European average and a high degree of macroeconomic stability while displaying structural vulnerabilities and persistent internal disparities. Table 3 summarizes selected socioeconomic and gender equality indicators for Austria compared with the EU27.

Table 3 Socioeconomic conditions in Austria compared with the EU27

	Austria	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	116.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	27.7	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	16.9	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	87.8	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	77.0	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	66.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	91	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market figures confirm an overall positive picture, which is however marked by major gender differences. The employment rate among those aged 15–64 is 77.5% for men and 70.7% for women (Eurostat 2024b). Although these values are higher than the European average (75.3% and 66.2%, respectively), the gender gap remains pronounced and reflects deep imbalances in paid work and professional opportunities. This gap has direct consequences for women’s economic autonomy and contributes to perpetuating traditional models of labor participation.

Austria also performs above the EU average across all dimensions of the Gender Equality Index (money, work, knowledge, and health), indicating a relatively more advanced context, although gaps remain, particularly in the area of knowledge (Table 3). Early school leaving is 9.2% among boys and 7.0% among girls, revealing vulnerabilities that may affect social mobility and the quality of labor market entry (Eurostat 2024a).

The demographic structure is another salient factor. The old-age dependency ratio is 30.2, below the European average (33.9) yet still indicative of a progressively aging population (Eurostat 2024e). This trend implies growing pressure on pension and welfare systems and calls for effective intergenerational support policies. Territorial distribution shows that 30.2% of the population lives in rural areas, a figure that translates into inequalities in access to services, educational opportunities, and infrastructure (OECD 2023a). The share of the foreign-born population (22.1%) is among the highest in Europe (Eurostat 2022).

Finally, the social expenditure of 31.6% of the GDP reflects an extensive and articulated welfare system (OECD 2024b). Austria's welfare model has helped contain inequalities and absorb the effects of economic crises and labor market transformations. However, public support is less effective in addressing emerging challenges, such as youth precariousness, aging, and the reconciliation of work and family life. In sum, Austria's socioeconomic and institutional structure combines high levels of well-being and macroeconomic stability with persistent gender gaps, demographic challenges, and social vulnerabilities.

I.1.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Austria ranks among the European countries with the most consolidated democratic institutions and a political tradition strongly anchored in the rule of law and respect for fundamental rights. At the same time, the value landscape reveals tensions and ambivalences, especially in relation to gender equality, social inclusion, and the protection of minorities.

According to Freedom in the World, Austria scores 93/100 in 2024, classified as “Free”, confirming a solid guarantee of political and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index produced by the Economist Intelligence Unit assigns the country 8.28/10, placing it among “full democracies” and indicating a political system characterized by pluralism, participation, and institutional stability (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). The Rule of Law Index is also high (0.79), pointing to effective law enforcement, an independent judiciary, and a relatively efficient institutional context, although with room for improvement regarding case duration and access to justice (World Justice Project 2024). In line with these results, V-Dem's civil liberties index reaches 0.91, underscoring the advanced level of protection of fundamental rights (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

On gender equality, the picture is more subtle. Austria's overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 71.7, in line with the EU27 average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, the time dimension—concerning the distribution of care and domestic work—scores 68.4 (vs. 68.5 EU), indicating that caregiving responsibilities still fall disproportionately on women (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Lagging even more is power, which measures women's presence in decision-making; with 57.1 compared to an EU average of 61.4, Austria remains below the European average, reflecting persistent underrepresentation of women in top positions in politics and the economy (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

The institutional value landscape is also shaped by inclusion and pluralism policies. The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) gives Austria a score of 53 (MIPEX 2023), indicative of mid-level integration policies, with significant progress in schooling and health but persistent obstacles regarding citizenship and political participation. The LGBTQI+ rights framework is notably more problematic. According to Rainbow Europe, Austria scores only 23.17/100, one of the lowest values in the EU (ILGA-Europe 2025). This reflects important legislative gaps, such as the absence of hate crime aggravating circumstances based on sexual orientation or gender identity and the lack of full legal recognition of rainbow families.

The Austrian people's attitudes toward the EU offer another perspective on Austria's potential closeness to European values. In 2024, 49% of Austrians report trusting the European Parliament, a figure slightly below the EU average yet indicative of a relatively stable link with the European project (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Austria presents itself as a solid democracy characterized by efficient institutions, high standards of civil liberties, and a widespread respect for fundamental democratic values. However, the full realization of gender equality remains an open challenge—particularly regarding access to positions of power—as does the creation of a truly inclusive environment for migrants and LGBTQI+ people. Trust in European institutions remains relatively high, but the persistence of Eurosceptic segments and the difficulty of translating equality principles into everyday practices reveal a value system in transition, where democratic principles coexist with tensions linked to identity, belonging, and rights.

I.1.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Austria display a complex dynamic in which significant openings toward equality coexist with entrenched stereotypes and cultural resistances that continue to shape the trajectories of women and men in both public and private spheres. As displayed in Figure 24, based on data from the Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), expectations about women’s caregiving responsibilities have not disappeared. Although slightly below the EU average, these figures reveal a deeply rooted conception that associates family care primarily with women’s responsibilities and implicitly denies full compatibility of employment and motherhood.

Figure 24 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Austria

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Cultural norms concerning masculinity also reflect an ambivalent picture. If, on the one hand, 74% of Austrians deem it “acceptable” for a man to cry—a sign of a gradual overcoming of traditional emotional stereotypes—on the other hand, a more rigid normative model persists: 25% consider a man who takes parental leave to show a lack of ambition for their career, 27% maintain that the man should have “the final say” in family decisions, and 49% believe men

are “naturally less competent than women” at housework (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Attitudes toward gender equality are further complicated by a growing climate of cultural polarization. Around 47% of Austrians believe that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Overall, these perceptions depict a society in which traditional models and new norms coexist and compete. On the one hand, significant openings toward equality emerge—especially in the public sphere and in the emotional representation of masculinity; on the other hand, cultural expectations still assign primary caregiving to women and decision-making and breadwinning roles to men. Moreover, the perception that feminism has overshot its goals and the desire to “stabilize” equality gains indicates a risk of defensive reactions and backlash against gender policies.

In Austria, attitudes toward gender and sexuality show clear generational gradients that intersect with persistent gender gaps. Support for the idea that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” is high overall but strongest among young women (93% vs. 86% of young men), while agreement declines slightly with age—more among men (down to 82% at 56+) than among women—and disagreement grows modestly in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Hostile gender stereotypes follow the opposite pattern. Women reject them far more than men at every age: among under-35s, 76% of women say harassment is “never/rarely” exaggerated, compared with 46% of men; the “often/always” option is chosen by 4% of young women and 15% of young men. With age, skepticism rises for both sexes, especially women (12% “often/always” at 56+), while rejection drops. A similar gradient appears for the claim that women try to gain power over men, with young men endorsing it more (24% vs. 10% of young women) and women’s endorsement rising somewhat in older cohorts (15%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). “Benevolent” sexism shows a different pattern. Men are more likely than women to reject the idea that women should be protected by men (65–67% “never/rarely” across ages). Among women, rejection is lower—especially among younger cohorts (45%)—while endorsement (“often/always”) is highest among young women (18%) and declines with age (14% at 56+)

Taken together, these patterns suggest a double movement. Younger Austrians—especially women—are the most supportive of LGBTQI+ freedoms and the most resistant to hostile

gender stereotypes. At the same time, traces of benevolent sexism persist among young women, even as older women become more critical of both benevolent and hostile gender norms. Men, in contrast, maintain a higher endorsement of hostile stereotypes at every age, with only modest generational softening. The result is a value landscape where age pushes attitudes in a broadly egalitarian direction, while gender still structures where doubts and residual traditionalism linger.

I.1.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Austria is a structural and persistent problem that continues to significantly affect the quality of democracy and the full realization of fundamental rights. Although the country has an advanced legal framework and a consolidated institutional system, prevalence levels, awareness of rights, and access to services still show ample room for improvement.

According to data from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. (2024), 35.7% of Austrian women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15. This figure, higher than the EU27 average (31%), confirms the systemic diffusion of the phenomenon and indicates that violence cannot be considered marginal or residual. Forms of violence perpetrated by partners or ex-partners reveal the structural dimension even more clearly. Around 37.8% of women report having experienced psychological violence, physical violence or threats, and/or sexual violence, a figure significantly higher than in many European countries and one that reflects the breadth of control and coercion dynamics unfolding within intimate relationships (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures may be interpreted not only as a sign of high prevalence but also as an indication of a greater ability to recognize and name nonphysical forms of violence, often normalized in everyday culture.

A critical element concerns knowledge of and access to support services. Only 3% of women victims of violence report not being aware of the existence of help services, a value well below the European average (19%) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2015). However, only 36.1 were aware of the right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). These results highlight a gap between general knowledge of service availability and awareness of specific

entitlements, suggesting that limited information about concrete rights can hinder help-seeking and constrain effective access to protection—especially for the most vulnerable.

The most extreme forms of violence portray an even more dramatic reality. The rate of intentional homicides of women by partners or relatives in Austria is 0.63 per 100,000 inhabitants, while the comparable figure for men is 0.29 (Eurostat, 2023). This high incidence points to serious gaps in the capacity to prevent violent escalation and to intervene promptly in high-risk cases. It also underlines how lethal violence remains deeply rooted in relational and domestic dynamics, with profound implications for victim protection and security policies.

On the legal and institutional front, Austria has taken important steps. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on November 14, 2013, and entered into force on August 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). This places the country among the active Council of Europe members in the fight against gender-based and domestic violence. However, the gap between the legislative framework and its effective implementation remains significant. Persistently high levels of violence and the relatively high incidence of femicides indicate that prevention and protection policies are still insufficient and that a gap exists between formal principles and operational practices.

I.1.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a privileged lens through which to observe the interaction between democracy, gender inequalities, and power dynamics in Austrian society. The emerging picture is that of a consolidated and formally robust institutional system marked by elements of fragility, polarization, and widespread skepticism toward representative institutions.

Voter turnout is the first indicator of democratic quality. In the 2024 European elections, turnout in Austria was 56.25%, above the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This reflects a relatively high degree of civic mobilization and a widespread sense of belonging to the European project while still remaining below participation levels typically recorded in national elections.

On gender representation, women hold 42% of seats in Austria's parliament, above the European average (33%) and a sign of progress over the past decade in promoting women's

access to elected office. The ideological distribution of the party system is another key element. According to ParlGov data (ParlGov 2023), the vote share of Austria’s conservative People’s Party (ÖVP) is 37.5, and that of the Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ) is 16.2. These figures reflect a trend common to many European democracies: the growth and consolidation of conservative and nationalist forces, with important consequences for social policies, civil rights, and gender equality.

The quality of democracy is confirmed by several indicators. V-Dem’s Electoral Democracy Index assigns Austria 0.84 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), slightly below the Nordic countries but still high in the European context. Austria’s democracy is thus based on solid institutions and an effective system of checks and balances, even if critical issues remain regarding the slowness of judicial processes and equitable access to justice.

Trust in political institutions, however, is moderate. Only 8.8% say they trust politicians (value from 8 to 10 on a scale of 0–10) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), while 48% express trust in the national government and 41% in political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Trust in European institutions is higher—56% of Austrians say they trust the European Parliament, a figure exceeding that for national institutions and may be indicative of the legitimating role the EU continues to play in the country (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). This distance is also reflected in interest in politics—54% of the population declares being interested in political life (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), while a significant share remains detached or disillusioned regarding institutions’ ability to address everyday needs.

Attitudinal data point to a citizenry broadly committed to democratic norms yet not immune to illiberal temptations. In the World Values Survey (Wave 7), 66.6% rate authoritarian alternatives as “very bad”, but a non-negligible minority provides more accommodating evaluations; likewise, 79.8% say political violence is “never justifiable”, while small shares deem it acceptable “in some circumstances” (Haerpfer et al. 2024). Although small, its existence signals a potential risk of radicalization, especially amid growing political polarization and identity conflicts.

Austria's level of polarization is rated 2.09/4 by V-Dem (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating a political system marked by strong ideological and cultural divisions. Economic power distribution is likewise significant—with a score of 2,36/4, power is predominantly concentrated among the wealthiest classes, although the middle and working classes retain some influence.

In Austria, ideological self-placement is predominantly centrist across all cohorts, but age and gender shape the extremes. Among women, centrism grows with age, right-wing identification remains limited, and the far right is minimal (0.6–1.7%). Younger women stand out on the left—10.4% place themselves on the far left and 18.1% on the left (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Men also converge at the center but show a thicker conservative tail—the right attracts 12.2% of those under 35 and around 15–16% in older groups, while the far right remains higher than among women (2.0–4.1%). On the left, younger men reach 17.7% (left) and 4.1% (far left), with slight declines in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, gendered polarization emerges at the margins. Younger women cluster more on the far left, while men—especially from midlife onward—are more present on the right and far right, despite centrism remaining dominant for all.

Overall, Austria's political system appears to be a delicate equilibrium. Solid institutions and growing gender representation coexist with low levels of trust, selective participation, increasing polarization, and the presence of minorities inclined to accept authoritarian alternatives. These elements depict a complex terrain for political socialization and for the evolution of democratic norms, in which formal adherence to liberal principles intertwines with the dynamics of distrust, fragmentation, and cultural resistance.

I.1.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial for understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Austria, the online ecosystem is marked by the broad diffusion of digital information and relatively high trust in web-based content while also showing significant vulnerabilities, especially in media literacy and exposure to content hostile to democracy and gender equality.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread. According to a recent Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), 39% of the population report reading news online every day, a share in line with the European average and indicative of the centrality of digital media in Austria’s public and political life. In parallel, 39% say they regularly use social networks as a source of political information, confirming the growing role of digital media as spaces for socialization and public-opinion formation.

Trust in online sources is relatively high—49% of Austrians say they trust news found on the internet, while 39% trust information disseminated through social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These values, above the EU average, indicate an information environment in which digital media enjoy significant legitimacy but also signal potential vulnerability to the spread of false or manipulative content.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widespread. Around 78% of the population considers disinformation a “serious problem for democracy”, slightly below the EU average (81%) but still indicative of high awareness (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, about 24% report having been “often” or “very often” exposed to misleading content in the week before the survey. However, the ability to recognize fake news remains limited—only 15% feel “very confident” they can identify it, while over half (55%) say they can do so “only sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and effective skills indicates substantial room for improvement in civic and digital education.

The dimension of online radicalization deserves particular attention, especially regarding misogynist and anti-egalitarian communities. Austria is among the European countries where the presence of active users in misogynist online networks has been documented. According to an analysis by Moonshot for the European Commission, between 2017 and 2020, 10 Austrian users were identified on incels.is, one of the main digital platforms linked to the “manosphere” ideology (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These online spaces combine hostility toward women’s rights with anti-democratic and anti-feminist narratives, fueling gender radicalization and rejection of equality and pluralism.

Austria's digital environment thus has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media offer significant spaces for access to information, political participation, and public debate, with levels of trust and engagement above the European average. On the other hand, high exposure to disinformation, still-limited critical skills, and the structured presence of misogynist and anti-democratic communities pose concrete risks to the quality of public debate and democratic resilience.

I.1.7 Youth inclusion and agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country's ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Austria, the picture appears relatively favorable compared with the European average—especially in relational terms and cultural openness—yet significant fragilities persist in pathways to empowerment, access to education, and socioeconomic autonomy.

According to the Youth Progress Index (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), Austria scores 88/100, placing it in the medium–high range of European countries. This value reflects a combination of relatively strong material conditions and positive perceptions of social inclusion but also the presence of areas where the transition to adulthood is hindered by structural barriers. A particularly positive element is openness to diversity. Data indicate that Austrian youth evaluate opportunities for socialization and inclusion very favorably—80% regard Austria as a “good place” for immigrants, and 80% consider it so for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These values—higher than perceptions in the general population—attest to the younger generations' more inclusive and cosmopolitan stance, which may, in the long term, help reinforce democratic values and respect for rights. The relational dimension is also positive—80% of young people favorably evaluate opportunities to make friends and build social networks, indicating relatively robust youth social capital.

On the educational and economic front, some areas still warrant attention. The share of young men leaving education or training early is 9%, compared with 7% among young women (Eurostat 2024a) These are relatively low values, and both remain below the EU average, yet they nonetheless highlight small but persistent gender differences in school continuity. More broadly, Austria combines openness to diversity, solid social networks, and a general

orientation toward inclusion with challenges that continue to emerge in the labor market, gender equality, and opportunities for upward mobility.

I.1.8 Being socialized in Austria

Being socialized in Austria means growing up in a procedural democracy with strong formal guarantees but low political trust and pronounced polarization. This combination shapes how authority and participation are learned, often producing ambivalent orientations toward public life. Gender norms evolve slowly—women’s presence in public life has expanded, yet expectations of male authority, breadwinning, and restrained emotionality remain influential. Younger cohorts endorse more egalitarian values, but these coexist with enduring stereotypes around leadership and family roles. The digital sphere intensifies these contradictions, circulating both democratic and reactionary scripts. Overall, masculine gender norms in Austria tend to oscillate between egalitarian aspirations and attachments to hierarchy, control, and traditional family expectations.

I.2 BELGIUM

I.2.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Belgium’s socioeconomic landscape combines a level of development above the European average with the stabilizing capacity of a mature welfare state while still exhibiting structural vulnerabilities and enduring internal disparities (Table 4).

Table 4 Socioeconomic conditions in Belgium compared with the EU27

	Belgium	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	116.00	100,00
Gini coefficient	22	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	18.2	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	90.9	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	75.7	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	73.4	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	88.5	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market confirms an overall positive picture but remains marked by gender asymmetries. Among people aged 15–64, the employment rate is 70.2% for men and 63.3%

for women (Eurostat 2024b). Despite good outcomes on the Gender Equality Index dimensions that capture economic resources and labor-market participation (Table 4), the persistence of this gap reflects deep imbalances in paid work and career opportunities, with direct consequences for women’s economic autonomy across the life course.

Education and skills are strategic strengths highlighted by strong horizontal segregation. The segregation index is 67.6, indicating pronounced sorting across fields of study. Tertiary students in STEM are 10 females per 1,000 people, while men are 24 per 1,000 people (Eurostat 2023b). The women’s graduation ratio is 24.1 women per 100 men on the reported measure (Eurostat 2023a), and early leaving remains low and gendered (9.2% for boys and 4.8% for girls) (Eurostat 2024a). Together the score on the gender index on knowledge, these data reveal strong human-capital pipelines as well as “glass walls” that channel trajectories early and later translate into occupational segregation Table 4.

Demographic and territorial structures add another layer of constraint and opportunity. Belgium is highly urban (rural population 8.37%) (OECD 2023a) and aging (old-age dependency ratio 31.3) (Eurostat 2024e), with a sizable foreign-born population of 19.7% (Eurostat 2022). These features sustain economic dynamism and labor supply but require continuous investment in integration, intergenerational support, and local service capacity. A broad welfare architecture—social expenditure at 28.6% of GDP (OECD 2024b)—mitigates shocks and compresses inequality, while the gender index on health signals strong health capabilities (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Family policy remains a key lever for closing the care gap that feeds back into employment and pay. Paternal leave stands at 4 (length), with an average payment level of 78.6 on scale (OECD 2024a), indicating the presence of support but also scope to strengthen incentives for men’s take-up. In sum, Belgium’s socioeconomic and institutional structure couples high income, low measured inequality, and expansive social spending with persistent gender gaps, field-of-study segregation, and demographic pressures. The country’s central assets—robust welfare and strong human capital—deliver more inclusive outcomes as care, segregation, and integration bottlenecks are faced in tandem.

I.2.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Belgium ranks among the European countries with the most consolidated democratic institutions and a political tradition strongly anchored in the rule of law and the protection of fundamental rights. The country's liberal-democratic profile is reflected in a Freedom in the World score of 96/100 (Freedom House 2025), a Democracy Index of 7.64/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), a Rule of Law value of 0.78 (World Justice Project 2024), and a Civil Liberties score of 0.96 (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Together, these indicators point to a stable institutional environment characterized by pluralism, effective legal enforcement, and robust guarantees of civil rights, even if efficiency and access issues still invite ongoing attention.

Regarding gender equality, the picture is generally strong but uneven across dimensions. Belgium's overall Gender Equality Index stands at 76.1 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling performance above the EU average. Yet the time dimension—capturing the distribution of care and domestic work—lags at 64.7, while the power dimension—women's presence in decision-making—performs notably better at 72.3 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This asymmetry suggests that formal equality and access to leadership have advanced further than the equal sharing of unpaid work, with evident knock-on effects on labor market participation and careers.

Inclusion and pluralism policies are core strengths. Belgium records 100 on the migrant-integration policy measure in the dataset (MIPEX 2023) and 100 for hate-speech/hate-crime protections related to sexual orientation and gender identity. The Rainbow Europe score reaches 76, indicating a comparatively advanced LGBTQI+ rights framework (ILGA-Europe 2025). These institutional features underpin a rights environment broadly aligned with European equality norms.

Public attitudes toward the EU complement this picture. Trust in the European Parliament is high (59% “tend to trust”) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), while 17% consider that European unification has “gone too far” (0-3 on a scale of 0–10) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), pointing to a relatively stable anchoring in the European project even amid wider continental debates.

I.2.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Belgium reveal a familiar ambivalence: broad support for equality in public life coexists with persistent expectations around family roles that continue to shape everyday behavior. As displayed in Figure 25, based on data from the Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), expectations about women’s caregiving responsibilities have not disappeared but represent the expression of a minority of Belgians. These figures, while not majoritarian, indicate a durable association between care and femininity that helps explain why the time (65) domain remains the laggard in gender-equality architecture despite strong scores elsewhere (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Figure 25 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Belgium

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of workplace fairness are equally revealing. A clear majority—65.2%—say women are treated less fairly at work (versus 3.2% who say men are), while 31.6% perceive equal treatment (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). However, the same public endorses parity in leadership—76% agree that gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Preference for leaders is largely gender-neutral—14% would prefer a man, 16% a woman, and 66% express no preference—suggesting that

symbolic acceptance of women's leadership has diffused widely (King's Global Institute for Women's Leadership and Ipsos 2024).

Attitudes toward sexual harassment show some residual skepticism. Regarding the claim that women exaggerate harassment at work, answers are distributed as 8.5% "never", 32.4% "rarely", and 43.3% "sometimes" (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Read together with structural indicators, these attitudes clarify a consistent pattern—normative and symbolic support for equality in the public sphere advances faster than the equal sharing of unpaid care and everyday practices, with consequences for labor market participation and career progression.

Taken together, these patterns point to gendered polarization at the margins. Younger women are most represented on the left, whereas men—at every age—are more present on the right (and slightly more on the far right). With age, both sexes gravitate toward the center, narrowing but not erasing the gender gap.

1.2.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Belgium remains a structural challenge that intersects with equality, health, and access-to-justice agendas. On the prevalence side, 31.3% of ever-partnered women report having experienced psychological violence, physical violence (including threats), and/or sexual violence by an intimate partner, while 29.1% of women report violence by any perpetrator (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). In the Gender Equality Index, Belgium's Violence composite stands at 25.9, signaling progress in some protective dimensions but confirming that exposure and harm remain non-negligible (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Knowledge of rights and navigation of services show a clear asymmetry between general service visibility and rights literacy. Awareness of the existence of support services reaches 77.5% (Eurostat 2021a), yet awareness of the right to free legal aid is only 37.6% (Eurostat 2021a). This gap suggests that while many women know that help is "out there", fewer know the concrete entitlements that can unlock representation, protection orders, and sustained follow-up—an information bottleneck that can depress help-seeking and constrain effective protection, especially for the most vulnerable.

On the legal and institutional front, Belgium has long aligned with European platforms. It signed the Istanbul Convention on September 11, 2012, ratified it on March 14, 2016, and entered it into force on July 1, 2016 (Council of Europe 2025).

1.2.5 Political dimension

Belgium's political system combines consolidated liberal-democratic institutions with areas of social contestation that show through participation, representation, trust, and the distribution of influence. Electoral mobilization is very high—turnout in the 2024 European elections was 89%—sustained by compulsory voting and a long tradition of civic participation (European Parliament 2024). Women's descriptive representation is comparatively strong—43% of seats in the national parliament are held by women—indicating steady progress in access to elected office (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Institutional quality indicators remain robust—the Electoral Democracy Index stands at 0.89, consistent with free competitive elections and pluralism (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

At the same time, confidence in representative institutions is only moderate. People living in Belgium place trust in political parties at 39%, trust in the national parliament at 50% and trust in the European Parliament at 59%; only 10.4% say that European unification has “gone too far” (total 0-2 on scale 0-10) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), signaling a broadly positive anchoring in the EU.

Polarization and influence patterns help explain why equality agendas remain politically salient. Political polarization is rated 2.00/4, while power distributed by socioeconomic position is 3.09/4, indicating influence skewed toward the better off, even within a high-capacity welfare state (Varieties of Democracy 2024). The Government Coalition Left-Right Index at 1.186 points to a slightly right-of-center governing profile (Varieties of Democracy 2024). In sum, Belgium pairs strong rules and high participation with middling trust and measurable polarization—conditions that keep distributional and gender-equality questions open to contestation, even as women's representation and EU-level legitimacy remain comparatively high.

According to ParlGov data (ParlGov 2023), the New Flemish Alliance (N-VA) secures 16.7% of the vote, the Parti Socialiste (PS) has 13.3%, and Vlaams Belang (VB) has 12.0%. This configuration mirrors a pattern seen across many European democracies: the growth and

consolidation of national-conservative poles—here, the Flemish N-VA/VB bloc—pushing the agenda toward identity, migration, and law-and-order issues, with significant implications for social policy, civil rights, and gender equality. At the same time, the PS remains the principal francophone left anchor on redistribution and welfare, making coalition formation an exercise in balancing both ideological and linguistic cleavages.

Finally, generational and gender differences help shape the political arena. In Belgium, ideological self-placement is overwhelmingly centrist across cohorts, but age and gender still contour the tails of the distribution. Among women, the center dominates and even grows with age. Women’s identification with the right is modest in youth and rises with age (for older cohort reaches 20.9%), while the far right remains marginal. On the left pole, young women stand out: 6.2% of women aged 35 or younger choose the far left and another 27.8% place themselves on the left (falling to 21.3% and 12.1% in the two older cohorts) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Among men, the center is likewise the modal choice, but the right-hand tail is thicker than among women. The right attracts 30.9% of men aged 35 or younger and 27.7–25.9% among those aged 36–55 and 56+, and the far right—though small—remains consistently higher for men (3.0–4.1%) than for women (1.6–3.4%). On the left, men aged 35 or younger report 15.7% on the left and 2.6% on the far left; with age, both shares dip slightly (left 15.5–13.4%, far left 2.7–4.1%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

1.2.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now crucial to understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Belgium, the online ecosystem combines wide access to digital news with comparatively high trust in web-based content while also revealing vulnerabilities in media literacy and exposure to hostile or manipulative narratives. The use of digital platforms for news is widespread. According to Eurobarometer, 43% of Belgians report reading news online every day—with a further 18% doing so two or three times a week—underscoring the centrality of digital media in public and political life (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). In parallel, trust in online sources is substantial—51% say they tend to trust websites for news, while 34% extend that trust to

social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These values indicate a high degree of legitimacy for digital media but also signal potential vulnerability to the spread of false or manipulative content.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widespread. Around 78% consider the existence of false or misleading news a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c); self-reported exposure is frequent, with 19% “very often” or “often” encountering such content in the previous week (European Commission. Directorate-General for Communication & Kantar. 2022). However, the ability to recognize falsehoods remains limited—only 9% feel very confident in identifying disinformation, and 48% are somewhat confident (ParlGov 2023), pointing to a persistent gap between awareness and diagnostic skills.

The dimension of online radicalization also deserves attention. Belgium appears in the European mapping of misogynist/anti-egalitarian communities online: between 2017 and 2020, analyses identified Belgian users on incels.is, one of the main platforms associated with the “manosphere” ideology (13 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021).

Belgium’s digital environment thus has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media provide significant arenas for information access, political participation, and public debate, backed by relatively high trust. On the other hand, high exposure to disinformation, limited critical skills, and the documented presence of misogynist communities pose concrete risks for the quality of public discourse and democratic resilience.

I.2.7 Youth inclusion and agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Belgium, the picture appears relatively favorable—especially in relational terms and cultural openness—yet significant fragilities persist in pathways to empowerment, access to education, and socioeconomic autonomy. According to the Youth Progress Index (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), Belgian youth report strong conditions for social inclusion. A particularly positive element is openness to diversity. The data indicate that young people evaluate opportunities for socialization and inclusion very favorably—80% regard Belgium as a “good place for

immigrants”, and 80% consider it so for gay and lesbian people. The relational dimension is also positive, with 80% favorably evaluating opportunities to make friends and build social networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These values—higher than perceptions usually found in the general population—point to a more inclusive and cosmopolitan stance among younger generations, which, in the long run, can reinforce democratic values and respect for rights. On the education side, pipelines are strong. The share of young women aged 25–29 with 12–18 years of education reaches 88.7%, signaling high attainment at the moment in which careers consolidate (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022).

Early school leaving is 9.2% among boys and 4.8% among girls, a medium level according to EU standards. The pattern is clearly gendered, with boys more exposed to early dropout risks. (Eurostat 2024a). In sum, Belgium socializes new generations within high-attainment education pipelines and a rights-rich institutional setting, but gendered study choices, unequal care expectations, and the employment gap at entry continue to shape agency and autonomy.

I.2.8 Being socialized in Belgium

Being socialized in Belgium means growing up within strong democratic institutions that ensure high participation and substantial female representation, yet every day, trust in politicians remains moderate, and political influence unevenly distributed. Gender equality shows a specific imbalance. Public-sphere opportunities are strong, but care work remains unequally shared, maintaining expectations that link responsibility and provision to men. Social attitudes support balanced leadership but retain elements of traditional family norms. Digital media are widely used, accompanied by concerns about disinformation and low confidence in identifying it. In this environment, masculine gender norms in Belgium balance openness to equality with persistent expectations of responsibility, emotional restraint, and family-centered roles.

I.3 BULGARIA

I.3.1 Socioeconomic structure and institutional structure

Bulgaria’s socioeconomic landscape sits considerably below the EU average in terms of material prosperity and remains marked by structural vulnerabilities Table 5.

Table 5 Socioeconomic conditions in Bulgaria compared with the EU27

	Bulgaria	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	66.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	39.6	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	30,3	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	66.6	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	70.9	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	57.8	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	78.3	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Outcomes in the labor market are uneven and continue to display gender asymmetries. Among 15–64-year-olds, employment stands at 74.1% for men and 67.6% for women (Eurostat 2024b). The gap points to ongoing disadvantages in women’s employment, affecting income, economic autonomy, and pension accrual over the life course. Education and skills are characterized by strong horizontal segregation and modest STEM output. The segregation index is 56.7, and the flow of STEM graduates remains limited—female graduates in science, mathematics, computing, engineering, manufacturing, and construction are 12.2 per 1,000 people aged 20–29 (Eurostat 2023b). Early school leaving is low and nearly gender-neutral (8.1% boys; 8.2% girls), yet the knowledge domain of the Gender Equality Index reaches only 57.8 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling weak pipelines into higher-paid male-dominated fields.

Demographic and territorial structures add further constraints. Bulgaria’s rural population share is 12.9% (OECD 2023a), and the population is aging rapidly (old age dependency ratio 38.2) (Eurostat 2024e), while the foreign born share is very small (3.3%) (Eurostat 2022), limiting migration-driven rejuvenation and skills inflows. A comparatively lean welfare state—social expenditure at 20.5% of GDP (OECD 2024b)—offers thinner automatic stabilizers than its higher-spending EU peers. Health capabilities, captured by the Gender

Equality Index Health, sit mid-table (Table 5). Family policy is a lever with mixed signals. Paternal leave is short (2.1 weeks) but relatively well paid (average payment 90), a design that may encourage take-up but still limits time at home and the rebalancing of care (OECD 2024a). In sum, Bulgaria combines low average income and high inequality with moderate employment, persistent educational segregation, and accelerated aging under a relatively light welfare architecture.

1.3.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Bulgaria presents a mixed-value profile: electoral freedoms are formally guaranteed, yet the quality of liberal-democratic practice and equal rights protections lag behind EU front runners. Freedom in the World rates Bulgaria 77/100 (“Free”) for 2024 (Freedom House 2025), signaling a solid baseline of civil and political liberties, even though the value is among the lowest in Europe. On broader regime performance, the Democracy Index stands at 6.34/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), while the Rule of Law Index is 0.56 (World Justice Project 2024). In line with this, V-Dem’s civil liberties index reaches 0.84 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating protections that are present but weaker than those in the EU core. Regarding gender equality, Bulgaria’s outcomes remain below the EU27 average. The Gender Equality Index overall score is 64.5, with time at 63.8, showing significant gender imbalances in unpaid care and domestic work, consistent with the EU-wide pattern, and power at 58.8, reflecting limited female presence in top decision-making roles (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

The inclusion and pluralism contexts are uneven. The MIPEX indicator appears as 100 on the 0–100 methodology scale (MIPEX 2023), while Rainbow Europe records a low 23.17/100, signaling significant gaps in the legal protection and recognition of LGBTIQ+ people (ILGA-Europe 2025). Together, these data suggest a legal policy framework that is uneven across the domains of equality and nondiscrimination.

Public attitudes toward the EU are comparatively muted. According to the Eurobarometer, 20% of Bulgarians say they trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), pointing to a society where attachment to the EU project is present but not deeply rooted.

In sum, Bulgaria is a free electoral democracy with weaker rule-of-law performance, below-average gender-equality outcomes, and a restrictive LGBTQI+ rights framework. Trust in EU institutions is modest. The overall pattern is one of formal alignment with European values coexisting with implementation gaps—particularly around justice, power-sharing, and minority protections—leaving the value system in a gradual contested transition rather than full consolidation.

1.3.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Bulgaria reveal a coexistence of gradual openings toward equality and resilient traditional scripts that still organize family life, work, and leadership. Family role views remain a core site of traditionalism. As displayed in Figure 26, based on data from (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), agreement with traditional gender-role norms is markedly higher than the EU27 average across all items. Large majorities endorse statements such as “women should give priority to family responsibilities over their career” and believe that “family life suffers when the mother has a full-time job”, indicating a persistently conservative attitudinal profile relative to the broader EU context.

Figure 26 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Bulgaria

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

These levels point to enduring expectations that caregiving is primarily a woman's duty and that paid work and motherhood are in tension. Perceptions of workplace fairness show a more ambivalent picture. These views weigh against women's access to power, even where formal opportunities exist.

Norms around masculinity mirror these results. A large majority—about 67%—say it is acceptable for men to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Finally, the strong family role expectations noted above, together with persistent stereotypes about women's competence and authority, show that the underlying gender order remains hierarchical.

Taken together, Bulgaria's value landscape combines openings (greater acceptance of men's emotional expression; sizable shares perceiving equal treatment at work) with resilient traditionalism (strong support for maternal prioritization of family and for male leadership). The result is a field of cultural contestation in which egalitarian norms advance unevenly and continue to meet resistance shaped by long-standing role expectations.

1.3.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Bulgaria is likewise a structural problem, with prevalence and protection gaps that constrain the full enjoyment of rights. According to the Fundamental Rights Survey, 11.9% of Bulgarian women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Focusing on partners and ex-partners reveals the intimate, relational nature of the phenomenon—20.5% of ever-partnered women report psychological, physical (including threats), and/or sexual violence (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These levels confirm that violence cannot be treated as marginal and that control and coercion frequently unfold within close relationships.

Awareness and access indicators underscore uneven pathways to help. While a large majority of women report knowing that support services exist (85.9%), only 29.5% say they are aware of the right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This mismatch—broad knowledge of services but weak knowledge of concrete entitlements—can deter help-seeking and limit effective protection, particularly for those facing economic or social barriers. On the legal front, Bulgaria signed the Istanbul Convention on 21 April 2016 but has not ratified it; consequently,

it has not entered into force domestically (Council of Europe 2025). The nonratification widens the gap between international standards and national implementation and weakens the coherence of prevention, protection, and prosecution measures. Overall, Bulgaria presents a contradictory picture: significant prevalence and intimate-partner patterns, relatively high awareness of service availability but low awareness of legal rights, and a legal framework that remains incomplete without Istanbul Convention ratification.

I.3.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Bulgaria reveals a formally democratic system that coexists with fragilities linked to participation, trust, and polarization. In the 2024 European elections, turnout was 33.78%, well below the EU average and indicative of limited electoral mobilization at the EU level (European Parliament 2024). Women hold 24% of the seats in the national parliament—below the European average—signaling that descriptive representation remains a pending frontier (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Public confidence and engagement are comparatively modest. According to the European Social Survey (ESS) data, individuals' mean trust in politicians and political parties hovers around 2.2/10, pointing to a pronounced confidence gap vis-à-vis representative institutions (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In contrast, attitudes toward the EU are less skeptical—51% report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Finally, V-Dem diagnostics highlight the conflict structure in which politics unfolds. Political polarization is measured at 2.70/4, and political power is assessed as concentrated toward higher socioeconomic strata (2.36/4), a combination associated with sharper elite-mass divides and a more contentious policymaking environment. According to ParlGov (ParlGov 2023), Bulgaria's party system is currently led by two closely matched blocs. GERB – Citizens for European Development of Bulgaria takes 28.7% of the vote, while We Continue the Change (PP) follows with 26.7%. This near parity signals a highly competitive, coalition-driven landscape in which smaller parties become pivotal for government formation. In short, these results depict a system where governability hinges on cross-party deals and where the direction of governance—particularly on justice and gender equality—depends on which side's priorities anchor the compromise.

Across generations, the political center remains the anchor, but it is most pronounced among midlife women, six in ten of whom place themselves at the center (61.9% vs. 50.0% of men aged 36–55). The sharpest divergence appears at the right-hand tail among young men: fully half of men ≤ 35 sit to the right of center (34.4% right plus 15.6% far right), with this profile softening as they age (men 56+: 16.2% right; 7.1% far right). Young women also lean right of center, though less starkly (≤ 35 : 35.8% right; 8.6% far right), and their rightward identification drops markedly in later life (56+: 11.2% and 8.6%). In contrast, the left grows with age for both sexes: among men 56+, 20.4% choose the left and 18.3% the far left (38.7% combined); among women 56+, 20.7% choose the left and 14.9% choose the right (35.6% combined) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In short, women are more stably centrist, especially in midlife, while young men pull the distribution rightward; with age, both sexes shift modestly left, thinning the rightward tail.

I.3.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now central to understanding political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks associated with disinformation and radicalization. In Bulgaria, the online ecosystem combines wide everyday use with a relatively high vulnerability to misleading content, particularly where media literacy and trust in social media are concerned.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread but more intermittent than in Western Europe. Around 29% of Bulgarians report reading news online every day, while a further 25% do so twice or three times a week. At the other end of the spectrum, 27% say they never read news on the Internet (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Social networks play a major information role—45% say they tend to trust information encountered on social media, and 47% tend to trust news found on websites more broadly—levels that make digital channels influential in the opinion-formation process (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a).

Awareness of the disinformation threat is high—80% of respondents consider the existence of false or misleading information a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Exposure is also intense—29% report they were very often exposed to disinformation the week before the survey and 26% were often exposed, while another 29% report sometimes (European Commission. Directorate General

for Communication. 2024a). However, self-assessed skills lag behind that exposure—only 18% feel very confident that they can recognize disinformation, 49% feel somewhat confident, and roughly 30% report low or no confidence (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

As elsewhere in Europe, the online radicalization dimension warrants attention. EU mapping of misogynist and “manosphere” ecosystems highlights the presence of such communities in Bulgaria (9) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). Even where country-level measurements vary, this environment creates clear risks for gender equality and democratic resilience.

Taken together, Bulgaria’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media provide low-barrier spaces for information access and participation. On the other hand, high reported exposure to disinformation, middling trust filters, and limited confidence in detection create favorable conditions for manipulation and polarization. The policy challenge is twofold: strengthen digital and critical-media competences across the population and target prevention against online radicalization—especially misogynist and anti-egalitarian communities—through evidence-based counternarratives, platform cooperation, and support for independent, trustworthy news ecosystems.

I.3.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a core stress test for Bulgaria’s democratic resilience and its ability to guarantee equal opportunities to the next generation. The picture is mixed—progress in schooling and visible civic energies coexist with headwinds from economic insecurity, uneven local opportunities, and sustained out-migration. On the educational front, the share of young women aged 25–29 with 12–18 years of schooling reaches 80.6%, pointing to a relatively solid base of female human capital (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). According to the data, early leavers remain non-negligible and only slightly gender-differentiated (boys 8.1% and girls 8.2%, 2024), a pattern that still feeds into later disadvantages in job quality and pay (Eurostat 2024a).

In the relational and pluralism sphere, youth (15–29) offer positive yet ambivalent assessments—around 60% consider Bulgaria a good place for immigrants (0.6), around 90% rate the opportunities to make friends as good (0.9), and acceptance of gays and lesbians

stands at around 50% (0.5) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). Taken together, these data depict a generation capable of building robust social networks and partly open to diversity but with clear room for improvement on LGBTIQ+ inclusion. Bulgaria’s youth landscape couples resilience—high educational aspirations and strong family networks but with constraints: slow empowerment, field-of-study segregation, uneven territorial opportunities, and brain-drain pull.

I.3.8 Being socialized in Bulgaria

Being socialized in Bulgaria means growing up where democratic rights are formally guaranteed but institutional effectiveness is weaker and everyday opportunities are shaped by income constraints and a limited welfare state. Trust and participation are fragile, influencing how young people relate to authority and change. Gender relations show persistent inequalities: educational and occupational segregation is strong, women’s decision-making power is limited, and care work remains feminized. Cultural attitudes continue to privilege male authority and protective roles. Digital environments play a major role in socialization yet limited critical literacy heightens exposure to misogynistic and anti-egalitarian narratives. As a result, masculine gender norms in Bulgaria often draw on hierarchical and protective ideals, with more collaborative orientations emerging.

I.4 CROATIA

I.4.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Croatia’s socioeconomic landscape is characterized by a level of development below the European average and a mixed degree of macroeconomic resilience while displaying structural vulnerabilities and persistent internal disparities (Table 6). This confirms a more limited capacity to generate material well-being than the EU standard in a context still shaped by shocks and ongoing structural transitions.

Table 6 Socioeconomic conditions in Croatia compared with the EU27

	Croatia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	77.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	29,6	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	21,7	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	74.7	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	73.3	74.2

Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	53.9	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	85.2	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Income distribution also shows some critical aspects, indicating recurrent vulnerabilities, partly shaped by territorial and socioeconomic divides but broadly comparable to patterns observed in several EU countries. The labor market offers a nuanced picture and remains marked by gender asymmetries. Among people aged 15–64 years, the employment rate is 71.1% for men and 65.4% for women, compared with 75.3% and 66.2% for the EU27, respectively (Eurostat 2024b). Men’s employment lags below the EU average, while the gender gap remains comparable to European patterns, with direct consequences for women’s economic autonomy across the life course.

The EIGE Gender Equality Index corroborates these imbalances (Table 6). In contrast, early school leaving is very low—2.6% for boys and 1.4% for girls, well below EU27 levels—an asset for medium-term employability (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographic structure adds constraints. The old-age dependency ratio is 36.6, above the EU27 (about 34%), indicating faster population aging and rising pressure on pensions and care (Eurostat 2024e). Rural residency involves 42.7% of the population (OECD 2023a)—substantially higher than typical EU shares—translating into uneven access to services, education, and infrastructure. The foreign-born population (13.5%) remains modest by Western EU standards (Eurostat 2022), supporting the labor supply but posing integration challenges in specific localities.

Finally, social expenditure at 22.5% of the GDP limits the welfare state’s redistributive and shock-absorbing capacity (OECD 2024b). In contrast, the health domain of the Gender Equality Index is 85.2, broadly consistent with EU performance (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Paternity leave combines short duration (2 weeks) with high average payment (100 on scale)—a design that eases take-up costs yet still offers limited time for fathers’ involvement (OECD 2024a).

In sum, Croatia’s socioeconomic and institutional structure couples lower incomes, slightly higher inequality, underpowered skills and knowledge, greater rurality and faster aging, and a

lighter welfare effort with several stabilizers—very low early school leaving, solid health outcomes, and incremental gains in women’s participation. The policy frontier mirrors these contrasts. Upgrading tertiary skills (especially STEM and de-segregation measures), investing in rural services, and strengthening work–family policies will be pivotal to convert gradual improvements into inclusive and sustainable growth.

I.4.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Croatia combines formally consolidated democratic institutions with a value landscape that remains ambivalent about gender equality and inclusion. According to Freedom in the World, Croatia scores 82/100 in 2024 (“Free”), confirming broad guarantees of political and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025). The Economist Intelligence Unit’s Democracy Index places Croatia at 6.5/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). On the Rule of Law Index, Croatia records 0.61, signaling mid-range performance in impartial justice and constraints on government (World Justice Project 2024). In line with this, V-Dem’s civil liberties index stands at 0.90, pointing to comparatively strong formal protections for fundamental rights (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

The gender-equality picture is more uneven. Croatia’s overall Gender Equality Index is 59.7—well below the EU27 average (about 71)—with particularly low scores on time (48.6) and power (44.2) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating persistent imbalances in unpaid care and underrepresentation of women in decision-making.

Regarding inclusion policies, MIPEX gives Croatia 71, suggesting comparatively well-designed—if unevenly implemented—frameworks for integration (MIPEX 2023). The LGBTQI+ rights environment is mid-table in the EU—Rainbow Europe scores Croatia at 46.34/100, reflecting a mix of enacted protections and outstanding gaps (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Public attitudes toward the EU remain cautiously positive. In 2024, 58% of Croatians say they trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Croatia presents a democracy with solid formal guarantees and broadly protected civil liberties but with pronounced challenges in translating equality principles—especially around care distribution and women’s presence in power—into everyday practice. Integration and

LGBTQI+ frameworks are developing, and trust in EU institutions is steady, yet the distance from EU averages on gender equality underscores a value system still in transition.

I.4.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Croatia reveal a layered picture in which clear openings toward equality coexist with resilient stereotypes that continue to shape women’s and men’s lives in both the public and private spheres. Family role representations remain one of the areas in which traditional views are most visible. The Eurobarometer data (Figure 27) show sizable shares endorsing statements that place caregiving primarily on women (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 27 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Croatia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality in the workplace confirm this ambivalence, indicating a relatively small recognition of structural disadvantages for women, even as traditional views on role division endure. The political sphere displays the same duality. On the one hand, there is broad support for gender balance in leadership and for the idea that mixed teams perform well. On the other hand, stereotypes about women’s competence and authority are

widespread. Together, these attitudes show that symbolic biases about female leadership persist alongside formal support for equality.

Norms around masculinity are similarly mixed. A very large majority (76%) find it acceptable for a man to cry—evidence of movement away from rigid emotional norms—and about 57% say that “men are naturally less competent than women to perform household tasks” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Attitudes toward gender equality also play out against a climate of cultural contestation. While many Croatians back parity and mixed-gender leadership, a nontrivial share perceive that “feminism has gone too far” (44%), signaling potential backlash risks and a desire to “stabilize” the scope of recent equality gains (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In Croatia, attitudes toward gender and sexuality show clear generational divides that are further sharpened by gender. Hostile stereotypes are most common among older cohorts. The share of men saying women “often/always” try to gain power by controlling men increases from about 25% among under-35s to 46% among those 56+, with women displaying a similar age gradient (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Younger Croatians of both sexes are therefore the least receptive to these narratives.

“Benevolent” sexism (“women should be protected by men”) is broadly rejected—majorities in all groups select “never/rarely”—but pockets of support persist. Endorsement is higher among older men, and a small residue appears among younger women, revealing how ambivalence can coexist with broader egalitarian shifts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

LGBTQI+ attitudes show the sharpest generational gap. Agreement that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” peaks among young women (around 69%), exceeds that of young men (54%), and declines with age, especially among women (around 50% at 56+). Among men, disagreement rises notably in older cohorts (approaching 30%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). The overall picture is one of a youth-led, female-led shift toward inclusion, counterbalanced by more entrenched skepticism among older cohorts, particularly older men.

Taken together, Croatia’s gender norm mirrors other countries’ formula of “openings amid resistance”—support for parity and more flexible masculinities advances, yet enduring expectations about caregiving, authority, and leadership continue to shape opportunities and everyday negotiations of gender. The result is a contested terrain in which egalitarian norms and traditional scripts coexist—and in which policy, education, and representation can tip the balance toward more substantive equality.

I.4.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Croatia is a structural and persistent problem that continues to affect the quality of democracy and the full realization of fundamental rights. Although the country has a solid legal framework and a consolidated institutional system, prevalence levels, awareness of rights, and effective access to services still show ample room for improvement.

According to recent evidence from the Fundamental Rights Agency, about one in four women aged 18–74 in Croatia have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15 (25%). While this is below the EU27 reference (32%), it nonetheless confirms the systemic diffusion of the phenomenon and indicates that violence cannot be considered marginal or residual. Looking specifically at intimate relationships, 28% of ever-partnered women report psychological violence, physical violence or threats, and/or sexual violence—a share that highlights how coercion and control unfold within the private sphere (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures may be read not only as signs of prevalence but also as an indication of improving capacity to recognize and name nonphysical forms of abuse that everyday culture has long normalized.

A critical element concerns knowledge of and access to support. While 86% of women report being aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), awareness of concrete entitlements is more limited—only 48% say they know about the right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This gap between general knowledge that “help exists” and awareness of specific rights can hinder help-seeking and constrain effective access to protection—especially among the most vulnerable.

The most extreme forms of violence portray an even more dramatic reality. The annual homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member stands at 0.30

per 100,000 inhabitants. This rate points to remaining weaknesses in risk assessment, early intervention, and multiagency coordination for high-risk cases (Eurostat 2023c).

On the legal and institutional front, Croatia has taken important steps. It signed the Istanbul Convention on January 22, 2013, ratified it on June 12, 2018, and entered it into force on October 1, 2018—placing the country within the Council of Europe’s advanced framework on prevention, protection, and prosecution (Council of Europe 2025). Overall, Croatia presents a contradictory picture—a modern legal architecture coexists with a non-negligible prevalence, low awareness of concrete rights, and a nontrivial incidence of lethal domestic violence.

I.4.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a clear lens on how democracy, gender inequalities, and power dynamics interact in Croatia. The picture is that of a formally solid institutional system yet one that contends with low electoral engagement, significant polarization, and persistent skepticism toward representative politics.

Turnout in the 2024 European elections was 21.35%. This very low participation signals weak mobilization in second-order contests and a fragile sense of connection with the European arena (European Parliament 2024).

On gender representation, Croatia’s parliament accounts for 33% of women Members of Parliament—roughly in line with the EU average (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Democratic quality indicators sketch a mixed landscape. V-Dem’s Electoral Democracy Index places Croatia around 0.72, pointing to competitive elections and functioning checks-and-balances, although below top EU performers (Varieties of Democracy 2024). At the same time, political polarization is elevated (2.8/4), reflecting pronounced ideological and cultural divides. Power distribution by socioeconomic position (2.2/4) suggests that political influence remains skewed toward higher-income groups (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Recorded levels of political violence are low (0.3) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), but their persistence warrants continued prevention.

Attitudinal data reinforce the sense of a constrained democratic compact. Confidence in political parties and politicians remains weak, with citizens often reporting limited trust in their capacity to deliver (23%).

According to ParlGov (2023a), Croatia's 2020 parliamentary arena was dominated by the Croatian Democratic Union, which won 37.3% of the vote. The Social Democratic Party (SDP) followed with 23.9%. In short, these results depict a system in which governability turns on coalition bargains—and in which the direction of policy, including on rule of law, justice reform, and gender equality, depends on which junior partners anchor the compromise.

Across generations and genders, Croatia's left–right landscape is overwhelmingly centrist, and that anchoring grows stronger among women in midlife (women 36–55: 62.8% center; men 36–55: 60.7%). The picture diverges at the tails. Among men, the right flank thickens with age—young men (≤ 35) place 29.5% on the right or far right, ease off in midlife (23.5%), and then climb to 35.2% after 56 (22.1% right; 13.1% far right). Women remain less right-leaning across the board. The far right is particularly marginal among young women (3.6% vs. 12.3% of young men); their combined right-hand share edges up from 17.2% (≤ 35) to 17.3% (36–55) and 24.9% (56+) but never catches up to men's (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

On the left, women are modestly more present than men at every age. Among the youngest, 21.9% of women choose the left or far left (men: 18.5%); among the oldest, the gap persists (women: 24.0%; men: 18.3%). The far left remains small overall but is notably higher for young women (8.3%) than young men (4.8%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In short, centrism dominates. Men, especially the 56+ cohort, carry the thicker conservative tail, while women lean a touch more to the left and keep the radical right comparatively narrow, most visibly in the youngest generation. Taken together, Croatia's political arena is a delicate equilibrium: formal robustness and incremental gains in women's representation coexist with a very low EU election turnout, high polarization, and unequal power distribution.

I.4.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now central to understanding political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks tied to disinformation and radicalization. In Croatia, the online ecosystem combines high everyday use of digital news with moderate trust in web-based content, alongside clear vulnerabilities—especially around media literacy and exposure to hostile or manipulative narratives.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread. Around 53% of people in Croatia report reading news online every day—higher than the EU average reported in recent Eurobarometer waves (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a).

Trust in online sources is middling to moderate—50% of Croatians say they tend to trust news found on websites, and 40% say the same of information encountered on social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This pattern— websites are trusted more than social networks—mirrors broader European trends but still signals a sizable audience that could be vulnerable to low-quality or manipulative content. Concerns about disinformation are widespread. Around 84% of respondents consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy, slightly above the EU27 picture (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, individuals report having been “often” or “very often” exposed to misleading content in the week prior to the survey (37%, combining “very often” and “often”). However, the skills gap persists—only about 12% feel “very confident” in recognizing false or misleading content, while a much larger share expresses only partial confidence or uncertainty European Parliament, Brussels 2022b).

Online radicalization dynamics also warrant attention—particularly misogynist and anti-egalitarian communities. As documented by the European Commission’s scan with Moonshot, Croatian users were identified on incels.is between 2017 and 2020, a platform associated with the broader “manosphere” and with narratives hostile to gender equality and pluralism. While the footprint appears comparatively small (6), its presence points to the real risks of gendered polarization and gateway pathways toward anti-democratic content (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021).

Overall, Croatia’s digital environment has two faces. On one side, the internet and social media are major gateways to information, participation, and debate—backed by high daily news consumption online. On the other hand, frequent exposure to disinformation, only modest confidence in spotting it, and the documented presence of misogynist communities pose concrete challenges to the quality of public discourse and democratic resilience.

I.4.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key barometer of democratic resilience and a country's capacity to guarantee real opportunities to the next generation. In Croatia, the picture is mixed—encouraging signs on the social/relational side sit alongside structural hurdles that still constrain empowerment, education-to-work transitions, and economic autonomy.

Relationally, Croatian youth report strong opportunities to make friends and build networks, and they express some—but not uniform—openness to diversity. Judgments about Croatia as a “good place” for immigrants and for gay and lesbian people are more ambivalent than in the most inclusive EU countries, pointing to a value climate that is moving in an egalitarian direction but still marked by pockets of cultural resistance. In fact, on the education side, the foundation is solid—81% of young women aged 25–29 have completed 12–18 years of schooling, indicating substantial female human capital (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). In the relational sphere, youth (15–29) report strong opportunities to make friends (0.8), suggesting fairly robust social networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). In contrast, the indicators of openness and inclusion are weak—only 0.4 rate the country as a “good place” for immigrants, and 0.4 express acceptance of gays and lesbians. In short, a lively peer network coexists with low openness to diversity, with 0.4 sitting at the lower end of the scale networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), creating a bottleneck for youth inclusion that is fully aligned with equality and pluralism. Taken together, Croatia's youth landscape shows robust social capital and improving conditions but also structural constraints—notably in labor market entry, gender equality in paid work, and inclusive norms toward minorities.

I.4.8 Being socialized in Croatia

Being socialized in Croatia means entering a democratic setting that protects rights but still displays visible gaps in gender outcomes. Care work is strongly feminized, and leadership pathways are narrow for women as their careers advance. Attitudes show marked internal contrasts. Younger people—especially young women—express strongly egalitarian views, while older groups maintain more skeptical or hostile stereotypes. The digital sphere amplifies these differences, spreading both inclusive and grievance-based narratives. Consequently, masculine gender norms in Croatia develop amid competing cues, combining

emergent egalitarian ideals with enduring expectations linked to authority, protection, and family hierarchy.

1.5 CYPRUS

1.5.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Cyprus sits slightly below the EU average for material prosperity but pairs this with comparatively balanced distributional outcomes (Table 7).

Table 7 Socioeconomic conditions in Cyprus compared with the EU27

	Cyprus	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	95.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	29.9	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	17.1	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	84.1	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	77.3	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	66.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	87.4	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is dynamic yet still gendered. Among people aged 15–64 years, male employment is 80.3% and female employment is 71.1%, a gap of roughly 9 points that weighs on women’s earnings, autonomy, and pension accrual over the life course (Eurostat 2024b).

Education and skills send mixed signals. Horizontal segregation across fields of study is high (index 54.8) gaps (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and the pipeline of female STEM graduates remains thin (8.8 per 1,000 people aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2023b).

Early school leaving among boys is 8.2% and lower among girls (Eurostat 2024a); the EIGE knowledge domain reaches 66.1 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating that pathways into better-paid male-dominated technical fields are still underbuilt.

Demography and territory add both constraints and openings. The old-age dependency ratio is 23.6 (Eurostat 2024e), signaling aging pressures that are milder than those in several EU peers. Health capabilities are strong (Health is about 87.4) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Work–family reconciliation remains a weak lever. Paternity leave is very short with an average payment of about 72, a design unlikely to equalize care at home (OECD

2024a). On gender equality overall, Cyprus highlights especially large gaps in decision-making positions (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

In sum, Cyprus pairs material prosperity only slightly below the EU average, with moderate inequality. The institutional system is sound, but this resilience has not yet translated into equal opportunities—the labor market still shows an employment gap, pronounced educational segregation, and a thin female STEM pipeline. Demography and health are not the weak spots, while work–family reconciliation policies—very short, low-impact paternity leave—do not rebalance family care burdens.

I.5.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Cyprus presents itself as a liberal democracy with robust civil rights guarantees and generally stable institutions, even as gaps remain in gender equality and inclusion. On core democratic quality, the country is rated Free by Freedom House with 91/100 (Freedom House 2025). The Economist Intelligence Unit’s Democracy Index is 7.38/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). The gender-equality picture is more uneven. Cyprus’s overall Gender Equality Index is 60.9, well below the EU27 average (about 71). The country performs above EU levels in time (58.4), highlighting unequal divisions of unpaid care, and in power (28.8), far below the EU average (about 61.4). This points to women’s underrepresentation in decision-making roles (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Inclusion policies mirror this middle-of-the-pack profile. MIPEX is 62 (MIPEX 2023), a mid-range result that combines strengths in some service areas with barriers to long-term security and participation. On LGBTQI+ rights, Rainbow Europe scores Cyprus at 31/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), highlighting a sizable gap with EU leaders.

Public attitudes toward the European project are more cautious than in many member states. Around 43% of individuals say they trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These figures suggest a pragmatic, sometimes skeptical, engagement with EU institutions—not hostile but short of the confidence levels seen in higher-trust countries.

In sum, Cyprus couples strong civil liberties and competitive elections with middling rule-of-law performance and a distinct gender-equality deficit concentrated in care and power.

Progress on inclusion (migrant integration and LGBTQI+ rights) is tangible but incomplete.

Raising women’s representation in decision-making, rebalancing unpaid care, and deepening trust in democratic institutions—national and European—are the levers most likely to move Cyprus closer to the Union’s best performers.

I.5.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Cyprus draw a mixed picture: clear openings toward equality in public life coexist with traditional expectations of family roles and lingering stereotypes about women’s leadership. As displayed in Figure 28, based on data from the Eurobarometer, family roles are where conventional views are most visible (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 28 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Cyprus

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of fairness at work are ambivalent—recognition of workplace inequality remains widespread despite a public narrative of “equal treatment”. Norms around masculinity show both movement and inertia. Acceptance of emotional expression is very broad—83% say it is acceptable for a man to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, more prescriptive views persist in the private sphere—24% think men should have the final say in important family decisions. Everyday gender scripts

also surface in competence expectations—46% agree that men are naturally less competent than women in household tasks, a stereotype that recognizes gendered practice at home while also reifying it. Regarding caregiving and careers, 22% say men who take parental leave show a lack of ambition, a nontrivial minority that can discourage take-up and reinforce the unequal division of unpaid care (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In Cyprus, attitudes toward gender and sexuality vary sharply by generation and, to a lesser extent, by gender. Younger cohorts are consistently more egalitarian, while ambivalence and harsher stereotypes grow with age. Women generally remain more progressive than men.

On LGBTQI+ rights, support is strongest among the young—about two-thirds of women and six in ten men under 35 agree that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish—and it softens with age. Among those 56+, agreement falls to around half of women and slightly less among men, with neutrality and disagreement becoming more common (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Hostile gender stereotypes show a reverse gradient. Rejection is highest among younger men and midlife women but declines in older groups, where firm endorsement becomes more frequent. The claim that women seek power by controlling men is particularly divisive: endorsement peaks among men aged 36–55 (around four in ten), while women remain less hostile across ages (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). “Benevolent” sexism follows yet another pattern. Men largely reject the idea that women should be protected by men (about three in four “never/rarely”), whereas a small residue of protectionist sentiment persists among young women and fades with age, giving way to clearer rejection in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Cyprus shows polarization concentrated at the margins. Older people are overrepresented among both the strongest skeptics and the firmest opponents, while the center of gravity remains with women, especially younger women, who are the most LGBTQ-affirming and least receptive to hostile stereotypes.

Taken together, Cyprus’s value landscape reveals a double movement. In public life, there is strong symbolic support for equal representation and little backing for outright male primacy in leadership. In private life, however, traditional family role expectations remain resilient, and trait-based stereotypes still weigh on perceptions of women’s authority. Progress on

gender equality will hinge on narrowing this gap—normalizing men’s participation in care, expanding parental leave take-up, and challenging the “emotional/authority” bias that continues to shadow women in leadership.

1.5.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Cyprus remains a systemic challenge that affects democratic quality and the full exercise of rights. The country has put in place a modern legal and institutional framework, yet prevalence, knowledge of rights, and effective access to protection reveal clear gaps between formal commitments and everyday realities.

Prevalence data point to a problem that is widespread rather than marginal. An estimated 36.1% of women report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15—below the EU27 average of roughly 31% but still affecting more than one in four women (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024).

Focusing on intimate relationships, 44.5% of ever-partnered women report psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by a partner or ex-partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). This figure underscores how control and coercion within couples remain a central locus of harm, including forms of abuse that are nonphysical but deeply injurious.

Awareness and access indicators show a two-speed system. On the one hand, 76.4% of women are aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), a relatively high reach for first-line help. On the other hand, only 26.3% know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a)—a critical step for protection orders, prosecution, and longer-term redress. This mismatch suggests that information campaigns and frontline contact work better than rights-based guidance through the justice chain; without the latter, victims may disengage or settle for short-term safety without durable legal protection.

The most extreme outcomes, while rarer, demand sustained vigilance. The intentional homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member stands at 0.11 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), signaling failures in early risk detection, coordinated response, and sustained perpetrator management.

On the legal front, Cyprus has aligned itself with European standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on June 6, 2015, ratified it on November 10, 2017, and entered it into force on

March 1, 2018 (Council of Europe 2025). This anchors national policy in a comprehensive framework spanning prevention, protection, prosecution, and integrated policy. However, the data above implies an implementation gap: prevalence remains substantial, knowledge of concrete entitlements (such as legal aid) is incomplete, and lethal violence has not been eliminated.

Overall, Cyprus presents a contradictory picture. There is real institutional progress and broad awareness of where to seek help—but uneven knowledge of enforceable rights, persistent intimate-partner abuse, and non-negligible lethal cases.

I.5.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a privileged lens through which to observe how democracy, gender inequality, and power interact in Cypriot society. The portrait that emerges is of a system that is institutionally liberal and reasonably stable yet marred by weak descriptive representation of women, low confidence in domestic politics, and a degree of polarization that complicates consensus-building.

The first indicator to be considered is participation. In the 2024 European elections, Cyprus recorded a 58.9% turnout—comfortably above the EU average (about 51%) (European Parliament 2024). This points to comparatively strong civic mobilization in EU contests, even if participation in national politics remains more uneven.

Representation lags behind mobilization. Women occupy roughly 14% of seats in the national parliament—far below the EU reference point of about one-third (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The thin pipeline of women into elected office constrains whose interests set agendas and slows the translation of equality norms into policy.

On democratic quality, Cyprus scores solidly but not exceptionally. Freedom House classifies the country as “Free” (around 87/100) (Freedom House 2025). The Economist Intelligence Unit places it at 7.38/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), while the World Justice Project Rule-of-Law score sits near 0.67 (World Justice Project 2024). In the V-Dem suite, civil liberties are strong (about 0.89), and the electoral democracy score is in the low-to-mid 0.7s (Varieties of Democracy 2024)—consistent with competitive elections and meaningful checks and balances, although shy of the best-performing EU democracies.

Public confidence is the soft underbelly. In Cyprus, individuals who trust political parties are 13% and 21% the national government (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Attitudinally, most citizens cleave to democratic norms. Large majorities reject political violence as justifiable, and outright support for authoritarian shortcuts remains limited. However, nontrivial minorities express some openness to “strong-leader” solutions (16.4% say that it is very good having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections) (Haerpfer et al. 2024)—an ever-present risk factor in a low-trust environment.

The ideological distribution of Cyprus’s party system shows a plural field anchored by a center-right plurality and a strong left counterweight. In the 2021 parliamentary election, Democratic Rally led with 27.8% of the vote, followed by Progressive Party of Working People with 22.3% and the centrist Democratic Party with 11.3% (ParlGov 2023). These results point to a system in which conservative and liberal-centrist forces hold a negotiating edge but must accommodate a substantial left presence—an equilibrium with clear implications for coalition bargaining and for the direction of social policy, civil rights reforms, and gender-equality agendas.

On the generational side, every ideological “world” is dominated by the 56+ group, and the extremes are particularly so: the radical right is largely older (about 57% of men and 70% of women are 56+), and the radical left is also predominantly over 56. The center remains the largest pole but is likewise aged (around 49% 56+ for both sexes). Young people (≤ 35) are a minority everywhere and scarcely present at the extremes—evidence that age, rather than nudging people to the center, selects those who remain at the sharp edges of the system.

Within each age cohort, gender differences are clear. Under 35, men and women are mostly centrist, but young men lean more left (far left and left is about 30%), while young women show a slight tilt to the moderate right. Among those 36–55 years, the gap widens—women stay strongly anchored at the center (about 56%), whereas men display a much thicker right/far-right tail. After 56+, polarization increases for both sexes—men grow at the tails, including on the far left, while women remain more centered, although with a nontrivial share on the far right. In sum, men, especially in midlife, show a stronger rightward inclination; women maintain a more moderate centrist profile, with less pronounced ideological swings

over the life course (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Taken together, Cyprus presents a delicate equilibrium. Robust civil liberties and competitive elections coexist with low domestic trust, underrepresentation of women, and meaningful polarization. High EU election turnout and comparatively warmer views of EU institutions are clear strengths. The strategic tasks ahead are rebuilding confidence in national politics, widening women's access to decision-making, and easing socioeconomic asymmetries that sharpen polarization—so that the country's formal democratic strengths translate into broader legitimacy and inclusive governance.

I.5.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is now central to how Cypriots learn about politics, form opinions, and—at the risky end—encounter disinformation and gender-hostile content. Cyprus's online ecosystem combines wide everyday exposure to digital news with relatively high trust in web sources but with notable blind spots in media literacy and resilience.

The daily use of digital platforms for news is substantial. About one in four Cypriots (about 41%) say they read news on the internet every day or almost every day (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), underlining the centrality of online media in political socialization. Social networks also play a big role in citizens' information diets, functioning as hubs in which news, commentary, and identity politics mix and spread quickly. Trust in what people find online is comparatively high. Roughly 28% say they tend to trust news on websites, and 45% report trust in information from social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This legitimacy for digital sources makes the online sphere an indispensable arena for public debate, but it also multiplies potential exposure to misleading or manipulative content.

Awareness of the threat of disinformation is widespread. About 88% of Cypriots agree that false or distorted information is a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Self-reported exposure is also elevated—around 41% say they encountered disinformation “very often” or “often” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022b). When it comes to skills, confidence is mixed—14% feel very confident that they can recognize disinformation, while 51% are somewhat

confident (European Parliament, Brussels 2022b). The gap between high awareness and uneven detection skills points to an urgent need for sustained media and information literacy efforts.

In short, Cyprus's digital environment has a dual face. It offers vibrant channels for participation, information, and mobilization, yet it is characterized by high exposure to disinformation and by significant inequalities in critical digital and media skills

I.5.7 Youth agency

Cyprus socializes its younger generations in a generally supportive environment for education and social ties while exposing them to familiar Mediterranean constraints around labor market entry, gendered expectations, and a still-cautious cultural openness. On the relational side, youth report good opportunities to make friends and build networks. Perceptions of diversity are more ambivalent. Acceptance of gays and lesbians is clearly present among young people but remains below the levels observed in the EU's most liberal countries, and openness to immigrants is comparatively cautious. In short, the everyday social fabric is strong, yet cultural inclusion advances unevenly across issues.

Education pipelines are a relative strength. Around nine in ten young women aged 25–29 have 12–18 years of schooling (about 89%) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), signaling high attainment at the transition to stable work. Early school leaving is gendered but contained—about 14.5% of boys exit early versus 8.2% of girls (Eurostat 2024a), a gap that foreshadows later differences at entry into the labor market.

Cyprus's youth profile reveals a striking split between educational success and social openness. Among young women aged 25–29, 89.3% have completed 12–18 years of schooling—well above the EU27 benchmark of 84% (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This points to strong human-capital pipelines and a generation of women entering adulthood with robust credentials and, potentially, high aspirations for work and civic life.

However, these gains coexist with cooler attitudes toward diversity. Openness to immigrants among youth (15–29) stands at 0.60, compared with 0.80 in the EU, and acceptance of gays and lesbians is 0.50 versus an EU average of 0.70. In other words, education is running ahead of inclusion. At the same time, the relational fabric looks healthy. The perceived opportunity

to make friends among Cypriot youth is 0.80, on par with the EU figure, suggesting dense social networks that could be mobilized for bridge-building (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). Taken together, Cyprus nurtures highly educated young women and well-connected youth communities but still faces attitudinal headwinds around immigration and LGBTQI+ inclusion.

I.5.8 Being socialized in Cyprus

Being socialized in Cyprus means growing up in a liberal institutional environment with strong educational pathways but limited trust in domestic political actors. Labor market transitions reveal persistent gender inequalities and low female representation in power. Cultural expectations assign caregiving to women and decision-making to men, especially among older cohorts. Online information is central but shaped by high exposure to disinformation and uneven media literacy. Within this landscape, masculine gender norms in Cyprus reflect a blend of democratic openness and traditional role expectations, producing identities that move between inclusiveness and continuity with established norms.

I.6 CZECHIA

I.6.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Czechia combines solid macroeconomic performance with relatively even income distribution while still facing structural bottlenecks in gender equality and human-capital allocation.

Table 8 Socioeconomic conditions in Czechia compared with the EU27

	Czechia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	91.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	24,1	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	11,3	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	79.5	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	69.1	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	61.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	85.1	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is tight but remains gendered. Employment among those aged 15–64 reaches 81.1% for men and 69.5% for women, a gap of roughly 11–12 points that depresses

women's earnings trajectories and long-term economic autonomy (Eurostat 2024b). This pattern is mirrored in the Gender Equality Index, signaling decent performance overall but persistent penalties in pay and job quality for women (Table 8).

Education and skills show mixed signals. Horizontal segregation across study fields is substantial (segregation index 46.8) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and the pipeline of female STEM graduates is modest (11.8 per 1,000 people aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2023b). At the same time, early school leaving is very low and gender-neutral (boys 5.3% and girls 5.4%) (Eurostat 2024a). The knowledge domain sits at 61.1 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), pointing to the underrepresentation of women in higher-paid male-dominated technical tracks despite broad attainment gains.

Demography and territory pose moderate, manageable pressures—21.25% of the population lives in rural areas, and the old-age dependency ratio is 32.3 (slightly below the EU average) (OECD 2023a). The foreign-born share is 10.1% (Eurostat 2022), implying a relatively limited—but growing—migration contribution to labor supply and skills. Welfare capacity is lean by EU standards (social expenditure 22.1% of GDP) (OECD 2024b), which constrains automatic stabilizers. In contrast, health capabilities are strong (EIGE Health 85.1) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

When it comes to policies supporting the reconciliation of work and family life, paternity leave remains limited (its duration is 2 weeks, and the average payment is 62.5) (OECD 2024a), a design that is unlikely to bring about significant changes in care norms within the household. In sum, Czechia's model mixes low inequality and strong institutional quality with a persistent gender employment gap, notable educational segregation, and a relatively light welfare state. Closing pay and participation gaps, widening female STEM pathways, and strengthening work–family reconciliation—especially fathers' leave—are the levers most likely to translate macro stability into broadly shared gender-equal opportunity.

1.6.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Czechia's institutional landscape points to a well-consolidated liberal democracy, with some stubborn gaps in gender equality and inclusion. Freedom House rates the country “Free” (about 95/100) (Freedom House 2025), the Economist Intelligence Unit gives it 8.08/10 on the Democracy Index (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024),

and the World Justice Project’s Rule of Law score stands at 0.74 (World Justice Project 2024). Together, these indicators depict competitive elections, effective checks and balances, and broadly protected rights.

Regarding gender equality, the picture is more uneven. The overall Gender Equality Index is 59.9—below the EU27 benchmark—while the time domain is 57, and the power domain is just 34.9 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling persistent imbalances in unpaid care and a thin presence of women in decision-making roles. Integration and minority-rights metrics tell a similar “middle-of-the-pack” story—MIPEX is around 64 (MIPEX 2023), and Rainbow Europe scores Czechia 47/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025). These data mirror the country’s score of 0 on ILGA-Europe’s 2025 indicator measuring the presence of hate speech and hate crime legislation inclusive of gender identity and/or sexual orientation (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Attitudes toward the EU are cooler than in high-trust member states. Only about one-third report trust in the European Parliament (about 47%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In short, Czechia combines robust civil liberties and solid institutional performance with lagging gender equality—in care and power—plus incomplete inclusion for migrants and LGBTQI+ people. Closing these gaps—especially by expanding women’s access to leadership and strengthening equal-treatment frameworks—would bring the country’s social model closer to the strengths of its democratic institutions.

I.6.3 Gender norms

Gender norms in Czechia combine clear openings toward equality with stubborn stereotypes that still shape everyday roles and authority. As displayed in

Figure 29, on leadership, sizable minorities endorse classic biases, and workplace perceptions reflect the same ambivalence (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 29 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Czechia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Masculinity scripts have softened in some respects—84% say it is acceptable for men to cry. However, backlash currents are evident, with 52% agreeing that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In the private sphere, traditional hierarchies persist. About 26% think men should have the final say in important family decisions, 28% view men who take parental leave as lacking ambition, 34% say the lower-paid father should stop working to care for children, and 48% naturalize domestic work by claiming that men are “naturally” less competent (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Politically, stereotypes endure—57% believe men are more ambitious than women (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Read alongside the leadership and workplace figures above, the picture is one of gradual liberalization in

some attitudes but shows persistent cultural expectations that constrain women's authority and penalize men's caregiving.

Overall, the value landscape is transitional. Public support for gender balance is meaningful (59%), and norms around male emotional expression are relatively liberal (about 84%). However, symbolic barriers to women's authority remain (25% of men make better leaders than women) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Narrowing the gap will require normalizing men's share of unpaid care and increasing women's visibility in top roles—practical shifts that can erode the lingering stereotypes documented here.

I.6.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Czechia remains a structural concern. Prevalence is far from negligible, awareness of concrete rights is uneven, and lethal cases persist despite incremental institutional progress.

Regarding prevalence, Eurostat's gender-based violence indicators point to a nontrivial share of women affected. Among ever-partnered women, 33.5% report psychological and/or physical (incl. threats) or sexual violence by a current or former partner. Looking more broadly, 19.7% of women report physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15. While this level sits below EU27 averages (30.7) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), it is sufficiently high to confirm that gender-based violence is a systemic, not residual, phenomenon.

Knowledge of enforceable rights shows important gaps. Only 53% of women are aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), and only 16.8% are aware of free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a)—a bottleneck that can limit access to restraining orders, prosecution, and longer-term redress, even when general awareness of "support services" exists. At the extreme end of harm, Czechia records an intentional homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member of 0.36 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), underscoring the need for earlier risk detection and coordinated perpetrator management. Legally and institutionally, the picture is mixed. Czechia signed the Council of Europe's Istanbul Convention on May 2, 2016 but has not ratified it to date, leaving the comprehensive "4Ps" framework (prevention, protection, prosecution, and integrated policy) only partially

embedded in national law and practice (Council of Europe 2025). In sum, Czechia's gender-based violence landscape combines measurable prevalence and a non-negligible femicide rate with an incomplete international legal anchor (signature without ratification of the Istanbul Convention).

I.6.5 Political dimension

Czechia's political profile combines solid institutions with selective participation, persistent gender-representation gaps, and nontrivial polarization. In the 2024 European elections, turnout was 36.5%, among the lowest in the EU (about 45%), pointing to weak mobilization at the supranational level (European Parliament 2024). Women hold only 24% of parliamentary seats—well below the EU reference of 33%—underscoring slow progress in descriptive representation (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

In the 2021 Czech parliamentary election, the party system tilted decisively to the right-of-center. The Civic Democratic Party won 27.8% of the vote, narrowly ahead of Action of Dissatisfied Citizens 2011 with 27.1%. Taken together, these two conservative or centrist-populist forces hold 54.9% of the vote, pointing to the same pattern seen elsewhere in Europe: the consolidation of conservative and nationalist-leaning currents (ParlGov 2023). This balance of power has meaningful consequences for the direction of social policy, civil rights, and gender-equality agendas, which are likely to be shaped by the priorities of these dominant blocs.

Overall, Czechia pairs robust institutions and broad civil rights protections with low EU-level participation, underrepresentation of women in politics, and polarizing party dynamics. Priorities ahead include widening women's access to decision-making, rebuilding confidence in representative institutions, and boosting civic mobilization so that formal system strength translates into more inclusive legitimacy and fairer governance.

I.6.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial for understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Czechia, the online ecosystem is characterized by the broad diffusion of digital information and nontrivial trust in web-based content while showing vulnerabilities—especially around media literacy and exposure to content hostile to democracy and gender equality.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread. Country results from the Eurobarometer show that roughly 60% of Czechs say they read news online every day or two or three times a week, levels broadly in line with the EU average (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a) and indicative of the central role of digital media in Czech public and political life.

Trust in online sources is meaningful, although mixed. In the same Eurobarometer, around 39% of Czechs say they tend to trust news they find on social networks, while 57% tend to trust news find on websites (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These figures suggest that digital media enjoy notable legitimacy but also that a sizable share of the public approaches them cautiously.

Disinformation as a democratic threat is widely recognized. In the Eurobarometer survey on disinformation, large majorities in Czechia (76%), lower than in the EU (82%), judged disinformation to be a serious problem for democracy—around 29% being often or very often exposed to misleading content in the preceding week. However, only a small minority say they are very confident they can recognize false news (18%); most feel confident only sometimes (38%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). The pattern points to high awareness but limited detection skills—classic signs that civic and digital education could be strengthened.

Overall, Czechia’s digital sphere is both central and fragile. Most people now get news online, and a meaningful share says they trust web sources. However, large majorities also see disinformation as a serious threat, many report frequent exposure to misleading content, and only a small minority feel very confident spotting it. This mix—high reliance, middling trust, and limited verification skills—creates fertile ground for manipulation and for the spread of narratives hostile to democracy and gender equality.

I.6.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Czechia, the overall picture is relatively favorable by European standards—especially on openness and social ties—yet important fragilities remain in pathways to empowerment, education continuity, and socioeconomic autonomy.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Czech young people report strong social connectedness and openness to diversity. Large majorities say their country is a good place for immigrants and for gay and lesbian people, and they rate the opportunity to make friends positively (0.9) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). In fact, using Youth Progress Index (2022) indicators, the picture for young people is broadly positive, especially for girls' schooling and peer connectedness. Educational attainment is very high among young women: 94% of 25–29-year-olds have completed 12–18 years of education) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), a strong signal of gender parity in upper-secondary/tertiary pathways. Among youth aged 15–29 years, openness toward immigrants is 0.7, still below the European level (0.8), opportunities to make friends score 0.9, and acceptance of gays and lesbians is 0.8 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). Taken together, these scores suggest a cohort that is highly educated, socially embedded, and comparatively inclusive of diversity—conditions that typically correlate with better democratic engagement and smoother transitions to adulthood.

On the education and labor market front, however, structural gaps persist. Early school leaving among those aged 18–24 years is similar for both sexes in Czechia (men 5.3% and women 5.4%) (Eurostat 2024a), signaling the risk of weaker transitions to stable employment for the youth population. In short, Czech young people show strong relational capital and cultural openness but still face gender-differentiated risks in education continuity and ongoing barriers to full socioeconomic independence.

I.6.8 Being socialized in Czechia

Being socialized in Czechia means growing up in a liberal democracy with strong civil rights but persistent gender differences in work, care, and power. Women hold a limited share of parliamentary seats, and gender-based violence remains a serious concern, with the Istanbul Convention still unratified. Attitudes combine support for gender balance with private-sphere expectations that favor male decision-making and women's caregiving. Digital news use dominates information routines, yet concern about disinformation is high, and confidence in detecting it is low. In this context, masculine gender norms in Czechia emerge where formal equality coexists with traditional expectations within households and with persistent stereotypes about leadership and caregiving.

I.7 DENMARK

I.7.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Denmark couples very high prosperity with unusually even life chances. In 2024, its GDP per capita in PPSs is 128, while income dispersion is among the lowest in Europe and the population at risk of poverty or social exclusion is 18% (Table 9).

Table 9 Socioeconomic conditions in Denmark compared with the EU27

	Denmark	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	128.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	21.5	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	18	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	89.5	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	82.8	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	70.2	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	87.9	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Although below the EU average, it still signals non-negligible pockets of vulnerability, particularly among groups affected by labor market and housing pressures (Eurostat 2024f). Employment is strong for both sexes—79.9% of men and 74.5% of women aged 15–64 years—leaving a comparatively small gender gap (about 5.4 pp) and outperforming the EU averages (75.3% and 66.2%) (Eurostat 2024b). The EIGE scores confirm this strength. However, the knowledge pipeline shows frictions. Horizontal segregation across study fields is sizable (segregation index 59.5) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), women remain underrepresented in STEM (about 19.3 graduates per 1,000 aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2023b), and early school leaving, while low by international standards, is not negligible (boys 11.1% and girls 9.6%) (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographic pressures are manageable but real. About 28% of residents live in rural areas (OECD 2023a), the old-age dependency ratio is 32.5 (Eurostat 2024e), and the foreign-born share has reached 18.3% (Eurostat 2022), making migration relevant to skills and labor supply. Social spending stands at around 26.4% of GDP (OECD 2024b)—sizeable, though leaner than some Nordic peers—while the EIGE Health domain is very high (87.9). The design of work–family policies combines both incentives and constraints. Paternity leave is brief (2

weeks) and compensated at 49.7% (OECD 2024a), a configuration that indicates institutional support but is likely too limited to bring about substantial changes in caregiving norms at home.

In sum, Denmark's model blends high prosperity, compressed inequality, and very strong institutions with a still-visible gender gap in the labor market's upper rungs and persistent segregation in education.

I.7.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Denmark ranks among the European countries with the most consolidated democratic institutions and a political tradition strongly anchored in the rule of law and respect for fundamental rights. At the same time, the value landscape reveals tensions and ambivalences, especially in relation to gender equality, social inclusion, and the protection of minorities.

According to Freedom in the World, Denmark scores 97/100 in 2024, classified as “Free”, confirming a solid guarantee of political and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index produced by the Economist Intelligence Unit assigns the country 9.28/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing it among “full democracies” and indicating a political system characterized by pluralism, participation, and institutional stability. The Rule of Law Index is also high (0.90) (World Justice Project 2024), pointing to effective law enforcement, an independent judiciary, and a relatively efficient institutional context, although with room for improvement regarding case duration and access to justice. In line with these results, V-Dem's civil liberties index reaches 0.96, underscoring the advanced level of protection of fundamental rights (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

The institutional value landscape is also shaped by inclusion and pluralism policies. MIPEx gives Denmark a score of 51 (MIPEx 2023), indicative of mid-level integration policies, with progress in several areas but persistent obstacles regarding citizenship and political participation. The LGBTQI+ rights framework is comparatively strong—according to Rainbow Europe, Denmark scores about 80/100, reflecting an advanced legal and policy environment, although there is room for improvement in specific protections and implementation (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Danish people's attitudes toward the EU offer another perspective on the country's potential closeness to European values. In 2024, about 50% of Danes report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), a figure around the EU average and indicative of a relatively stable link with the European project.

In sum, Denmark presents itself as a solid democracy characterized by efficient institutions, high standards of civil liberties, and a widespread respect for fundamental democratic values. However, the full realization of gender equality remains an open challenge—particularly regarding the distribution of unpaid care time—as does the creation of an ever more inclusive environment for migrants and LGBTQI+ people.

I.7.3 Gender norms

In Denmark, gender norms tilt clearly toward equality in public life, even as traces of traditionalism linger in the private sphere of care. On the structural side, Denmark's overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 78.8, above the EU27 average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, the time dimension—concerning the distribution of care and domestic work—stands at 72.7 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating that caregiving responsibilities still fall disproportionately on women. More advanced than the EU average is power (77.7) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), which measures women's presence in decision-making, although some underrepresentation persists in top positions in politics and the economy.

This picture is echoed in attitudes about family roles. As displayed in

Figure 30, based on data from the Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), expectations about women's caregiving responsibilities have not disappeared but represent the expression of a minority of the Danes.

Figure 30 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Denmark

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of fairness in the workplace present ambivalence. While Denmark is an egalitarian frontrunner with many outcomes, 53% of respondents still think men are treated better than women at work—an explicit acknowledgment that inequalities remain. At the same time, as shown in Figure 1, there is broad support for gender-balanced leadership.

Norms around masculinity are notably flexible. An overwhelming 92% say it is acceptable for a man to cry, suggesting that traditional emotional scripts for men have softened. Gender-related attitudes among the Danish population reveal a society that is generally egalitarian but still marked by the persistence of certain traditional views about gender roles in family and public life. Only 4% of respondents agree with the statement that “men should have the

final say in important family decisions”, indicating that strongly patriarchal norms have very limited support in Denmark. Similarly, 5% believe that “men who take parental leave show a lack of ambition for their career”, reflecting a high level of social acceptance of men’s involvement in caregiving and a relatively advanced shift toward more balanced gender roles. However, some stereotypes remain entrenched. About 14% agree that “men are naturally less competent than women to perform household tasks”, a view that still reinforces gendered divisions of domestic labor, albeit from an inverted perspective. Moreover, 32% of respondents think that “if the father’s pay is lower than the mother’s, he should be the one to give up work to look after the children” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This suggests that economic rationality continues to underpin decisions about caregiving, reflecting a persistent gendered expectation that men’s employment is secondary when their income is lower. Attitudes regarding gender differences in the political sphere also show lingering inequalities—24% of respondents agree that “men are more ambitious than women in politics” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). While a minority, this perception may still influence gendered expectations around political leadership and representation.

Taken together, Denmark’s value landscape is distinctly pro-equality: strong public support for gender-balanced leadership, low endorsement of overtly sexist claims, and open norms around men’s emotional expression. The frontier of change lies in the intimate economy of time—who steps back from paid work, who does routine care, and how comfortable people feel with women’s assertiveness in public.

I.7.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Denmark remains a structural and persistent challenge that affects the country’s democratic fabric and the full realization of women’s fundamental rights.

Despite a comprehensive legal framework and well-developed institutional mechanisms, prevalence levels, awareness of rights, and access to services reveal significant gaps that limit the effectiveness of existing policies.

According to data, around 47.5% of women aged 18–74 years in Denmark report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15. Within intimate relationships, about 45% of ever-partnered women report psychological, physical

(including threats), or sexual violence (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024)—illustrating how coercion and abuse often unfold within the private sphere and underscoring the continued prevalence of gendered power imbalances in intimate life.

While 72.4% of women state they are aware of the existence of support services, only 31% know about the right to free legal aid (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). This gap between general awareness and knowledge of concrete entitlements can act as a significant barrier to help-seeking, particularly among women in vulnerable circumstances.

At the most extreme end of the spectrum, gender-based violence can be fatal. In Denmark, the annual homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member is 0.51 per 100,000 inhabitants—a figure that still points to shortcomings in risk assessment, prevention, and coordinated response in high-risk cases (Eurostat 2023c).

On the legal and institutional sides, Denmark has taken substantial steps to align itself with European standards. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on October 11, 2013, ratified it on April 23, 2014, and entered it into force on August 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025), embedding Denmark firmly within the Council of Europe’s advanced framework for preventing and combating violence against women.

In sum, Denmark presents a mixed picture. A robust legal architecture and high levels of awareness coexist with persistent prevalence, uneven knowledge of legal rights, and non-negligible rates of severe violence. The persistence of these challenges underscores the need for continued investment in prevention, survivor support, legal empowerment, and cross-sector coordination to ensure that rights on paper translate into effective protection in practice.

I.7.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides a privileged lens through which to observe how democratic quality, gender inequalities, and power dynamics interact in Danish society. The picture that emerges from the data is that of a consolidated and robust institutional system, broadly trusted at the European level and supported by comparatively high civic engagement but not immune to polarization and pockets of skepticism toward parties and politicians. In the 2024 European elections, voter turnout was 58.25%, clearly above the EU average (51%)

(European Parliament 2024). This points to a sustained capacity for civic mobilization and a stable sense of attachment to the European project—although, as in most countries, participation remains lower than in national contests. Women hold 44% of seats in the national parliament, a level that stands well above the EU average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) and signals steady progress in women’s access to elected office over the last decade. Denmark scores 0.92 on V-Dem’s Electoral Democracy Index (Varieties of Democracy 2024), placing it among Europe’s top performers and confirming the strength of electoral competition, media freedom, and checks and balances. In the conflictual climate, political polarization is reported at 0.51—moderate by comparative standards but meaningful enough to shape discourse and party competition (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Support for authoritarian leadership in Denmark is very limited—only 4.9% of respondents agree that having a strong leader who does not have to deal with parliament or elections would be a good way of governing (Haerpfer et al. 2024), underscoring broad support for democratic institutions.

The 2022 Danish parliamentary elections produced a highly fragmented landscape, with no single party able to govern alone. The Social Democrats remained the largest force, with 27.5% of the vote, while the Liberal Party followed with 13.3%. Newer actors gained significant ground: the Moderates secured 9.3%, and the right-wing Denmark Democrats entered parliament with 8.1%. The Socialist People’s Party also maintained a stable presence at 8.3% (ParlGov 2023). These results highlight a competitive and pluralistic system in which coalition-building and cross-bloc cooperation are essential for forming a government. Denmark’s political arena is characterized by strong institutions, above-average electoral participation, and substantial gender representation.

I.7.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now crucial to understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Denmark, the online ecosystem is characterized by very wide use of digital media and comparatively high engagement on social networks, alongside clear vulnerabilities in media literacy and exposure to misleading content.

The use of digital platforms for news is extensive. About 65% of Danes report that they read news on the internet, underscoring the centrality of digital media in Denmark's public and political life (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a).

Trust in online sources shows a mixed picture. Roughly 38% of respondents say they tend to trust news found on websites, while about 39% express trust in information disseminated via social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These figures indicate that digital media enjoy nontrivial legitimacy, but they also signal potential susceptibility to the diffusion of false or manipulative content when verification skills are uneven.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widespread. According to data, around 81% of Danes consider disinformation a problem for democracy—well above the already high EU baseline (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, 16% report having been often or very often exposed to misleading content in the week prior to the survey, whereas only a small minority (7%) feel very confident in their ability to recognize it (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and effective skills suggests substantial room for improvement in civic and digital education.

The dimension of online radicalization deserves attention, particularly with regard to misogynist and anti-egalitarian communities. Denmark appears among countries where incel-related activity (12) has been detected on platforms such as incels.is (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These spaces mix hostility to women's rights with anti-democratic and anti-pluralist narratives, feeding gendered radicalization and rejection of equality norms.

Overall, Denmark's digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media provide broad access to information, participation, and debate—supported by high levels of online news use and sizable trust in web sources. On the other hand, high perceived disinformation, meaningful self-reported exposure, and limited strong confidence in detection skills constitute tangible risks for the quality of public debate and democratic resilience.

I.7.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country's capacity to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Denmark, the overall picture that emerges is favorable by European standards—especially on social relations and cultural openness—but with nontrivial fragilities in the transition from school to work and in the persistence of gender gaps in educational trajectories.

A particularly positive element concerns openness to diversity and relational resources. Youth inclusion in Denmark is characterized by strong educational outcomes and a highly inclusive social environment. A very high 91.7% of young women aged 25–29 years have attained between 12 and 18 years of education (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), reflecting significant gender equality in access to schooling and learning opportunities. Young Danes also display particularly open and tolerant attitudes—90% report openness toward immigrants, while 80% believe they have good opportunities to make friends and build social networks. Acceptance of sexual diversity is similarly widespread, with 90% of youth expressing acceptance of gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These indicators point to a generational profile marked by inclusivity, social cohesion, and progressive values, strengthening the foundations of democratic participation and equal opportunity. These patterns suggest that younger Danes can act as carriers of egalitarian and pluralistic values, reinforcing the country's democratic culture in the long run.

On the educational and economic front, however, vulnerabilities surface. The share of early leavers from education and training is 11.1% among young men and 9.6% among young women (Eurostat 2024a). While the male value is close to the EU reference, the female rate is noticeably above the EU27 average (7.7%), signaling that gendered hurdles in school continuity persist even within an otherwise high-performing system. These gaps matter because they translate into more fragile entries into the labor market and can widen inequalities in later life.

Taken together, Denmark's youth present a dual portrait. On the one hand, they show strong relational networks, openness to diversity, and a cultural orientation toward inclusion that bodes well for democratic resilience. On the other hand, early-leaving differentials, gender

asymmetries, and the challenges of securing stable socioeconomic autonomy indicate unfinished business on the road from education to empowerment.

I.7.8 Being socialized in Denmark

Being socialized in Denmark means growing up in a society in which equality, social trust, and democratic values are deeply institutionalized. Work–family reconciliation is strongly supported, and women’s leadership is normalized. Despite this, subtle expectations about caregiving and ambition still shape interactions. Young people experience highly inclusive environments, although some structural inequalities remain. Digital spaces support wide participation but also host misogynistic or anti-democratic content. Overall, masculine gender norms in Denmark develop within an egalitarian framework while still negotiating residues of traditional family roles and pressure arising from digital hostility.

I.8 ESTONIA

I.8.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Estonia combines solid macro-stability with a development level still below the EU average. In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs signals a compact, fast-modernizing economy that faces a sizable convergence gap with Western Europe. Income dispersion sits close to the EU average and percentage of people are at risk of poverty or social exclusion reflects vulnerabilities that growth has not yet fully alleviated (Table 10).

Table 10 Socioeconomic conditions in Estonia compared with the EU27

	Estonia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	79.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	28.5	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	22.2	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	74.0	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	78.5	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	59.8	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	85.7	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is a comparative strength and notably gender balanced. Employment among 15–64-year-olds is 76.2% for men and 75.2% for women—an exceptionally small gap by EU

standards and above the EU female benchmark. EIGE scores mirror this picture on paid work but the money domain reaches 74.0, indicating below-average economic outcomes driven by gender differences in earnings and job quality (Table 10).

Education is a mixed field. Horizontal segregation across study fields remains marked (segregation index 48.2) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and the pipeline into STEM is modest (15.1 women graduates in STEM per 1,000 aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2023b). Early leaving is higher than desirable—13.3% for boys and 8.6% for girls (Eurostat 2024a)—risking widening skill gaps and constraining social mobility. EIGE’s knowledge (59.8) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) underscores these frictions in skill distribution and field choice.

Demography and territory shape opportunity structures. A relatively large share of the population lives in rural areas (43.5%) (OECD 2023a), which can translate into uneven access to services and jobs. The old-age dependency ratio is 32.2 (Eurostat 2024e), signaling manageable but growing aging pressures. Foreign-born residents account for 16.1% (Eurostat 2022), making integration policy salient for labor supply and cohesion. Social protection is comparatively lean (about 17.2% of GDP) (OECD 2024b), which supports fiscal prudence but leaves less room than Nordic peers for cushioning risks across the life course.

Health and family policies show both assets and constraints. The health domain is high (85.7) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), reflecting good outcomes and access. Fathers are entitled to 4.3 weeks of paternity leave, usually with full pay (OECD 2024a)—a supportive yet relatively short provision that, on its own, is unlikely to transform caregiving norms or significantly reduce the gender gap in unpaid work. Correspondingly, EIGE’s overall score is 60.8, with time (64.4) showing significant gender imbalances in unpaid care and domestic work, consistent with EU-wide patterns, and power (32.8), revealing underrepresentation in decision-making (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

In sum, the country’s next frontier lies in converting macro-stability and digital strengths into broader social inclusion—reducing early leaving, strengthening the skills pipeline, especially into STEM, tackling horizontal segregation, and expanding support across rural territories. Estonia’s model blends high employment and resilient institutions with unfinished business on equality of outcomes, educational pathways, and the intimate economy of time and care.

I.8.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Estonia stands firmly among Europe's consolidated democracies, with institutions deeply anchored in the rule of law, civil liberties, and political pluralism. Its democratic architecture is strong. In 2024, the country scores 96/100 in Freedom in the World (Freedom House 2025), confirming a robust protection of political rights and individual freedoms. The Democracy Index is 8.13/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing Estonia within the group of "full democracies" characterized by competitive elections, active participation, and institutional stability. The Rule of Law Index reaches 0.82 (World Justice Project 2024), signaling an independent judiciary, effective enforcement mechanisms, and generally efficient public institutions. The V-Dem civil liberties index stands at 0.96, among the highest in the EU (Varieties of Democracy 2024), highlighting the depth of Estonia's commitment to fundamental rights and freedoms.

Inclusion and pluralism represent further areas of tension. Estonia's SIGI score (13.1) indicates moderate institutional discrimination (OECD 2023b), pointing to the remaining structural and normative barriers to gender equality. Policies on migrant integration also reveal limits. In fact, MIPEX scores 48 (MIPEX 2023). LGBTQI+ rights protections are also uneven. With a Rainbow Europe score of 11.59/100 on hate speech law/hate crime law on gender identity and/or sexual orientation (ILGA-Europe 2025), Estonia lags far behind many EU countries, reflecting gaps in the legal recognition of same-sex families, weak anti-discrimination protections, and insufficient legal provisions on hate crimes.

Public attitudes reveal a society that broadly supports the European project but retains elements of caution and ambivalence. Trust in the European Parliament stands at 63%, suggesting a stable connection to EU governance (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Estonia embodies many of the core democratic and institutional values of the European project—political freedoms are robust, the rule of law is solid, and civil liberties are well protected. However, the path toward a fully inclusive democracy remains incomplete. Deep gender inequalities, limited representation of women in power, partial integration of migrants, and weak LGBTQI+ protections reveal a gap between formal rights and their practical realization. Trust in European institutions is substantial but tempered by notable

skepticism, reflecting a value landscape in which democratic principles coexist with persistent cleavages linked to gender, identity, and belonging.

I.8.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Estonia reflect progress toward equality, which increasingly shapes public opinion and institutional practices, yet traditional expectations about gender roles remain deeply embedded in many areas of social life. The result is a complex and sometimes contradictory cultural configuration, in which progressive norms coexist with persistent stereotypes that continue to influence both private behaviors and public life.

Family and care-related attitudes illustrate the endurance of traditional expectations, as shown in Figure 31, based on Eurobarometer data (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 31 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Estonia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

These figures indicate a continued normative expectation that men should remain the primary decision-makers and that caregiving remains a female responsibility. These cultural

norms reflect the slow pace of change in perceptions of men's caregiving roles, despite evolving family structures and increased female labor market participation.

Views about domestic work and competence further underline gendered assumptions. About 45% of Estonians still consider men “naturally less competent” than women at performing household tasks, reinforcing stereotypes of domesticity as inherently female. This perception not only sustains gendered divisions of unpaid labor but also shapes broader cultural expectations of femininity and masculinity. Moreover, 66% of the population believes that men are more ambitious than women in politics, a view that continues to limit perceptions of women's political leadership potential and sustains gendered hierarchies in the public sphere. Attitudes toward gender roles and behaviors in Estonia reveal a mix of enduring stereotypes and progressive shifts (Figure 31). These figures highlight the persistence of deeply rooted cultural expectations regarding femininity and authority, which continue to shape perceptions of women's roles in public life and may act as barriers to their full participation in decision-making spheres. The notion that assertiveness and leadership are inherently masculine traits remains influential, reinforcing structural inequalities and symbolic biases.

At the same time, however, a significant majority (73%) agree that it is acceptable for men to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), pointing to a gradual shift in the cultural norms surrounding masculinity and emotional expression. This openness suggests that traditional stereotypes about male emotional restraint are losing their hold, at least in part, and that new models of masculinity—more compatible with emotional vulnerability and relational sensitivity—are gaining ground. On the one hand, awareness of gendered barriers is widespread—many Estonians recognize ongoing inequalities and structural obstacles to women's advancement. On the other hand, the persistence of stereotypes about competence, ambition, and decision-making authority suggests that symbolic barriers remain powerful, even as formal equality progresses. These mixed signals reveal that while Estonian society increasingly values gender equality, the cultural underpinnings of inequality are far from fully dismantled.

Attitudes toward feminism and equality initiatives add a further layer of complexity. A significant share of the population (54%) believes that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), reflecting a backlash sentiment that mirrors broader European trends. Such attitudes suggest that while the

principle of gender equality is widely accepted, efforts to advance it further are sometimes perceived as excessive or unfair, pointing to an undercurrent of resistance and cultural defensiveness.

In sum, Estonia's gender norm landscape is defined by ambivalence. On the one hand, support for equality, diversity, and pluralism is growing, particularly among younger generations, and public discourse increasingly rejects rigid gender roles. On the other hand, longstanding stereotypes about care, leadership, ambition, and competence remain influential, shaping expectations in both the family and public spheres. The perception that gender equality efforts have overreached, combined with enduring symbolic hierarchies, indicates that Estonia's journey toward a fully egalitarian society is ongoing—shaped by generational shifts but constrained by deeply ingrained cultural legacies.

1.8.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Estonia is a structural challenge that weighs on women's rights and the quality of democratic life. Despite a solid legal and institutional framework, prevalence, knowledge of rights, and effective access to protection remain uneven.

Available indicators point to a phenomenon that is far from marginal—41% of ever-partnered women report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence from an intimate partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Broadening the lens, 33.1% of women report physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures underscore persistent patterns of coercion and control within intimate relations, as well as in wider social contexts.

Awareness and access reveal important gaps. While general knowledge that support services exist is comparatively widespread (89.7% aware) (Eurostat 2021b), only 43% know about the right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This asymmetry—high general awareness but much lower awareness of concrete entitlements—can deter help-seeking and limit the practical enforceability of rights, especially for women facing economic or social vulnerabilities. At the severe end of the spectrum, Estonia records an annual homicide rate of 0.41 per 100,000 women killed by an intimate partner or family member (Eurostat 2023c).

This level signals room for improvement in early risk detection, coordinated protection, and perpetrator management.

On the legal front, Estonia is aligned with European standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on December 2, 2014, ratified it on October 26, 2017, and entered it into force domestically on February 1, 2018 (Council of Europe 2025). Implementation, however, remains the decisive frontier, translating laws into timely protection, survivor-centered services, and sustained prevention.

Overall, Estonia presents a mixed picture. Modern legal architecture and broad awareness of services coexist with significant prevalence, limited knowledge of concrete rights, and a non-negligible rate of lethal violence.

1.8.5 Political dimension

The political dimension helps reveal how democratic quality, gender inequality, and power dynamics interact in Estonia. The overall picture is of a consolidated, rules-based democracy with strong civil-liberties protections but also limited participation, moderate polarization, and uneven trust in representative institutions.

In the 2024 European elections, voter turnout was 37.64%, clearly below the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This signals weaker civic mobilization at the EU level and a looser sense of attachment to European electoral contests compared with national politics.

Women hold about 30% of the seats in parliament. This is below the EU average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating progress but continued underrepresentation of women in elected office and, by extension, in political decision-making. Public trust in EU institutions is comparatively high—around 70% of Estonians report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), a level that exceeds the trust typically recorded for national parties and suggests a meaningful legitimating role for the EU in Estonia's political landscape.

Indicators point to moderate political polarization and to socioeconomic power that is not highly concentrated by EU standards (power distributed by socio-economic position 29.3) (Varieties of Democracy 2024). At the same time, attitudinal tolerance for political violence remains very low (index 1.29) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), consistent with strong

normative commitments to peaceful democratic competition. Only 24% of respondents reported that they “tend to trust” political parties, and trust in the national government was similarly modest, at 38% (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These figures point to a significant detachment from key democratic institutions and suggest widespread skepticism regarding their effectiveness and responsiveness. Confidence in parliament is also weak, indicating that representative bodies may struggle to maintain legitimacy and public engagement. Although a clear majority reject authoritarian alternatives, a notable share of the population displays ambivalence. While 45.3% strongly disagree with the idea that “having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections” is desirable, smaller but significant minorities do not rule it out—25.6% are neutral, 13.4% somewhat agree, and 3.4% fully support such a system (Haerpfer et al. 2024). These results suggest that dissatisfaction with institutional performance and political elites may feed into latent preferences for more centralized, leader-focused governance.

The results of the 2023 national elections in Estonia paint a picture of a competitive and pluralistic political landscape characterized by a balance between centrist-liberal forces, conservative-nationalist actors, and emerging political movements. The Estonian Reform Party consolidated its position as the leading political force, securing 31.2% of the vote. At the same time, the electoral performance of more conservative and populist forces signals a diversified political field and a fragmented policy agenda. The People’s Union of Estonia/Conservative People’s Party achieved 16.1% of the vote, consolidating its position as the main opposition force and demonstrating sustained support for more nationalist, sovereigntist, and socially conservative policies. Similarly, the Estonian Centre Party obtained 15.3% of the vote, indicating that it remains a key player despite some erosion of its electoral base (ParlGov 2023).

In sum, Estonia’s political system combines high institutional quality and civil liberty guarantees with lower EU-level participation, gender underrepresentation in parliament, and moderate polarization. Strengthening women’s descriptive representation, raising turnout, especially in European contests, and deepening everyday trust in representative institutions emerge as the key levers for consolidating democratic resilience.

I.8.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial to understanding political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks of disinformation and radicalization. In Estonia, a highly connected society, the online ecosystem combines very wide news consumption on the Internet with uneven trust in digital sources and nontrivial exposure to misleading content.

Reading news online is spread about 57% of Estonians report doing so every day and 15% two or three times a week (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust is mixed and asymmetrical: 51% tend to trust news on websites, while 24% say they trust information on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This pattern signals significant legitimacy for social feeds as information channels, but it also heightens the risk that low-quality content circulates with few credibility checks. A large majority regard disinformation as a problem for democracy (79%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022), and self-reported exposure is meaningful (about 23% “often/very often” in the preceding week) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). However, only around 8% feel very confident that they can recognize false or manipulative content (European Parliament, Brussels 2022), revealing a gap between awareness and operational media literacy skills. Evidence indicates detectable—though comparatively small—incel-related activity in Estonia (1) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). Such misogynist “manosphere” spaces pair hostility to gender equality with anti-pluralist narratives and can act as gateways to gendered and anti-democratic radicalization.

Estonia’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, exceptionally high online news uptake supports participation and access to information. On the other hand, low–moderate trust calibration, regular exposure to disinformation, and limited strong confidence in detection skills create vulnerabilities that can be exploited by hostile actors and anti-egalitarian communities.

I.8.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key marker of democratic resilience and equal opportunity. On the relational and cultural sides, young Estonians report strong social connectedness but only moderate levels of openness toward diversity. Around 80% say they have good opportunities

to make friends and build social networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), indicating a solid foundation for youth social capital. However, openness toward immigrants and acceptance of gays and lesbians both stand at about 60% (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), suggesting that while tolerance is widespread, it is not as deeply embedded as it is in the Nordic context. These figures reflect a youth environment that is cohesive and relationally inclusive but still evolving in terms of embracing minority groups and broader forms of diversity.

Educationally, outcomes diverge by sex. Early leaving remains a vulnerability: 13.3% among boys and 8.6% among girls (Eurostat 2024a). The male rate sits above the EU reference, and the female rate is still slightly elevated, suggesting gendered hurdles in completion and a risk of weaker labor market entry for some cohorts. Taken together, Estonian youth display strong female attainment and solid social networks, alongside male-skewed early leaving and only middling cultural openness toward minorities.

I.8.8 Being socialized in Estonia

Being socialized in Estonia means growing up in a highly digitalized democracy with strong institutional guarantees but uneven civic participation. Turnout is low, and some ambivalence toward concentrated leadership remains. Gender relations reflect considerable progress in employment yet show persistent inequalities in leadership, care, and authority. Online communication is central, but limited media literacy allows polarized narratives to spread. In this environment, masculine gender norms in Estonia take shape at the intersection of digital saturation, institutional modernity, and durable expectations, associating masculinity with authority, independence, and emotional restraint.

I.9 FINLAND

I.9.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Finland's socioeconomic profile couples high stable development with a broadly inclusive labor market and a large protective welfare state. In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs confirms solid average living standards. Income dispersion is contained and the share at risk of poverty or social exclusion is comparatively low, indicating an effective capacity to compress inequalities without eliminating them entirely (Table 11).

Table 11 Socioeconomic conditions in Finland compared with the EU27

	Finland	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	103,00	100.00
Gini coefficient	24.8	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	16.8	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	86.7	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	78.6	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	59.7	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	91.7	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is a clear strength and strikingly gender-balanced—employment among 15–64-year-olds is 72.8% for men and 72.4% for women (Eurostat 2024b). EIGE’s index reflects this, signaling high participation and earnings capacity, while knowledge points to enduring educational stratifications (Table 11). Horizontal segregation remains notable (46.7% of tertiary students are in education/health/welfare/humanities/arts) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and STEM output is moderate (19.8 graduates per 1,000 aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2023b). Early leaving from education is contained but gendered (11.8% boys and 7.4% girls) (Eurostat 2024a).

Demography and territory add structural pressure. A sizable 38.7% of the population lives in rural areas (OECD 2023a), with an old-age dependency ratio of 37.8 (Eurostat 2024e), underscoring aging-related demands on pensions, health, and care. The foreign-born share (10.3%) (Eurostat 2022) sustains labor supply and diversity while keeping integration policy salient across regions.

The welfare state remains expansive and shock-absorbent—social expenditure is 31.4% of GDP. Health outcomes are excellent (EIGE Health 91.7) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Family policy has expanded fathers’ entitlements but remains modest in length on paper (paternity leave 3 weeks, average payment around 80%) (OECD 2024a), limiting its ability alone to reshape unpaid-care norms.

I.9.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Finland stands out among European democracies for the strength and stability of its political institutions, a longstanding commitment to the rule of law, and a deeply embedded culture of civil liberties and fundamental rights. Democratic governance is robust. According to Freedom in the World (Freedom House 2025), Finland scores 100/100 and is classified as “Free”, reflecting comprehensive protections for political rights and civil liberties. The Democracy Index places Finland among the world’s most advanced democracies with a score of 9.3/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), pointing to strong institutions, political pluralism, and a high level of citizen participation. The Rule of Law Index is similarly high (0.88) (World Justice Project 2024), highlighting effective judicial independence and institutional performance. V-Dem’s Civil Liberties Index (0.95) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) confirms a consolidated framework for the protection of fundamental freedoms.

The country also performs strongly on gender equality, although important challenges persist. Finland’s overall score on the Gender Equality Index (76) remains above the EU average, reflecting substantial parity in many spheres. The time dimension (68.7) suggests continuing inequalities in the distribution of unpaid care work, while the power dimension (75.8) indicates a relatively strong presence of women in decision-making, even if full parity has not yet been achieved (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Inclusion policies are comparatively well developed. Finland’s approach to migrant integration is among the most comprehensive in Europe, with MIPEX scores pointing to high standards in access to rights, education, and social participation (MIPEX 2023). In the domain of LGBTQI+ rights, Finland performs better than many of its EU peers. According to Rainbow Europe, the country scores 61/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), well above the EU average, although ongoing debates about legal recognition and anti-discrimination protection highlight areas for further progress.

Public attitudes mirror this institutional landscape. Trust in European institutions is relatively strong. Around half of Finnish respondents report confidence in the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), demonstrating a broadly supportive orientation toward EU membership.

In sum, Finland exemplifies a deeply rooted democratic culture characterized by robust institutions, high levels of civil liberty protection, and a strong commitment to equality and inclusion. However, the value landscape is not without its tensions. Persistent gendered divisions of care, ongoing struggles for full LGBTQI+ recognition, and the integration of a diversifying society point to areas where democratic ideals have yet to be fully realized. The result is a political and cultural context that combines exceptional institutional strength with evolving debates on equality, diversity, and belonging—making Finland both a model of democratic resilience and a society still negotiating the boundaries of inclusion.

1.9.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Finland display a relatively egalitarian profile compared to most EU countries, although traces of traditional views and symbolic stereotypes remain.

As displayed in Figure 32, based on data from the Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), expectations about women’s caregiving responsibilities have not disappeared but represent the expression of a minority.

Figure 32 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Finland

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

These values, well below the EU average, reflect the strong institutionalization of the dual-earner model and the broad acceptance of maternal employment. Still, they indicate that caregiving responsibilities continue to be culturally associated with women, albeit in a residual way.

Perceptions of inequality at work confirm this ambivalence. A majority (66%) believe that men and women are treated equally at work, underscoring widespread confidence in workplace fairness. At the same time, stereotypes about women's authority persist. These figures point to a context where equality is largely normalized, but symbolic barriers about female leadership remain.

Attitudes toward masculinity also reveal ambivalence. On the one hand, acceptance of nontraditional male roles is high—91% of Finns agree that it is acceptable for men to cry, a clear sign of openness toward emotional diversity (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, gendered domestic expectations endure—35% consider men “naturally less competent” at housework, and 9% think that men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition for their careers (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These views suggest that, while egalitarianism dominates, cultural residues still shape male identities in the private sphere. However, 54% of Finns believe that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These shares underline that Finland's cultural climate is among the least hostile to gender equality in Europe, although patriarchal attitudes have not disappeared entirely.

In Finland, attitudes toward gender roles and sexuality display clear generational and gender divides. Younger cohorts are generally more egalitarian, while older groups express greater ambivalence or skepticism, with women consistently more supportive of equality than men.

On LGBTQI+ rights, support is high across all groups but strongest among young women (94% vs. 88% of young men). Agreement declines modestly with age, especially among men, but women remain more supportive even in the oldest cohort (86% vs. 77%), with older men more likely to disagree (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Hostile attitudes follow the opposite gradient. The belief that women exaggerate sexual harassment increases sharply with age—endorsement rises from 16% to 68% among men and from 3% to 84% among women. Rejection falls accordingly, especially among older women, indicating a pronounced generational shift in the perceived credibility of women’s claims (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). The idea that women seek power over men also grows with age. Endorsement remains low among the young for both sexes but rises markedly among older respondents, reaching around 61% of men and 69% of women 56+, suggesting an internalization of gendered narratives in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Views of “benevolent” sexism follow yet another pattern. The rejection of the idea that women should be protected by men increases with age for both sexes, yet men consistently reject the norm more strongly (77% of men 56+ vs 53% of women). Conversely, young women show the highest attachment to protectionist views, with endorsement declining across age groups (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, Finland shows a mix of progressive attitudes led by younger cohorts—especially women—and persistent traditional narratives among older generations, in which skepticism and protective norms remain more entrenched.

In sum, the Finnish landscape of gender norms is one of broad egalitarian consensus, reinforced by strong institutional frameworks and cultural acceptance of equality. However, beneath this progressive picture, symbolic stereotypes about leadership and domestic roles persist, particularly among men and older cohorts. The result is a value system that is markedly more open than the European average but still marked by subtle resistances that shape how equality is practiced in everyday life.

I.9.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Finland remains a significant structural problem that continues to shape gender relations, democratic quality, and the full realization of fundamental rights. Despite a robust legal framework, relatively advanced welfare institutions, and high awareness of gender equality, violence against women remains widespread and signals persistent gendered power imbalances.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, 57.1% of women in Finland aged 18–74 years report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15—among the highest shares in the EU and well above the European average. The prevalence of violence perpetrated by partners or ex-partners is also considerable—52.6% of women report having suffered psychological violence, physical violence or threats, and/or sexual violence within intimate relationships (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures reflect not only the systemic nature of gender-based violence but also a relatively high societal capacity to recognize and report forms of abuse that extend beyond physical violence alone.

Awareness of and access to support services show mixed results. While around 90% of women victims report being aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b)—a comparatively high level within the EU—only 33% are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This gap suggests that although general knowledge of services is widespread, a limited understanding of concrete legal entitlements may hinder victims' ability to seek help and assert their rights, particularly in the most vulnerable situations.

The most severe forms of violence reveal a particularly troubling picture. The annual rate of intentional homicides of women committed by partners or family members is 0.61 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c). These data highlight persistent challenges in preventing violent escalation and underscore the ongoing need for early intervention strategies and effective risk assessment mechanisms.

From a legal and institutional perspective, Finland has established a comprehensive framework to combat gender-based violence. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on April 17, 2015, and brought it into force on August 1, 2015 (Council of Europe 2025). These steps signal Finland's commitment to European standards in the prevention of violence, victim protection, and prosecution of perpetrators. However, as the data show, the distance between legal commitments and their effective implementation remains substantial.

In sum, Finland's landscape of gender-based violence is characterized by deep contradictions. A strong institutional and legal framework coexists with persistently high levels of violence, gaps in victims' awareness of their rights, and worrying levels of lethal violence within

intimate and family contexts. This tension reveals the structural nature of gender-based violence and underscores that formal legal progress, while necessary, is not sufficient on its own. Closing the gap between rights and their effective realization remains one of the most urgent challenges for ensuring security, justice, and substantive gender equality in Finland.

I.9.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Finland provides a particularly insightful lens through which to understand how democratic institutions, gender equality, and power distribution intersect within a highly institutionalized and socially cohesive context. Finland stands out for its strong democratic traditions, robust institutional framework, and consistently high levels of civic engagement while also revealing new forms of polarization and persistent challenges in political trust and representation.

Democratic participation and representation remain among the most consolidated in Europe. Voter turnout in the 2024 European elections reached 40% (European Parliament 2024), and Finland maintains one of the most gender-equal parliaments in Europe. Women occupy 47% of parliamentary seats, well above the EU average of 33% (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This strong representation reflects both Finland's historical legacy of women's political participation and ongoing efforts to promote gender parity in decision-making arenas. The party landscape is characterized by ideological diversity and relative stability.

However, citizens' trust in political institutions is more complex. Trust in domestic political actors remains more restrained—38% express confidence in political parties, and about 56% trust the national parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Interest in politics remains moderate, with just 14% of respondents declaring it very interested (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), pointing to a certain distance between citizens and political elites despite Finland's institutional strengths.

Attitudes toward democracy and governance confirm a strong attachment to liberal norms. Nonetheless, similar to many European societies, Finland is not immune to polarization. Ideological divides are increasingly visible, particularly around questions of identity, immigration, and gender. V-Dem assesses Finland's level of political polarization at 1.18/4

(Varieties of Democracy 2024)—moderate by international standards but notable in a country historically characterized by consensus-oriented politics.

The ideological distribution of the party system in Finland reflects dynamics similar to those observed in other European democracies. According to recent election results (2023), the center-right National Coalition Party obtained 20.8% of the vote, while the far-right Finns Party—a radical right populist force with strong nationalist and anti-immigration positions—secured 20.1%. The SDP followed closely with 19.9%, and the centrist Centre Party received 11.3% (ParlGov 2023). This configuration illustrates the consolidation of conservative and nationalist actors, whose growing influence has significant implications for social policy, civil rights, and gender equality debates in Finland.

The ideological landscape in Finland reveals marked differences across generations and between men and women, highlighting how political socialization is shaped by age and gendered experiences. Across generations, a clear polarization trend emerges, with younger cohorts significantly more represented on the left and among far-left positions, while older groups lean increasingly toward the center, right, and far right. Among men, support for far-right positions rises steeply, from 15.4% among those under 35 to 55.1% among those over 56, while among women, the same trajectory culminates in an even sharper generational gap, from just 4.1% to 81.6% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Conversely, left-wing and far-left preferences are strongest among the youngest, suggesting that generational replacement could shift the ideological balance in the long term. There are significant gender contrasts within the same age groups. Men are consistently more concentrated in the center and right-wing blocs across all cohorts, with 40% of those under 35 identifying with centrist positions and around 31% with the right. Women, by contrast, are more likely to support the left and progressive forces, especially in younger age groups: 32% of women under 35 align with the left, compared to only 12.6% of men. At the same time, far-right support remains considerably lower among young women (1.1%) than among their male counterparts (6.9%), although the gender gap narrows—and even reverses—among older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Together, these patterns illustrate how generational replacement and gendered trajectories are likely to shape Finland's political landscape, with younger cohorts and women pushing

toward more progressive positions, while older men remain more anchored to conservative and far-right orientations.

Taken together, Finland’s political system combines deep democratic consolidation and strong gender representation with signs of emerging challenges: declining electoral participation, moderate institutional trust, and growing polarization. While these dynamics do not threaten the country’s democratic foundations, they illustrate the evolving nature of political socialization in Finland—one where enduring democratic value coexists with new cleavages and tensions linked to gender, identity, and participation.

I.9.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now central to political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks of disinformation and radicalization. In Finland, the online ecosystem is highly developed and generally trusted, yet it also shows vulnerabilities linked to critical skills and exposure to content hostile to democracy and gender equality.

The use of digital platforms for news is massive—73% report reading news online every day (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust is relatively high for news on websites (about 44% “tend to trust”), while it is more cautious about information on social networks (15%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This mix confirms the centrality of digital media in Finland’s public sphere but also points to potential channels for misleading content.

Perceived risk is very high—83% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, confidence in recognizing fake news remains limited (17% “very confident”, but 61% answer “somewhat” confident) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022), highlighting a gap between awareness and effective verification skills. Moreover, in Finland, perceptions of exposure to disinformation reveal both widespread contact with misleading content and a significant degree of uncertainty. According to the data, 6% of respondents reported encountering disinformation “very often” and 12% reported encountering it “often” in the previous week, while the largest share (36%) said they had been exposed “sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). These figures suggest that while disinformation is a routine part of many people’s online experiences, a substantial portion of the population may

underestimate its frequency or struggle to identify it, highlighting the importance of strengthening media literacy and critical digital skills.

Online radicalization is an additional concern. Between 2017 and 2020, Finnish users were identified on incels.is (at least 12 accounts) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), a platform associated with the “manosphere”, in which misogynistic and anti-pluralist narratives circulate. This presence shows that even in a high-civic-capital context, there are communities hostile to gender rights and democratic norms.

Overall, Finland’s digital environment has a dual face. It offers broad access to information and participation, supported by comparatively high trust, but coexists with high perceived exposure to disinformation, inadequate critical self-efficacy, and organized pockets of online misogyny. The policy challenge is twofold: strengthen media literacy and critical thinking across the life course and prevent radicalization through targeted interventions against communities that spread gendered hatred and anti-democratic rhetoric.

I.9.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key pillar of democratic vitality and social cohesion, reflecting a country’s capacity to ensure equal opportunities and support the transition to active citizenship. In Finland, the overall picture is highly positive, with strong indicators of cultural openness, relational capital, and social integration, although some challenges remain in terms of economic autonomy and educational trajectories.

Finland ranks among the top European countries for youth inclusion, scoring about 90/100 in the Youth Progress Index (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This very high value reflects a favorable combination of social capital, tolerance, and inclusive attitudes, highlighting the extent to which younger generations benefit from—and contribute to—an open, rights-based society.

Finnish youth are particularly positive about diversity and inclusion—80% view Finland as a good place for immigrants, and 90% perceive it as a good place for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These figures, which are markedly higher than those for the general population in many European countries, underscore a generational shift toward more cosmopolitan and egalitarian values. The social-relational dimension is equally strong, with 80% of young people reporting that they have

good opportunities to make friends (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), indicating a solid base of social trust and interpersonal networks.

Despite these strengths, some vulnerabilities persist, particularly regarding education and labor market integration. Early school leaving is relatively low—9.3% among young men and 7.4% among young women (Eurostat 2024a)—yet the gender gap remains, reflecting enduring inequalities in educational attainment and pathways.

Overall, Finland offers an enabling environment for young people characterized by inclusive attitudes, strong opportunities for socialization, and high educational engagement. At the same time, persistent gender gaps and challenges linked to economic independence highlight the need for a continued policy focus on ensuring that all young people can fully realize their potential. The country's strong foundation of tolerance and social capital provides a crucial resource for democratic resilience, as younger generations emerge as beneficiaries and drivers of Finland's inclusive and egalitarian social model.

I.9.8 Being socialized in Finland

Being socialized in Finland means growing up in a consolidated democracy with strong welfare support and substantial female political representation. Polarization around identity, immigration, and gender, however, has increased. Attitudes reveal broad support for equality, but there are lingering stereotypes about protection and leadership in some parts of the population. Younger groups emphasize diversity and inclusion but still face structural barriers in education and employment. The digital environment expands civic engagement but also hosts misogynistic narratives. Consequently, masculine gender norms in Finland reflect egalitarian institutional foundations and emerging tensions linked to cultural change and digital polarization.

I.10 FRANCE

I.10.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

France's socioeconomic landscape combines above-EU average development with a large protective welfare state while displaying persistent territorial and social disparities. In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs confirms solid capacity to generate material well-being even amid global shocks and structural transitions. Income dispersion is slightly above the EU mean,

indicating moderate but non-negligible inequality in spite of strong average prosperity (Table 12).

Table 12 Socioeconomic conditions in France compared with the EU27

	France	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	99.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	30.4	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	20.5	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	84.8	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	73.4	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	65.9	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	88	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is steady but remains gendered. Among people aged 15–64, employment is around 72% for men and 66% for women (Eurostat 2024b)—near EU benchmarks yet leaving a nontrivial participation and job-quality gap that weighs on women’s economic autonomy and career progression. The Gender Equality Index mirrors this two-sided picture. France’s overall score is mid-70s, with money (high-80s) and work (mid-70s) performing strongly, while knowledge points to horizontal segregation across fields of study and unequal pipelines into STEM and top-paying sectors (Table 12). Early school leaving is comparatively low in EU terms (male 9% and female 6%) (Eurostat 2024a). The French higher education system continues to reflect clear patterns of gender segregation, both horizontally and vertically. In 2024, 60.7% of tertiary students are concentrated in education, health, welfare, humanities, and the arts—fields traditionally dominated by women (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This figure illustrates the persistence of horizontal segregation, whereby women remain overrepresented in care-oriented and cultural sectors, while being underrepresented in technical and scientific domains.

About 27% of the population lives in rural areas, and the old-age dependency ratio is around 34 (OECD 2023a), underscoring aging pressures on pensions and care systems. The foreign-born share—14% (Eurostat 2022)—sustains labor supply and diversity while keeping integration policy central to social cohesion. France’s universalist welfare architecture remains one of Europe’s largest—social expenditure is 30.6% of the GDP (OECD 2024b),

cushioning shocks and compressing inequalities. Family policy has moved toward more balanced care. Paternity leave is 4.2 weeks with substantial wage replacement (up to a ceiling) (OECD 2024a)—a meaningful step, although not sufficient on its own to close the domestic time gap. Health outcomes are strong, yet the time dimension scores indicate that unpaid care remains unevenly shared, and the power dimension still trails money and work dimensions despite recent gains in politics and business (Table 12). In sum, France blends above-average prosperity and a powerful welfare state with unfinished business on gender equality in time and power and on translating macro-stability into evenly shared life chances.

I.10.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

France ranks among the European democracies with the strongest institutional frameworks and a longstanding tradition of constitutionalism, civil liberties, and pluralism. The country's democratic system is well established and enjoys a high level of legitimacy, yet its value landscape also reflects persistent tensions, particularly in the areas of gender equality, minority inclusion, and public attitudes toward European integration. According to Freedom in the World, France scores 89/100 in 2024 and is classified as “Free” (Freedom House 2025), reflecting robust protections for political rights and civil liberties. The Democracy Index, published by the Economist Intelligence Unit, assigns France a score of 8/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing it among the world's full democracies and attesting to a political system characterized by stable institutions, competitive elections, and broad. The Rule of Law Index is similarly high (0.72) (World Justice Project 2024), pointing to strong legal enforcement, judicial independence, and relatively efficient institutional performance. These results are supported by V-Dem's Civil Liberties Index, which stands at 0.91 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), confirming France's solid record of protecting fundamental freedoms and individual rights. France's overall Gender Equality Index score is around 76, above the EU average, signaling considerable progress toward gender parity in many areas (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Inclusion and diversity policies show a similarly mixed picture.

France's score on MIPEX to measure policies to integrate migrants is about 79 (MIPEX 2023), suggesting inclusive policies, although challenges remain in the areas of political participation and naturalization. The situation is more complex when it comes to LGBTQI+ rights.

According to Rainbow Europe, France scores 61/100, a result that, while higher than the EU

average (51) (ILGA-Europe 2025), still reveals significant gaps and areas where legal protections and social recognition could be strengthened. Public attitudes toward the EU offer further insight into the country's value orientation. Trust in the European Parliament stands at 50%, indicating a stable connection to the European project (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). In conclusion, France combines strong democratic credentials with a deep-rooted commitment to the rule of law, pluralism, and individual rights. However, the landscape of values remains marked by challenges, including gendered divisions in care and power, the incomplete inclusion of LGBTQI+ communities, and ongoing debates over European integration. These tensions highlight a society in transition—one that upholds fundamental democratic principles while grappling with the complexities of equality, diversity, and social cohesion in a changing political and cultural context.

I.10.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in France reveal a complex interplay between progressive values and persistent traditional beliefs, shaping how gender roles are understood and enacted in the public and private spheres. Significant progress toward equality has been achieved, yet enduring stereotypes continue to structure expectations around family, work, leadership, and masculinity. Family roles remain one of the domains in which traditional norms are most entrenched. According to Eurobarometer data (Figure 33), values are below the EU average but reflect the persistence of gendered expectations that tie caregiving primarily to women, casting doubt on the compatibility between motherhood and employment. Perceptions of inequality in the workplace underscore this tension.

Figure 33 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in France

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

About 66% of French respondents believe that men are treated better than women at work, a figure that highlights widespread awareness of persistent gender disparities (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, this recognition coexists with cultural beliefs that legitimize traditional divisions of labor, suggesting that equality is still viewed through a lens that normalizes male privilege in the economic sphere. Attitudes toward political leadership mirror this ambivalence. On the one hand, there is substantial support for gender parity—77% of respondents agree that “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Attitudes toward political leadership reflect this ambivalence (Figure 33), suggesting that although overt resistance is confined to a minority, subtle biases continue to shape perceptions of female leadership. Cultural conceptions of masculinity also reflect shifting norms alongside lingering traditional expectations. A large majority (91%) consider it acceptable for men to cry, indicating a gradual erosion of rigid emotional stereotypes (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, more conservative views persist—35% believe men are “naturally less competent” at household tasks (although below the European score—49%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These beliefs show that while

emotional norms around masculinity are becoming more flexible, traditional divisions of responsibility within the family remain deeply rooted.

Generational and gender patterns offer further nuance. In France, support for LGBTQI+ rights shows an unusual generational gradient. Agreement that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” is slightly higher among older cohorts (around 43% for both men and women 56+) than among the under-35s (25%), with younger respondents displaying more neutrality or ambivalence. Gender differences, however, remain substantial. Across all ages, women are markedly more supportive than men—over 95% of young women agree with the statement, compared with 85% of young men (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Opinions on hostile stereotypes are also gendered. Men are more likely than women to believe that women “exaggerate” harassment claims or “seek to gain power”, with endorsement particularly pronounced among older men (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Protective norms show the reverse pattern—men are far more likely to reject the idea that “women should be protected by men” (up to 72% among older men), while women remain more ambivalent, with about one-third endorsing the protectionist view (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, these contrasts highlight how gender continues to structure attitudes in France. Women are consistently more supportive of equality and less receptive to hostile or paternalistic norms, while men—especially in older cohorts—remain more attached to traditional or hierarchical views.

Overall, the landscape of gender norms in France is shaped by a dual dynamic. On the one hand, there is increasing openness toward egalitarian ideals, particularly among younger generations and in attitudes toward masculinity and LGBTQI+ rights. On the other hand, entrenched stereotypes around caregiving, leadership, and family authority continue to shape social expectations and limit progress. The result is a society in transition, where significant steps toward equality coexist with cultural resistances that still structure everyday life and institutional practices.

I.10.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in France remains a profound structural challenge that continues to affect women’s rights, social cohesion, and the effective functioning of democracy. Despite a

comprehensive legal framework and significant institutional efforts, prevalence levels, awareness of rights, and access to protection services reveal persistent shortcomings that hinder the country's ability to guarantee full gender equality and safety. According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (2024), 34.5% of women in France aged 18–74 years report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15—a figure slightly above the EU27 average (31%) and indicative of the systemic nature of violence (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Within intimate relationships, the problem is even more pronounced—30.2% of women report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence from a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures demonstrate the depth of coercive and controlling dynamics in intimate settings and underline the extent to which violence remains normalized in everyday life.

Awareness of available support services is relatively widespread but far from sufficient. About 85% of women are aware of the existence of services for victims of violence (Eurostat 2021b), yet only 28% know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This gap between general service awareness and knowledge of specific entitlements illustrates how structural barriers—such as limited information, bureaucratic complexity, and socio-economic vulnerability—can limit victims' ability to seek help and enforce their rights effectively. At the severe end of the spectrum, lethal violence remains a major concern. France records one of the highest rates of femicide in Western Europe, with 0.39 per 100,000 women killed by a partner or family member annually—a figure significantly higher than the EU average (Eurostat 2023c). These data point to persistent weaknesses in early risk detection, inter-agency coordination, and protective interventions, as well as a failure to address recurring patterns of escalating violence before they culminate in fatal outcomes. On the legal and institutional front, France has been a committed actor in combating gender-based violence. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on July 4, 2014, and the convention entered into force on November 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). Legislative reforms have strengthened the criminalization of domestic violence, expanded protection orders, and improved the training of police and judicial personnel. Nevertheless, the gap between legal standards and their practical implementation remains significant. Persistent prevalence levels, low reporting rates, and barriers to justice reveal that formal legal progress

has yet to fully translate into substantive protection on the ground. In summary, the French landscape of gender-based violence is defined by stark contrasts—robust legal instruments and a broad institutional commitment coexist with high prevalence, uneven access to support, and a continuing pattern of lethal violence. These contradictions underscore the urgent need for more effective prevention strategies, improved victim support services, and a stronger focus on transforming social norms that tolerate or normalize violence.

I.10.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides a crucial perspective for understanding how democracy, gender inequalities, and power dynamics intersect in France. The overall picture is that of a consolidated and institutionally robust democratic system but one that also displays significant fragilities: declining trust in representative institutions, persistent gender imbalances, and growing ideological fragmentation. Voter participation offers a first indication of democratic vitality. Turnout in the 2024 European elections was 51.5% (European Parliament 2024), slightly above the EU average (51%), pointing to moderate civic engagement and a stable, if not enthusiastic, sense of belonging to the European project. Participation rates are typically higher in national elections, indicating that EU-level contests continue to be perceived as less decisive for citizens' everyday lives. Women's representation in politics shows mixed progress. Women currently hold around 39% of seats in the National Assembly, slightly above the EU average (33%) but still short of parity (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This reflects important advances in gender representation over the past decades, driven by parity laws and party quotas, yet it also highlights the persistence of structural barriers to women's full participation in political decision-making.

Institutional indicators confirm France's democratic strength. The V-Dem Electoral Democracy Index stands at 0.87 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), reflecting free and fair elections, institutional checks and balances, and a pluralistic political landscape. However, these formal strengths coexist with critical challenges. Trust in political institutions remains modest—only 13% of citizens report trusting political parties, while 18% trust the national parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). This skepticism is also reflected in broader political attitudes. About 40.5% of French respondents strongly reject the idea that “having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections” would be desirable. However, significant minorities display

ambivalence—17.7% say it is fairly good, and 5.2% fully support such an alternative (Haerpfer et al. 2024). This openness to executive centralization reflects both dissatisfaction with the effectiveness of representative institutions and a desire for more decisive political leadership—trends that, if unchecked, could pose risks to democratic resilience. Polarization has deepened in recent years, driven by socioeconomic inequalities, territorial divides, and cultural conflicts around identity, secularism, and migration.

Economic power is also unevenly distributed (2.86/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), with wealthier groups exerting disproportionate political influence despite the continued relevance of middle-class and working-class constituencies. The 2022 French legislative elections confirmed a highly fragmented and competitive party landscape, reflecting deep ideological pluralism and growing polarization. President Macron's centrist alliance the Republic Onwards! | Renaissance remained the dominant force, winning 25.8% of the vote, but it fell short of an absolute majority, forcing the government to rely on alliances to pass legislation. The left-wing coalition Unbowed France (La France Insoumise, FI) emerged as the second largest parliamentary force, with a vote share of 25.7%. Meanwhile, the far-right National Rally (Rassemblement National, FN) achieved 18.7% of the vote (ParlGov 2023). This result marked a significant strengthening of radical right representation and reflected a broader shift in French public opinion, highlighting voter dissatisfaction with traditional parties and growing divisions over issues such as immigration, national identity, and Europe.

In France, younger cohorts are more balanced across the spectrum, while older groups polarize more strongly. Among men younger than 35, 29% place themselves on the left and 21% on the far right. In contrast, among men older than 56, 49% identify with the far left and 46.5% with the right. Women show a similar age gradient—only 15.7% of those younger than 35 place themselves on the right, compared to 53.7% among those older than 56, with far-right identification rising from 18.9% to 59.5%. Women are consistently more left-leaning, with 32–33% across all age groups on the left, compared to 29–38% of men. Men, however, are more represented on the far right (21% aged 35 or younger and 39% older than 56 years) than women (19% aged 35 or younger and 59% older than 56 years). Both genders converge around the center (40–50%), but polarization at the extremes is more pronounced among men, while women shift more sharply to the right with age (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Taken together, these trends depict a complex political environment. France’s democratic system remains institutionally solid and continues to guarantee fundamental rights, but public trust is limited, polarization is significant, and a notable segment of the population expresses openness to illiberal alternatives. Gender representation is improving but incomplete, and generational and gender-based cleavages structure political preferences. This constellation of dynamics makes France a revealing case of a democracy that is both resilient and contested—one where the future trajectory of democratic norms, gender equality, and institutional legitimacy remains deeply intertwined.

I.10.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension has become a central arena for political socialization, opinion formation, and the circulation of ideas—including those that challenge democratic norms and gender equality. In France, the online ecosystem is highly developed and widely used, but it is also characterized by uneven trust, substantial exposure to disinformation, and the presence of radicalizing communities that can shape gendered and anti-democratic narratives. Digital platforms are now the primary source of news and political information for a large share of the French population. According to Eurobarometer data, around 36% of French people report reading news online every day, and 24% of French say “two or three times a week” (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024b). Trust in digital sources is mixed. About 33% of French respondents say they trust news found on websites, while 18% report trusting information shared via social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024b). These figures reveal a relatively cautious approach to online content, particularly on social platforms, where concerns about reliability and bias remain widespread. Nonetheless, the significant share of the population that relies on online sources highlights their legitimacy—and their potential to shape public perceptions and democratic attitudes.

Awareness of the risks posed by disinformation is high, yet it coexists with limited confidence in detection skills. About 87% of French respondents consider disinformation to be a “serious problem for democracy” (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022), one of the highest rates in the EU, underscoring widespread concern about its impact on electoral processes, social cohesion, and institutional trust. However, only 11% of respondents feel “very confident” in their ability to identify fake news, while 57% report that

they can recognize it “only sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). Moreover, nearly 24% report encountering misleading or false content “often” or “very often” in the week preceding the survey (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This combination of high awareness and low confidence illustrates a critical gap in media literacy, leaving citizens vulnerable to manipulation despite their recognition of the problem.

The risks associated with online environments extend beyond misinformation to include exposure to radicalizing and misogynistic content. Research conducted by the European Commission and Moonshot between 2017 and 2020 identified significant French user activity in “manosphere” spaces (33) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), including platforms such as incels.is, where hostility toward women, feminism, and gender equality is openly promoted. These spaces often intersect with broader anti-democratic and conspiratorial narratives, offering alternative masculinities defined by resentment, dominance, and rejection of pluralism. They also serve as recruitment grounds for extremist communities, linking gender-based hatred with broader authoritarian and exclusionary ideologies.

I.10.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key indicator of democracy’s vitality and its ability to guarantee equal opportunities for the next generation. In France, the overall picture is mixed. While young people benefit from relatively strong social networks, high levels of civic engagement, and growing openness to diversity, structural inequalities and persistent barriers continue to limit full empowerment and socioeconomic autonomy. According to the Youth Progress Index, young people report strong social connectedness—70% say they have good opportunities to make friends and build networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), suggesting that youth social capital is robust and that young generations are embedded in relatively cohesive peer environments. Attitudes toward diversity among young people reveal a nuanced picture. Around 80% of young people consider France a “good place” for immigrants, and 80% believe it is welcoming for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These figures, while indicating significant openness, remain slightly below the levels observed in Nordic countries and point to an ongoing process of cultural change rather than a completed transition toward inclusive norms. The fact that younger cohorts are consistently more positive than the general

population also suggests a generational shift in values, with long-term implications for social cohesion and democratic resilience. However, important challenges persist in education and in the transition to adulthood.

Early school leaving is 9.4% among boys and 6.1% among girls, a medium level comparable to several EU countries. Gender differences persist, with boys being more affected (Eurostat 2024a). While both figures are slightly below the EU average, they highlight persistent gender disparities in educational trajectories and point to vulnerabilities that can affect future employment prospects and social mobility. In sum, being young in France today means growing up in a context that combines strong relational resources and increasing cultural openness with persistent structural barriers and social divides. The younger generation's inclusive values and social capital represent important assets for democratic renewal, but the obstacles they face in education, employment, and autonomy reveal the need for more comprehensive policies to support equal opportunities.

I.10.8 Being socialized in France

Being socialized in France means growing up in a stable democracy with strong civil liberties and a comprehensive welfare system, combined with low trust in political actors and increasing ideological tensions. Normative support for gender parity coexists with persistent stereotypes around family roles and leadership credibility. Younger people tend to challenge these norms more consistently. Digital platforms facilitate civic engagement as well as the spread of misinformation and gender-hostile discourse. Within this setting, masculine gender norms in France develop amid the coexistence of formal equality, cultural ambivalence, and digitally amplified contestation.

I.11 GERMANY

I.11.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Germany's socioeconomic profile combines high development with broad labor market participation while facing pressures from aging and skill stratification. In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs confirms strong average living standards. Income dispersion is close to the EU norm and 21.1% of the population is at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Table 13).

Table 13 Socioeconomic conditions in Germany compared with the EU27

	Germany	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	115.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	28.1	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	21.1	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	88.4	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	77.0	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	57.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	89.7	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is robust and comparatively gender-balanced—among 15–64-year-olds, employment reaches 80.7% for men and 74.1% for women (Eurostat 2024b). EIGE’s domain scores point in the same direction. Work indicates a good level of gender equality in earning capacity and participation. However, education and skill allocation remain uneven. The knowledge domain stands at 57.1, horizontal segregation is notable (43.9) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and STEM output is moderate (about 14.1 graduates per 1,000 aged 20–29) (Eurostat 2023b). These patterns constrain mobility and feed sectoral shortages, despite overall strength.

Demography and territory add further structural challenges. Only 15.6% of the population lives in rural areas (OECD 2023a)—limiting geographic disparities relative to more rural member states—but the old-age dependency ratio (35.2) (Eurostat 2024e) underscores mounting pressures on pensions, health, and long-term care. A large foreign-born share (20.2%) (Eurostat 2022) sustains labor supply and innovation while keeping integration and cohesion high on the policy agenda.

Germany’s welfare state is extensive but leaner than in some continental neighbors—social expenditure equals 27.9% of GDP (OECD 2024b). Health outcomes are strong (89.7) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), but there is no specific “paternity leave” law (OECD 2024a). Institutional quality remains a core asset. In sum, Germany’s socioeconomic and institutional structure blends high prosperity, solid employment, and resilient institutions with persistent education/skill segmentation, aging-related pressures, and pockets of vulnerability that require targeted, inclusion-oriented policies.

I.11.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Germany stands among the European countries with the most consolidated democratic institutions and a political tradition strongly rooted in the rule of law and fundamental rights. At the same time, the value landscape reveals ambivalence, particularly in relation to gender equality, migrant integration, and LGBTQI+ rights.

According to Freedom in the World, Germany scores 95/100 and is classified as “Free” (Freedom House 2025), confirming robust guarantees of political rights and civil liberties. The Democracy Index assigns the country a score of 8.73/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing it among the “full democracies” and highlighting a stable system of pluralism, participation, and institutional performance. In line with these results, V-Dem’s Civil Liberties Index reaches 0.94 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), underscoring a strong and consolidated protection of fundamental rights.

Germany’s overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 72, slightly above the EU average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, challenges persist in the knowledge (57.1) and power (71.5 vs. 61.4 EU) domains (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), in which women remain underrepresented in top decision-making positions despite recent improvements. The time dimension (65) also points to continuing inequalities in the distribution of unpaid care work (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

With respect to inclusion, Germany scores 69 on MIPEX (MIPEX 2023), reflecting relatively advanced policies on access to education, labor market participation, and health but showing persistent limitations in the areas of political participation and long-term residence. The framework for LGBTQI+ rights also displays mixed results. According to Rainbow Europe (ILGA-Europe 2025), Germany scores 0 on hate speech law/hate crime law (gender identity and/or sexual orientation).

Public attitudes toward the EU provide an additional perspective. In 2024, 38% of German respondents declared that they trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). At the same time, around 6% believe that European integration has “gone too far” (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), signaling the presence of Eurosceptic currents, although not dominant.

In sum, Germany combines solid democratic institutions, high standards of civil liberties, and comparatively advanced equality and integration frameworks. However, the persistence of gendered divisions of care, gaps in women's access to top decision-making roles, and incomplete protection for LGBTQI+ people highlight areas where democratic ideals are only partially realized. Trust in European institutions is relatively robust, but the presence of Eurosceptic minorities and ongoing debates around inclusion and equality reveal a value system in transition, in which consolidated democratic principles coexist with emerging tensions over identity, belonging, and rights.

I.11.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Germany reveal a similarly complex configuration in which notable progress toward gender equality coexists with enduring stereotypes and traditional expectations that continue to shape the social roles of women and men in both private and public spheres. Family-related norms remain one of the domains where traditional conceptions are most entrenched, as shown in Figure 34 (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These percentages point to the persistence of cultural expectations that position women primarily as caregivers and suggest a widespread belief that motherhood and full labor market participation are difficult to reconcile.

Figure 34 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Germany

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality in the workplace reinforce this ambivalent picture. A substantial share of respondents (71%) believe that men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), indicating a broad awareness of gender-based inequalities and structural barriers. However, this acknowledgment coexists with traditional attitudes that normalize and justify gendered divisions of labor and responsibility, demonstrating how cultural norms can persist even alongside the recognition of inequality.

The political domain further illustrates these contradictions. On the one hand, public opinion is largely favorable to gender parity in decision-making—67% of respondents consider “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, gender stereotypes continue to undermine women’s legitimacy as leaders (Figure 34). These attitudes reveal persistent symbolic biases that restrict the acceptance of women in positions of power, even when formal support for equality is widespread.

A cultural understanding of masculinity also exhibits ambivalence. A large majority of Germans (88%) consider it “acceptable” for a man to cry—a signal of a gradual erosion of

rigid emotional stereotypes—yet more traditional expectations endure. For example, 14% believe that men taking parental leave “show a lack of ambition for their career”, 12% think that men should have “the final say” in family decisions, and 49% maintain that men are “naturally less competent than women” in housework (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These results show how cultural scripts continue to associate masculinity with authority, decision-making power, and detachment from domestic responsibilities.

The cultural debate is further complicated by the perception that gender equality efforts have overreached. Nearly 34% of Germans believe that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), pointing to a social climate in which the pursuit of equality increasingly encounters resistance and backlash dynamics.

In Germany, attitudes toward gender norms show marked generational divides. Skepticism about harassment claims increases with age. Among men, the share saying women exaggerate such claims rises from about 28% (under 35) to nearly 38% (56+), while among women it grows more sharply (from 21% to 46%). Perceptions that women seek to gain power over men follow a similar pattern, increasing from roughly one-quarter to almost half for both sexes (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Support for paternalistic views—such as the idea that women should be protected by men—declines modestly with age among men (from 38% to 32%), while among women, it remains more stable and slightly higher in the oldest cohort (around 34%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). These trends suggest that traditional stereotypes are more entrenched among older generations, whereas younger cohorts display comparatively more egalitarian orientations, even if stereotypes persist.

Gender differences are present but less pronounced than age differences. Women are generally less skeptical of harassment claims and slightly more likely to reject paternalistic norms (49% of older women vs 44% of older men say protection is “never/rarely” needed) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). On views about power dynamics, however, differences are smaller and sometimes reversed, with women in some age groups reporting higher agreement that women seek control.

Overall, gender norms in Germany are marked by structural ambivalence. On the one hand, significant progress has been made toward more egalitarian conceptions of gender roles, with growing support for parity in leadership and increasing acceptance of nontraditional masculinities. On the other hand, deeply ingrained stereotypes continue to influence expectations about family responsibilities, leadership, and authority.

I.11.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Germany is a structural problem that constrains women's rights and full democratic inclusion, despite a mature legal framework and strong welfare institutions. Survey indicators point to a phenomenon that is both widespread and often embedded in intimate relations. Roughly one-third of women report having experienced psychological and/or physical/sexual violence by a partner or ex-partner since age 15 (about 32%), while violence by any perpetrator affects about one-quarter of women (about 26%) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These levels confirm that gender-based violence is neither marginal nor episodic and that coercive control and nonphysical abuse remain part of everyday gendered power relations.

Knowledge of concrete rights and pathways to help is uneven. Only around 25% of women are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a), and about two in five (41%) know about specialized support services (Eurostat 2021b). This gap between general sensitivity to the issue and awareness of specific entitlements can discourage reporting and hinder access to effective protection, especially for the most vulnerable.

The most extreme outcomes underscore urgency. The annual homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member is 0.6 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), a reminder that failures in early risk assessment and protection can escalate into lethal violence. Legally, Germany has aligned with European standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on October 12, 2017, and entered it into force domestically on February 1, 2018 (Council of Europe 2025). However, the data above indicate a persistent implementation gap—high prevalence, low rights awareness, and continued lethal cases signal that prevention, early intervention, and victim-centered access to justice remain uneven across Länder and services.

Overall, Germany's picture is one of strong formal commitments coexisting with substantial practical shortcomings. Reducing gender-based violence will require sustained investment in primary prevention, systematic risk management, stronger coordination among police, health, and justice, and a significant boost in rights literacy so that legal guarantees translate into real safety for women.

I.11.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a privileged lens through which to observe the interactions among democracy, gender inequalities, and power dynamics in German society. The resulting picture is that of a highly consolidated and institutionally robust democratic system but one that faces growing polarization, selective disengagement, and rising distrust toward representative institutions.

Voter turnout provides the first indicator of democratic vitality. In the 2024 European elections, participation in Germany reached 64.7%, well above the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This relatively high level of turnout signals broad civic mobilization and a strong sense of European belonging, although participation remains below the levels typically seen in national elections.

Gender representation in political institutions shows steady but incomplete progress. Women currently hold 35% of seats in parliament, a share that exceeds the EU average (33%) but remains significantly below parity (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). While Germany has seen important advances in female political participation, persistent barriers continue to limit women's access to top decision-making positions.

According to ParlGov data, in the 2021 German federal election, the SPD emerged as the largest party, with 25.7% of the vote. The Greens followed with 14.8%, while the Free Democratic Party (FDP) secured 11.5%. The far-right Alternative for Germany obtained 10.3% of the vote, indicating a stable presence of radical right-wing politics in the Bundestag. Together, the SPD, Greens, and FDP command 52.0% of the vote, forming a strong parliamentary majority (ParlGov 2023). This outcome reflects a fragmented but plural party system, where coalition building remains crucial, and highlights the capacity of Germany's electoral system to represent a broad spectrum of political preferences.

Trust in political institutions presents a more nuanced picture. Only about 32% of respondents say they trust political parties, 34% trust the national parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c)). In contrast, trust in European institutions is slightly higher, suggesting that the EU continues to serve as an important source of legitimacy in German political life.

Attitudinal data confirm a society broadly committed to democratic norms but not immune to authoritarian temptations. The vast majority of citizens reject authoritarian alternatives and political violence, but small minorities consider them acceptable under certain conditions (4% say “very good”, and 16.9% say fairly good when there is a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections) (Haerpfer et al. 2024). These findings highlight latent vulnerabilities in the context of increasing ideological conflict and identity-based polarization.

Germany’s political system also reflects significant social and structural inequalities. The V-Dem Polarization Index scores Germany at 2.13/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating a moderate but rising level of ideological and cultural division. At the same time, economic power concentration stands at 2.92/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), suggesting that influence remains heavily skewed toward wealthier strata, even as the middle class retains some political weight.

Generational and gender differences also structure political orientations in Germany. Across age groups, the center dominates, attracting around 60–64% of men and women. Left-wing identification is consistently stronger among women (25.5% among those under 35 and 25.0% among those aged 36–55 years) than among men (20.5% and 18.0%, respectively), while right-wing preferences are more common among men (up to 14.6%) than among women (generally below 9%). Support for the far left and far right is marginal in all groups, with slightly higher far-left shares among women and slightly higher far-right shares among men (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Generational differences are visible within ideological extremes. Older cohorts form a disproportionate share of radical positions—individuals aged 56 and over account for 55.6% of men and 75.0% of women identifying with the far right, and they make up 52.3% of far-left men and 48.7% of far-left women (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). These patterns indicate that ideological extremism—on the left and the

right—is concentrated among older generations, while younger cohorts are more inclined toward centrist or moderate-left positions. Gender differences remain present but moderate—women lean slightly more to the left, whereas men show stronger support for right-wing and far-right positions.

In sum, Germany’s political system is characterized by strong democratic institutions, solid participation, and growing gender representation but also by uneven trust, selective engagement, and the rising influence of nationalist forces. This complex mix shapes a political environment in which formal democratic norms coexist with deepening ideological divides and in which gender continues to structure political preferences and power relations.

I.11.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial to understanding political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks tied to disinformation and radicalization. In Germany, the online ecosystem is highly developed and widely used for information, but it combines comparatively solid trust in professional online news with more caution toward social platforms—together with clear vulnerabilities in critical skills and targeted exposure to hostile content.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread. About 37% read news on the internet every day, and 16% read it two or three days a week (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), signaling the centrality of digital media in public and political life. In parallel, regular reliance on social networks for news and political information is substantial but clearly lower than reliance on websites from news outlets.

Trust patterns mirror this split. Around 36% of Germans say they tend to trust news found on websites, whereas only about one-quarter express trust in information on social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This asymmetry suggests that professional online news retains legitimacy, while social feeds are viewed more skeptically. However, they still function as important gateways to information and debate.

Perceptions of disinformation as a democratic threat are widespread. Around 76% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, reported exposure is nontrivial—approximately 5% say they encountered disinformation very often in the previous week, around 12% say they encountered it often, with the largest groups reporting exposure

sometimes or rarely (both 26%) and only about 14% saying never (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). However, confidence in recognizing false content remains limited—about 13% feel very confident and a larger share somewhat confident (53%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and effective verification skills points to a persistent need for media literacy investment across age groups.

Online radicalization is an additional concern. Germany has been among the countries where users have been identified on misogynist “manosphere” platforms (e.g., incels.is), which blend hostility to women’s rights with anti-pluralist narratives (189 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These communities can act as vectors of gendered hatred, democratic distrust, and mobilization into broader extremist ecosystems.

Overall, Germany’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media provide expansive arenas for access to information, participation, and debate, sustained by relatively high everyday use and higher trust in professional online news. On the other hand, frequent contact with misleading content, only moderate self-efficacy in recognizing it, and the structured presence of misogynist/anti-democratic niches pose concrete risks for the quality of public debate and democratic resilience.

I.11.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Germany, the overall picture is favorable by European standards—especially for social relations and cultural openness. However, important fragilities persist in the transition to autonomy, access to education, and labor market entry.

According to the Youth Progress Index, 90.8% of young women aged 25–29 years had completed between 12 and 18 years of education, highlighting a high level of educational attainment (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). Among youth aged 15–29 years, attitudes were generally inclusive, with 90% expressing openness toward immigrants, 80% feeling that they had opportunities to make friends, and 80% showing acceptance of gays and lesbians.

On the educational and economic front, early school leaving remains around 9% for boys and 5% for girls, a medium level in line with EU trends (Eurostat 2024a). Gendered differences persist and require continued attention. While Germany performs close to or better than several EU peers on many youth outcomes, these figures point to persistent inequalities in school continuity and to the risks of weaker labor market attachment for specific groups.

In sum, German youth display a strong openness to diversity, dense relational networks, and a broadly inclusive cultural orientation. At the same time, they face structural hurdles linked to schooling pathways, gender gaps, and the transition to economic independence.

I.11.8 Being socialized in Germany

Being socialized in Germany means growing up in a context of strong democratic institutions and high material security, along with political fragmentation and selective disengagement. Gender relations combine widespread support for balanced leadership with persistent expectations of women’s caregiving and men’s authority. Emotional expression among men is increasingly accepted, but stereotypes about harassment, protection, and domestic competence remain. Digital environments broaden participation while circulating anti-feminist or anti-pluralist narratives. Overall, masculine gender norms in Germany emerge through the interaction of egalitarian ideals with cultural residues that continue to assign authority, provision, and control to male roles.

I.12 GREECE

I.12.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Greece’s socioeconomic profile sits below the EU average in material terms but combines steady post-crisis stabilization with enduring structural vulnerabilities and marked internal inequalities (Table 14).

Table 14 Socioeconomic conditions in Greece compared with the EU27

	Greece	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	70.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	31.6	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	26.9	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	73.5	83.4

Gender Equality Index (Work)	69.4	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	57.7	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	85.2	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs signals more limited average living standards. Income dispersion is comparatively high and the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion remains elevated, highlighting substantial and persistent vulnerabilities linked to socioeconomic and territorial divides (Table 14). Labor market indicators confirm this dual picture and reveal a sizable gender gap. Employment among 15–64-year-olds stands at 72.0% for men versus 54.6% for women (Eurostat 2024b)—a gap that constrains women’s economic autonomy and feeds cumulative disadvantages over the life course. Consistently, EIGE’s index places Greece below the EU mean overall, with the work and money dimensions showing progress yet leaving clear room for improvement; power highlights women’s underrepresentation in decision-making, while knowledge reflects field segregation and skills mismatches (Table 14)(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) . Early school leaving is very low (boys 3.7% and girls 2.4%) (Eurostat 2024a), which is a strength of long-term human capital, although horizontal segregation remains notable (a large share of tertiary students concentrated in education/health/welfare/humanities/arts) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Demography and territory add pressure points. Roughly 30% of the population lives in rural areas (OECD 2023a), and the old-age-dependency ratio reaches 36.7 (Eurostat 2024e), underscoring aging-related strains on pensions, health, and long-term care. The foreign-born share is about 11% (Eurostat 2022), sustaining labor supply and diversification while making integration policy salient. Social protection efforts are substantial but below highly redistributive models, with social expenditure around 23.7% of the GDP (OECD 2024b). Health outcomes are comparatively good (EIGE Health 85.2) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Family policy has strengthened fathers’ rights on paper (paternity leave is about 2.8 weeks, typically paid at or near full wage) (OECD 2024a), but its duration limits its transformative potential for care sharing unless complemented by workplace and service reforms.

Overall, Greece combines low-to-mid economic capacity with resilient core institutions and targeted social policy gains. However, high poverty risk, wide gender gaps in paid work and

power, aging, and territorial inequalities continue to test the inclusiveness and sustainability of its development model.

I.12.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Greece's democratic tradition is deeply rooted in the country's political history, with strong constitutional guarantees for fundamental rights and an institutional system committed to pluralism and the rule of law. At the same time, however, its normative landscape is characterized by significant tensions, especially in the areas of gender equality, social inclusion, and minority protection, revealing a society in which democratic principles coexist with persistent structural and cultural limitations.

Institutionally, Greece remains a robust liberal democracy with areas for improvement—Freedom in the World (85/100) (Freedom House 2025), Democracy Index (8.07) (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), Rule of Law (0.60) (World Justice Project 2024), and Civil Liberties (0.87) (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

The picture is more complex when it comes to gender equality. Greece's overall score on the Gender Equality Index stands at 59.3 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), significantly below the EU average (71) and one of the lowest scores in the EU (EIGE 2024). Particularly weak are the power dimension (33.2), indicating persistent underrepresentation of women in political and economic decision-making roles, and the knowledge (57.7) dimension, which reflects gender segregation in education and occupational fields (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The time dimension (69.5) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) shows that domestic and caregiving responsibilities continue to fall disproportionately on women, revealing the persistence of traditional gender roles in private life.

The institutional landscape is further shaped by policies on inclusion and diversity. MIPEX gives Greece a score of 67 (MIPEX 2023), indicating mid-range integration policies with progress in access to education and healthcare but significant barriers to political participation and citizenship. The legal framework for LGBTQI+ rights remains problematic. According to Rainbow Europe, Greece scores 57/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), reflecting persistent legislative gaps, such as limited recognition of same-sex parenthood and

incomplete legal protection against hate crimes and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity.

Public attitudes toward the EU provide additional insight into Greece's alignment with European values. In 2024, 54% of the population reported trust in the European Parliament—slightly above the EU average—indicating a relatively strong connection to the European project (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). However, 5.2% of Greeks believe that European integration has “gone too far”, showing the existence of Eurosceptic tendencies that, while limited, influence public discourse (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Greece presents itself as a consolidated democracy with effective institutions, strong civil liberties, and a generally positive attitude toward the European project. Nevertheless, persistent gender inequalities—especially in political representation and the division of domestic work—and the limited legal recognition of LGBTQI+ rights remain significant barriers to full equality and social inclusion. Despite a relatively high level of trust in EU institutions, the coexistence of democratic consolidation with cultural and institutional constraints reveals a value system in transition, where liberal-democratic principles interact with enduring inequalities and contested notions of identity and belonging.

I.12.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Greece are characterized by deep ambivalence. On the one hand, significant shifts toward more egalitarian models are evident, particularly among younger generations and women. On the other hand, traditional stereotypes about family roles, leadership, and masculinity remain deeply ingrained and continue to shape gender relations in both the private and public spheres.

Figure 35, based on Eurobarometer data, observes that family roles remain one of the areas where traditional expectations are most persistent (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These figures, which are higher than the EU average, indicate that motherhood is still strongly associated with primary caregiving responsibilities and that the reconciliation of employment and family life is often seen as incompatible with women's full labor market participation.

Figure 35 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Greece

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of workplace inequality reflect a similar ambivalence—34.9% of Greeks believe that men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), pointing to a widespread awareness of structural discrimination. However, this awareness coexists with cultural expectations that legitimize a gendered division of labor and reinforce traditional hierarchies.

Views of women’s political leadership reveal a comparable tension. A significant 86% of respondents consider it “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful” (ESS ERIC 2025), suggesting broad normative support for parity in public life. However, stereotypes about women’s competence persist (Figure 35). These attitudes highlight the coexistence of formal support for equality with lingering symbolic biases.

Cultural norms around masculinity are similarly contradictory. While there is growing openness to redefining traditional male roles—86% of Greeks believe it is acceptable for a man to cry—certain traditional expectations persist. About 13% of Greeks think that men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition, 23% believe men should have the final say in family decisions, and 53% consider men naturally less competent than women in household tasks (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These

figures illustrate how entrenched ideas about masculinity and authority continue to shape gender relations in the domestic sphere.

A significant share of public opinion also expresses resistance to gender equality progress—49% of respondents believe that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This perception of “overreach” reflects cultural polarization and signals a potential backlash against gender equality policies.

In Greece, attitudes toward gender norms show clear generational divides and enduring traditional views, although some cohort shifts are evident. Support for LGBTQI+ rights is strongest among younger people and declines sharply with age. Agreement that gay and lesbian people should be free to live as they wish falls from 83% to 51% among men and from 88% to 59% among women between the youngest and oldest groups (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Age also shapes skepticism about gendered experiences. Beliefs that women exaggerate harassment claims remain relatively low but rise slightly among older men while staying very low among women. Perceptions that women seek power over men are stable and comparatively high among men across ages (around 38–40%) but far lower among women (around 20%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Paternalistic expectations weaken across generations. The endorsement of the idea that women should be protected by men decreases from 12% to 7% among men and from 23% to 13% among women. Gender differences are substantial. Women are consistently more supportive of LGBTQI+ rights, more likely to reject skeptical views about harassment, and far less inclined to believe that women seek control (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, the data show a strong generational gradient—with younger Greeks, especially women, expressing more progressive and egalitarian attitudes—and a persistent gender gap, as men remain more receptive to hostile stereotypes and traditional role expectations. Ambivalence and residual traditionalism persist, particularly around family roles and leadership, and perceptions that “feminism has gone too far” may fuel defensive reactions.

1.12.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Greece represents a structural and deeply entrenched social problem that continues to undermine democratic quality, gender equality, and the effective protection

of fundamental rights. Despite the existence of a legal framework aligned with European standards and significant institutional efforts, prevalence levels remain high, and substantial gaps persist in awareness, prevention, and access to support services.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), 36.3% of women in Greece aged 18–74 years report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15. This figure, slightly above the EU average (31%), highlights the systemic nature of the problem and shows that gender-based violence remains a widespread reality rather than an exceptional occurrence. The situation is even more alarming in the context of intimate relationships—41.8% of Greek women report having experienced psychological violence, physical abuse or threats, and/or sexual violence by a partner or ex-partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These data reveal how coercion and control are often embedded within family and intimate dynamics, reflecting persistent gender power asymmetries.

Knowledge of and access to support services show a mixed picture. Awareness of available support services is relatively widespread, with 90% of victims aware of their existence (Eurostat 2021b), indicating the effectiveness of public communication strategies and civil society initiatives. However, awareness of specific legal entitlements remains low—only 34.9% of women know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This substantial gap between general awareness and knowledge of concrete rights suggests that many victims may still face significant barriers in seeking justice and asserting their rights, particularly those in vulnerable socioeconomic conditions.

The most extreme manifestations of gender-based violence illustrate the gravity of the problem. The annual rate of intentional homicides of women perpetrated by partners or family members in Greece stands at 0.23 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c).

These alarming figures underscore critical shortcomings in the capacity to detect early signs of violence, assess risk effectively, and intervene before escalation occurs. It also reflects persistent structural deficiencies in Greece's protective mechanisms, particularly in cases involving repeated violence and high-risk perpetrators.

From a legal and institutional perspective, Greece has taken important steps to address gender-based violence. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on June

18, 2018, and brought it into force on October 1, 2018 (Council of Europe 2025). These steps signal a formal commitment to European standards on prevention, victim protection, and prosecution. However, the significant prevalence of violence, the high incidence of femicides, and the persistent gaps in legal awareness point to challenges in fully translating legislative commitments into effective protection on the ground.

In sum, Greece's landscape of gender-based violence reveals a paradoxical situation. A comprehensive legal and institutional framework coexists with persistently high prevalence levels, substantial gaps in victims' knowledge of their rights, and a disturbing frequency of lethal violence in intimate and family settings.

I.12.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides a privileged vantage point for understanding how democracy, gender inequality, and power dynamics intersect in Greek society. The resulting picture is one of a democratic system with deeply rooted institutions and high citizen engagement but marked by persistent challenges, including limited trust in political actors, ideological polarization, and significant gender disparities in political representation.

Voter turnout offers an initial measure of democratic vitality. In the 2024 European elections, turnout in Greece reached 62.2%, well above the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This relatively high level of participation reflects both a strong civic orientation and a deeply ingrained perception of elections as key channels for political voice.

On gender representation, progress remains uneven. Women hold 38% of seats in the Greek parliament—slightly above the EU average (33%) but below the levels observed in some Northern and Central European democracies (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This suggests that while significant advances have been made in opening up political institutions to women, structural barriers and cultural norms still constrain their full participation in decision-making.

The ideological distribution of the party system provides additional insights. The results of the 2023 national election in Greece reflect a political landscape dominated by a strong center-right force alongside a fragmented opposition. New Democracy (ND) emerged as the clear winner, securing 40.6% of the vote and consolidating its position as the main governing party. The main opposition, the left-wing SYRIZA, significantly trailed behind, with 17.8% of

the vote, marking a notable gap between the first and second parties. The center-left PASOK followed with 11.8%, while the far-left Communist Party (KKE) maintained a stable but minor presence, winning 7.7% (ParlGov 2023).

The absence of a significant far-right force among the leading parties suggests that the Greek party system remains anchored around a center-right majority and a divided left-wing opposition. However, the presence of KKE on the far left indicates that ideological diversity continues to shape the parliamentary landscape. Overall, the 2023 election underlines the dominance of ND and a consolidated conservative bloc while highlighting the fragmentation and weaker electoral performance of parties to its left.

Institutional quality remains solid but is not without weaknesses. V-Dem's Electoral Democracy Index assigns Greece a score of 0.87 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), placing it slightly above the EU average and confirming the robustness of electoral processes, pluralism, and checks and balances. However, systemic issues—such as judicial inefficiencies and uneven access to justice—still affect perceptions of institutional effectiveness and legitimacy.

Public trust in political institutions is relatively low. About 54% trust the national government, and 45% trust political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), while interest in politics is moderate—25% of the population declare being quite interested in political life, and about 7% state that they are very interested (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), but a segment remains distant or skeptical regarding institutions' capacity to respond to citizens' needs. Attitudinal data reveal similar ambivalence. While a majority (69.8%) rate authoritarian alternatives as “very bad”, small but noteworthy minorities offer more tolerant assessments (2.9% say that is very good and around 6% that is fairly good) (Haerpfer et al. 2024). These findings highlight a generally pro-democratic public but one that is not entirely immune to illiberal currents.

Polarization constitutes a significant structural feature of the Greek political landscape. V-Dem assigns the country a polarization score of 1.16/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating intense ideological and cultural fragmentation. Economic power distribution also shows concentration. With a score of 3.2/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), wealth and

influence remain disproportionately in the hands of the most affluent classes, although middle- and working-class groups retain some political leverage.

Generational and gender divides shape political orientations in Greece, with clear age-related shifts. Older cohorts show a marked tendency toward the right and far right, while younger generations are more likely to align with the left or center. Among men, support for the right rises sharply with age, increasing from 15.46% among those under 35 to 49.21% among those aged 56 and over, while far-right support follows the same trajectory, from 17.39% to 49.28%. Left-wing identification also grows with age, from 23.84% to 40.70%. Centrist preferences are highest among the middle-aged (37.80%) before falling slightly among the oldest (35.00%). Among women, the patterns are similar. Support for the right grows from 15.71% among the youngest to 51.43% among the oldest, and far-right identification remains relatively strong among older women (42.86%). Far-left support among women also increases with age, indicating that ideological polarization intensifies in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Across gender, the center remains the dominant orientation but declines with age for both groups. Among men, centrist support drops from 55.28% to 39.41%, and among women, it declines from 56.47% to 50.09%. Men consistently report higher support for the right and far right, reaching 35.14% and 7.66%, respectively, among those over 56, compared with 25.95% and 3.24% among women. Women show slightly higher support for the left (20.78% among the youngest, compared with 16.67% for men) and remain more concentrated in centrist positions. Overall, political preferences in Greece become more polarized and more right-leaning with age, while gender differences persist—men are more inclined toward conservative and far-right positions, whereas women tend to align more with centrist or left-leaning orientations (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, the Greek political system presents itself as a complex equilibrium: high electoral participation, consolidated democratic institutions, and meaningful—though incomplete—advances in gender representation coexist with widespread distrust, strong ideological polarization, and persistent socioeconomic power imbalances. These dynamics create a challenging environment for political socialization and democratic consolidation, in which

formal adherence to liberal democratic norms interacts with deep-rooted skepticism, structural inequality, and competing visions of the political community.

I.12.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial for understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Greece, the online ecosystem combines a very high reliance on digital sources with uneven critical skills and notable exposure to misleading content.

Reading news online is widespread—50% of Greeks report doing so every day or almost every day, confirming the centrality of digital media in Greece’s public and political life (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust is differentiated by channel—54% say they tend to trust news on websites, while a lower—though still substantial—40% tend to trust information circulating on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This pattern indicates broad legitimacy for online news alongside caution toward social media.

Perceptions of disinformation risk are pronounced, with 86% of respondents viewing false or misleading online content as a serious threat to democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Exposure is frequent: 17% report encountering disinformation very often, 22% often, 32% sometimes, 19% rarely, and 5% never in the preceding week (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). However, detection confidence remains moderate—17% feel very confident they can recognize disinformation, 50% are somewhat confident, 28% are not very confident, and 4% are not at all confident—revealing a persistent gap between awareness and skills (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

As in other EU countries, Greek users are active in online spaces that spread misogynistic and anti-pluralist narratives (such as parts of the “manosphere”), highlighting the need for targeted prevention strategies and counter-speech initiatives. A total of 16 users have been identified in these communities (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). Greece’s digital environment has a dual face: intense use and comparatively high trust in web news coexist with substantial exposure to disinformation, only moderate high-confidence detection, and pockets of online misogyny.

I.12.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country's capacity to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Greece, the picture is mixed. While young people show strong openness to diversity and social interaction, significant structural barriers remain in education, employment, and the transition to independent adulthood.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Greece scores 82.5/100, placing it in the mid-range among European countries (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This result reflects relatively weaker material conditions and socioeconomic opportunities compared with the EU average but also highlights important strengths in terms of inclusiveness and relational capital.

A particularly relevant dimension is cultural openness. Greek youth show relatively inclusive attitudes—70% consider Greece a “good place” for immigrants, and around 60% perceive it as welcoming for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). While these levels point to a generation generally more open to diversity than the wider population, they also reveal that acceptance is not universal and that there remains considerable room for progress, especially regarding attitudes toward sexual minorities.

The relational dimension is also encouraging. About 79% of young people positively evaluate opportunities to make friends and build social networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), suggesting a solid base of youth social capital and an environment conducive to participation and civic engagement.

However, the educational and economic dimensions reveal substantial challenges. The share of young men leaving education or training early stands at 11.1%, while among young women, it is 7.7% (Eurostat 2024a). Although slightly below the EU average, these figures highlight persistent gender differences and difficulties in ensuring continuous educational participation. Furthermore, structural constraints in the labor market—characterized by high youth unemployment and precarious job opportunities—make the transition to economic independence particularly complex and often delayed.

Overall, the landscape of youth inclusion in Greece presents a dual picture. On the one hand, young people show high levels of inclusiveness, strong relational networks, and a progressive

cultural orientation. On the other hand, they face persistent barriers linked to educational attainment, gender inequalities, and limited socio-economic mobility.

I.12.8 Being socialized in Greece

Being socialized in Greece means growing up in a democracy that guarantees rights but faces strained trust, economic instability, and strong polarization. Gender inequalities in employment and decision-making remain pronounced, and family roles continue to emphasize women’s caregiving responsibilities. Younger cohorts support diversity and challenge patriarchal expectations, while older groups retain more traditional views. As a result, masculine gender norms in Greece are shaped by competing pressures, combining elements of care and openness with strongly rooted expectations of hierarchy and family-centered authority.

I.13 HUNGARY

I.13.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Hungary’s socioeconomic landscape is characterized by levels of development below the European average and a more fragile macroeconomic structure while still demonstrating areas of resilience and notable progress.

Table 15 Socioeconomic conditions in Hungary compared with the EU27

	Hungary	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	77.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	25.1	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	20.2	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	73.8	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	76.6	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	58.7	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	87.5	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

In 2024, GDP per capita in PPSs confirms a significantly lower level of material well-being and economic capacity. This indicator reflects persistent structural constraints on growth and productivity, which continue to shape the country’s position within the European economic space. Income distribution appears moderately unequal but slightly better than the EU

average. With a Gini index of 25.1, Hungary shows relatively low income inequality, while sizable segments still face socioeconomic vulnerability (Table 15). However, 20.2% of the population remains at risk of poverty or social exclusion, a figure only slightly below the European average and indicative of persistent socioeconomic vulnerability linked to territorial disparities, social stratification, and differences in access to public services (Table 15).

The labor market presents a generally positive picture in terms of participation but is marked by pronounced gender differences. The employment rate among those aged 15–64 is 78.7% for men and 71.4% for women (Eurostat 2024b). While these values are above the European averages (75.3% and 66.2%, respectively), the gender gap remains substantial, pointing to structural inequalities in professional opportunities and career progression. These disparities translate into lower female economic autonomy and contribute to the persistence of traditional gendered divisions of labor.

The EIGE Gender Equality Index provides further evidence of this structural imbalance (Table 15). Early school leaving is 10.7% among boys and 9.9% among girls (Eurostat 2024a), indicating vulnerabilities in the education system that may hinder social mobility and reduce young people's ability to enter the labor market under favorable conditions.

Demographic trends pose additional challenges. The old-age dependency ratio is 31.9, slightly below the European average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e) but points to a progressively aging population and rising pressure on welfare and pension systems. Territorial disparities remain pronounced, with 18.36% of the population living in rural areas (OECD 2023a)—a share lower than in many European countries but still associated with unequal access to infrastructure, services, and employment opportunities. Moreover, the share of the foreign-born population is only 7.1%, among the lowest in the EU (Eurostat 2022), highlighting limited demographic renewal and potential constraints on labor supply and economic dynamism.

Social expenditure represents 18% of the GDP, below the EU average (about 24% based on the information available for the countries considered) (OECD 2024b), reflecting a less extensive welfare model (Eurostat 2024). In sum, Hungary's socioeconomic structure

combines moderate economic performance and labor market resilience with persistent gender gaps, demographic fragility, and structural vulnerabilities.

I.13.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Hungary's institutional and value landscape reveals a democracy with consolidated formal structures but notable fragilities in the quality of governance, protection of rights, and inclusiveness. According to Freedom in the World, Hungary scores 65/100 in 2024, categorizing it as "Partly Free" (Freedom House 2025) and highlighting significant democratic backsliding in recent years, particularly concerning judicial independence, media freedom, and civil society space (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index is 6.51/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), signaling persistent deficiencies in political pluralism, checks and balances, and participation. The Rule of Law Index (0.51) (World Justice Project 2024) further underscores these institutional weaknesses, pointing to challenges in judicial effectiveness, protection of rights, and equality before the law. V-Dem's civil liberties score of 0.82 confirms a constrained rights environment (Varieties of Democracy 2024), in which formal guarantees coexist with systematic restrictions on dissent and associative freedoms.

Inclusion and pluralism present further structural challenges. Hungary scores 46.3 on MIPEX on hate speech law/hate crime law (gender identity and/or sexual orientation) (MIPEX 2023), indicating limited support for migrant inclusion and persistent obstacles in areas such as political participation, long-term residence, and anti-discrimination (MIPEX 2023). The situation for LGBTQI+ rights is also critical. Rainbow Europe assigns Hungary 23/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), reflecting restrictive legislation, weak protection against hate crimes, and the absence of legal recognition for same-sex families.

Public attitudes toward the EU reflect this ambivalence. Trust in the European Parliament stands at 58%, signaling a moderate level of attachment to the European project (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024). At the same time, 4.6% of the population believes that European integration has "gone too far", revealing a significant Eurosceptic current (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

In sum, Hungary's value landscape is characterized by a mix of institutional continuity and democratic erosion. Formal democratic institutions remain in place, but their quality and inclusiveness are undermined by weakened checks and balances, limitations on civil liberties, and deep gender and minority inequalities. The persistence of exclusionary policies toward migrants and LGBTQI+ people, coupled with ambivalent public attitudes toward European integration, underscores a political culture in transition—one in which democratic norms coexist uneasily with illiberal tendencies and contested understandings of equality and rights.

I.13.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Hungary display the same double movement seen elsewhere. Some openings toward equality coexist with deeply rooted stereotypes that still shape roles at home, in the labor market, and in politics.

Gender equality also lags behind the European benchmark. Hungary's overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 57.8, significantly below the EU average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The time dimension, at 61.2 (vs. 68.5 EU), indicates a strongly gendered division of domestic and care responsibilities, while the power dimension, at 27.1 (vs. 61.4 EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), reflects a deep underrepresentation of women in political, economic, and social decision-making. These figures illustrate entrenched gender hierarchies and limited institutional commitment to equality promotion.

According to Eurobarometer data (

Figure 36), family role representations remain strongly traditional. These figures point to a persistent cultural script that associates care primarily with women and questions the full compatibility of motherhood and employment (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 36 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Hungary

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceived inequality at work confirms this ambivalence. In Hungary, 19.6% say women are treated less fairly at work (vs. 6.2% who say men are), while 74.1% think the sexes are treated the same (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)—evidence that many Hungarians recognize gender gaps, yet a majority normalizes the status quo.

The political sphere mirrors these tensions (

Figure 36). On the one hand, there is broad normative support for parity. On the other hand, stereotypes about women's authority are widespread (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Norms around masculinity and family decision-making are similarly mixed. A large majority (75%) considers it acceptable for a man to cry—signaling some softening of emotional norms—yet prescriptive expectations persist—44% think men should have the final say in important family decisions, and 39% believe men who take parental leave show a lack of ambition (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Household labor remains feminized in people's minds, with 74% agreeing that men are naturally less competent at housework, while 42% say that if the father earns less than the mother, he should be the one to give up work to look after the children. Finally, signs of backlash are clear: 46% agree that feminism has “gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In Hungary, attitudes toward gender norms and equality reveal a complex picture shaped by both generation and gender. Acceptance of sexual diversity remains uneven. Support for the idea that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish changes little across male cohorts (around 31–32%) and is slightly higher among older women than younger ones (39% vs 28%), but overall disagreement remains substantial among older groups (around half of both men and women) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Skepticism about sexual harassment follows a similar gradient. Around one-quarter of men in most cohorts believe that women often exaggerate harassment claims, rising to one-third among those 56+. Among women, skepticism increases more sharply with age, reaching nearly half in the oldest cohort. Still, younger women are the most likely to reject the idea of exaggeration (63% vs. 42% of young men), showing a consistent gender gap in perceptions of sexual violence (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Beliefs that women seek power over men also rise with age for both sexes, increasing from around one-fifth among younger respondents to more than 40% among the oldest. A large

share of both men and women say this happens at least “sometimes”, suggesting a broader climate of suspicion toward women’s agency, particularly among older cohorts. Paternalistic expectations remain present as well. Men’s endorsement of the idea that women should be protected by men increases with age (from 20% to 38%), while women’s endorsement stays slightly higher but stable (around 36–37%). Most respondents in both genders reject this view; however, its persistence—especially among older men—indicates that traditional hierarchies remain embedded (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

In sum, younger cohorts tend to be more supportive of diversity and less anchored in traditional gender hierarchies, but age-related differences are not always linear, and gender gaps remain substantial across all age groups. While a significant share of the Hungarian population supports equality and rejects stereotypes, entrenched beliefs about gender roles, sexual harassment, and women’s power persist. Hungary’s value climate blends formal support for parity with strong residual traditionalism in leadership, decision-making at home, and the gendered division of care—an ambivalent equilibrium that sustains symbolic and practical barriers to full equality, even as some norms, especially around male emotional expression, become more permissive.

I.13.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Hungary remains a pervasive and deeply rooted social problem, exerting a significant impact on women’s fundamental rights, equality, and participation in public and private life. Despite the existence of a legislative framework formally aligned with European standards, prevalence levels, awareness of rights, and access to services continue to highlight significant weaknesses in the country’s response to this phenomenon.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, 49.1% of Hungarian women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15, a figure that closely mirrors the EU27 average (31%) and illustrates the structural nature of gender-based violence in Hungarian society. Even more telling are the dynamics within intimate relationships—54.6% of women report having experienced psychological violence, physical violence or threats, and/or sexual violence from a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These data indicate that

coercion and abuse remain deeply embedded within intimate and family relations, reflecting persistent power imbalances and cultural norms that normalize violence in the domestic sphere.

Knowledge and access to support services present a mixed picture. Awareness of specific rights and legal entitlements remains more limited—only 29.9% of victims know about their right to free legal aid (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), while 56.3% are aware of specialized services designed to support survivors (Eurostat 2021b). This gap between general awareness and concrete knowledge illustrates how insufficient dissemination of information can deter victims from seeking help, thereby undermining the effectiveness of the protection system.

The most extreme forms of violence offer a particularly stark perspective. The rate of intentional homicides of women by intimate partners or family members in Hungary is 0.52 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c). This figure highlights serious shortcomings in the ability of institutions to prevent escalation and protect those at risk, revealing a persistent vulnerability to the most severe manifestations of gender-based violence.

On the legal and institutional front, Hungary signed the Istanbul Convention on March 14, 2014, but it has not ratified it, placing the country in a minority among EU member states (Council of Europe 2025). The lack of ratification significantly weakens the binding force of European standards in domestic law and limits the development of coherent and comprehensive strategies for prevention, protection, and prosecution.

Overall, Hungary's situation reveals a paradoxical landscape—relatively high awareness of support services and widespread recognition of the problem coexisting with significant prevalence levels, high rates of lethal violence, and a substantial gap between legislative commitments and effective implementation. The failure to ratify the Istanbul Convention further undermines institutional capacity, suggesting that gender-based violence remains one of the most pressing tests of Hungary's ability to guarantee safety, justice, and substantive gender equality.

I.13.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a privileged lens through which to observe how democracy, gender inequalities, and power relations interact in Hungary. The picture that emerges is that

of a system with formal electoral competition and stable governing majorities but marked by democratic backsliding, strong polarization, and widespread skepticism toward representative institutions.

In the 2024 European elections, turnout in Hungary was about 59.5%, slightly above the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This points to robust mobilization around European-level contests, even as participation remains uneven across national and local arenas. Women occupy roughly 14% of the seats in Hungary's parliament, well below the EU average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This gap signals persistent barriers to women's access to elective office and limits the gender balance of political decision-making.

Multiple indicators point to a constrained democratic environment. The EIU Democracy Index places Hungary around 6.5/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), while V-Dem's Electoral Democracy Index is close to 0.44 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), signaling weakened checks and balances and shrinking pluralism. Together, these measures indicate institutions that function electorally but with curtailed counterpowers and reduced space for dissent.

Levels of political trust and civic engagement in Hungary reveal a complex and often contradictory picture, reflecting both widespread skepticism toward representative institutions and persistent inequalities in political participation. Trust in political actors remains relatively low. In 2024, 32% of the population report that they "tend to trust" political parties, while 41% express trust in the national government (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Civic engagement and interest in politics also show signs of detachment. In 2023, only 8.6% of Hungarians described themselves as "very interested" in politics, while 28.3% reported being "quite interested". The largest shares of the population expressed more distant attitudes: 36.4% said they are "hardly interested", and 26.7% reported being "not at all interested" (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

The quality of democracy is further influenced by structural and attitudinal factors. Political violence remains relatively low (0.36) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) but not negligible, suggesting the presence of underlying tensions and a potential for conflict, particularly in

polarized contexts. Economic power distribution is also uneven, with a score of 2.02 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating that influence remains concentrated among wealthier social groups, while the middle and working classes have a more limited capacity to shape policy outcomes.

Finally, political polarization is a defining feature of Hungary's political system. With a score of 3.87 (on a 0–4 scale) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), polarization is significantly higher than in many EU countries, reflecting entrenched ideological divisions, confrontational political discourse, and deep societal cleavages. This heightened polarization not only exacerbates distrust and alienation but also undermines the potential for consensus-building and collaborative governance. In the 2022 elections, the central political confrontation was between the Alliance of Hungarian Civic Party (Fidesz) and the Christian Democratic People's Party (KDNP) and the main opposition force, the Democratic Coalition (DK).

According to the data (ParlGov 2023), Fidesz–KDNP secured 54.1% of the vote, consolidating its position as the dominant governing force. The DK, on the other hand, received 35.7% of the vote within the broader opposition alliance. Politically, the Fidesz–KDNP represents a national-conservative and Christian-democratic platform that continues to dominate Hungary's political arena, while the DK positions itself as the center-left/social-liberal pole of the opposition.

Generational patterns in Hungary reveal clear shifts in ideological alignment. Among the youngest men (≤ 35), the center is dominant (57.1%), but its prevalence declines steadily with age, falling to 41.1% among those aged 36–55 years and 37.4% among those over 56 years. Support for the far right rises correspondingly, from 12.6% among the youngest to 22.2% in the oldest cohort, while the mainstream right strengthens with age, peaking at 24.7% in midlife. Women follow a similar trajectory, although with lower initial centrism (48.6% among those ≤ 35) and a clearer shift toward the right over time. Among women aged 56 years and over, the right reaches 23.9% and the far right 16.8%, while the center falls below 40% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

The age composition of ideological families reflects these shifts. Older cohorts are disproportionately represented at the extremes—48.8% of male and 46.4% of female far-right identifiers are aged 56 or above. The far left also shows an older profile, especially

among women, 47% of whom belong to the oldest cohort. In contrast, centrists are more evenly distributed by age, although younger groups remain comparatively stronger than at the extremes (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender adds a further layer. Among the youngest, men are more strongly concentrated at the center (57.1%) than women (48.6%). With age, men polarize more sharply, showing a notable rise in far-right support (22.2% among those over 56) and a decline in left-wing identification. Women maintain a modest but stable presence on the far left (around 8–11% across ages) and gradually shift toward the right as they grow older (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, Hungary's political arena appears to be a delicate and contested equilibrium: high mobilization and durable governing coalitions coexist with declining democratic quality, limited gender representation, selective trust, and strong polarization. This configuration shapes a demanding terrain for political socialization and the consolidation of democratic norms, in which formal adherence to electoral competition intertwines with the centralization of power, fragmentation, and cultural resistance.

I.13.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial for understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Hungary, the online ecosystem combines very wide use of digital information channels with comparatively low trust in social platforms and clear worries about false or manipulative content.

The use of digital platforms for news is extensive. Eurobarometer items indicate that 59% of people in Hungary read news on the internet every day or almost every day (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), underscoring the centrality of online media in public and political life. Social networks are also used for political information, but people tend to trust them less than other online sources.

Trust in online sources shows this split—47% of Hungarians say they tend to trust news on websites, while 30% say they tend to trust information on online social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This points to an information environment in which the web is widely used but where social feeds are viewed with caution.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widespread. About 83% agree that the existence of mis- and disinformation is a problem for democracy (European Commission, Directorate General for Communication, 2024c). However, skill confidence lags—only 12% feel very confident that they can recognize disinformation when they encounter it, while most feel confident only “to some extent” (51%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). Exposure is nontrivial—46% report encountering misleading content often or very often in the previous week (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

The radicalization dimension also deserves attention. As flagged in the European Commission–supported scan of misogynist communities (2 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), Hungarian users were identified on incels.is (2017–2020), a core forum of the “manosphere”. These spaces combine hostility toward women’s rights with anti-egalitarian, anti-democratic narratives, creating risks that intersect with gendered harassment and offline harm.

Overall, Hungary’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet is a major gateway to news and civic information, and trust in general web sources is moderate. On the other hand, low trust in social networks, high perceived disinformation risk, modest detection confidence, and the documented presence of misogynist communities create vulnerabilities for public debate and democratic resilience.

I.13.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s capacity to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Hungary, the picture is more mixed than the EU average—relational resources and some positive attitudes coexist with weaker empowerment pathways and constraints in education-to-work transitions.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Hungary scores 80.56/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This score signals decent basic conditions but also substantial room for improvement in social inclusion and youth capabilities. On the relational front, perceptions are comparatively positive—around 80% of young people rate the opportunities to make friends as good (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), indicating a reasonably robust peer network and social capital. Cultural openness, however, is uneven. Only 40% of Hungarian youth say their country is a good place for

immigrants, while acceptance of gays and lesbians sits near 50%—lower than the levels observed in many Western EU countries (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These attitudes point to a generational field that is less cosmopolitan than the EU norm and more exposed to identity polarization.

Educational indicators reinforce this duality. On the one hand, female educational attainment among 25–29-year-olds is high (around 86% completing 12–18 years of schooling) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), suggesting strong potential in women’s human capital. On the other hand, early school leaving remains a vulnerability—the share is similar for boys (about 11%) and girls (about 10%) (Eurostat 2024a). These patterns echo broader constraints on socioeconomic autonomy and mobility. Taken together, Hungarian youth display solid relational ties and strong female attainment, but they face weaker inclusion scores overall, lower cultural openness, and gendered risks in education-to-work transitions.

I.13.8 Being socialized in Hungary

Being socialized in Hungary means growing up where democratic institutions function with weakened checks and balances, deep polarization, and limited trust. Political narratives often highlight strong leadership and traditional values. Gender norms emphasize male authority and provision, while caregiving is assigned to women. Skepticism toward harassment claims and limited acceptance of gender diversity persist. Digital platforms disseminate both civic content and anti-feminist, anti-democratic narratives that reinforce hierarchical scripts. In this setting, masculine gender norms in Hungary frequently center on authority, protection, and gender conformity, even as youngers explore more egalitarian alternatives.

I.14 IRELAND

I.14.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Ireland’s socioeconomic structure is defined by very high levels of economic development and robust macroeconomic performance, combined with persistent inequalities, gender gaps, and demographic challenges that shape social inclusion and equality of opportunity (Table 16).

Table 16 Socioeconomic conditions in Ireland compared with the EU27

	Ireland	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	211.00	100.00

Gini coefficient	23.1	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	16.7	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	86.6	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	77.2	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	68.6	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	94.6	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

In 2024, the GDP per capita in purchasing power standards (PPS) positions Ireland among the wealthiest economies in the European Union (EU). This figure reflects the country's strong capacity to generate material well-being and sustain high income levels, even amid global economic volatility and structural transitions (Table 16).

Income distribution appears more balanced than the EU average, yet notable disparities remain, indicating a comparatively equitable distribution of income. Nevertheless, 16.7% of the population remains at risk of poverty or social exclusion, below the EU27 average of 21.4% (Table 16).

The labor market is dynamic and inclusive overall, with high employment rates but notable gender disparities. Employment among those aged 15–64 years is 78.4% for men and 70.6% for women (Eurostat 2024b). Although both rates exceed the EU averages (75.3% and 66.2%, respectively), the gender gap remains significant and reflects enduring structural imbalances in access to paid work and career progression. These disparities have direct consequences for women's economic independence and perpetuate traditional divisions of labor and care.

Ireland's performance on gender equality indicators reveals a similar duality. The money (and work dimensions perform strongly, reflecting women's growing participation and earning capacity (Table 16). However, horizontal and vertical segregation persist, limiting women's access to STEM fields, decision-making roles, and high-level positions. The knowledge dimension remains a weak point, pointing to the unequal distribution of education and skills (Table 16). Early school leaving is relatively low but still gendered—3.5% of boys and 2.9% of girls exit education prematurely (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographic trends add to the complexity of Ireland's socioeconomic landscape. The old age dependency ratio stands at 23.6, well below the EU average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e),

reflecting a comparatively young population and less immediate pressure on pension systems. However, demographic sustainability is increasingly reliant on migration—22.6% of the population is foreign-born (Eurostat 2022), a share that contributes to economic dynamism but also requires effective policies for integration and social cohesion. Territorial inequalities persist as well, with 56.8% of the population living in rural areas (OECD 2023a), where access to services, educational opportunities, and infrastructure is more limited.

Ireland devotes 14.4% of its GDP to social expenditure (OECD 2024b), reflecting a comparatively lean welfare state. While the system has helped mitigate inequality and buffer labor market shocks, it faces challenges in addressing emerging risks, such as youth precariousness, rising housing costs, and the reconciliation of work and family life.

Overall, Ireland’s socioeconomic landscape presents a paradoxical picture. High levels of prosperity, strong labor market performance, and relatively equitable income distribution coexist with persistent gender gaps, social vulnerabilities, and territorial disparities.

I.14.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Ireland is among the EU countries with the most consolidated democratic institutions and a political tradition strongly anchored in the rule of law and respect for fundamental rights. At the same time, the value landscape shows some tensions, particularly around gender equality, social inclusion, and minority protection.

According to Freedom in the World, Ireland scores 97/100 in 2024 (“Free”) (Freedom House 2025), confirming strong guarantees of political and civil liberties. The Economist Intelligence Unit’s Democracy Index assigns 9.19/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing Ireland among the “full democracies” and indicating a system marked by pluralism, participation, and institutional stability. The Rule of Law Index is likewise high (0.82) (World Justice Project 2024), pointing to effective law enforcement and an independent judiciary, although room for improvement remains in the access and timeliness of justice. In line with this picture, V-Dem’s Civil Liberties Index reaches 0.96 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), underscoring the very advanced protection of fundamental rights.

Inclusion and pluralism policies further shape the institutional value landscape. The Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) gives Ireland 94, signaling one of the EU’s strongest

integration frameworks, with a particularly good performance on access to rights and equal treatment (MIPEX 2023). The LGBTQI+ rights framework is comparatively advanced in EU terms—Rainbow Europe reports a score of around 66.7/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), reflecting broad legal protection while highlighting the remaining gaps.

Public attitudes toward the European project are broadly supportive. In 2024, 57% of people in Ireland report trusting the European Parliament, a figure above many EU peers and indicative of a stable link with the EU (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). At the same time, only about 5.3% believe European integration has “gone too far”, suggesting that Euroscepticism is present but not dominant (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Ireland presents itself as a solid democracy with efficient institutions, very high civil-liberty standards, and strong adherence to core European values. The full realization of gender equality remains an open challenge—especially regarding unpaid care—while migrant inclusion and LGBTQI+ protections are comparatively robust. Trust in EU institutions is high, yet translating equality principles into everyday practices continues to be a central task in a value system that balances liberal commitments with ongoing social transformations.

I.14.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Ireland display a complex dynamic in which clear openings toward equality coexist with persistent stereotypes that still shape the life courses of women and men in both the public and private spheres. On gender equality, the evidence is mixed. Ireland’s overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 73.4, above the EU27 average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, the time dimension—care and domestic work—scores 59.5 (vs. 68.5 EU), indicating that unpaid care still falls disproportionately on women. In contrast, power—women’s presence in decision-making—stands at 67.6 (vs. 61.4 EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), reflecting comparatively strong representation in political and economic leadership. Eurobarometer data (

Figure 37) for Ireland show that family-role representations remain one of the domains where traditional models are most visible (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 37 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Ireland

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

These data reveal a deeply rooted conception that still associates family care primarily with women’s responsibilities and implicitly questions the full compatibility of employment and motherhood. Perceptions of inequality in the workplace confirm this ambivalence. Around 45% of people in Ireland say that men are treated better than women at work, indicating a widespread acknowledgment of persistent structural discrimination (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, this awareness coexists with cultural views that continue to legitimize a gendered division of labor and family responsibilities.

Cultural ambivalence is also evident in the political sphere. On the one hand, there is broad support for gender balance in leadership—a clear majority (72%) of respondents consider “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, enduring stereotypes about women’s competence and authority remain (

Figure 37). These attitudes point to the persistence of symbolic biases about female leadership alongside the formal endorsement of equality.

Norms concerning masculinity show a similarly mixed picture. A large majority of people (91%) in Ireland deem it acceptable for a man to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)—signaling a gradual loosening of traditional emotional stereotypes—yet more rigid expectations persist. Meaningful minorities consider that men who take parental leave show a lack of ambition for their careers, maintain that men should have “the final say” in important family decisions (15%), or think men are “naturally less competent than women” at housework (45%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Attitudes toward equality are further complicated by polarization around feminism. A noticeable share of respondents (45%) in Ireland agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). LGBTQI+ attitudes show clear generational contrasts. The agreement that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” rises with age among men (from 16.8% under 35 to 51.9% at 56+) and women (from 18.3% to 44.1%). However, when looking across genders, overall support is overwhelmingly high—over 90% of young women and 90.4% of young men agree, and disagreement remains low, even in the oldest cohorts (62.8% of older men and 55.3% of older women disagree) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). This mix points to a broad consensus moderated by generational variation in intensity.

Views on sexual harassment claims are more polarized. Among men, the share saying women “never/rarely” exaggerate rises with age (17.7% to 49.1%) but so does the proportion believing exaggeration happens “often/always” (peaking at 63.3% among older men). Women show a similar duality—rejection of exaggeration increases from 22.6% to 37.4%, but “often/always” responses also rise (up to 53.3% at 56+) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Beliefs that women seek power over men show parallel patterns. Among men, “never/rarely” responses increase from 15.6% to 54.7%, but “often/always” also grows (to nearly 19%). Women follow the same progression (22.1% to 42.2% for “never/rarely”), while “often/always” ranges from 10–13% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Paternalistic norms show enduring gender differences. A majority of men (61–72%) say women should “never/rarely” be protected by men, compared with 43–58% of women. Women remain more likely to endorse protection “often/always” (20–25% vs. 8–12% of men) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, Ireland displays strong support for equality—especially among younger women—alongside age- and gender-based pockets of skepticism, traditionalism, and backlash that remain salient across several dimensions. In sum, the landscape of gender norms and attitudes in Ireland is marked by a twofold movement: growing openings toward more egalitarian models coexist with the persistence of entrenched stereotypes, shaping social trajectories and setting the boundaries within which male and female identities are constructed.

I.14.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Ireland is a structural and persistent problem that affects democratic quality and the full realization of fundamental rights. Despite a solid legal framework and an increasingly coordinated institutional response, levels of prevalence, knowledge of rights, and effective access to services still show clear scope for improvement.

According to the Fundamental Rights survey, 35% of ever-partnered women in Ireland report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by an intimate partner since the age of 15. This share is slightly above the EU27 average, confirming that violence cannot be treated as a marginal phenomenon. Looking beyond the couple, 40.7% of women report having experienced at least one form of violence by any perpetrator (any type) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), a figure that underscores

the breadth of coercion and control dynamics that women encounter across social settings. These values may also reflect a comparatively high ability to recognize and name nonphysical forms of abuse that are often normalized in everyday culture.

Knowledge of and access to support are mixed. Among women (victims and nonvictims), around 94% say they are aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), but only about 28.9% are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This gap between general awareness of services and awareness of specific legal entitlements suggests that limited information about concrete rights can hinder help-seeking and constrain effective access to protection—especially for the most vulnerable.

The most severe forms of violence remain worrying. The annual rate of intentional homicides of women by partners or family members stands at 0.30 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), signaling the need to strengthen early warning mechanisms, risk assessment, and rapid intervention capacity in high-risk cases.

On the legal and institutional front, Ireland has taken important steps. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on November 5, 2015, ratified it on March 8, 2019, and entered it into force domestically on July 1, 2019 (Council of Europe 2025). These commitments align Ireland with Council of Europe standards on prevention, protection, and prosecution. Nonetheless, the distance between formal guarantees and lived safety persists: the combination of substantial prevalence, uneven awareness of rights, and non-negligible lethal violence indicates that prevention and protection policies still need consolidation and better reach.

Overall, Ireland presents a contradictory picture. An advanced legal framework and growing service infrastructure coexist with persistently high levels of psychological and physical/sexual violence, incomplete knowledge of legal entitlements, and episodes of lethal violence within intimate and family contexts. Closing the implementation gap—by boosting rights awareness, strengthening victim pathways to support, and sharpening risk-reduction tools—remains essential to guarantee security, justice, and substantive gender equality.

1.14.5 Political dimension

The political dimension offers a privileged lens through which to observe the interaction among democracy, gender inequalities, and power dynamics in Irish society. The emerging picture is that of a consolidated and formally robust institutional system but marked by areas

of fragility, selective participation, and pockets of skepticism toward representative institutions.

Voter turnout is the first indicator of democratic quality. In the European elections, turnout in Ireland was 45%, in line with the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This points to a comparatively weaker mobilization for EU contests and suggests that participation peaks are still concentrated in national electoral cycles.

Levels of political trust and civic engagement in Ireland reveal a complex and somewhat fragmented picture of democratic participation. In 2024, only 36% of citizens reported that they “tend to trust” political parties, while 48% expressed trust in the national government (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These figures, although not negligible, indicate a significant degree of skepticism toward representative institutions and reflect broader concerns about the quality of governance and accountability.

Civic interest in politics also remains relatively modest. In 2023, just 13.1% of the population described themselves as “very interested” in political affairs, while a larger share (33.8%) reported being “quite interested”. However, disengagement is substantial—27.8% said they are “hardly interested”, and 25.2% declared themselves “not at all interested” in politics (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). This distribution points to a political culture characterized by widespread detachment and limited everyday engagement with public life.

Political violence, while not extremely high, remains a concern—with a score of 0.93 in 2024 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), it signals the persistence of underlying tensions and potential conflict within the political system. This combination of low trust, limited engagement, and non-negligible political violence reflects a challenging environment for democratic socialization—one in which institutional legitimacy is fragile, participation is selective, and contentious dynamics continue to shape the political landscape.

Regarding gender representation, women hold 28% of seats in Ireland’s national parliament—close to the EU average (33%)—and the result of gradual progress in access to elected office, although parity remains some distance away (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Polarization and power distribution appear contained but not negligible. V-Dem registers low-to-moderate political polarization (around 0.4 on a 0–4 scale), while

economic power is assessed as concentrated but with meaningful middle-class influence (score around 2.5/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

The ideological distribution of the party system is another key element. According to the results of the 2020 general election (ParlGov 2023), the Irish party landscape is dominated by three major parties: the centrist Fianna Fáil (22.2% of the vote), the left-wing Sinn Féin (24.5%), and the center-right Fine Gael (20.9%). Together, these parties account for nearly 70% of the total vote share and reflect a system historically structured around centrist and mainstream formations. Unlike many other European democracies, Ireland has so far been less affected by the rise of far-right parties.

Ideological self-placement in Ireland reflects pronounced generational and gender differences. Younger cohorts are more dispersed across the spectrum, while older groups show stronger concentration on the right and far right. Among men under 35, 15.6% position themselves on the far left and 19.8% on the left, with only 12.9% choosing the center. Right-wing identification increases sharply with age, reaching 24.8% among those aged 36–55 and 64.0% among those aged 56 and over, while far-right support rises from 0% among the youngest to 87.9% in the oldest male cohort. Women follow a similar but less extreme pattern—younger women lean more to the far left (28.6%) and left (21.2%), while among those aged 56 and over, centrist and right-wing positions become dominant (38.5% and 63.1%). Far-right support among women also increases with age, from 2.7% to 67.5% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender differences remain visible across cohorts. The center is consistently more attractive to women than to men (64.2% vs. 57.0% among those under 35; 70.2% vs. 61.4% among those aged 36–55). Men display higher left-wing identification across all ages (23.4% vs. 16.2% among the youngest; 12.1% vs. 10.1% among those over 56), while women show slightly higher far-left support at younger ages (9.5% vs. 6.5%), although this decreases with age. Right-wing alignment strengthens with age for both genders but remains higher among men (13.1% under 35, 17.8% over 56) than among women (7.4% and 15.4%, respectively). Support for far-right positions is marginal among younger cohorts but increases significantly with age, particularly among men (6.5% vs. 6.0% among women aged 56+) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Ireland exhibits a clear generational divide—younger cohorts, especially women, lean more toward left and far-left positions, whereas older cohorts gravitate toward the right and far right. Gender adds another layer of differentiation, with women more concentrated at the center and men more present at both ideological extremes. These dynamics signal a widening generational and gendered diversification of political preferences, with potential implications for mobilization and party competition.

In sum, Ireland’s political system appears to be a delicate but positive equilibrium—solid institutions and comparatively high attachment to European governance coexist with below-EU turnout in European elections, incomplete gender parity in representation, and moderate polarization. These elements depict a terrain where formal adherence to liberal principles intersects with challenges of participation, inclusion, and the continuing effort to translate constitutional guarantees into everyday democratic engagement.

I.14.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial to understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Ireland, the online ecosystem is characterized by widespread use of digital media and comparatively high confidence in web-based information, alongside clear vulnerabilities in media literacy and exposure to hostile content toward democracy and gender equality.

The use of digital platforms for news is intense. About 48% of people in Ireland read news online every day (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), underscoring the centrality of digital media in public and political life. In parallel, reliance on social networks as information spaces is notable, although citizens’ confidence distinguishes sharply between sources—around 44% tend to trust news found on websites, whereas roughly 26% tend to trust information circulating on social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This gap suggests that while the internet is a primary gateway to current affairs, people remain more cautious about the credibility of platform-mediated content.

Concerns about disinformation are widespread. Roughly 85% of Irish respondents consider the existence of false or manipulative information a “serious problem for democracy” (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). A small but

nontrivial share report encountering misleading content very often or often in the week prior to the survey, while only a minority feel “very confident” they can recognize disinformation; most describe themselves as only somewhat confident. This mismatch between awareness and effective detection points to a substantial need to strengthen civic and digital competences.

The radicalization dimension also deserves attention. As documented in European scans of misogynist online ecosystems, a small number of Irish users (9) were identified on incels.is between 2017 and 2020 (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), indicating that explicitly anti-egalitarian communities are present—albeit on a limited scale—and can diffuse narratives hostile to women’s rights and democratic pluralism.

Overall, Ireland’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media offer broad access to information and avenues for participation, with everyday online news use among the highest in the EU and trust in web news relatively strong. On the other hand, high perceived risks from disinformation, uneven critical skills, and the detectable presence of misogynist/anti-democratic communities pose concrete challenges to the quality of public debate and democratic resilience. The policy priority is twofold: upgrade media literacy and critical thinking skills across the population and design targeted prevention and counter-radicalization strategies that reduce the reach of gender-hostile and anti-democratic content online.

I.14.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Ireland, the overall picture is comparatively favorable by EU standards—especially in terms of cultural openness and relational capital—yet important vulnerabilities persist along pathways to empowerment, education-to-work transitions, and socioeconomic autonomy.

On composite measures of well-being and inclusion, Ireland reflects strong material conditions and positive perceptions of social participation. Attitudes among the young show broad—if not universal—openness to diversity. About 90% of 15–29-year-olds consider Ireland a “good place” for immigrants, and around 80% say the same for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). The relational dimension

is also robust, with a large majority of young people reporting good opportunities to make friends (90%) and build social networks, signaling dense youth social capital that can support participation and voice.

Educational pathways are a relative strength but still gendered. Early school leaving is low—about 3.5% among young men and 2.9% among young women (Eurostat 2024a). At the same time, women’s educational attainment is very high in the transition-to-adulthood cohort (e.g., a large majority of women aged 25–29 have completed 12–18 years of schooling) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022); however, these advantages do not always translate seamlessly into secure, well-paid jobs.

Taken together, Ireland’s youth combine high tolerance, strong social ties, and solid educational outcomes with persistent hurdles linked to housing affordability, labor market precarity, and uneven opportunities for autonomous living. The policy challenge is to convert inclusive attitudes and strong schooling into stable empowerment trajectories—through affordable housing, quality entry-level jobs, and targeted supports that sustain participation and agency across the transition to adulthood.

I.14.8 Being socialized in Ireland

Being socialized in Ireland means growing up in a democracy characterized by strong civil liberties and high international trust, paired with selective domestic engagement. Economic prosperity coexists with territorial and class-based inequalities. Gender equality has advanced institutionally, but unpaid care remains feminized and leadership stereotypes endure.

Cultural attitudes are generally tolerant, although some express skepticism toward feminism.

Digital news use is high, and concern about misinformation is widespread. Accordingly, masculine gender norms in Ireland develop at the intersection of liberal values, class-structured opportunities, and lingering expectations around ambition, responsibility, and protection.

I.15 ITALY

I.15.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

The Italian socioeconomic framework is characterized by an intermediate position within the EU, combining elements of stability with structural weaknesses.

Table 17 Socioeconomic conditions in Italy compared with the EU27

	Italy	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	98.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	31.1	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	23.1	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	80.6	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	65.5	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	61	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	89.3	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

In 2024, the GDP per capita in PPSs indicates a level of economic well-being slightly below European standards, confirming the country’s persistent difficulty closing the gap with the more advanced economies of the area (Table 17).

Income distribution reveals even sharper disparities and the population share vulnerable to poverty or social exclusion also persists at a significant level. These values place Italy among the countries with the highest internal inequalities, highlighting the vulnerability of weaker social groups (Table 17).

The labor market mirrors these gaps. The population aged between 15 and 64 years’ employment rates equal 71.1% for males and just 53.3% for females. The gender gap is particularly pronounced compared to the EU average of 75.3% for men and 66.2% for women (Eurostat 2024b). Low female participation in paid work results in reduced economic autonomy and a structural delay in convergence with European partners.

The Gender Equality Index by EIGE supports this scenario. The work dimension is particularly critical, while the money dimension shows a smaller gap. These results highlight that the fragility of the female employment system remains one of the main structural obstacles to reducing gender inequalities (Table 17).

Demographic composition emerges as another core factor. The old age dependency ratio stands at 38.4 (population aged 65+ compared to the working-age population), substantially higher than the EU average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e). This indicates increasing pressure on pension and welfare schemes, as well as the need for intergenerational support policies.

In addition, the share of foreign-born residents is significant, at 11.3% (Eurostat 2022). Migration represents a crucial factor for demographic and economic sustainability, but it also raises challenges linked to integration and social cohesion.

Overall, Italy's socioeconomic and institutional structure is contradictory. On the one hand, it ensures moderate levels of well-being and a certain macroeconomic stability. On the other hand, it remains marked by wide income inequalities, persistent gender gaps, strong demographic pressures, and a welfare system that is not always capable of addressing new social challenges.

I.15.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Italy is among the European countries with a consolidated democracy, but the landscape of values and institutions reveals significant ambivalence. According to Freedom House's Freedom in the World Index, Italy scored 89 out of 100 in 2024, classified as "free" (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index also gave Italy a relatively high score of 7.58 out of 10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), pointing to a stable democracy with room for improvement, especially regarding political participation and institutional efficiency. According to the World Justice Project's Rule of Law Index, Italy stands at 0.66 (World Justice Project 2024). The score is not surprising; it reflects well-known structural problems, such as the excessive duration of judicial proceedings and persistent obstacles to guaranteeing equal access to justice. The picture changes, however, if one looks at V-Dem's Civil Liberties Index. Here, Italy reaches 0.91 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), suggesting a strong record in the protection of civil rights. Still, even this relatively high value conceals some weaknesses, especially when it comes to ensuring that liberties are equally safeguarded in practice.

Looking at European values through the prism of gender equality, the results are mixed. Italy scored 69.2 on the 2024 EIGE Gender Equality Index, just below the EU27 average of 71. On the one hand, the time domain—which tracks how care work and domestic tasks are divided—scored 67.4, showing significant gender imbalances in unpaid care and domestic work, consistent with the EU-wide pattern (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This confirms what many observers already note—the burden of family responsibilities still falls unevenly on women. On the other hand, the power domain tells a more positive story—

with 66.5 points, Italy performs better than the EU average (61.4), indicating that women have gained greater, still incomplete, visibility and access to decision-making positions (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

When referring to the European value of pluralism, other fields that deserve attention are migrant integration and LGBTQI+ rights. On MIPEX, Italy scored 78, which places it among the countries with relatively inclusive policies (MIPEX 2023). The outlook is far less favorable, however, for LGBTQI+ rights. In the Rainbow Europe Index, Italy reached only 24 out of 100, well below the EU average of 51.1 (ILGA-Europe 2025). Particularly striking is the score of zero for hate crime–aggravating circumstances linked to sexual orientation or gender identity. This gap makes clear that legislation in this area is still incomplete and lacks real effectiveness (ILGA-Europe 2025).

I.15.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Italy reveal strong ambivalence—signs of change toward greater openness coexist with persistent traditional stereotypes limiting full gender equality.

One key indicator concerns perceptions of family roles, as displayed in Figure 38, based on data from the Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These data reflect a deeply rooted view linking family well-being to women’s willingness to sacrifice their careers.

Figure 38 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Italy

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of gender inequality in the workplace confirm this contradiction. About 59% of Italians believe men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This shows a widespread awareness of structural discrimination, but it coexists with conservative views on role division.

A positive sign emerges in the political sphere—80% of Italians believe it is “good” for politics to have a gender balance in leadership positions, reflecting growing openness to equality in the public sphere (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, negative stereotypes persist (Figure 38). A substantial share of the population continues to associate women with excessive emotionality and a presumed lack of authority, casting doubt on their suitability for leadership and on the legitimacy of women expressing strong opinions in public.

These stereotypes also shape men’s expectations. On the one hand, there is greater openness—85% of Italians find it acceptable for a man to cry, in line with the EU average (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, many traditional views remain—27% think “men should have the final say in important family decisions”, and 63% believe “men are naturally less competent than women at

housework”. Similarly, 26% see paternity leave as a sign of low ambition, while only 41% would accept a father quitting work if he earned less than his partner (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In Italy, attitudes toward gender roles, sexuality, and power relations reflect strong generational divides and persistent gender differences. On LGBTQI+ rights, support is highest among younger cohorts—81.2% of young men and 89.0% of young women agree that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish, while older respondents are less supportive (65.6% of men and 65.3% of women) and make up most of those who disagree (64.4% of men and 72.4% of women in the 56+ group) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of sexual harassment show even sharper divides. Among those who believe exaggeration is “often/always” the case, more than half are older men (53.2%) or older women (60.3%). Among younger respondents, rejection of this idea is more common (25.1% of young men and 24.5% of young women say “never/rarely”), although skepticism persists among some groups (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Views about women “seeking power” follow the same pattern—endorsement of “often/always” peaks among older respondents (47.5% of older men and 50.7% of older women), while the youngest cohorts remain less likely to hold this view (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Attitudes toward women’s protection by men also reflect generational change. Among those who support protection “often/always”, older respondents again make up the largest share (44.3% of men, 35.2% of women). However, rejection of this paternalistic view is also led by the oldest cohort (48.3% of older men and 54.7% of older women), indicating that polarization around this norm increases with age. Gender differences remain substantial across all dimensions. Young women are consistently the most egalitarian—76.2% reject harassment exaggeration, only 6.6% believe women frequently seek control, and 36.0% reject protection norms—while young men show higher skepticism and stronger attachment to traditional views (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In sum, Italy’s gender norms and attitudes show a dual movement: signs of openness and support for equality,

especially in public life, coexist with resilient stereotypes constraining women's trajectories and reinforcing traditional models of masculinity.

I.15.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Italy is a structural problem at levels similar to or slightly higher than the European average, with important implications for social cohesion and the protection of fundamental rights. According to the EU Gender-based violence survey (2023), 32% of Italian women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15, slightly above the EU27 average (31%) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). This highlights the pervasiveness of gender-based violence as a systemic rather than a residual phenomenon.

Looking at partner violence, differences become sharper. In Italy, 25.9% of women report psychological violence from a current or former partner, compared to the European average of 32% (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). This gap can be interpreted in two ways: it could suggest a lower prevalence in Italy, or it could reflect cultural difficulties in recognizing and reporting such abuse, often normalized or downplayed.

According to data (Eurostat 2023c), the rate of intentional homicides committed by a partner or family member is 0.32 per 100,000 inhabitants for women, compared to 0.18 for men. This disparity highlights the gendered nature of lethal violence, which disproportionately targets women within domestic and intimate relationships.

Institutionally, Italy signed the Istanbul Convention in 2012, ratified it in 2013, and brought it into force in 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). This formal commitment places Italy among active Council of Europe members in combating violence against women and domestic violence, ensuring an advanced legal framework. However, the gap between legal principles and concrete application remains significant—high levels of physical violence and low victim awareness suggest that prevention and protection systems require further strengthening.

Overall, Italy's situation is marked by a clear contradiction: a solid legal framework and political recognition of the issue coexist with persistently high violence levels and insufficient access to support. This tension reflects the difficulty of translating institutional commitments

into effective prevention and protection practices, making gender-based violence a crucial test for the country's democratic and inclusive capacity.

I.15.5 Political dimension

Politics offers a privileged lens through which to observe the interplay of democratic values, gender inequalities, and power dynamics in Italy. Indicators show a complex picture, marked by institutional consolidation but also challenges related to representation, trust, and polarization.

Voter turnout in the 2024 European elections was 48%, close to the EU27 average (51%) but still relatively low (European Parliament 2024). This points to selective engagement among Italians, reflecting both continuity with European trends and widespread disillusionment with political institutions' effectiveness in daily life.

In terms of gender representation, women hold 34% of parliamentary seats, broadly in line with the EU average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Although the female presence in institutions has improved, it still falls short of parity and positions Italy on the European middle ground, reflecting only partial effects of gender-balancing policies introduced in recent years.

Ideological distribution is another key factor. According to ParlGov (ParlGov 2023), around 42.5% of seats are held by right-wing or far-right parties, with Fratelli d'Italia commanding 26% of the vote. This reflects a broader European trend of strengthened conservative and nationalist forces. V-Dem's Government Coalition Left-Right Index places Italy firmly on the right, with major implications for policy priorities, especially in social policy, civil rights, and gender equality. Regarding democratic quality, Italy scores 0.8 on the Electoral Democracy Index (Varieties of Democracy 2024), signaling free elections and political pluralism.

Citizen trust in political institutions remains low. According to data, only 33% trust the national parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Trust in political parties is even lower (25%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), showing a persistent gap between citizens and institutions. This detachment is mirrored in low political interest—only 3% of Italians say they are very interested in politics, and 26% are quite interested (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

According to the 2024 Eurobarometer, 59% of Italians reported trust in the European Parliament—evidence of a continuing bond with EU institutions (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). More critical is the perception of alternative regimes. The World Values Survey (Wave 7) shows that 31% of Italians consider it “good” or “fairly good” for a leader to govern without parliament or elections (Haerpfer et al. 2024). Italian data collected in 2018 reveal a latent fragility of democratic attitudes, likely fueled by socioeconomic insecurity and widespread perceptions of institutional inefficiency.

Attitudes toward political violence provide further insight into the state of democratic culture in Italy. According to the World Values Survey (Haerpfer et al. 2024), an overwhelming majority of respondents (77.7%) believe that political violence is “never justifiable”, suggesting a strong normative rejection of violence as a political tool. However, around one in five respondents express at least some degree of justification, with nearly 10% placing themselves at the midpoint of the scale or above. Although still a minority, this segment indicates the presence of a small but non-negligible tolerance for political violence, which, in the context of rising polarization and distrust in institutions, could become a risk factor for democratic stability. V-Dem estimates political polarization in Italy at 2.5 out of 4, indicating strong divides along political and cultural lines, with identity-based clashes prevailing over programmatic debate. Socioeconomic power distribution scores 2.28 out of 4, showing a predominant role of wealthy classes, although middle and lower classes retain some influence (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

The ideological distribution of the Italian electorate shows a strong generational component and significant gender differences, reflecting broader social and political dynamics. Political self-placement in Italy is strongly shaped by age, with more radical positions concentrated among older cohorts. On the far left, 69.23% of male identifiers and 42.86% of female identifiers are aged 56 years or over, and the broader left also skews older—45.45% of left-leaning men and 37.00% of left-leaning women belong to the oldest cohort. Centrism is more evenly distributed by age but still tilts toward older respondents, especially among women, 45.58% of whom are over 56 years of age. Right-wing orientations follow a similar pattern—50.21% of men and 52.76% of women identifying with the right are in the oldest group, and the far right shows an even stronger concentration among older Italians (50.77% of men and

57.38% of women aged 56+) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender differences appear within each age group. Centrism is the most common position for both men and women and is slightly more prevalent among women—49.78% of men and 51.32% of women under 35 choose the center. Among those aged 56 or above, the proportions choosing the center are still substantial: 40.52% of men and 50.39% of women. Left-wing identification declines with age for both genders but more sharply among women (22.64% under 35 vs. 13.37% over 56). Right-wing support increases with age, from 20.35% to 24.84% among men and from 17.36% to 25.97% among women. Far-right support remains limited but rises modestly across cohorts for men (5.19% to 7.19%) and women (3.40% to 6.78%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

These patterns indicate that ideological extremism in Italy is disproportionately concentrated among older generations, while younger cohorts cluster more around the political center. Gender further shapes this configuration. Women are consistently more centrist and less polarized, whereas men are more represented at both the left and right extremes. These dynamics suggest that Italian political preferences are structured by the combined effects of generational change and gendered political socialization. Overall, Italy's political dimension is characterized by unstable equilibrium—on the one hand, formally strong democratic institutions and improving gender representation, and on the other hand, fragmented politics marked by polarization, low trust, and significant openness to non-democratic alternatives.

I.15.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is now crucial for understanding political and value socialization, as well as risks linked to disinformation and online radicalization. In Italy, digital engagement is widespread, but vulnerabilities regarding the quality and reliability of information are evident.

According to Eurobarometer, 43% of Italians read online news daily, reflecting the centrality of the digital ecosystem in public life (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust in online sources, however, is ambivalent. About 55% trust news found on the internet—well above the EU average (43%)—and 39% trust social media information, compared to 31% in the EU27 (European Commission. Directorate General for

Communication. 2024a). These figures suggest that Italians are more likely than others to grant credibility to digital sources, despite widespread awareness of disinformation risks.

Perceptions of fake news as a democratic threat are very high—85% of Italians consider disinformation a serious problem, slightly above the EU average (81%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Nearly 30% report being exposed “often or very often” to misleading content in the week before the survey, confirming a high circulation of distorted narratives. Despite this, only 9% feel “very confident” in recognizing disinformation, while more than half (51%) say they can do so only “sometimes” (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This mismatch between risk awareness and response capacity highlights structural vulnerability, which can amplify hostile narratives against democratic and gender equality values.

A relevant concern is male online radicalization, expressed through misogynistic communities such as the manosphere. The incels.is forum is emblematic. According to a study by Moonshot for the European Commission (2021), between 2017 and 2020, at least 44 users self-identified as Italy-based (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). While partial, this figure places Italy among European countries with a significant presence in such misogynistic reactionary networks. These communities combine hostility toward women’s rights with the delegitimization of democratic institutions, creating fertile ground for spreading anti-equality and anti-democratic ideologies.

Overall, Italy’s digital dimension follows a dual trajectory. On the one hand, the internet and social networks offer broader spaces for information and political socialization than in other European countries, with relatively high trust in digital media. On the other hand, widespread disinformation, weak recognition skills, and the structured presence of misogynistic and anti-democratic communities pose risks that undermine public debate and democratic resilience.

I.15.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is crucial for understanding a country’s democratic quality and social resilience since young people are often the most exposed to cumulative structural inequalities and digital vulnerabilities. In Italy, the picture is mixed. There are some strengths in relational and cultural dimensions but persistent fragilities in empowerment and social mobility.

According to the Youth Progress Index (2022), Italy scored 84.38 out of 100, (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), placing it in the European middle ground. This multidimensional index combines objective indicators and subjective perceptions, capturing not only material conditions but also young people's sense of social inclusion.

A positive aspect is relational capital. Data show that young Italians give relatively favorable evaluations of opportunities for socialization and inclusion—76 out of 100 rate Italy as a good place for immigrants, and 76 out of 100 rate Italy as a good place for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This is significant, as these data reveal greater openness among younger generations compared to the general population, suggesting the potential for more inclusive and democratic socialization. Friendships and social ties are also evaluated positively, at 82 out of 100, indicating that despite structural difficulties, Italian youth maintain some social cohesion and trust.

However, challenges remain. The Youth Progress Report highlights underperformance in key areas, such as access to quality education, individual empowerment, and autonomous decision-making. These reflect structural limitations already evident in education and employment—higher school dropout rates among young men (12.2%) compared to young women (7.1%) (Eurostat 2024a), among the lowest female labor force participation rates in Europe (53.3% vs. the EU27 average of 66.2%) (Eurostat 2024b), and social mobility still heavily conditioned by family and territorial background.

In this context, Italian youth stand at a crossroads between value openness and socioeconomic exclusion risks. On the one hand, they show greater acceptance of diversity, stronger social bonds, and appreciation for inclusive environments. On the other hand, they face material and symbolic barriers that limit autonomy.

I.15.8 Being socialized in Italy

Being socialized in Italy means growing up in a democracy that guarantees rights but struggles with low political trust, high polarization, and debates about strong leadership. Gender inequalities remain deep. Care work is unevenly distributed, female employment is low, and leadership remains male-dominated. Public endorsement of equality coexists with doubts about women's authority and the persistence of male breadwinner expectations. Younger cohorts express more inclusive views but encounter structural barriers to autonomy. Digital

spaces, widely trusted, allow disinformation and gender-hostile content to circulate easily. Within this landscape, masculine gender norms in Italy emerge through tensions among egalitarian aspirations, traditional family models, and contentious digital environments.

I.16 LATVIA

I.16.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Latvia’s socioeconomic profile combines below EU income levels with some areas of resilience and gradual convergence. As Table 18 shows, the GDP per capita in PPSs signals a still modest capacity to generate material well-being by EU standard. Income distribution is comparatively unequal, indicating comparatively high income inequality and a social structure where disparities remain marked, and the share at risk of poverty or social exclusion remains high, pointing to persistent territorial and class-based vulnerabilities.

Table 18 Socioeconomic conditions in Latvia compared with the EU27

	Latvia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	71.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	31.2	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	24.3	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	69.6	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	77.5	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	52.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	79	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Employment among 15–64-year-olds is 72.3% for men and 70.0% for women (Eurostat 2024b). The gender gap is relatively small, and female participation is comparatively high, but qualitative barriers (career progression and pay) remain.

Gender-equality metrics confirm this ambivalence. Work performs relatively well, while money is weaker. Knowledge is low (Table 18), consistent with strong educational segregation (about 61.2% of tertiary students concentrated in education/health/humanities) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) and a thin STEM pipeline (10.8 graduates aged 20–29 per 1,000 population) (Eurostat 2023b). Early school leaving remains non-negligible

(9.6% boys; 6.1% girls) (Eurostat 2024a), with implications for mobility and entry into quality jobs.

Demographically, Latvia faces medium-term pressures—the old age dependency ratio is 33.9 (Eurostat 2024e). Roughly 21.5% of residents live in rural areas (OECD 2023a), and the foreign-born share is 12.7% (Eurostat 2022)—levels that support demographic balance but require effective integration policies.

On the welfare side, social expenditure is about 19.7% of the GDP (OECD 2024b). This indicates a leaner welfare state—helpful in absorbing shocks but less equipped to tackle emerging risks, such as youth precarity, care–work reconciliation, and regional gaps.

Overall, Latvia combines steady female labor participation with higher inequality, segmented human capital, and a limited welfare capacity. Closing the distance with EU standards will hinge on investments in skills (especially STEM), measures against early school leaving, reduction of pay and territorial gaps, and a gradual strengthening of social protection to turn participation into broad-based, inclusive growth.

1.16.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Latvia combines solid formal democratic guarantees with areas of fragility around inclusion and gender equality. In Freedom in the World 2024, the country scores 89/100 (“Free”) (Freedom House 2025), while the EIU Democracy Index places it at 7.66/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), pointing to an electoral system that works with broad civil-political rights. The World Justice Project Rule of Law Index is 0.73 (World Justice Project 2024), and V-Dem’s civil-liberties score is a high 0.94 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), together indicating comparatively strong safeguards for expression, association, and due process, even if justice efficiency and equal access remain recurring concerns.

On gender equality, the picture is more mixed. The Gender Equality Index for Latvia stands at 62.6 (EU-27 at 71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)—women’s participation in work is comparatively strong, but outcomes in money/earnings and particularly knowledge/skills are weaker, and power (decision-making) lags behind the EU benchmark. These gaps reflect persistent vertical and horizontal segregation and a still unequal distribution of care.

Inclusion and pluralism policies show a mid-range profile. Migrant integration policies in Latvia are moderate rather than expansive, and protection for LGBTQI+ people remain limited compared to leading EU countries. This indicates a significant scope for strengthening anti-discrimination measures and improving legal recognition frameworks. Latvia scores 66 on MIPEX (MIPEX 2023), while its hate speech and hate crime legislation related to gender identity and/or sexual orientation—as assessed by Rainbow Europe—remains very low at 11.59 (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Public attitudes toward the EU are generally supportive but not uniformly enthusiastic—trust in the European Parliament hovers around 60% (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), while a smaller minority expresses more skeptical views. In particular, 9.3% of respondents adopt a strongly Eurosceptic position, rating integration as having “gone too far” (0 on a 0–10 scale) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, Latvia presents itself as a free and functioning democracy with robust civil-liberty protection. The most pressing “values” challenges lie in translating these formal strengths into substantive equality and inclusion—narrowing gender gaps (especially in power and care), deepening migrant and LGBTQI+ protections, and bolstering institutional trust—so that constitutional commitments are felt more evenly across society.

I.16.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Latvia show a similarly ambivalent landscape, in which significant progress toward equality coexists with enduring traditional expectations that shape gender roles in both private and public life. Family roles remain a domain in which traditional models exert a strong influence. According to Eurobarometer data (Figure 39) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), persistent norms exist in Latvia that link caregiving predominantly to women and question the compatibility of motherhood and paid employment.

Figure 39 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Latvia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality in the workplace further reflect this duality. Around 23% of Latvians believe that men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), highlighting an awareness of enduring gendered hierarchies. However, such awareness coexists with the widespread acceptance of traditional gender divisions in both professional and domestic spheres. In the political domain, this tension is also evident. While 59% of respondents agree that it would be “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful”, stereotypes about women’s authority persist (Figure 39) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Attitudes toward masculinity reflect a similar complexity. Although most Latvians now accept that men can show vulnerability—with 71% saying it is acceptable for a man to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)—rigid expectations remain. Around 31% think men should have the final say in family decisions, and 53% believe men are naturally less competent at housework (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Moreover, 18% view men who take parental leave as lacking ambition, reinforcing traditional ideas about male breadwinning and ambition (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Views on feminism reveal further polarization—51% of Latvians believe feminism has “gone too far”

(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), signaling a broader cultural backlash against gender equality policies and suggesting that equality gains are not yet fully consolidated in public opinion.

Generational and gender differences shape attitudes toward sexuality and gender roles. Attitudes toward gender and sexuality in Latvia reveal a complex interplay between progressive trends and deeply rooted traditional views, with notable variations across generations and genders. Support for the idea that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish increases with age among men (from 27.1% among those under 35 years of age to 46.6% among those over 56 years of age) and even more markedly among women (from 16.5% to 58.2%), suggesting that older cohorts are more accepting of this domain than younger ones. However, disagreement also rises substantially with age (up to 55.8% among older men and 70.2% among older women), indicating strong polarization in older generations. Across genders, women show slightly higher levels of agreement than men in all age groups, while men are more divided between neutrality and open rejection (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of whether women exaggerate claims of sexual harassment are also marked by generational and gender divides. Younger respondents, particularly women, are more likely to believe such claims are “never or rarely” exaggerated (23.8% of young women vs. 25% of young men), but skepticism grows with age, especially among women, with 68.8% of those over 56 years of age choosing “often or always”. Men show a more balanced distribution between “sometimes” and “often”, whereas women display a sharper age-related shift from dismissiveness to suspicion.

Similarly, the belief that women try to gain power by controlling men intensifies with age. The proportion of respondents selecting “often or always” rises significantly among older groups (44.2% of men and 59.7% of women over 56), revealing persistent hostile gender stereotypes, particularly among older women. Men tend to split between “sometimes” and “often”, while women are more likely to endorse the most negative view in later life (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Finally, views on protective gender roles remain strongly traditional, particularly among older respondents. The idea that women should be protected by men is most firmly rejected among

older men (50.7%) and women (62.9%), but younger cohorts show less rejection and even some support for benevolent sexism. Striking gender differences emerge: men are far more likely to reject protective roles outright (over 77% of young men say “never or rarely”), while women—especially younger ones—display greater acceptance of such norms (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Overall, attitudes in Latvia reveal a society negotiating equality-oriented values and persistent gendered expectations. Age amplifies polarization—older cohorts are simultaneously more supportive of LGBTQI+ rights and more accepting of hostile or paternalistic stereotypes. Gender continues to structure attitudes, with women often showing both stronger endorsement of equality and, paradoxically, deeper adherence to protective or hostile stereotypes in specific domains. This duality suggests that while normative change is underway, traditional gender ideologies continue to exert a powerful influence, particularly among older generations.

In sum, Latvia’s gender-norm landscape is characterized by a complex coexistence of progressive and traditional elements. Younger generations—especially women—show greater support for LGBTQI+ rights, more egalitarian attitudes, and less tolerance for hostile stereotypes. However, significant cultural resistance persists, particularly among older cohorts and men, and perceptions of feminism as “excessive” remain widespread. These dynamics reveal a society in transition—one where the egalitarian ideal is increasingly embraced but continues to contend with deeply rooted beliefs about gender roles, authority, and family responsibilities.

I.16.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Latvia remains a pervasive structural problem that significantly undermines democratic quality, gender equality, and the effective protection of fundamental rights. Despite the existence of a comprehensive legal framework and institutional structures aimed at prevention and support, high prevalence levels, gaps in awareness, and persistent barriers to accessing services reveal enduring weaknesses in the country’s response to this issue.

According to data from the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), 25.1% of women in Latvia aged 18–74 report having

experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15. This figure is notably above the EU average (31%) and reflects the systemic nature of gender-based violence, which remains deeply embedded in social and cultural dynamics rather than being an isolated or marginal phenomenon. Violence within intimate relationships is particularly widespread—30.1% of Latvian women report having suffered psychological violence, threats, physical abuse, and/or sexual violence by a partner or ex-partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), indicating entrenched patterns of control and coercion in private life.

Awareness of support services is relatively widespread—66% of victims report being aware of the existence of specialized services (Eurostat 2021b) and 53% of women are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a), suggesting that while general awareness is high but not common. This lack of information can discourage victims from seeking help and reduce their access to legal and protective instruments, particularly among the most vulnerable groups.

The most severe forms of violence further expose the systemic nature of the problem. Latvia records a rate of 1.88 intentional homicides of women by partners or relatives per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c). This stark gender gap underscores both the heightened risk faced by women and the persistent shortcomings in risk detection, prevention, and timely intervention mechanisms.

Legislatively, Latvia has formally committed to addressing gender-based violence. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on May 18, 2016, ratified it on January 10, 2024, and entered it into force on May 1, 2024, signaling its alignment with European standards on preventing and combating violence against women (Council of Europe 2025). However, as in many European countries, the gap between legislative commitments and their implementation remains significant. Persistently high prevalence rates, limited awareness of legal rights, and the continued occurrence of lethal violence indicate that prevention and protection policies still fall short of their intended goals.

Overall, Latvia's situation reveals a deeply contradictory landscape. On the one hand, the country has strengthened its legal and institutional framework and achieved relatively high levels of awareness of support services. On the other hand, violence remains widespread,

access to concrete legal rights is insufficient, and extreme forms of violence continue to occur at rates above the European average. These dynamics expose the limits of formal equality and highlight gender-based violence as a critical challenge for Latvia's capacity to ensure safety, justice, and substantive equality for women.

I.16.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides a revealing lens for understanding the relationship among democracy, gender inequality, and power dynamics in Latvia. The picture that emerges is one of relatively stable institutions and democratic consolidation, combined with persistent fragilities, political polarization, and significant public skepticism toward representative institutions.

Voter turnout is the first key indicator of democratic quality. In the 2024 European elections, turnout in Latvia was 33.8%, significantly below the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This low participation suggests a limited degree of civic mobilization and a weaker sense of belonging to the European project, reflecting a certain detachment from supranational politics—a pattern that is also visible in national-level participation trends. In terms of gender representation, women hold 30% of the seats in the Latvian parliament, slightly below the European average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) and indicating that progress toward gender parity in political decision-making remains incomplete.

The ideological composition of the political landscape reveals additional complexities. The results of the 2022 national elections in Latvia reflect a fragmented but competitive party system characterized by a significant dispersion of votes across several political forces and the absence of any single dominant party. According to ParlGov data (ParlGov 2023), the elections confirmed the Unity party as the leading political force, with 19.0% of the vote. This result, while consolidating Unity's position at the center of Latvia's political landscape, does not allow it to govern alone and necessitates coalition-building—a recurring feature of Latvian politics. The Green and Farmers' Union emerged as the second largest party, gaining 12.4% of the vote, while the Latvian Green Party followed closely with 11.0% of the vote. On the nationalist-conservative side, the National Alliance won 9.3% of the vote, confirming its consolidated base and continued appeal among voters prioritizing national identity and

traditional values. The populist and protest-oriented For Stability! achieved a notable breakthrough with 6.8% of the vote, while the Progressives and Latvia First secured 6.2% of the vote—signaling the growing pluralism of Latvia’s political landscape and the electorate’s appetite for new political alternatives.

Overall, the 2022 elections confirm Latvia’s tradition of coalition politics and multiparty competition. No single party commands a majority, and government formation depends on complex negotiations among ideologically diverse parties. The results also highlight an increasingly pluralistic political arena, in which established forces coexist with emerging actors and where identity, regional, and populist agendas continue to play a decisive role.

The quality of Latvia’s democracy is confirmed by key indicators. The Electoral Democracy Index assigns the country a score of 0.84 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), consistent with a functioning representative system based on pluralism and institutional checks and balances. Trust in political institutions is low, signaling a deeper crisis of political legitimacy. Confidence in the national government stands at 34%, and trust in political parties is at 17% (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Political engagement also remains limited. Only 5.9% of the Latvian population declares being very interested in politics and 20.8% quite interested (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), pointing to a widespread sense of detachment and disillusionment about the political system’s ability to respond to citizens’ needs.

Attitudinal data underscore the coexistence of democratic commitment and latent authoritarian tendencies. According to the World Values Survey (Haerpfer et al. 2024), 16.6% of Latvians consider authoritarian alternatives “very bad”, but a non-negligible minority express more permissive views—35.5% say it is fairly good having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections. These data point to potential vulnerabilities in democratic culture, especially in the context of rising polarization and identity-based conflicts.

Latvia’s political polarization is rated 1.14/4 by V-Dem (Varieties of Democracy 2024), suggesting a moderately polarized system marked by ideological divisions and increasing partisan segmentation. Power distribution by socioeconomic position also reflects significant

inequalities, with a score of 2.84/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating that economic elites retain a disproportionate influence on policy outcomes.

Political self-placement in Latvia displays marked generational and gendered patterns. Older cohorts are substantially more polarized than younger cohorts. Among men aged 56 and over, support for both the far left (40%) and the far right (39.5%) is high, while 55.5% still place themselves at the center. Younger men are far less polarized: 20% identify with the far left, 30.2% with the far right, and only 18.7% with the center. Among women, these generational contrasts are even sharper. Younger women show a more asymmetric profile, with 37.5% on the far left and 16.4% on the far right, whereas older women display strong dual polarization, with 50% placing themselves on the far left and 67.2% on the far right. Older women are also far more likely than younger women to identify with the traditional left (66.7% vs. 7.1%) and right (63.9% vs. 15.9%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).. These patterns indicate that ideological polarization in Latvia is driven primarily by older cohorts, while younger groups remain more fragmented and less firmly anchored to ideological extremes.

Gender differences further shape the distribution of political preferences. The center is the leading ideological position for both men and women but is consistently more common among women, ranging from 53.3% to 62.4% across age groups, compared with 47.1% to 55.4% among men. Men are more present at the extremes—far-right identification reaches 21.3% among men under 35 and 15.3% among those aged 36–55, compared with 14.3% and 8.8% among women, respectively. A similar though milder pattern emerges for the far left—men report slightly higher shares (3.3–4.7%) than women (0.8–3.9%). Men are also somewhat more inclined to identify with the right, particularly in midlife (29.4% vs. 19.2%), while women cluster more consistently around the center (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

In conclusion, Latvia's political system is marked by a paradoxical coexistence of institutional stability and deep political disillusionment. Low turnout, limited trust, and growing polarization coexist with stable democratic structures and moderate levels of pluralism. Gender representation is improving but still below the European average, while ideological divides—particularly those shaped by age and gender – remain significant. Together, these dynamics outline a political environment in which formal democratic norms persist, but social

fragmentation, inequality, and skepticism continue to challenge the consolidation of a more inclusive and participatory democratic culture.

I.16.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is central to political socialization and opinion-formation in Latvia. Everyday news use online is widespread, and the web is a primary gateway to public information. Eurobarometer items suggest that around 54% Latvians read news on the internet every day, while many others do so several times a week (16%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust splits by channel—about 38% they tend to trust news on websites, a percentage that mirrors trust in online social networks (32%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), signaling caution toward platform-mediated content. Concern about false or manipulative information is high—73% see disinformation as a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022), and 23% report encountering misleading content often or very often (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). Skills confidence lags behind awareness—only about one in nine feel “very confident” in spotting disinformation (around 10%), while a majority feel confident only “to some extent” (around 54%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

Overall, Latvia’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, high online news consumption and relatively strong trust in website-based news support access to information and participation. On the other hand, low trust in social networks, high perceived disinformation risk, and modest detection confidence can create vulnerabilities for the quality of public debate. The policy priority is twofold: strengthen media literacy and critical thinking skills across the population, and design targeted prevention and counter-radicalization strategies—especially toward gender-hostile and anti-democratic content.

I.16.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Latvia, the overall picture is more mixed compared with the European average—while the relational dimension and opportunities for building social capital appear relatively strong, significant challenges persist in terms of cultural openness, pathways to empowerment, and socioeconomic autonomy.

According to the Youth Progress Index (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), Latvia scores 83.5/100, a value that sits on the EU27 average. This value reflects a combination of moderate material conditions and uneven perceptions of social inclusion, highlighting the presence of structural barriers that continue to shape young people's transition to adulthood.

Openness to diversity is one of the areas in which limitations are most evident. About 60% of Latvian youth consider their country a “good place” for immigrants, and 50% express the same view regarding gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These figures, significantly lower than the EU average, indicate that younger generations in Latvia still face challenges in embracing pluralism and diversity, suggesting that cultural attitudes may evolve more slowly here than in other European contexts.

The relational dimension, however, presents a more positive picture. Around 80% of young people favorably evaluate opportunities to make friends and build social networks, pointing to the presence of strong peer relations and relatively robust social capital among youth. Such networks can act as important resources for social participation and engagement, even in the context of more limited cultural openness.

On the educational and economic front, structural weaknesses remain evident. The share of young men who leave education or training early is 9.6%, while among young women, it is lower (6.1%) (Eurostat 2024a). Although these values are close to the European average, they reveal persistent gender inequalities in access to and continuity of education and underline the difficulties many young people encounter in making a smooth transition from school to stable employment.

Overall, Latvia's youth landscape is characterized by a dual dynamic—on the one hand, strong relational networks and some degree of social capital, and on the other hand, weaker cultural openness, ongoing gender disparities, and structural barriers to socio-economic independence. These elements suggest that while Latvian youth possess important resources for civic engagement and democratic participation, additional efforts are needed to strengthen inclusion, equality, and opportunities for empowerment.

I.16.8 Being socialized in Latvia

Being socialized in Latvia means growing up in a democracy with formal protections but low political participation, limited trust in parties, and openness to concentrated authority among some groups. Gender norms remain strongly shaped by traditional expectations of male provision and female caregiving, despite advances in women’s employment. Attitudes toward leadership, harassment, and gender equality reveal significant internal polarization. Digital life is central but marked by uneven media literacy and exposure to disinformation. In this context, masculine gender norms in Latvia evolve between egalitarian tendencies among younger cohorts and durable hierarchical expectations across older segments.

I.17 LITHUANIA

I.17.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Lithuania’s socioeconomic landscape mixes continued convergence with the EU and with stubborn structural gaps. In 2024, the GDP per capita in PPS signals income levels still below the EU average. Inequality is comparatively high (Gini and people are at risk of poverty or social exclusion) (Table 19).

Table 19 Socioeconomic conditions in Lithuania compared with the EU27

	Lithuania	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	88.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	33.7	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	25.8	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	70.9	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	76.2	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	59.3	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	83.4	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is relatively robust and unusually balanced by gender. Employment among those aged 15–64 years is 74.2% for men and 73.0% for women (Eurostat 2024b), a small gap that masks qualitative disadvantages for women in pay and progression. The EIGE Gender Equality Index confirms this duality. The work domain is comparatively strong , while money is weaker, mirroring lower returns (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)Table 19) . The knowledge domain is low (59.3) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024),

consistent with strong horizontal segregation (a large share of tertiary students in education/health/humanities) and a thin STEM pipeline (11.2 graduates in science/tech/engineering per 1,000 people aged 20–29) (Eurostat 2023b). Early school leaving remains non-negligible (10.0% boys and 6.8% girls), with implications for mobility and entry into quality jobs (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographically, pressures are mounting. The old age dependency ratio is 31.2 (near the EU average) (Eurostat 2024e) (Eurostat 2022), while the foreign-born share is 10.9%. Using the OECD typology, only about 8% of residents live in predominantly rural regions (OECD 2023a)—an unusual distribution that still translates into service and opportunity gaps outside the main urban centers. On the welfare side, social expenditure is about 16.9% of the GDP (OECD 2024b), a comparatively lean safety net that cushions shocks but has a limited capacity to tackle new risks (youth precarity, regional divides, care–work reconciliation).

In sum, Lithuania combines high female labor participation and sound democratic guarantees with elevated inequality, skill segmentation, and a modest welfare effort. Closing the gap with EU standards will require sustained investment in skills (especially STEM), action on early school leaving, pay and power gaps, and targeted regional and social protection measures so that growth translates into broad-based, inclusive well-being.

I.17.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Lithuania combines consolidated liberal–democratic institutions with some unresolved tensions around equality and inclusion. Freedom in the World classifies Lithuania as “Free” (89/100) (Freedom House 2025), while the Democracy Index places it at 7.59/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), indicating a political system characterized by pluralism, competitive elections, and generally effective institutions that uphold fundamental rights and freedoms.

On gender equality, the picture is more nuanced. Lithuania’s overall Gender Equality Index stands at 65.8, below the EU average (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The work domain performs comparatively well, indicating strong female participation in the labor market, but time (62.1) and, especially, power (55.5) lag behind, reflecting persistent gendered divisions in unpaid care work and the continued underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This suggests that

while formal equality is largely achieved, translating it into substantive equality in the spheres of domestic labor and political influence remains a major challenge.

The inclusion and pluralism dimensions are similarly mid-range. MIPEX sits around 51 (MIPEX 2023), reflecting moderate policies that support integration but still leave significant barriers, especially regarding long-term residence, political participation, and anti-discrimination enforcement. Protection for LGBTQI+ people also remains limited compared to EU standards. Rainbow Europe scores Lithuania around 23.2/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), with hate crime and hate speech provisions only partially comprehensive. This highlights clear room for improvement in strengthening legal recognition, safeguarding rights, and fostering a more inclusive environment for sexual and gender minorities.

Public attitudes toward European integration are broadly positive, indicating relatively strong support for Lithuania's role in the EU. Around 60% of Lithuanians report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), suggesting substantial confidence in supranational governance. At the same time, a small but noteworthy minority expresses Eurosceptic views, with about 4.7% believing that European integration has “gone too far” (answer 0 on a scale of 0–10) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). This indicates that while support for EU membership is widespread, there remain undercurrents of skepticism that policymakers cannot ignore.

Overall, Lithuania presents itself as a free, rule-based democracy with strong institutional guarantees of civil liberties and fundamental rights. However, the main “values” challenges lie in translating formal commitments into lived realities—closing persistent gender gaps in power and care responsibilities, deepening protections for migrants and LGBTQI+ communities, and sustaining high levels of public trust.

I.17.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Lithuania present a similarly complex picture in which significant shifts toward equality coexist with enduring stereotypes and traditional expectations that continue to shape the roles of women and men in both public and private life. According to Eurobarometer data (Figure 40), family-role conceptions remain among the most resistant to change (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and

Consumers. 2024). These results, considerably above the EU average, point to a deeply rooted belief that caregiving is primarily a female responsibility and highlight persistent doubts about the compatibility of employment and motherhood.

Figure 40 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Lithuania

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of gender inequality in the labor market reveal the same ambivalence. Roughly 31% of respondents believe that women are treated less fairly at work, compared with 7% who say the opposite, while a majority (62%) consider treatment to be equal (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This signals a widespread recognition of structural inequalities but also suggests that many Lithuanians perceive the workplace as largely gender-neutral, despite evidence of persistent disparities.

In the political sphere, attitudes show a similar duality (Figure 40). On the one hand, there is support for gender balance in leadership positions. On the other hand, gender stereotypes remain widespread, reflecting enduring symbolic biases that coexist with formal support for equality in representation. Norms surrounding masculinity also mirror these contradictions: around 69% of respondents say that it is ‘acceptable’ for a man to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), and a meaningful segment of the

population believes that men should have the ‘final say’ in major family decisions (20%) or that taking parental leave signals a lack of ambition (27%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These beliefs reinforce the traditional male breadwinner model and highlight the persistent gendered division of labor in both domestic and public life.

Public opinion on gender equality is further complicated by evidence of cultural backlash. A significant share of Lithuanians believes that “feminism has gone too far” (29%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), revealing a growing sense of fatigue and resistance to gender equality policies. This suggests a risk that further progress may encounter not only structural obstacles but also societal pushback against perceived overreach.

Attitudes toward gender and sexuality show clear generational gradients that intersect with persistent gender gaps. Across cohorts, the questions on whether gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish show a strong age effect—support is highest among younger men (39.1%) and women (34.1%) but declines substantially among older men (24.8%) and fluctuates among women, reaching 39.0% again among the oldest. Opposition, by contrast, is heavily concentrated among the over-56 group (about 48.0% of men and 56.4% of women among those who disagree), confirming that resistance to LGBTQI+ rights is largely a feature of older generations. Perceptions of sexual harassment claims show a similar generational gradient. Among men, the share of those who believe exaggeration is “often or always” rises from 21.97% among the youngest to 40.15% among the oldest, while the share of those who believe “never or rarely” declines from 41.44% to 24.32%. Among women, skepticism intensifies even more sharply with age, with frequent exaggeration rising from 15.46% to 58.76%. Age also shapes perceptions of power dynamics—the belief that women often seek control over men increases with age for both men (from 25.89% to 34.82%) and women (20.67% → 49.04%). Finally, the idea that women should be protected by men shows the same pattern, with younger cohorts more likely to reject this view (“never or rarely”: 41.46% among young men) and older groups showing higher support for traditional protection roles (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Across genders, the picture is equally revealing. Support for LGBTQI+ rights is similar among younger men and women (about 57% agree), but gender differences widen with age—older

men are more likely to oppose (54.24%) than older women (46.07%). On harassment exaggeration, women under 35 are much less skeptical than men (about 50.55% vs. 36.80% say it is “never or rarely” exaggerated), but this gap narrows with age. Regarding power relations, men are consistently more likely to think that women often seek control (43–46%) than women themselves (22–29%), while women more often choose intermediate positions (“sometimes” 51–53%). A similar gender gap appears in beliefs about protection—across all age groups, men are considerably more likely to think women should “often or always” be protected (around 44–46%) compared to women (22–29%), who are more inclined to say “sometimes” (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Taken together, these findings highlight a persistent generational divide, with younger cohorts generally more egalitarian, less skeptical, and less attached to traditional gender roles, and older cohorts more conservative across all items. They also reveal gendered patterns—men tend to be more resistant to progressive views, more likely to interpret women’s actions as manipulative, and more supportive of traditional protection norms, whereas women—especially younger ones—adopt more moderate or progressive positions, although older women remain more traditional on issues such as sexuality and gender dynamics.

Taken together, these patterns reveal a society in transition. Younger Lithuanians—especially women—tend to be more egalitarian in their views on gender roles and sexuality, while older cohorts and men across age groups remain more attached to traditional norms. Despite notable shifts toward equality, persistent beliefs about gendered responsibilities in the family, leadership, and emotional expression continue to shape expectations and social trajectories. The result is a normative landscape defined by coexistence—progressive values are increasingly embraced, but deeply ingrained stereotypes continue to anchor gender relations in long-standing cultural scripts.

I.17.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Lithuania remains a structural and deeply entrenched problem that continues to undermine women’s rights, gender equality, and the overall quality of democracy. Despite an evolving legal framework, growing service provision, and increasing

public attention, violence against women remains widespread, and critical gaps persist in prevention, protection, and victim support.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, around 25% of Lithuanian women report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence since the age of 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024)—a figure that, while slightly below the EU average, still signals the systemic and pervasive nature of the phenomenon. Violence within intimate relationships is even more widespread. Approximately 31% of women report having suffered psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence from a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These data underscore that gender-based violence in Lithuania cannot be considered a marginal or exceptional occurrence; rather, it is a structural component of gender relations, reflecting enduring power imbalances and coercive dynamics embedded in everyday life.

Knowledge of and access to support services present a mixed picture. On the one hand, general awareness is strikingly high—99.2% of women know that help services exist (Eurostat 2021b), a level that demonstrates the success of public information campaigns and institutional outreach. On the other hand, awareness of specific legal rights and entitlements remains limited. Only 63.2% of women are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a)—a gap that reveals how general knowledge does not necessarily translate into practical ability to seek assistance. This mismatch suggests that information dissemination strategies need to become more targeted, accessible, and actionable, particularly for vulnerable groups, such as rural women, older women, and those in economically dependent relationships.

The most severe manifestations of gender-based violence further highlight the urgent need for improved prevention and response systems. The intentional homicide rate of women killed by partners or family members is estimated at around 1.12 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), a figure that significantly exceeds that of many EU countries. This high level of lethal violence points to serious shortcomings in risk assessment, early warning mechanisms, and rapid intervention protocols. It also reflects structural deficiencies in coordination between law enforcement, judicial authorities, and social services, which too often fail to prevent the escalation of violence into fatal outcomes.

From an institutional and legal perspective, Lithuania's progress remains incomplete. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on June 7, 2013, signaling a formal commitment to align its national framework with the most advanced European standards. However, ratification and entry into force are still pending, which means that key obligations—such as comprehensive prevention measures, integrated victim support services, and systematic perpetrator accountability—remain only partially implemented (Council of Europe 2025). This legal gap weakens Lithuania's capacity to tackle gender-based violence effectively and hinders the development of a coordinated long-term strategy for eradication.

Overall, Lithuania's gender-based violence landscape is marked by contradictions. On the one hand, there has been notable progress in awareness, service provision, and institutional engagement. On the other hand, prevalence levels remain high, intimate partner violence is widespread, lethal outcomes are alarmingly frequent, and full alignment with international standards is still lacking. Bridging the gap between formal commitments and effective implementation—particularly through ratifying the Istanbul Convention, strengthening prevention systems, improving access to justice, and ensuring rapid intervention in high-risk cases—will be essential if Lithuania is to guarantee women's safety, uphold fundamental rights, and fulfill its democratic promises.

I.17.5 Political dimension

Lithuania's political arena couples consolidated democratic guarantees with pockets of fragility, polarization, and limited confidence in representative institutions. Participation lags behind EU benchmarks. In the 2024 European elections, turnout was below the EU average (28.97 vs. 50.74) (European Parliament 2024), signaling weak mobilization in supranational politics. Descriptively, representation is improving but not yet parity. Women hold about 29% of seats in the national parliament (vs. 33% in the EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), a sign of gradual but incomplete progress toward gender-balanced decision-making.

Democratic quality indicators also illuminate structural tensions: V-Dem's "power distributed by socioeconomic position" sits near 2.98/4, implying influence skewed toward higher socioeconomic groups, and political polarization about 1.27/4, moderate but non-trivial (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Political violence is rated low (0.25), but the existence of

minorities open to illiberal shortcuts keeps a residual risk on the radar (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

Trust metrics underscore the legitimacy gap. According to data, around 60% trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), but confidence is far thinner at home. In fact, 42% tend to trust the national government, and 35% are tilted toward political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). The result is a familiar paradox—institutions are substantively democratic, yet citizens' attachment to them is selective and cautious.

According to ParlGov (ParlGov 2023), the 2020 parliamentary elections in Lithuania revealed a fragmented yet clearly center-right-leaning political landscape, with the Homeland Union emerging as the dominant force. The conservative party secured 25.8% of the votes, significantly ahead of its competitors. The Lithuanian Peasant and Greens Union, a centrist-populist formation, came in second, with 18.1% of the votes. Overall, the results reflect a competitive multiparty system characterized by the strengthening of the center right and a relatively balanced distribution of votes among several political actors, making coalition building essential for forming a government.

Political self-placement in Lithuania reveals a marked generational divide, especially at ideological extremes. Among men, far-right identifiers are predominantly older—50.0% are aged 56 years or over, compared with 15.0% under 35 years of age. A similar pattern emerges on the right, where older men account for 48.05% of identifiers. The far left shows a different age profile, with the largest share found among men aged 36–55 years (51.85%), followed by those over 56 years (29.63%). Among women, the generational gradient is even clearer. Older women make up the majority of those on the far left (56.14%) and constitute a large share of far-right identifiers (42.37%). Moderate positions also lean older among women, with 53.52% of those on the left and 41.16% of centrists belonging to the oldest cohort (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, ideological polarization in Lithuania is largely driven by older generations, while younger cohorts remain less present at the extremes and more likely to occupy moderate positions.

Patterns across genders further clarify these dynamics. Centrism is the dominant stance for all age groups but declines with age, particularly among men. Nearly 60% of men under 35 years

of age identify with the center, compared with 45.27% of those over 56 years old. As centrism declines, right-wing identification grows, with support rising from 17.12% to 24.32% across generations, and far-right alignment increasing from 5.41% to 13.51%. Among women, centrism remains the majority position at all ages, falling only moderately, from 56.25% among the youngest to 50.19% among the oldest. Their ideological trajectory differs from that of men—younger women show comparatively higher far-right identification (13.19%), but this decreases with age, while older women become increasingly represented on the left (14.45%) and far left (12.17%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In sum, Lithuania presents a stable electoral democracy with robust civil-liberty protections and a plural party system, but participation deficits, modest women's representation, socioeconomic concentration of political power, and middling trust complicate the consolidation of a more inclusive, high-engagement democratic culture.

I.17.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is crucial to understanding political socialization, opinion-formation, and risks linked to disinformation and radicalization. In Lithuania, the online ecosystem is characterized by very widespread use of digital news and cautious trust in platform content while showing clear vulnerabilities in media literacy and exposure to material hostile to democracy and gender equality.

The use of digital platforms for news is high. About 62% report reading news online every/almost every day (a further 15% several times a week) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), underscoring the centrality of digital media in public and political life. In parallel, social networks are widely used to follow politics, but trust is uneven—39% tend to trust news on websites, whereas only 19% trust information from social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), confirming skepticism toward platform-mediated content.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widespread. About 80% of Lithuanians consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Around 27% say they were exposed often/very often to misleading content in the previous week (another 37% “sometimes”). However, the ability to recognize false news remains limited—only 11% feel

very confident identifying it, while roughly half feel confident only to some extent (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

Online radicalization deserves attention, especially in misogynist and anti-egalitarian communities. Lithuania registers only a small number of identified users on incels.is (3 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), but these spaces link hostility to women's rights with anti-democratic narratives, fueling gendered radicalization and rejection of pluralism.

Lithuania's digital environment therefore has a dual face. On the one hand, the internet and social media provide broad access to information and channels for participation. On the other hand, high perceived disinformation risk, low trust in social platforms, and modest verification skills—alongside pockets of gender-hostile communities—pose risks to the quality of debate and democratic resilience. The policy challenge is twofold: strengthen digital/media literacy so that citizens can recognize and counter false or hateful content and develop targeted prevention against online radicalization that spreads gendered hatred and anti-democratic rhetoric.

I.17.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key indicator of democratic resilience and a society's capacity to guarantee equal opportunities and agency to new generations. In Lithuania, the picture is characterized by a mix of notable progress—particularly in openness to diversity and relational resources—and structural fragilities that continue to constrain young people's empowerment, socio-economic autonomy, and participation.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Lithuania scores 84/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), placing it in the medium range among European countries. This value reflects improvements in material living conditions and social inclusion but also highlights persistent structural obstacles that complicate young people's transition to independent adulthood. One of the most encouraging aspects is openness to diversity. Lithuanian youth express attitudes significantly more inclusive than those of the general population—50% consider their country a “good place for immigrants”, and 50% think it is a “good place for gay and lesbian people” (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum

2022). These results suggest that younger generations are considerably more cosmopolitan and rights-oriented, a trend that may strengthen democratic norms and pluralism over time.

Relational capital is another strong point. About 80% of young Lithuanians positively evaluate opportunities to make friends and build social networks (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), indicating that interpersonal trust and peer connections remain robust. Such networks can play a crucial role in facilitating civic participation, shaping political attitudes, and promoting collective agency.

However, significant challenges persist on the educational and socioeconomic fronts. The share of early leavers from education or training stands at 10% among young men and 6.8% among young women (Eurostat 2024a). While these rates are lower than the EU average, they point to a gender gap that reflects structural inequalities in educational access and completion.

Overall, the youth landscape in Lithuania presents a dual picture. On the one hand, there is a clear orientation toward inclusion, openness to diversity, and strong relational networks, all of which are vital resources for democratic renewal. On the other hand, structural barriers in education, labor market entry, and social mobility continue to constrain the full realization of youth potential.

I.17.8 Being socialized in Lithuania

Being socialized in Lithuania means growing up in a stable democracy marked by persistent inequalities, uneven trust, and strong traditional expectations around gender. Caregiving is widely seen as a female responsibility, and authority within families is often associated with men. Younger generations show greater openness to diversity and equality, but resistance to feminism and doubts about women's credibility remain. Digital environments provide both opportunities for plural learning and exposure to misogynistic and exclusionary narratives. Consequently, masculine gender norms in Lithuania develop amid expanding egalitarian values and enduring expectations that prioritize strength, provision, and emotional reserve.

I.18 LUXEMBOURG

I.18.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Luxembourg’s socioeconomic landscape is characterized by a level of economic development far above the European average and a high degree of macroeconomic stability while displaying structural vulnerabilities and persistent internal disparities. GDP per capita in PPS places the country among the EU’s most advanced economies. This figure confirms an exceptional capacity to generate material well-being and a very high average income, even in a global context marked by economic shocks and structural transitions (Table 20).

Table 20 Socioeconomic conditions in Luxembourg compared with the EU27

	Luxembourg	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	242.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	30.4	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	20	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	94.1	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	80.1	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	69.5	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	90	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Despite this strong position, income distribution has some critical aspects. With a Gini index, above the European average, Luxembourg records slightly higher income inequality. At the same time, the share of the population at risk of poverty or social exclusion reveals the persistence of vulnerable segments. These data indicate a system capable of maintaining high living standards while containing, though not eliminating, inequality (Table 20).

The labor market confirms an overall positive picture but is marked by gender differences that remain significant. The employment rate among those aged 15–64 years is 72.1% for men and 67.2% for women (Eurostat 2024b). Although these values are close to or above the European average (75.3% and 66.2%, respectively), the gender gap continues to reflect imbalances in paid work and professional opportunities. This disparity has direct implications for women’s economic autonomy and contributes to the persistence of traditional labor market patterns.

This picture is corroborated by the EIGE Gender Equality Index, according to which Luxembourg scores 75.4 overall, clearly above the EU average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The money and work dimensions perform strongly, reflecting high female participation and strong earning capacity (Table 20). However, imbalances persist in the education system and labor market, as shown by the knowledge index, which highlights unequal distribution across fields of study and skills, and by vertical and horizontal segregation that still limits women's access to decision-making positions (Table 20). Early school leaving is 10.7% among boys and 7.3% among girls, revealing vulnerabilities that may influence social mobility and the quality of labor market entry (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographic structure is another salient factor. The old age dependency ratio is 21.7, which is significantly below the European average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e). This trend implies growing pressure on pension and welfare systems and calls for comprehensive intergenerational support policies. The foreign-born population (51%) is among the highest in Europe (Eurostat 2022), representing both a key driver of demographic and economic dynamism and a challenge to integration and social cohesion.

Finally, social expenditure equivalent to 24% of the GDP reflects a generous and comprehensive welfare model (OECD 2024b). This framework has helped mitigate inequality and cushion the effects of economic crises and labor market transformations. However, public support remains less effective in addressing emerging challenges, such as youth precariousness, population aging, and the reconciliation of work and family life. In sum, Luxembourg's socioeconomic and institutional structure combines very high levels of well-being and macroeconomic stability with persistent gender gaps, demographic challenges, and social vulnerabilities.

I.18.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Luxembourg presents a social and political environment strongly aligned with the core values of the EU, showing a particularly high commitment to democratic governance, individual freedoms, and the rule of law. According to Freedom House, the country achieves a maximum score of 97/100 for political rights and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025), while the EIU Democracy Index (8.88) (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024) confirms a consolidated liberal democracy with high institutional performance. Similarly, the

Rule of Law Index (0.83) and Civil Liberties (0.95) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) indicate a robust legal framework and strong protection of fundamental rights. These scores reflect not only the efficiency of public institutions but also a deeply rooted culture of legality and civic responsibility.

Public trust in representative institutions is comparatively high according to European standards. In 2024, 58% of Luxembourg citizens express trust in the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Political culture and participation patterns reveal a balanced ideological orientation and moderate polarization. Luxembourg's Government Coalition Left-Right Index stands at 0.69, placing the governing coalition near the political center (Varieties of Democracy 2024). This moderate positioning facilitates social cohesion and pragmatic policymaking.

Tolerance and social openness are defining features of Luxembourgish society. The Rainbow Europe Index (89/100) and the existence of comprehensive anti-hate and anti-discrimination laws (scores 66.67 and 100) (ILGA-Europe 2025) underscore a strong institutional commitment to equality irrespective of gender identity or sexual orientation. Its MIPEX score of 89 reflects a favorable approach to migrant integration (MIPEX 2023).

In sum, Luxembourg's European values profile is characterized by a deeply embedded democratic culture, robust institutional trust, and strong social inclusiveness. The country aligns closely with the EU's foundational principles of equality, liberty, and the rule of law. Nonetheless, residual adherence to traditional family norms and gender roles signals that the consolidation of gender equality in everyday practices remains an ongoing process within an otherwise highly liberal and democratic social order.

I.18.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Luxembourg display a complex dynamic in which clear openings toward equality coexist with persistent stereotypes that still shape the life courses of women and men in both the public and private spheres. On gender equality, the evidence is mixed. Luxembourg's overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 75.4, above the EU27 average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, the time dimension—care and domestic work—scores 62.8 (vs. 68.5 EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating that unpaid care still falls disproportionately on women. In contrast,

power—women’s presence in decision-making—stands at 68 (vs. 61.4 EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), reflecting comparatively strong representation in political and economic leadership.

Based on Eurobarometer data (Figure 41), family-role representations remain one of the domains in which traditional models are most visible (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Although these readings are near the EU average, they reveal a deeply rooted conception that still associates family care primarily with women’s responsibilities and implicitly questions the full compatibility of employment and motherhood.

Figure 41 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Luxembourg

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality in the workplace confirm this ambivalence. Around 55% of people in Luxembourg say that men are treated better than women at work, indicating a widespread acknowledgment of persistent structural discrimination (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, this awareness coexists with cultural views that continue to legitimize a gendered division of labor and family responsibilities.

Cultural ambivalence is also evident in the political sphere (Figure 41). On the one hand, there is broad support for gender balance in leadership. On the other hand, enduring stereotypes about women's competence and authority remain. These attitudes point to the persistence of symbolic biases about female leadership alongside the formal endorsement of equality.

Norms concerning masculinity show a similarly mixed picture. A very large majority (around 94%) in Luxembourg deem it acceptable for a man to cry (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)—signaling a loosening of traditional emotional stereotypes—but more rigid expectations persist. Meaningful minorities still consider that men who take parental leave show a lack of ambition for their career (6%), maintain that men should have the final say in important family decisions (9%), or view men as naturally less competent than women at housework (31%) (European Commission. Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Attitudes toward equality are further complicated by polarization around feminism. A noticeable share of respondents in Luxembourg (43%) agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Overall, these perceptions depict a society in which traditional models and new norms coexist and compete. On the one hand, substantial openings toward equality emerge—especially in support of gender-balanced leadership and in more flexible models of masculinity; on the other hand, cultural expectations still assign primary caregiving to women and decision-making/breadwinning roles to men. The idea that equality has already gone far enough suggests a risk of defensive reactions and a backlash against gender-equality policies. In sum, the landscape of gender norms and attitudes in Luxembourg is marked by a twofold movement: growing openings toward more egalitarian models coexist with the persistence of entrenched stereotypes, shaping social trajectories and setting the boundaries within which male and female identities are constructed.

I.18.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Luxembourg remains a structural and persistent challenge that undermines democratic quality and the full realization of fundamental rights. Despite a consolidated legal framework and an active institutional commitment to prevention and

protection, the data reveal that prevalence, awareness, and effective access to services still leave significant room for improvement.

According to the 2024 FRA/EU surveys, 47.4% of ever-partnered women in Luxembourg report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by an intimate partner since the age of 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Although this figure is below the EU27 average, it confirms that violence remains a widespread social phenomenon that cannot be regarded as marginal. When considering all perpetrators, 45.4% of women report having experienced at least one form of gender-based violence (any type) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), underscoring the diffuse nature of coercion and abuse across different life contexts.

Knowledge of and access to protection services also reveal important gaps. Among women—both victims and nonvictims—about 64.5% are aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), while only 24.1% know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This significant discrepancy between general and specific awareness of rights suggests that for many women, limited knowledge of concrete entitlements and procedures may hinder help-seeking and reduce the practical effectiveness of protection systems.

On the institutional side, Luxembourg has taken decisive steps to align national legislation with international standards. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on August 7, 2018, and entered it into force on December 1, (Council of Europe 2025). These milestones consolidated the national framework for the prevention, protection, and prosecution of gender-based violence, reinforcing coordination among judicial, social, and law enforcement institutions. However, the gap between formal commitments and lived experiences persists—the coexistence of moderate prevalence and the uneven awareness of rights indicate that implementation and accessibility of protection measures require further consolidation.

Overall, Luxembourg presents a complex picture. An advanced legal and institutional structure coexists with persistent manifestations of psychological and physical violence, limited awareness of legal entitlements, and a need to strengthen coordination between prevention, protection, and enforcement. Bridging this implementation gap—by enhancing rights knowledge, improving access to services, and strengthening rapid intervention

capacity—remains crucial to ensuring real safety, justice, and substantive gender equality for all women.

I.18.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides a valuable lens through which to examine the relationship among democracy, gender inequalities, and power distribution in Luxembourg. The resulting picture is that of a stable and institutionally consolidated democracy, characterized by strong civic engagement and high-quality governance but also by moderate polarization and limited trust in political elites.

Voter turnout represents the first indicator of democratic vitality. In the 2024 European elections, turnout in Luxembourg reached 82.29%, which was markedly above the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). This very high participation rate reflects the country's longstanding culture of civic engagement and the presence of compulsory voting, which fosters a consistent level of mobilization across the electorate.

In terms of gender representation, 33% of seats in the national parliament are held by women (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This result indicates a sustained commitment to gender parity in politics and reflects both institutional measures and cultural openness toward women's participation in public life. The configuration of Luxembourg's party system also offers insight into the broader political landscape. The 2018 national elections in Luxembourg produced a fragmented but balanced political landscape, confirming the country's tradition of coalition governance. The Christian Social People's Party (CSV) emerged once again as the largest political force, winning 27.1% of the vote. However, despite its plurality, the CSV remained in opposition, as the governing coalition was renewed among the center-left and liberal parties. The Democratic Party obtained 16.4%, maintaining a central role in coalition negotiations. The Luxembourg Socialist Workers' Party followed closely with 15.7%, while the Greens (déi Gréng) achieved a historic result, garnering 14.1% of the vote and consolidating their influence in progressive politics (ParlGov 2023).

Trust in political institutions, however, shows some nuances. According to Eurobarometer data (2024b), 45% express trust in political parties and 76% in the national government (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These values still suggest relatively stable confidence in representative institutions.

According to V-Dem, the level of political polarization stands at 0.91/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating a low-intensity polarization and a relatively consensual political culture. Power distribution by socioeconomic position is similarly balanced, with a score of 3.07/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), suggesting that although economic elites maintain notable influence, decision-making power remains broadly shared among social groups. Taken together, these elements outline a political environment characterized by stability, inclusiveness, and strong formal democracy. Luxembourg combines one of the highest electoral participation rates in the EU, with near-gender parity in representation, low polarization, and high democratic standards.

I.18.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is essential to understanding the processes of political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks associated with disinformation and radicalization. In Luxembourg, the online ecosystem is characterized by the extensive diffusion of digital technologies and high levels of internet use, accompanied by comparatively strong trust in online information but also by persistent vulnerabilities in media literacy and critical digital competences.

The use of digital platforms for news consumption is widespread. According to Eurobarometer, 59% of the population report reading news online every day, a figure above the EU average (43%) and indicative of the centrality of digital media in Luxembourg's public and political life (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a).

Trust in online information is mixed. Around 34% of Luxembourgers say they trust news found on the internet, while only 17% express trust in information disseminated through social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These values, well below the EU average (43% and 31%, respectively), indicate a more cautious and selective approach to digital information sources. This skepticism may reflect Luxembourg's high overall media literacy and the strong position of traditional outlets in the national information landscape, in which public broadcasting and multilingual press maintain significant authority.

The perception of disinformation as a democratic threat is widely shared. About 87% of respondents in Luxembourg consider disinformation a "serious problem for democracy",

slightly above the EU average (82%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, 28% report having been “often” or “very often” exposed to false or misleading content during the week preceding the survey (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). However, the ability to detect misinformation remains limited—only 11% feel “very confident” that they can identify fake news, while 56% say they can do so “only sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and analytical capacity indicates substantial room for improvement in civic and digital education.

Luxembourg’s digital environment therefore presents a dual configuration. On the one hand, internet and social media use provide broad opportunities for access to information, civic participation, and public debate, with levels of engagement and trust among the highest in the Union. On the other hand, the country remains exposed to the risks of disinformation and limited critical digital literacy.

In this context, Luxembourg faces a twofold challenge: strengthening citizens’ digital and critical competences, enhancing their ability to recognize and counter false or hostile content, and developing targeted prevention strategies against online spaces that propagate gendered hatred and anti-democratic narratives.

I.18.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial indicator of democratic resilience and a country’s capacity to ensure equal opportunities for new generations. In Luxembourg, the picture appears largely positive compared with the European average—particularly in relational terms and cultural openness—yet some fragilities persist in pathways to autonomy, education, and empowerment.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Luxembourg scores 87.54/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), placing it among the upper tier of EU countries. This value reflects a combination of solid material conditions, extensive welfare support, and strong perceptions of social inclusion. Nonetheless, it also points to domains in which structural constraints continue to affect the transition to adulthood.

A particularly positive aspect concerns openness to diversity. Data from the Youth Progress Index show that 91% of young people consider Luxembourg a “good place” for immigrants,

and 87% view it as a good place for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This openness is reinforced by relational cohesion—77% of youth positively evaluate opportunities to make friends and build social networks, signaling a high level of youth social capital and trust-based interaction (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). Together, these indicators depict a youth population characterized by strong relational integration and pronounced cultural tolerance.

On the educational front, Luxembourg also performs well, although not without gender asymmetries. The share of young men leaving education or training early is 10.7%, while among young women, it stands at 7.3% (Eurostat 2024a). Both figures are below the EU averages (11% and 7.3%, respectively), indicating a comparatively effective educational system. However, persistent differences between boys and girls still point to structural inequalities in access to and continuity of schooling.

Socioeconomic inclusion presents a more complex picture. While Luxembourg's youth benefit from a robust welfare state and favorable living standards, access to stable employment and affordable housing remains a challenge—particularly for those outside the dual-education system or from migrant backgrounds. This tension between material well-being and structural obstacles underscores the complexity of youth trajectories in a high-income yet unequal context.

Overall, Luxembourg's youth display a strong openness to diversity, solid relational networks, and a cultural orientation toward inclusion. At the same time, they face barriers linked to labor market segmentation, gender inequality, and limited social mobility. The country's ability to sustain democratic resilience will therefore depend on its capacity to strengthen pathways to empowerment and autonomy for all young people, ensuring that inclusion translates into equitable opportunities across generations.

I.18.8 Being socialized in Luxembourg

Being socialized in Luxembourg means growing up in a small, prosperous, and institutionally stable state with high trust and strong welfare provisions. Everyday life unfolds within a multilingual, multicultural setting in which opportunities are abundant, but social spheres are sometimes segmented. Gender equality is advanced institutionally, but unpaid care remains uneven, and educational and occupational segregation persist. Attitudes combine

commitment to balanced leadership with subtle traditional expectations of ambition and caregiving. Digital media use is widespread, and concern about disinformation is high. Overall, masculine gender norms in Luxembourg emerge from the interplay between egalitarian aspirations and enduring, often understated, gendered expectations.

I.19 MALTA

I.19.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

The socioeconomic structure of Malta reveals the characteristics of a high income but internally unbalanced economy, marked by strong employment performance, rapid modernization, and persistent gender and social inequalities. The country combines a dynamic service-based system with comparatively low poverty risk but faces challenges in equality of opportunities and labor market segmentation.

Table 21 Socioeconomic conditions in Malta compared with the EU27

	Malta	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	109.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	31.8	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	19.7	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	84.8	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	81.0	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	71.4	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	87.9	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

According to Eurostat, Malta's GDP per capita in PPSs places the country slightly above the European average. The Gini coefficient, above the EU average, indicates comparatively high income inequality despite overall prosperity. The share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion is marginally below the EU27 rate (Table 21).

Employment outcomes are generally strong. In 2024, the employment rate among men (15–64) reached 85.4%, and among women, it reached 72.3% (Eurostat 2024b), both clearly above the EU averages (75.3% and 66.2%, respectively). These data underscore Malta's

robust labor market and the country's progress in female employment—a key dimension of gender equality in work (Table 21).

Education and skill composition reflect both strengths and enduring divides. However, it still shows horizontal segregation, with 40.2% of tertiary students enrolled in education, health, welfare, humanities, and arts—a concentration higher than the EU average (54.5%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), suggesting a narrower field distribution. Gender gaps persist in STEM disciplines, where women remain underrepresented (7.4 per 1,000 population aged 20–29 versus 15.5 in the EU) (Eurostat 2023b). Early school leaving is a continuing issue—11.7% of young men and 7.1% of young women leave education or training early (Eurostat 2024a).

The demographic profile highlights the pressures and advantages. The old age dependency ratio is 26.5%, below the EU average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e), suggesting a comparatively young population structure. Meanwhile, foreign-born residents account for 30.8% of the population (Eurostat 2022), one of the highest proportions in Europe. This demographic openness sustains the labor supply and contributes to economic dynamism, although it also poses challenges of social integration and housing affordability.

Taken together, Malta's socioeconomic structure combines sustained growth and high employment with persistent inequalities and a constrained welfare system. The country performs well in terms of material living standards and gender convergence in work, but gaps remain in income distribution, educational inclusion, and the balance between market dynamism and social protection. Strengthening redistribution, investing in skills diversification, and improving access to social services would help consolidate the social foundations of Malta's economic success.

1.19.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

The system of values in Malta reflects a dynamic interplay between strong attachment to European integration, traditional moral orientations, and gradual convergence toward more liberal and egalitarian norms. The country combines high levels of identification with the European project and trust in its institutions with persistent ambivalence regarding gender equality, family roles, and moral individualism.

According to the Eurobarometer, 72% of Maltese respondents express trust in the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These figures illustrate a strong pro-European orientation and a perception of the EU as a guarantor of stability, rights, and democratic standards.

Civic attachment is accompanied by substantial endorsement of democratic principles. According to Freedom House, Malta scores 87/100 on the Freedom in the World Index (Freedom House 2025), confirming its status as a consolidated democracy with robust civil liberties and effective institutions. Similarly, the Democracy Index assigns the country 7.93 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), situating it within the category of “full democracies”. The Rule of Law Index yields 0.67 (World Justice Project 2024), indicating functional judicial guarantees. Together, these data portray a system characterized by institutional solidity and widespread formal adherence to democratic norms.

According to data, Malta shows a SIGI score of 19.4 (OECD 2023b), the country shows relatively low levels of institutional discrimination, although traditional social norms still limit the achievement of full gender equality. Its MIPEX score of 63 (MIPEX 2023) reflects a generally favorable approach to migrant integration but with room for improvement in implementation and civic participation. In contrast, Malta stands out in the institutional protection of LGBTIQ+ rights, achieving 100/100 for hate speech and hate crime legislation and 89/100 on the Rainbow Europe Index (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Overall, Malta’s value system mirrors a society that is both deeply European and locally traditional. Strong trust in EU institutions, high levels of civic participation, and progressive legal frameworks coexist with enduring cultural conservatism and gendered moral codes. This tension between modernity and tradition—between institutional progress and social inertia—defines Malta’s distinctive position within the European landscape of values.

I.19.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Malta show a mixed configuration, in which openings toward equality coexist with elements of traditionalism that still orient everyday practices in both the public and private spheres. On gender equality, the evidence is ambivalent. Malta’s overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 70.1, close to the EU27 average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The time dimension—care and domestic work—is 59.4

(vs. 68.5 EU), indicating that unpaid care remains disproportionately borne by women. In contrast, power—women’s presence in decision-making—stands at 51.2 (vs. 61.4 EU) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling progress but also persistent underrepresentation in top positions—money (84.8) and work (81.0) point to comparatively strong participation and earning capacity, while knowledge (71.4) highlights enduring horizontal segregation across fields of study and skills (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

In Malta, attitudes toward masculinity and gender roles reflect a combination of progressive emotional norms and persistent traditional beliefs about family and politics. A striking 92% of respondents agree that it is acceptable for men to cry, well above the EU average of 85% (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), indicating a clear relaxation of emotional stereotypes and a growing acceptance of more open expressions of masculinity.

However, this shift coexists with enduring gendered expectations in other domains. Only 10% of Maltese respondents think that men should have the final say in important family decisions (vs. 20% in the EU) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), showing a relatively low endorsement of overt patriarchal authority. However, 44% believe that men are naturally less competent than women in performing household tasks, a figure close to the EU average (49%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), suggesting the persistence of cultural assumptions about gendered domestic competence.

When it comes to work and family balance, Eurobarometer data reflect a continued internalization of the male breadwinner model and limited normalization of paternal caregiving roles (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024) (Figure 42).

Figure 42 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Malta

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

In the public sphere, gendered perceptions of ambition and equality remain rooted (Figure 42)—61% believe that “feminism has gone too far” (vs. 45% in the EU) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These data depict a social context where emotional openness among men coexists with entrenched structural and symbolic asymmetries between genders—highlighting both progress in redefining masculinity and persistent resistance to broader gender equality narratives. In sum, Malta’s landscape of gender norms is marked by a dual movement: clear openings toward egalitarian models of participation and leadership go hand in hand with the resilience of traditional family roles and persistent stereotypes.

I.19.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Malta remains a structural and persistent problem that undermines the realization of equality and the effective protection of women’s rights. Despite a comprehensive legal framework and progress in institutional coordination, prevalence levels and awareness gaps indicate that violence continues to affect a significant share of women’s lives.

According to FRA/EU data, 24.5% of ever-partnered women in Malta report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by an intimate partner since the age of 15—a proportion slightly below the EU27 average (30.7%) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Looking beyond intimate relationships, 26% of women report having experienced at least one form of violence by any perpetrator (any type) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures highlight that coercion, control, and aggression remain widespread experiences across different spheres of women’s lives.

Knowledge of and access to support services reveal mixed results. Among women (victims and non-victims), 89.4% are aware of the existence of support service (Eurostat 2021b), while only 35% know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). The wide gap between general awareness and knowledge of specific rights suggests that many victims may not fully understand the legal and procedural tools available to them, which can delay or prevent help-seeking, particularly among the most vulnerable.

On the legal and institutional front, Malta has taken important steps in line with European and international standards. The country signed the Istanbul Convention on May 21, 2012, ratified it on July 29, 2014, and entered it into force domestically on November 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). Implementation has included the creation of specialized support services, national action plans, and awareness campaigns. However, persistent uneven access to justice indicates that formal alignment with European frameworks has not yet translated into full material protection and social transformation.

While progress in institutional measures is evident, cultural barriers, underreporting, and limited awareness of legal rights continue to weaken prevention and protection efforts. In sum, Malta’s situation is characterized by a consolidated legal system and growing institutional attention but also by persistently high prevalence, incomplete rights awareness, and non-negligible levels of lethal violence. Bridging the implementation gap—through expanded legal literacy, stronger victim support, and targeted prevention programs—remains essential to ensuring substantive safety, justice, and gender equality for all women.

I.19.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Malta offers an instructive example of the interaction among democratic consolidation, limited political pluralism, and a gradually improving—yet still incomplete—gender balance in representation. The Maltese system combines strong institutional stability and very high civic participation with structural vulnerabilities linked to polarization, limited trust, and persistent gender gaps in political power.

Voter turnout is among the highest in Europe. In the 2024 European elections, participation reached 73%, compared with the EU27 average of 51% (European Parliament 2024). This remarkable level of civic mobilization reflects both the small scale of the polity and the intensity of party identification that has historically characterized Maltese democracy.

Gender representation has improved over the past decade but remains below parity. Women hold 28% of seats in the national parliament, compared to a European average of 33% (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This indicates that decision-making structures continue to display male predominance, especially in ministerial and senior executive posts.

The 2022 national elections in Malta confirmed the dominance of the Labour Party (Partit Laburista), which secured a clear majority, with 55.1% of the popular vote. The Nationalist Party (Partit Nazzjonalista) remained the main opposition force, obtaining 41.7% of the vote (ParlGov 2023). This result consolidated the Labour Party's governing position, reflecting continuity in voter support and the relative stability of Malta's traditional two-party system. The electoral outcome also highlighted the persistence of a highly polarized yet stable political landscape, in which the Labour Party maintains a consistent advantage in both vote share and seat distribution.

Democratic quality remains high in comparative terms. Malta scores 0.79 on the V-Dem Electoral Democracy Index (Varieties of Democracy 2024), confirming a robust system of electoral competition, judicial independence, and checks and balances.

According to V-Dem, Malta's level of political polarization is 2.82/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating a system with significant ideological and affective divisions, partly reflecting entrenched two-party competition. The distribution of power by socioeconomic position (score 2.89/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) suggests that influence remains concentrated among upper social groups, with limited access to working-class and peripheral actors.

Levels of institutional trust in Malta show a moderate but meaningful differentiation between the political and governmental spheres. In 2024, 34% of respondents declared that they tend to trust political parties, while 47% expressed trust in the national government (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

This pattern suggests that while confidence in representative institutions remains relatively limited—reflecting a degree of public skepticism toward party politics—citizens maintain comparatively greater faith in the executive’s capacity to act effectively. The gap between party and government trust mirrors broader European trends but also points to a context in which governance performance may be perceived as more reliable than political mediation itself.

In sum, Malta’s political system is characterized by exceptional participation, stable democratic institutions, and growing but incomplete gender inclusion. However, it is also marked by enduring two-party polarization, modest trust in politicians, and a concentration of political power. These dynamics create a delicate balance between institutional robustness and civic fragility—where democratic commitment remains strong, but confidence and pluralism require renewed support to sustain an inclusive and resilient democracy.

I.19.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension represents an increasingly central component of socialization and political communication in Malta, shaping how citizens access information, form opinions, and engage in civic debate. The Maltese digital landscape is characterized by the widespread use of online media, relatively high trust in digital content, and growing awareness of the risks associated with disinformation and radicalization—particularly in relation to gender and democracy.

The use of digital platforms for news is extensive. According to Eurobarometer, 51% of Maltese report reading news online every day, a level broadly consistent with the EU27 average (43%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). The prevalence of digital news consumption reflects both Malta’s high internet penetration and its compact media ecosystem, in which online outlets complement traditional broadcast channels.

In Malta, trust in online information sources is significantly lower than the EU average, reflecting a cautious and selective approach to digital media. Only 38% of respondents report that they tend to trust information from websites, compared to 43% across the EU, while an even smaller share—just 21%—express trust in social networks (vs. 31% in the EU) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

These data suggest a relatively skeptical information environment in which citizens are more likely to question the reliability of online content, particularly on social platforms. This lower level of confidence could be interpreted as a form of critical distance, signaling awareness of disinformation risks and the limits of algorithm-driven news exposure.

At the same time, it may also reflect a lack of alternative trusted sources or lower overall engagement with digital media. In either case, Malta’s cautious stance highlights a population that is more resistant to unverified information flows—a potential asset for democratic resilience, provided it is accompanied by ongoing investment in digital literacy and quality journalism.

Awareness of the threat of disinformation is widespread. Around 81% of Maltese respondents consider false or misleading news a serious problem for democracy, in line with the EU average (82%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Around 29% report having been “often” or “very often” exposed to misleading or false content during the week preceding the survey (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). However, only 20% feel “very confident” in recognizing fake news, while 59% say they can do so “only sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This mismatch between awareness and critical capacity highlights persistent gaps in digital and media literacy, particularly among older cohorts and less-educated users.

The phenomenon of online radicalization represents a growing concern, including in relation to gendered hostility. Although Malta has not been identified as a hub of extremist digital activity, analyses by Moonshot for the European Commission reveal the presence of Maltese users interacting with “manosphere”-related communities, including incel and anti-feminist online spaces (2 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These environments, while numerically small, propagate misogynist, anti-

egalitarian, and sometimes anti-democratic narratives, thereby contributing to the broader dynamics of cultural polarization and hostility toward gender equality.

Overall, Malta's digital environment displays a dual configuration. On the one hand, the internet provides wide access to information, opportunities for civic engagement, and channels for public debate. On the other hand, exposure to disinformation, limited media literacy, and the diffusion of anti-feminist rhetoric online introduce tangible risks to democratic resilience and gender equality.

I.19.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion represents a crucial indicator of democratic vitality and a society's capacity to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Malta, the overall picture appears favorable when compared with the European average, especially in terms of relational cohesion, cultural openness, and civic participation. Nonetheless, structural barriers persist in access to education, employment, and full socioeconomic autonomy.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Malta scores 84.91/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), placing it in the upper range of European countries. This value reflects a combination of solid material living conditions, high levels of social trust, and a generally inclusive civic environment. Youth in Malta benefit from strong welfare coverage and close-knit community networks that foster belonging and social protection, even during transitions to adulthood.

A particularly positive aspect concerns openness to diversity and inclusion. Data show that Maltese youth overwhelmingly evaluate their country as a welcoming environment—83% of respondents consider Malta a “good place for immigrants”, and 91% describe it as a “good place for gay and lesbian people” 100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These figures—significantly above EU averages—illustrate a younger generation as more cosmopolitan and tolerant than the general population, which bodes well for the long-term consolidation of democratic and egalitarian values.

The relational dimension is equally strong. Around 80% of young people report positive opportunities for friendship and social networks, a sign of robust youth social capital and of a society in which informal ties and solidarity remain central to collective life. These indicators

also highlight Malta's dense associational fabric, in which family and peer relations play a major role in emotional and social integration.

However, challenges persist in education and in the transition to work. The share of early school leavers (aged 18–24 years) stands at 11.7% for men and 7.1% for women (Eurostat 2024a). Although these figures are in line with the European average, they reveal enduring gender differences and the continuing difficulty of ensuring that all young men complete secondary or post-secondary education.

In sum, Malta's youth landscape combines notable strengths with persistent structural fragilities. On the one hand, young Maltese benefit from a socially cohesive and inclusive environment marked by openness to diversity, dense relational networks, and above-average well-being. On the other hand, socioeconomic barriers, gendered inequalities in educational and labor outcomes, and limited mobility opportunities hinder full empowerment.

I.19.8 Being socialized in Malta

Being socialized in Malta means growing up in a democracy with exceptionally high participation, strong community ties, and longstanding partisan traditions. Gender equality in education and employment has improved, but attitudes show ambivalence—emotional expressiveness in men is accepted, while hierarchical ideas about ambition, leadership, and feminism remain widespread. Family and religious institutions continue to shape expectations, reinforcing conventional gender divisions. Digital use is high, although trust in online content is low. Within this environment, masculine gender norms in Malta often combine emotional openness with traditional notions of authority, responsibility, and protection.

I.20 THE NETHERLANDS

I.20.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

The Netherlands combines a level of economic development well above the EU average with strong macroeconomic stability while still displaying some structural vulnerabilities and internal disparities. The GDP per capita in PPSs places the country among the EU's most advanced economies. Income distribution is comparatively equal. At the same time, the share

of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion, markedly under the EU rate, evidence of a system that contains vulnerability even if it does not eliminate it (Table 22).

Table 22 Socioeconomic conditions in the Netherlands compared with the EU27

	The Netherlands	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	136.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	24.8	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	15.4	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	87.9	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	79.8	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	70.3	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	93.4	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is robust and highly participatory. Among those aged 15–64 years, 85.7% of men and 78.9% of women are employed—both well above EU averages. This pattern is mirrored in the EIGE Gender Equality Index, with very strong scores in money and work (Table 22). However, imbalances persist in education and occupational structure—the knowledge dimension stands at 70.3 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), early school leaving is 8.8% for boys and 5.2% for girls (Eurostat 2024a), and horizontal segregation across fields of study and jobs remains visible.

Demography adds mixed pressures. The old age dependency ratio is 31.8 (slightly below the EU average of 33.9) (Eurostat 2024e). A high foreign-born share (24.6%) (Eurostat 2022) fuels demographic and economic dynamism but also demands sustained integration policies. Territorial structure is overwhelmingly urban—only about 0.6% of residents live in areas classified as rural (OECD 2023a)—which can create service and infrastructure asymmetries for less-dense regions.

Social protection is sizable but not lavish by EU standards—social expenditure is about 18.9% of the GDP (OECD 2024b). This welfare model has cushioned shocks and labor market transitions, but it faces emerging challenges linked to aging, youth precariousness, educational segmentation, and work–family reconciliation.

In sum, the Netherlands couples broad-based prosperity, high employment, and resilient institutions with lingering gender and educational segmentation and demographic pressures.

Strengthening skills diversification, tackling horizontal segregation, and deepening inclusion policies are key to sustaining inclusive and sustainable growth.

I.20.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

The Netherlands stands out as a consolidated liberal democracy anchored in the rule of law and robust civil liberties. Freedom in the World rates the country 97/100 (“Free”) (Freedom House 2025), while the EIU Democracy Index places it firmly among full democracies at 9/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). The Rule of Law Index is 0.83 (World Justice Project 2024), and V-Dem’s civil-liberties score reaches 0.91 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating strong protections for rights and effective institutional checks.

On gender equality, the Dutch profile is clearly above the EU average but not free of asymmetries. The Gender Equality Index totals 78.8 (EU27: 71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Power is comparatively strong (75.3), reflecting women’s presence in political and economic decision-making, and time (76.9) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) suggests a more balanced sharing of unpaid care than in most EU countries—although gaps persist in everyday practice.

Policies of inclusion and pluralism are among the country’s strengths. The MIPEX score is 85 (MIPEX 2023), signaling a favorable framework for migrant integration. Protection of LGBTIQ+ rights is extensive—hate speech and hate crime provisions are high (46 and 34), and the Rainbow Europe Index is 64/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Public attitudes toward the EU are broadly supportive. About 46% of Dutch respondents report trust in the European Parliament, a mid–high level in the EU context and consistent with the country’s longstanding pro-European orientation.

In sum, the Netherlands couples very high democratic standards and rule-of-law performance with advanced equality and inclusion regimes. The remaining challenges concern translating formal parity into everyday practices—especially around care and work—while sustaining high social trust and inclusive citizenship in an increasingly diverse society.

I.20.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in the Netherlands show a strongly egalitarian profile according to EU standards, but some traditional expectations still shape everyday life—

especially around care and family roles. Family-role views are comparatively progressive. Only 3% agree that “men should have the final say in important family decisions”, and a minority endorse male-breadwinner reflexes; still, about 41% think that if the father earns less than the mother, he should be the one to stop working to care for children, signaling that economic hierarchies can reactivate conventional role assignments (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, stereotypes about domestic roles are present, as shown in Figure 43 (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 43 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in the Netherlands

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality at work remain ambivalent. Support for gender-balanced leadership is high, and the Gender Equality Index places the Netherlands well above the EU average (total 78.8; Time 76.9; Power 75.3) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), indicating comparatively balanced sharing of unpaid work and a solid female presence in decision-making. However, a nontrivial minority still endorses symbolic biases, pointing to pockets of cultural resistance (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Norms around masculinity are notably liberal. An overwhelming 95% say it is acceptable for men to cry, suggesting broad rejection of restrictive emotional norms and support for more expressive, nonhegemonic masculinities.

Among men, support for letting gays and lesbians ‘live as they wish’ increases with age: 23.2% among those under 35, 32.1% among those aged 36–55, and 44.7% among those aged 56 or above. However, outright disagreement is also more common in the older cohort (15.0% among men under 35 compared with 40.0–45.0% among those aged 56 or above). Women show a similar rise in agreement (from 26.4 percent to 42.9 percent), but older women shift more into the “neither agree nor disagree” camp (26.1% under 35 to 39.1% over), signaling ambivalence rather than open rejection.

Generational splits are sharper on gender-hostile items. Regarding the claim that women exaggerate sexual harassment, men who say “often/always” jump from 27.8% (under 35) to 50.5% (over), with “sometimes” also climbing (18.2% to 51.5%). Women move in the same direction—“often/always” rises from 13.6% to 53.9% and “sometimes” from 17.9% to 50.6%—while “never/rarely” falls (e.g., 43.7% to 26.2% among women).

The idea that women seek power by controlling men shows the same age pattern. Men answering “often/always” increase from 23.2% to 44.9% across cohorts, while women answering “often/always” increase from 17.3% to 40.3% (with a mid-life peak at 42.4% “often/always”). “Never/rarely” diminishes steadily for both sexes.

“Women should be protected by men” reflects a generational drift toward benevolent sexism. Men endorsing “often/always” rise from 20.2% (under 35) to 45.9% (over), and women endorsing “often/always” rise from 24.9% to 43.9%. Even so, rejection remains substantial in every cohort—“never/rarely” sits around 28–43% for men and 30–38% for women—showing that protective norms are contested rather than consensual (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Across genders, Dutch attitudes are strikingly liberal but not free of tensions. Support for the idea that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish is near-universal for both men and women and grows slightly with age. Among men, it rises from about 89% (≤ 35) to 95% (over), and among women, it rises from 96% to 96%+. On sexual harassment claims, women are consistently more skeptical of the “exaggeration” trope than men—62% of young women

say such claims are never or rarely exaggerated (vs. 52% of young men), but this restraint weakens with age—only 24% of women over say “never/rarely” (men 30%). A similar pattern appears on the idea that women “seek power by controlling men”—both sexes move from “sometimes” as the modal answer in youth to higher shares of “sometimes/often” with age; For women, 57% of those aged 35 or below choose ‘sometimes’, rising to 65% among those aged 56 or above; ‘often/always’ is also higher for women than for men in midlife (39% vs. 17%). Finally, “women should be protected by men” reveals a classic benevolent-sexism gap—young men are split (50% “never/rarely” and 18.5% “often/always”), while young women are notably more accepting of protection norms (36.5% ‘often/always’, rising to 40% among those aged 56 or above)(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In short, both men and women in the Netherlands strongly endorse LGBTQ freedom, but age and gender still shape views on harassment, power, and protection—with women less prone to dismiss harassment but more inclined than men to accept protective roles, especially in older cohorts.

Taken together, the Dutch pattern is one of high formal and cultural endorsements of equality with residual situational traditionalism—especially where care, earnings, and family decision-making intersect. The overall trajectory is egalitarian, but converting progressive attitudes into fully shared care practices and eliminating the last islands of symbolic bias remains an open task.

I.20.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in the Netherlands remains a structural challenge that continues to undermine equality and the effective protection of fundamental rights. Despite a comprehensive legal framework and an advanced welfare system, the persistence of intimate partner violence and the limited awareness of specific rights reveal an implementation gap between formal commitments and lived experiences.

According to the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (2024), 41.2% of women aged 18–74 years in the Netherlands report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Violence within intimate relationships remains a key concern—33.4% of ever-partnered women declare having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual

violence from a partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures are above the EU27 average (31% and 32%, respectively), confirming the structural nature of gender-based violence and the persistence of coercive and controlling behaviors within domestic and intimate settings.

Knowledge of and access to protection services present an uneven picture. Awareness of support services among women victims and nonvictims reaches 95.3% (Eurostat 2021b), while only 33.7% are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). This discrepancy points to a gap between general knowledge of available assistance and concrete awareness of legal entitlements, which can hinder help-seeking and weaken the overall effectiveness of protection measures.

The most severe outcomes of gender-based violence also require attention. The intentional homicide rate of female victims killed by a partner or family member stands at 0.27 per 100,000 inhabitants, which is below the EU average but is still indicative of the persistence of lethal violence in relational contexts (Eurostat 2023c). This underlines the need for continued investment in early detection and coordinated prevention.

The Netherlands has long aligned itself with international standards for combating gender-based violence. It signed the Istanbul Convention on November 14, 2012, ratified it on November 18, 2015, and entered it into force on March 1, 2016 (Council of Europe 2025). The country has established specialized shelters, helplines, and local intervention networks, but national reports still highlight gaps in coordination, data collection, and accessibility for migrant and minority women.

Overall, the Dutch context combines a strong legal and institutional foundation with persistent manifestations of psychological and physical violence and a limited awareness of rights. Bridging this implementation gap—through improved rights communication, better coordination across agencies, and sustained preventive work on the cultural and structural roots of violence—remains crucial to ensuring real safety, justice, and substantive equality for all women.

I.20.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in the Netherlands shows a consolidated liberal–democratic system with strong rule-of-law guarantees and comparatively high confidence in executive

institutions, alongside signs of fragmentation and selective trust in party politics. Voter participation in the 2024 European elections was 46.2%, below the EU27 average (51%) (European Parliament 2024), signaling moderate mobilization at the EU level relative to typically higher national turnouts. Women's descriptive representation is robust by EU standards—about 40% of members of the Lower House are women, reflecting steady—even if incomplete—progress toward parity. Trust patterns are differentiated—34% of residents say they tend to trust the national government, while 43% tend to trust political parties.

In the Netherlands' 2021 general election, the center-right liberal People's Party for Freedom and Democracy remained the largest force, with 21.9% of the vote. The liberal-progressive Democrats 66 secured 15.0% of the vote, consolidating its role as the main pro-EU, socially liberal counterweight. On the radical right, the Party for Freedom secured 10.8% of the vote, reflecting enduring support for nativist anti-immigration positions. The Christian Democratic Appeal secured 9.5% of the vote, anchoring the confessional center-right (ParlGov 2023). Together, these results underscore the Netherlands' fragmented multiparty landscape and the necessity of broad cross-ideological coalitions to form a stable government.

Attitudinally, views are mixed—29% judge “a strong leader who doesn't have to bother with parliament or elections” as very bad, about 25% see it as fairly good, and 6.3% view it as very good (Haerpfer et al. 2024). Polarization is present—V-Dem estimates it at 2.22/4—and influence leans toward higher socioeconomic groups, although less than in many peers (power distribution by socioeconomic position 1.29/4, i.e., relatively diffuse) (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

Generational and gender differences structure the political space, with women clustering at the center more than men at every age. Around 50% of young women (≤ 35) identify with the center compared with 44% of young men; in midlife, the shares are 55% for women and 51% for men, and among older groups, the shares are about 60% for women and 49% for men. Men maintain a thicker right-hand tail, with 27–29% identifying with the right across age groups, compared with 16–20% of women. The far right remains small overall but is consistently higher among men (around 3–4%) than among women (1–2%). On the left, young women outpace young men (27% vs. 20% on the left and 5.8% vs. 4.7% on the far left), while among older respondents, men slightly exceed women on the far left (4.5% vs. 3.5%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Age tends to pull both genders toward the center, most notably among women. For women, centrism rises from roughly 50% in youth to 55% in midlife and 60% among older groups, while left-wing identification declines from 27% to 22% and 15%. Right-wing alignment grows modestly from 16.5% to 17.5% and 19.9%, and far-right support increases slightly from 1.0% to 1.6% and 2.1%. For men, the center shares move from 44% in youth to 51% in midlife and 49% in older groups, right-wing identification fluctuates between 25.6% and 28.7%, the left shifts from 20.0% to 15.5% and back to 17.1%, and the far-right share remains stable at around 3–4% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, the distribution recenters with age, but the gender profile remains consistent—women gravitate more toward center-left positions, while men are more likely to align with center-right and far-right orientations.

Taken together, the Netherlands couples high-quality democratic institutions and near-parity representation with fragmented party competition and selective trust (stronger for government and EU bodies than for parties). This configuration sustains governance capacity but also poses ongoing challenges for party system legitimacy and for building stable majorities in an increasingly plural and polarized landscape.

I.20.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is central to political socialization and opinion formation in the Netherlands, combining very high connectivity with selective trust and clear concerns about disinformation.

The use of digital platforms for news is widespread—65% of Dutch residents report reading news online every day, signaling the centrality of digital media in public and political (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Trust patterns, however, are cautious—46% say they tend to trust information found on websites, while only 19% express trust in content circulating on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). This gap points to a relatively skeptical stance toward algorithm-driven feeds and a preference for more curated online sources.

Awareness of the democratic risks of misinformation is very high—87% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, about 12% report having been

often/very often exposed to false or misleading content in the week prior to the survey (European Parliament, Brussels 2022b). However, confidence in detection remains modest—only 8% feel “very confident” that they can recognize disinformation, while most report only occasional confidence (52%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022b)—evidence of a skills gap that civic and media literacy policies still need to address.

Online radicalization merits attention. Research for the European Commission has identified Dutch activity within misogynist “manosphere” spaces (e.g., incels.is, with around 39 Netherlands-linked accounts over 2017–2020) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These communities entwine hostility toward women’s rights with anti-democratic narratives, creating potential vectors for gendered polarization.

Overall, the Netherlands’ digital environment has a dual face: the internet enables broad information access and participation, but exposure to disinformation, low trust in social-platform content, and the presence (even if limited) of misogynist networks pose tangible risks for deliberative quality and gender equality.

1.20.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key barometer of democratic resilience and equal opportunity. In the Netherlands, the overall picture is favorable by European standards. Young people grow up in a materially secure, highly connected society with broad exposure to diversity and comparatively strong avenues for participation. Survey composites such as the Youth Progress Index place the country among the EU’s upper tier, reflecting solid living conditions and positive perceptions of inclusion. Youth indicators paint a broadly inclusive and well-equipped rising generation. In 2022, 92% of young women (25–29) had completed 12–18 years of education (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), pointing to near-universal upper-secondary/tertiary attainment and a strong foundation for economic autonomy. Attitudinally, youth show high openness and equality norms. Around 90% report openness toward immigrants, and around 90% express acceptance of gays and lesbians, while around 80% say they have good opportunities to make friends (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)—evidence of dense social capital that can ease integration and reduce isolation. Taken together, these figures suggest a cohort primed for democratic

participation and social cohesion; the policy challenge is to translate these assets into equal access to quality jobs and housing so that inclusive attitudes become inclusive outcomes.

Relationally, Dutch youth benefit from dense peer networks and everyday contact in multicultural settings—unsurprising in a country where foreign-born residents make up 24.6% of the population—factors that typically nurture openness and civic trust.

On the educational front, outcomes are strong but not free of gendered gaps. Early school leaving (18–24) is 8.8% among young men and 5.2% among young women (Eurostat 2024a), both better than EU averages but still signaling unequal risks of disengagement at the end of lower-secondary or during upper-secondary transitions.

Taken together, Dutch youth display strong social capital and everyday intercultural contact alongside solid educational performance, especially for girls. However, barriers remain—a persistent male disadvantage in early-leaving segmented entry routes into work and affordability pressures that complicate independent living. Sustaining high inclusion will require continued investment in the prevention of dropout, quality apprenticeships, and stable early-career jobs, as well as housing policies that make the transition to adulthood genuinely attainable for all.

I.20.8 Being socialized in the Netherlands

Being socialized in the Netherlands means growing up in a high-trust, rule-of-law democracy that emphasizes pluralism and autonomy. Gender equality is widely endorsed, with strong female economic participation, although expectations around caregiving and ambition continue to influence everyday choices. The political culture is coalition-oriented, fostering negotiation and moderation. Digital participation is intense, with cautious trust and widespread concern about disinformation; niche misogynistic communities occasionally gain visibility. Accordingly, masculine gender norms in the Netherlands develop within a setting that promotes balance and tolerance while still negotiating residual hierarchies linked to care, decisiveness, and public ambition.

I.21 POLAND

I.21.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Poland’s socioeconomic profile combines solid macro-stability with middling prosperity and some longstanding structural divides. The GDP per capita in PPSs is well below the EU average in material living standards. Income dispersion is comparatively low and the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion is 16%, suggesting that vulnerability is contained even if not eliminated (Table 23).

Table 23 Socioeconomic conditions in Poland compared with the EU27

	Poland	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	79.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	25	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	16	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	79.7	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	69.9	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	60.3	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	84.8	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is tight but gendered—employment among 15–64-year-olds reaches 77.8% for men and 67.2% for women (Eurostat 2024b). The EIGE Gender Equality Index shows weaker outcomes in economic domains (money and work) (Table 23).

Education sends mixed signals. Early school leaving is very low (4.8% men and 3.4% women), and STEM output is slightly above the EU average (16.1 graduates per 1,000 aged 20–29 years) (Eurostat 2024a). However, the knowledge dimension remains subdued (60.3) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and tertiary choices are strongly segregated (53.3% of students concentrated in education/health/welfare/humanities/arts), reinforcing horizontal and vertical divides that later echo in pay and careers. Demographically, pressures are rising but manageable—the old age dependency ratio is 31.8 (near the EU average) (Eurostat 2024e). A large rural share (34.8%) (OECD 2023a) and very low foreign-born population (2.6%) (Eurostat 2022) point to dispersed settlement patterns and limited migration-driven dynamism—both relevant for access to services, skills attraction, and long-term growth.

The governmental investment on welfare is moderate (23.1% of the GDP) (OECD 2024b), cushioning shocks but leaving scope to bolster family supports, active aging, and work–care reconciliation. In sum, Poland pairs low inequality, strong basic schooling, and stable employment with below-EU prosperity, a persistent gender gap in work, pay, power, and territorial-demographic constraints. Reducing skill segregation, strengthening women’s economic security and leadership, and investing in rural inclusion and care infrastructure will be central to more inclusive and sustainable growth.

I.21.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Poland presents a value profile of a consolidated—although not flawless—liberal democracy. In 2024, it scores 84/100 on Freedom in the World (“Free”) (Freedom House 2025), while the Democracy Index stands at 7.4/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). Rule-of-law performance is 0.66 (World Justice Project 2024) and V-Dem’s civil-liberties index is 0.9 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), together depicting solid protections for rights alongside areas where judicial independence, checks and balances, and equal access to justice face pressure.

On gender equality, the picture is clearly below the EU average. Poland’s overall score on the Gender Equality Index is 63.4 (EU27: 71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The Time dimension is comparatively stronger (71.5), but power—women’s presence in decision-making—remains weak (39.6) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling persistent underrepresentation in political and economic leadership and slower progress in parity.

Inclusion and pluralism policies are mixed. MIPEX is 63 (MIPEX 2023), indicating mid-range migrant-integration policies with notable room to grow in long-term residence, political participation, and anti-discrimination enforcement. On LGBTIQ+ equality, the framework is restrictive—hate crime and hate speech protections are limited, and Rainbow Europe places Poland at roughly 15/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), among the lowest in the EU—evidence of legislative gaps and contested social acceptance. In contrast, on the OECD SIGI, Poland records a low institutional–discrimination score (18.5) (OECD 2023b), reflecting formal gender-equality guarantees in family and civil law, albeit unevenly translated into everyday practice.

Public attitudes toward the EU remain comparatively positive—about 66% of Poles say they trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), indicating a continuing identification with the European project even amid domestic polarization.

In sum, Poland's value landscape combines robust civil liberties and democratic competition with mid-tier rule-of-law quality, lagging gender power parity, restrictive LGBTIQ+ protections, and only moderate integration policies. Trust in EU institutions is relatively strong, but translating formal rights into effective equality and inclusion—especially for women and LGBTIQ+ people—remains an open challenge within an otherwise stable democratic order.

I.21.3 Gender norms

Gender norms in Poland show a persistent pull of traditional family roles alongside slower, uneven movement toward equality. On outcomes, Poland's Gender Equality Index is 63.4 (EU27: 71). The country performs well on money (79.7) and reasonably on work (69.9) but lags on power (39.6) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)—evidence of women's underrepresentation in political and economic decision-making. The knowledge domain is 60.3 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), pointing to continued horizontal segregation by fields of study and skills. Based on Eurobarometer data,

Figure 44 show gender attitudes emphasizing family-first model (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 44 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Poland

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

At work, perceived inequality is widespread—53.6% say they are treated the same, but 36% say that men are treated better. At the same time, there is clear endorsement of parity in leadership—71% agree that gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Views that men are inherently better leaders or that women lack the authority to be taken seriously are opinions that are quite widespread (

Figure 44) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Norms around masculinity are ambivalent. A large majority (70%) say it is acceptable for men to cry, signaling a relaxation of restrictive emotional scripts (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, more rigid expectations persist in parts of the population—such as support for male breadwinning and for women’s primary responsibility for care—which continue to channel men toward provision and authority and women toward domestic roles (“for important family decisions, men should have a final say” 49%, and “overall, men are naturally less competent than women to perform household tasks” 64%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In Poland, data show pronounced and multidimensional generational and gender divides. On LGBTQI+ rights, younger women are the most supportive (78.9% agree gays and lesbians should live as they wish vs. 65.7% of young men). Among older cohorts, acceptance declines but remains higher among women (70.1% vs. 59.6% of men), even as disagreement becomes substantial (55.1% of older women and 59.6% of older men) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of sexual harassment are strongly shaped by age. Belief that women “often/always exaggerate” rises sharply from 16.1% to 64.5% among men and from 12.2% to 59.5% among women. Younger women are the least skeptical (68.9% say exaggeration is never/rarely), while older respondents show significant distrust, although women remain slightly less skeptical than men (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Views on whether women “seek to gain power” also intensify with age. Among men, “often/always” responses rise from 25.0% to 45.0% and from 21.9% to 40.9% among women. Within age groups, gender differences persist—37.4% of young men versus 23.6% of young women endorse this statement, and among those over 56 years old, the gap remains (46.8% vs. 32.6%).

Paternalistic norms show more mixed trends. The agreement that women should be protected by men declines among men (37.0% to 25.9%), while women peak in midlife (52.5% at ages 36–55 years) before dropping in younger and older cohorts. When comparing genders, young men reject protection more strongly (71.4% “never/rarely”) than young women (57.4%),

whereas older cohorts converge (80.4% of men and 76.1% of women reject the norm) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, younger Poles—especially women—adopt more inclusive and egalitarian attitudes, while older cohorts, particularly men, retain more traditional and hierarchical views. However, among older women, opinions are polarized rather than uniformly conservative, underscoring a cultural landscape that mixes durable traditional expectations with selective but growing openings toward equality.

1.21.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Poland remains a structural problem that constrains the quality of democracy and the effective enjoyment of fundamental rights. Despite a comprehensive legal framework and growing service provision, prevalence levels and uneven knowledge of rights point to an implementation gap between formal commitments and everyday protection.

According to recent EU data, about 19.6% of ever-partnered women in Poland report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by an intimate partner since age 15 (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). When all perpetrators are considered, the share rises to around 16.7% of women (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024), confirming that coercion and abuse are not marginal phenomena. Awareness indicators show a mixed picture. Roughly 96.6% of women (victims and non-victims) say they know that support services exist (Eurostat 2021b), but only about 49.3% are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a)—a gap that can discourage help-seeking and weaken access to justice. The gravest outcomes persist—the intentional homicide rate of women killed by a partner or family member is about 0.44 per 100,000 inhabitants, underscoring the need for earlier risk detection and better coordination across agencies.

On the institutional side, Poland signed the Istanbul Convention on December 18, 2012, ratified it on April 27, 2015, and entered it into force on August 1, 2015 (Council of Europe 2025). These steps aligned national provisions with European standards on prevention, protection, and prosecution. However, the coexistence of moderate-to-high prevalence, uneven rights awareness, and lethal incidents indicates that enforcement and accessibility still need strengthening—especially for women facing intersecting vulnerabilities.

Overall, Poland combines formal adherence to international norms with persistent manifestations of psychological and physical violence and a sizable knowledge gap on concrete entitlements. Closing this gap—through clearer rights communication, victim-centered pathways to legal aid, and faster multiagency response—remains essential to ensure real safety, justice, and substantive gender equality.

I.21.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Poland shows a formally competitive, institutionalized democracy combined with marked polarization, selective trust in institutions, and a party landscape that remains fragmented and adversarial. Turnout in the 2024 European elections was 40.7%, below the EU average (European Parliament 2024). Descriptive representation is still uneven—women hold about 28% of seats in the national parliament (men 72%), signaling progress but still short of parity (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

On democratic quality, Poland's scores are mixed. V-Dem's Electoral Democracy Index remains high by global standards (0.83) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), but governance indicators point to strains in checks and balances. Political conflict is pronounced—the political polarization index is very high (3.98/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), and power is concentrated toward higher socioeconomic groups (3.16/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), suggesting unequal influence over decision-making.

Trust patterns are differentiated. Trust in the national parliament is 51, and confidence in parties is weaker (around 40%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Attitudinally, liberal-democratic commitments coexist with illiberal temptations. A notable share of respondents rate “a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections” as acceptable (16% very good or fairly good) (Haerpfer et al. 2024).

In Poland, ideological self-placement varies clearly by generation and gender, reflecting how age and gendered socialization shape political orientations. Older cohorts are strongly overrepresented at the ideological extremes. Among those identifying with the far right, 62% of men and 68% of women are aged 56 or above, while only 12–15% are under 35 years old. The far left shows a similar age profile—nearly 47% of both men and women belong to the oldest cohort. However, younger women are more present on the far left (27%) than young

men (12.5%), suggesting some generational renewal within left-leaning positions among women. The moderate right is also skewed toward older respondents, especially men (47% over 56 compared with 44% of women). In contrast, centrism is more evenly distributed across cohorts, with roughly one-third of adherents in each age group. The left exhibits a more differentiated pattern—among women, it is relatively young (40% under 35 years old), whereas among men, it is concentrated in midlife (42% aged 36–55 years old) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender differences within age groups further refine this picture. Among younger adults (≤ 35), men cluster around the center (57.7%) and center right (17.2% right and 9.8% far right), while women lean more to the left (23.5% left and 9.5% far left) and are less present on the right (12.3% right and 7.8% far right). This suggests that young women express more progressive orientations, while young men favor centrist or moderate-right positions. In the middle-aged cohort (36–55 years old), both genders converge toward the center (45.2% of men and 50.2% of women), although men are slightly more represented on the left (18.1% vs. 16.0%) and at the far right (12.6% vs. 10.5%). Among older respondents (> 56), gender gaps widen again, Women display greater polarization, with higher shares at both extremes (10.7% far left and 29.3% far right), while men concentrate more in the moderate right (21.4%) and the center (36.1%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Poland's ideological landscape combines generational polarization—driven largely by older cohorts—with clear gender differences, as women are more present at the left and far-left ends of the spectrum, particularly at younger ages, while men are more concentrated at the center and right

The ideological distribution observed in survey data aligns closely with the broader party system and electoral outcomes in Poland. The 2019 national election results reflect both the dominance of the right and the erosion of the traditional left while also revealing how political coalitions have consolidated around ideological poles rather than the center.

The Law and Justice Party, together with its coalition partners Poland Together (Agreement) and United Poland, won 43.6% of the vote—a commanding majority that allowed the right to govern alone. In contrast, the Civic Platform—together with its allies such as the Greens, Modern, and the Movement for Silesian Autonomy—secured 27.4% of votes. This liberal-centrist coalition represents the moderate, pro-European opposition. The Democratic Left

Alliance—representing the traditional social-democratic left—garnered 12.6% of votes, a result of Poland’s fragmented and unfavorable electoral geography for the left (ParlGov 2023).

Taken together, Poland’s political arena combines strong electoral engagement and competitive party politics with high polarization, unequal political influence, and selective institutional trust. This configuration sustains alternation in power but also generates friction that can slow consensus-building on inclusion, gender equality, and the rule of law.

I.21.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is central to contemporary political socialization in Poland, coupling very high online news consumption with selective trust and strong concern about disinformation. Daily use of online sources is widespread—about 39% of residents report reading news on the Internet every day, underscoring the centrality of digital media in public debate. Trust, however, is differentiated. Roughly 62% say they tend to trust information on websites, while about 54% express trust in content circulating on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), pointing to a cautious stance toward algorithm-driven feeds and user-generated information.

Awareness of the democratic risks of misinformation is strikingly high. About 78% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Self-reported exposure is nontrivial—around 28% say they encountered false or misleading content often or very often in the week prior to the survey, with another large share encountering it sometimes (36%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). At the same time, confidence in detection is limited—only 7% feel very confident they can recognize disinformation, while 46% feel somewhat confident (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and operative skills signals the need for sustained media literacy efforts.

Online radicalization is a related concern. Monitoring of misogynist “manosphere” ecosystems identified dozens of Poland-linked accounts (37) on incels.is over 2017–2020 (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), indicating a visible—if numerically small—presence in communities where anti-feminist and anti-democratic narratives intermingle. These spaces can function as gateways to gendered polarization and broader distrust of pluralist institutions.

Overall, Poland’s digital environment has a dual face. The internet enables broad information access and everyday participation, but selective trust, high perceived disinformation, low detection confidence, and the documented footprint of misogynist networks pose real risks to deliberative quality.

I.21.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key barometer of democratic resilience and equal opportunity. In Poland, the overall picture is mixed—strong educational attainment and low early drop-out coexist with uneven social openness and gendered hurdles in the transition to autonomy.

On the educational front, outcomes are comparatively solid. About 91% of young women aged 25–29 have completed 12–18 years of education (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), pointing to a wide upper-secondary/tertiary base. Early school leaving remains low by EU standards—4.8% among young men and 3.4% among young women (Eurostat 2024a)—suggesting that most of the youth remains in education or training through the end of compulsory cycles.

Relationally and culturally, the youth profile is more ambivalent. Young Poles report good opportunities to make friends (around 80%), and a sizable majority express openness toward immigrants (65%), indicating everyday sociability and some cosmopolitan leanings. However, acceptance of gays and lesbians is lower (around 51%) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), signaling that generational liberalization on sexuality is partial and uneven across groups and places. Territorial structure compounds these divides—with roughly 35% of the population living in rural areas, place-based gaps in services, education pathways, and jobs continue to shape youth prospects.

Taken together, Polish youth benefit from strong schooling outcomes and dense social networks but face gender gaps in employment, urban–rural disparities, and limited inclusion of sexual minorities. Policy priorities include sustaining prevention of dropout, expanding quality apprenticeships and early-career jobs for young women and men alike, and fostering inclusive civic education that consolidates openness while reducing stigma toward LGBTQI+ peers.

I.21.8 Being socialized in Poland

Being socialized in Poland means entering a competitive electoral democracy characterized by strong polarization and sharply differentiated trust across institutions. Gender norms show deep ambivalence—balanced leadership teams are widely supported, but stereotypes about women’s responsibilities, authority, and credibility remain common. Political orientations differ markedly by age and gender, shaping distinct social cues for young men and women. Digital media dominate everyday communication, accompanied by limited confidence in spotting disinformation. In this environment, masculine gender norms in Poland emerge through the interaction of egalitarian aspirations with enduring expectations surrounding authority, protection, and emotional control.

I.22 PORTUGAL

I.22.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Portugal’s socioeconomic profile couples moderate prosperity with a relatively even income distribution and a still-significant set of structural pressures. The GDP per capita in PPS places the country below the EU average in terms of material living standards. Income dispersion is contained, and the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion is 19.7% (Table 24). The labor market is comparatively inclusive—among those aged 15–64, employment reaches 75.3% for men and 70.4% for women (Eurostat 2024b)—narrower than many EU gender gaps but still indicative of unequal attachment to paid work.

Table 24 Socioeconomic conditions in Portugal compared with the EU27

	Portugal	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	82.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	29.9	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	19.7	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	74.4	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	76.3	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	59.7	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	84.6	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Gendered performance in the economy and education is mixed. On the EIGE Gender Equality Index, Portugal performs relatively well in the domains of money and work, indicating

comparatively favorable conditions in terms of earnings and labor market participation. By contrast, the knowledge dimension remains weaker, pointing to persistent horizontal and vertical segregation across fields of study and skill formation (Table 24). Early school leaving has fallen but remains higher for boys (7.8%) than for girls (5.3%) (Eurostat 2024a), pointing to gendered risks during upper-secondary transitions.

Demography and territory amplify policy demands. The old age dependency ratio is high (38.2 vs. 34 EU) (Eurostat 2024e), signaling mounting pressure on pensions and care systems. Territorial structure remains mixed, with roughly 31% of the population in rural areas (OECD 2023a)—an enduring source of inequalities in access to services, transport, and opportunities. At the same time, a foreign-born share of 16% (Eurostat 2022) contributes to labor supply and dynamism while requiring sustained integration capacity.

Finally, social expenditure at about 24.1% of the GDP (OECD 2024b) reflects a midsized welfare state—effective at cushioning shocks but leaving room to bolster family support, long-term care, and work–care reconciliation. In sum, Portugal combines relatively even incomes and improving educational outcomes with below-EU productivity, a residual gender gap in work and pay, population aging, and territorial disparities. Tackling skills segregation, raising productivity, and strengthening care and inclusion infrastructure are central to sustaining inclusive growth.

1.22.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Portugal presents a consolidated liberal–democratic profile, broadly anchored in the rule of law and civil liberties while still facing gaps in gender equality and in the consistent protection of minority rights. Freedom House rates Portugal 96/100 (“Free”) (Freedom House 2025), confirming strong guarantees of political and civil rights. The Economist Intelligence Unit’s Democracy Index assigns 8.08/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), placing the country among full democracies. Rule-of-law performance is solid, although not top-tier (0.68 on the WJP index) (World Justice Project 2024), and V-Dem’s civil-liberties measure is high at 0.90 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), pointing to robust protections and effective checks and balances.

On gender equality, the picture is mixed. Portugal’s Gender Equality Index stands at 68.6 (close to, but still below, the EU average), with time at 67.8 (unequal sharing of unpaid care

persists) and power at 61.3 (women’s presence in decision-making improving but not yet parity) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Policies of inclusion are comparatively developed—the MIPEX score is around 67 (MIPEX 2023), indicating a generally favorable framework for migrant integration with remaining obstacles in long-term residence, political participation, and nationality pathways. Protection for LGBTIQ+ people is broader than in several peers; Portugal’s Rainbow Europe score is 67/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), reflecting substantial legal safeguards, even if implementation and some family law details leave room for progress.

Public attitudes toward the EU are supportive. In 2024, about 56% of respondents in Portugal tend to trust the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c), and only 6.4% say that European unification has “gone too far” (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025), signaling a stable pro-European orientation.

Overall, Portugal combines high democratic standards and civil liberty protections with a generally inclusive policy architecture. The main challenges lie in translating formal equality into everyday practice—narrowing gender gaps in care and leadership and sustaining effective inclusion for migrants and sexual- and gender-minority groups—while maintaining public trust and rule-of-law performance.

1.22.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Portugal show a dual picture—noticeable openings toward equality sit alongside residual traditional views that still shape roles at home and in public life.

Structurally, Portugal’s Gender Equality Index places the country close to the EU average (total: 68.6) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). However, the time domain (67.8) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) signals that unpaid care and domestic work still fall disproportionately on women. This helps explain why, despite broad support for equality, family-role expectations remain comparatively traditional in day-to-day practice.

Perceived inequalities at work persist even as formal opportunities expand. The power domain (61.3) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024) indicates improving—but still

incomplete—representation of women in political and economic decision-making. Based on Eurobarometer data,

Figure 45 shows that traditional family expectations remain mainstream (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 45 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Portugal

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Opinions on who should exit the labor market if one parent must is still breadwinner-oriented—39% say the father should give up work only if his pay is lower than the mother’s (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), that is, care is assigned according to earnings, not symmetry. Importantly, however, stigmas around fathers’ leave look weaker than expected—only 19% agree that men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). That combination—traditional expectations for mothers and relatively mild stigma for fathers who take leave—signals an opening for policy (better-paid and ring-fenced father quotas) to shift practice without colliding head-on with social disapproval. Attitudes toward women’s

leadership are genuinely ambivalent. On the one hand, a striking 85% believe that gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful—a broad principle-level endorsement of diversity. On the other hand, sizable minorities still subscribe to stereotypes that portray women as overly emotional, lacking authority, and less legitimate when expressing strong opinions in public (

Figure 45).

Norms around masculinity are loosening at the emotional edge but remain contested in the public sphere. A very large majority (91%) said it is acceptable for men to cry, signaling a relaxation of restrictive emotional scripts for men. However, this softening coexists with beliefs that keep politics coded as male—57% agree that men are more ambitious than women in politics. This sentiment aligns with stereotype-based doubts about women’s leadership and helps explain why descriptive representation changes more slowly than attitudes about teams (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In addition, there are signs of backlash or fatigue—46% agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). In a landscape that otherwise endorses gender-balanced leadership and tolerates paternal leave, this level of backlash suggests that progress in equality is perceived by many as zero sum—especially when it touches authority, voice, and public recognition. Attitudes toward gender roles and moral equality reveal both a generational divide and a pronounced gender gap, combining a gradual move toward inclusion with lingering traces of traditionalism—particularly among older cohorts and men.

Attitudes toward sexuality and gender norms show clear generational divides and persistent gender differences. Support for LGBTQI+ rights increases with age (from 21.3% to 41.2% among men and from 19.6% to 43.3% among women), but within cohorts, the gender gap is strikingly large—among younger respondents, 83.3% of men and 92.7% of women agree, and disagreement is marginal (around 7% and 1.5%). This signals that Portuguese youth—especially young women—internalize egalitarian norms on sexuality far more consistently than older groups (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Skepticism toward sexual harassment claims rises sharply with age—the proportion believing women “often/always” exaggerate increases from 18.6% to 48.8% among men and reaches 36.4% among older women. Younger cohorts are more trusting (56.3% of young men and 64.7% of young women say exaggeration is rare), indicating that doubts about women’s credibility are concentrated among older respondents (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Attitudes toward women “seeking power over men” follow the same logic. Among men, “often/always” responses grow from 22.8% to 44.3% and from 14.7% to 44.0% among women. In all age groups, the middle “sometimes” category dominates, reflecting a diffuse but moderate suspicion of women’s empowerment, with men consistently more distrustful than women (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Paternalistic norms show a slow decline across generations. The rejection of the idea that women should be protected by men (“never/rarely”) rises from 19.6% to 50.7% among men and from 12.5% to 54.6% among women. However, gender gaps persist—61.9% of young men reject male protection versus only 33.8% of young women, suggesting that some young women still interpret protection as care rather than hierarchy (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, Portugal presents a pattern of moderate egalitarianism combined with residual paternalism. Younger generations—especially women—are more accepting of sexual diversity, less skeptical of harassment claims, and more critical of traditional protection norms. Older cohorts, and men across all ages, maintain more conservative attitudes, producing a socialization environment where progressive and traditional orientations continue to coexist.

1.22.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Portugal remains a structural concern that constrains the full enjoyment of rights and democratic equality. Despite a solid legal framework and an articulated network of services, prevalence, knowledge of entitlements, and protection outcomes still reveal areas for improvement.

According to the latest FRA survey, 19.7% of Portuguese women (18–74) report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15 (European

Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Violence within intimate relationships is also significant—22.5% of ever-partnered women report psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual partner violence (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Although these levels are below the EU27 average (around 31% for any-perpetrator violence), they confirm that abuse is not marginal and that coercion and control persist within intimate and family settings.

Knowledge of and access to help show a mixed picture. Awareness of the existence of support services is very high (94.7%) (Eurostat 2021b), indicating that most women know where to turn for help. In contrast, awareness of the right to free legal aid is lower (61.2%) (Eurostat 2021a). This gap between general service awareness and concrete knowledge of legal entitlements can discourage help-seeking or weaken the ability to pursue protection orders and judicial remedies—especially among the most vulnerable.

The most extreme outcomes persist. The intentional homicide rate of female victims killed by an intimate partner or family member is 0.29 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), a figure that underscores the need for earlier risk detection, consistent case management, and rapid multiagency intervention when escalation signs appear.

On the institutional side, Portugal is aligned with international standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on February 5, 2013, and entered it into force on August 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). Nonetheless, the distance between legal commitments and lived protection remains—prevalence that is far from negligible, uneven knowledge of rights, and continued lethal cases all point to implementation gaps.

Overall, Portugal presents a contradictory landscape—a mature legal–institutional system and very high awareness of services coexist with persistent partner violence, limited understanding of specific legal rights, and ongoing lethal cases. Closing this gap—through stronger rights communication, earlier risk assessment, and more coordinated prevention and protection—remains essential to ensuring safety, justice, and substantive equality for all women.

I.22.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Portugal shows a consolidated liberal–democratic system with strong rule-of-law guarantees and broad—if selective—public trust, alongside signs of

fragmentation and persistent gender gaps in representation and power. Voter participation offers a first lens—turnout in the 2024 European elections was 56.5% (European Parliament 2024), slightly above the EU27 average and consistent with Portugal’s steady, if not exceptional, record of civic mobilization. Women’s descriptive representation is comparatively robust. About 42% of members of parliament are women (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), a level that places Portugal above the EU mean and reflects sustained progress toward parity.

On equality and inclusion, Portugal performs close to the EU average. The Gender Equality Index totals 68.6, with time (67.8) and power (61.3) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), signaling ongoing gaps in the distribution of unpaid care and in women’s access to decision-making. Integration and minority rights frameworks are comparatively favorable—MIPEX at 67 (MIPEX 2023). For LGBTQI+ rights, Rainbow Europe scores Portugal at 56/100, and dedicated hate speech/hate crime provisions are in place (46.3) on the ILGA legal-framework component (ILGA-Europe 2025), indicating progress with room to strengthen protections.

In Portugal’s 2022 national election, the Socialist Party (PS) achieved a clear and decisive victory, winning 42.5% of the vote and securing 120 seats, which represent 52.2% of parliament—enough to govern alone. The Social Democratic Party (PSD) came second, with 28.4% of the vote (31.3% of the total). The result granted the PS a strong mandate and a stable majority, consolidating the center left’s dominance and leaving the PSD in a more constrained opposition role (ParlGov 2023).

In Portugal, ideological self-placement reveals marked generational and gender divides, reflecting both enduring cleavages and the gradual consolidation of centrist orientations across cohorts. Political self-placement in Portugal shows a clear generational structuring, especially at ideological extremes. The far left is strongly concentrated among older respondents—74.2% of far-left men and 48.6% of far-left women are over 56 years old, while younger cohorts represent only small shares (7.6% and 13.6% under 35 years old). The broader left displays a similar age profile, with 50.0% of men and 53.4% of women belonging to the oldest group. Centrist is more evenly distributed but still tilts toward the older population, with around 47–48% of both men and women in the 56+ cohort and about one-third in midlife. The right also becomes progressively older, rising from 22.1% of young men

and 17.6% of young women to 45.3% and 49.4%, respectively, among those over 56 years old. In contrast, the far right peaks in midlife—48.7% of men and 39.3% of women aged 36–55—indicate a more recent and cross-generational orientation rather than one rooted in older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender patterns within age groups add nuance. Among the young (≤ 35), both men and women cluster heavily at the center (around 55%), with limited presence on either side. Young women are somewhat more present on the far left (10.1% vs. 4.5% of men) and less represented on the right (13.8% vs. 23.6%). In midlife (36–55), centrism remains dominant (52.6% of men and 60.6% of women), while men are slightly more represented on the left (16.4% vs. 17.9% of women) and far right (10.5% vs. 5.1%). Among older respondents (>56), the center continues to dominate (54–56%), but gendered polarization re-emerges—older women report higher shares on the left (20.7%) and far left (5.9%), whereas men show somewhat higher support for the right (18.1%) and far right (3.8%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Portugal's ideological landscape remains centered but is clearly shaped by generational dynamics. Older cohorts sustain the traditional left–right divide, while younger generations concentrate in the center and show limited engagement with extremes. Gender differences are modest but consistent, with women leaning more toward the left and far left and men leaning more toward the right and far right.

Taken together, Portugal couples high-quality democratic institutions and above-average female representation with mid-range equality outcomes and selective trust in parties and institutions. The main challenges lie in deepening women's access to power, consolidating rule-of-law performance, and sustaining confidence in representative politics.

1.22.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is central to political socialization and opinion formation in Portugal. The online ecosystem combines a very wide diffusion of digital news with selective trust and some clear vulnerabilities, especially around misinformation and gender-hostile content.

The use of digital platforms for news is extensive. About 39% of Portuguese report reading news online every day (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), underscoring the centrality of digital media in public and political life. In parallel, social networks are a routine information source for many users.

Trust in online sources is differentiated. Roughly 53% say they tend to trust information found on websites, while around 45% express trust in social network content (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This gap suggests greater confidence in curated online environments than in algorithm-driven feeds.

The perception of democratic risks is high. About 74% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, 21% report being often/very often exposed to misleading content in the week prior to the survey (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). Detection skills remain modest—only 12% feel “very confident” that they can recognize disinformation, while most report only partial confidence (European Parliament, Brussels 2022).

Online radicalization deserves attention, although current signals are limited (5 users)—monitoring of misogynist “manosphere” spaces identified negligible Portuguese activity on incels.is (2017–2020) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). Even if small, these communities entwine hostility toward women’s rights with anti-pluralist narratives and can act as vectors for gendered polarization.

Taken together, Portugal’s digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand, high everyday online news use expands access to information and participation. On the other hand, frequent exposure to disinformation, low trust in social-platform content, and limited detection confidence threaten deliberative quality.

I.22.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion in Portugal looks broadly positive in terms of schooling and participation, but it is constrained by aging pressures and uneven routes to autonomy. On the education side, early school leaving is comparatively low—7.8% among young men and 5.3% among young women (Eurostat 2024a)—well below the EU average and a strong platform for later outcomes.

Among Polish youth, the 2022 indicators sketch a socialization environment that is both resource-rich and broadly inclusive. Roughly 64% of women aged 25–29 have accumulated 12–18 years of education (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), signaling strong retention through upper-secondary and substantial exposure to tertiary pathways—an important foundation for gender equality, even if field segregation and uneven

school-to-work transitions can blunt its payoff. At the same time, the wider youth cohort (15–29) reports very high openness to immigrants (0.92) and abundant opportunities to make friends (0.86) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), suggesting dense peer networks and everyday contact with difference—conditions that typically reduce out-group anxiety and support cooperative norms. Acceptance of gays and lesbians is also high, although somewhat lower (0.79) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), indicating that sexuality remains a more contested boundary than ethnicity or sociability.

Taken together, these figures point to a generation with solid educational capital for young women and a social fabric conducive to inclusive values. The strategic task is to convert that capital into equal career outcomes and to close the residual gap on LGBTQI+ acceptance through targeted civic and relationship education.

I.22.8 Being socialized in Portugal

Being socialized in Portugal means growing up in a stable democracy marked by social trust, moderation, and broad support for equality. However, everyday norms still reflect subtle hierarchies in family and professional life. Caregiving remains associated with women, while authority and ambition retain gendered connotations. Younger generations are strongly inclusive, particularly regarding sexuality and diversity, although symbolic paternalism persists. Digital environments facilitate civic voice but also host misinformation and occasional gender-backlash content. Overall, masculine gender norms in Portugal take shape within a blend of egalitarian ideals, familistic traditions, and moderated expectations around authority and care.

I.23 ROMANIA

I.23.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Romania's socioeconomic structure is characterized by moderate levels of development, pronounced inequalities, and an ongoing process of institutional consolidation. The country combines sustained economic growth with structural vulnerabilities typical of semi-peripheral EU economies, remaining among the lower-income member states. At the same time, income distribution is relatively uneven, and exposure to poverty or social exclusion remains comparatively high (Table 25).

Table 25 Socioeconomic conditions in Romania compared with the EU27

	Romania	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	78.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	30.3	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	27.9	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	72.8	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	67.5	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	55.4	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	70.4	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market shows improving participation but enduring gender asymmetries. The employment rate among those aged 15–64 years is 72.0% for men and 55.3% for women (Eurostat 2024b), revealing one of the widest gender gaps in the EU. The low female employment rate reflects structural barriers related to care responsibilities, regional labor market segmentation, and the limited availability of flexible or high-quality jobs for women. These factors contribute to weaker economic autonomy among women and reinforce traditional gender roles within families.

According to the EIGE Gender Equality Index, Romania scores 57.5 overall (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), among the lowest in the EU, indicating persistent structural and normative inequalities. The country performs comparatively better in the domains of money and work, indicating some progress in wage equality and women’s labor market participation. However, it lags substantially in the areas of knowledge and power, pointing to persistent educational segregation and a pronounced underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions (Table 25).

Educational attainment continues to improve but remains marked by gendered. Early school leaving—15.4% among boys and 18.3% among girls (Eurostat 2024a)—remains well above the EU average. Rurality remains a defining feature of Romania’s social landscape, with 53.59% of the population living in rural areas (OECD 2023a) often facing restricted access to transport, healthcare, and digital services.

Demographically, Romania faces a shrinking and aging population. The old age dependency ratio of 31.2 is slightly below the EU average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e), but population aging is

accelerating, compounded by sustained emigration, especially of young and skilled workers. The foreign-born population remains small (3.1%) (Eurostat 2022), underscoring the country's limited role as an immigration destination and its continuing reliance on outward mobility as a demographic safety valve.

Romania's social expenditure, at around 17.6% of the GDP (OECD 2024b), is among the lowest in the EU, reflecting a modest and fragmented welfare state. Social protection systems provide limited coverage and effectiveness in addressing child poverty, long-term care, and income insecurity. Family policies remain underdeveloped, and access to childcare and eldercare is insufficient, reinforcing gendered patterns of unpaid work.

In sum, Romania combines economic convergence and macroeconomic stability with pronounced social inequality, weak welfare capacity, and persistent gender and territorial divides. Its institutional framework is stable and aligned with EU standards, but structural imbalances in employment, education, and social protection continue to constrain equal participation and upward mobility. Ensuring inclusive growth will require strengthening welfare provision, expanding quality employment opportunities—particularly for women—and investing in education and rural infrastructure to reduce the cumulative disadvantages that shape social and gender inequalities.

I.23.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Romania stands as a country where democratic institutions and civil liberties are formally guaranteed but remain affected by persistent structural weaknesses and implementation gaps. The country's political trajectory since EU accession has consolidated key democratic frameworks, but challenges related to governance quality, corruption, and participation continue to constrain the full realization of European democratic values.

According to Freedom in the World, Romania scores 85/100 in 2024 and is classified as "Free", confirming the presence of core political rights and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025). However, the Democracy Index produced by the Economist Intelligence Unit assigns the country 5.99/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), indicating that formal pluralism coexists with institutional fragility, low political engagement, and limited trust in governance. The Rule of Law Index (0.62) (World Justice Project 2024) also reflects a partial institutional capacity, with concerns regarding judicial independence,

corruption, and the equitable enforcement of rights. In the same vein, V-Dem's Civil Liberties Index (0.87) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) suggests that while fundamental freedoms are broadly respected, the effective protection of rights remains uneven.

On gender equality, Romania ranks among the lowest-performing countries in the EU. Its overall Gender Equality Index score is 57.5, well below the EU average of 71 (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The time dimension reaches 69.2, highlighting a persistent gender imbalance in care and domestic work, while power—which measures women's presence in political, economic, and social decision-making—scores only 32.8, pointing to entrenched barriers to representation (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

The broader institutional value landscape also reflects mixed progress in inclusion and minority rights. MIPEX gives Romania a score of 96 (MIPEX 2023). The LGBTQI+ rights framework remains incomplete. According to Rainbow Europe, Romania scores 0 on hate speech law/hate crime law (gender identity and/or sexual orientation) (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Romanians' attitudes toward the EU reveal a moderately positive orientation toward European values. In 2024, 52% of respondents report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Romania presents itself as a democracy in consolidation—characterized by the coexistence of institutional guarantees and uneven implementation. Civil liberties are largely respected, and alignment with European frameworks on gender equality and inclusion is evident at the normative level. However, weak governance, persistent gender gaps, and limited protection for sexual and gender minorities underscore a value system still in transition. Democratic principles and European commitments are firmly embedded in law but remain challenged in practice, revealing an ongoing struggle between aspiration and realization in Romania's path toward full democratic and social inclusion.

1.23.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Romania reveal a society in transition, in which formal support for equality coexists with strong traditional conceptions of gender roles. The persistence of conservative family ideals and gendered expectations continues to shape women's and men's positions in both the private and public spheres.

Family-role representations remain one of the areas in which traditional models are most entrenched. According to

Figure 46, based on Eurobarometer data, Romania points to a cultural model that continues to link femininity with caregiving and domesticity, reinforcing the perception that paid work and motherhood are difficult to reconcile (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Figure 46 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Romania

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of workplace inequality confirm the same ambivalence. About 13% of Romanians believe that men are treated better than women at work, reflecting widespread recognition of persistent gender gaps, but this awareness does not translate into broad cultural support for gender parity. In political life, attitudes reveal a similar dualism. On the one hand, 65% of respondents consider it “gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, traditional stereotypes remain strong about the role of a leader, illustrating the persistence of symbolic hierarchies that equate authority and leadership with masculinity (

Figure 46) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Norms of masculinity remain equally traditional. Although some change is observable, conventional models continue to prevail. Only 64% of Romanians consider it acceptable for a man to cry, while 58% believe that men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition for their career (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Moreover, 37% agree that “for important family decisions, men should have the final say”, and 58% believe that men are “naturally less competent than women” at housework (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These attitudes reveal a persistently rigid gendered division of roles, in which male authority and breadwinning remain culturally legitimized.

The climate around feminism and gender equality is marked by polarization. Nearly half of respondents (42%) agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

In sum, the landscape of gender norms in Romania is characterized by a coexistence of progressive and traditional orientations. While younger cohorts and urban populations show growing openness toward equality and diversity, traditional gender expectations continue to exert a strong influence on family and social life. Cultural ambivalence, resistance to feminism, and the enduring association between masculinity, authority, and economic provision reveal a society in which the transition toward full gender egalitarianism remains incomplete—negotiated between aspiration and convention, continuity, and change.

I.23.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Romania is a structural problem that continues to limit the full enjoyment of rights and the quality of democratic life. The legal and institutional framework has expanded, but prevalence, awareness of entitlements, and access to effective protection still reveal sizable implementation gaps.

Evidence from EU surveys shows that non-negligible shares of women report experiences of psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence—both by intimate partners and other perpetrators—confirming that gender-based violence cannot be treated as marginal. According to data, 48.9% of ever-partnered women in Slovakia report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence by an intimate partner, while 42.2% of women have experienced violence by any perpetrator (European Union Agency for

Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These underscore the structural and pervasive nature of gender-based violence in Slovak society, revealing that nearly half of women face abuse within intimate relationships and that violence extends far beyond the private sphere.

Knowledge of where to seek help is high in Romania, but awareness of specific rights (such as free legal aid) remains comparatively low (22.4) (Eurostat 2021a); this mismatch discourages help-seeking and weakens the ability to pursue protection orders and remedies. The gravest outcomes underscore the urgency of earlier risk detection—the intentional homicide rate of women killed by a partner or family member is about 0.29 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), a reminder that escalation to lethal violence still occurs and that case management and interagency coordination must be strengthened.

On the institutional front, Romania signed the Istanbul Convention on June 27, 2014, ratified it on May 23, 2016, and entered it into force on September 1, 2016, aligning national commitments with European standards on prevention, protection, and (Council of Europe 2025). However, the distance between the formal framework and everyday protection persists—prevalence that is far from negligible, uneven knowledge of legal entitlements, and continuing lethal cases all point to gaps in enforcement.

Overall, Romania presents a contradictory picture—a formal adherence to international norms and a high awareness of services coexist with lingering barriers to effective access to justice and comprehensive protection. Closing this gap—through clearer communication of rights, survivor-centered pathways to legal aid, and faster, better-coordinated multiagency responses to risk—remains essential to ensure safety, justice, and substantive gender equality.

1.23.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Romania offers a clear view of how a formally competitive democracy coexists with low institutional trust, gender underrepresentation, and high polarization. Turnout in the 2024 European elections was about 52% (European Parliament 2024), close to the EU average and indicative of steady—but not mobilizing—participation. Descriptively, women remain markedly underrepresented—roughly 19% of MPs are women (men 81%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), which mirrors broader gaps in access to political power.

On democratic quality, composite indicators place Romania well below the EU core but within a pluralist electoral framework—the Electoral Democracy Index sits around 0.63 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), pointing to competitive elections and basic safeguards. At the same time, rule-of-law constraints and uneven rights enforcement persist. Power is perceived as skewed toward higher socioeconomic groups (2.6/4), and the polarization index is very high (3.8/4) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), signaling a fragmented adversarial arena in which consensus-building is difficult.

The 2020 Romanian parliamentary elections reflected a fragmented but competitive political landscape, highlighting shifting alignments within the country’s democratic arena. The PSD emerged as the largest force, winning 33.3% of seats and 28.9% of the vote, maintaining its dominance, particularly in rural and less affluent regions. The National Liberal Party (PNL) followed closely, with 25.2% of the vote, confirming its status as the principal center-right alternative. The reformist alliance Save Romania Union and Party of Liberty, Unity and Solidarity achieved a significant breakthrough, securing 15.4% of the vote (ParlGov 2023).

Ideologically, Romania’s party system remains competitive but notably conflictual, with centrist identification coexisting alongside strong right–left cleavages and a visible far-right pole in public debate. Combined with the underrepresentation of women and persistent social inequalities, these features shape a political culture in which formal democratic guarantees are in place but effective responsiveness and inclusion lag behind.

Overall, Romania’s political system resembles a delicate equilibrium. Electoral competition and EU-level anchoring coexist with low domestic trust, intense polarization, and weak gender parity. Strengthening the rule of law, broadening women’s access to power, and rebuilding confidence in representative institutions—along with media literacy and anti-disinformation efforts—are pivotal for consolidating democratic quality and social cohesion.

I.23.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension is central to political socialization in Romania, shaping how people access information, form opinions, and encounter democratic risks. The use of digital platforms for news is present but comparatively modest. Only a small minority report reading news online every day (19%), a figure that points to a media diet still anchored in offline sources (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust is

selective—about 39% say they tend to trust information found on websites, while 33% extend that trust to content circulating on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), signaling greater confidence in curated online environments than in algorithmic feeds.

Concerns about information integrity are widespread. About 78% consider disinformation a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Self-reported exposure is substantial. Around 20% say they very often encountered misleading content in the previous week, and 25% often did so, with a further 35% sometimes exposed. However, detection confidence is limited—only 13% feel very confident that they can recognize falsehoods, while about half (49%) feel only somewhat confident. Large minorities report low confidence (European Parliament, Brussels 2022b). This gap between high awareness and modest operative skills underscores the need for sustained media literacy efforts.

Signals of online radicalization linked to misogynistic “manosphere” ecosystems appear minimal in Romania (4 identified incels.is users in the 2017–2020 scan) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021), but the combination of low daily digital news reliance, medium trust in websites, lower trust in social networks, and high disinformation exposure creates fertile ground for vulnerability—particularly when polarizing content targets gender equality and pluralist norms.

Overall, Romania’s online environment has a dual face. Digital media broaden access to information and participation, but selective trust, low daily use, high perceived disinformation, and limited detection confidence pose tangible risks to the quality of public debate.

I.23.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion represents a key indicator of democratic resilience and the ability of a society to provide equal opportunities across generations. In Romania, the picture is uneven. Material conditions and social participation lag behind European standards, but youth show strong relational ties and moderate openness to diversity, suggesting the potential for inclusive socialization if structural barriers are addressed.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Romania scores 78.98/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), a value placing it below the EU average and among countries with medium–low youth inclusion. This score reflects a combination of fragile socioeconomic foundations, persistent territorial and gender inequalities, and limited empowerment opportunities, particularly affecting young people in rural areas.

The relational and cultural dimensions offer a more nuanced picture. Data show that 86% of young Romanians (aged 15–29 years) consider their country a “good place” to make friends (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), revealing a relatively cohesive peer environment and solid informal networks. Openness toward immigrants (60%) is not so high, and acceptance of gays and lesbians remains significantly lower (30%) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), pointing to continued moral conservatism and lingering discomfort with sexual diversity and migrants—patterns reflecting the broader tension between modernization and traditionalism in Romanian society.

On the educational and economic front, disparities are stark. Early school leaving remains high, at 18.3% for men and 15.4% for women, both well above the EU27 average (Eurostat 2024a). This highlights serious weaknesses in the education-to-work transition and underscores persistent rural disadvantages.

Romania’s youth thus face a dual reality. On the one hand, strong relational networks and openness toward immigrants point to the potential for social cohesion and future democratic consolidation. On the other hand, educational inequalities, territorial gaps, and limited cultural acceptance of sexual diversity constrain the full realization of inclusive citizenship.

In sum, the Romanian case highlights youth potential constrained by structure. While social capital and partial cultural openness could support democratic resilience, high early school leaving, rural disadvantage, and selective inclusion norms continue to hinder equal opportunity. Overcoming these obstacles requires targeted investments in education, mobility, and inclusive value formation, ensuring that future generations are empowered to participate fully and equitably in the country’s democratic life.

I.23.8 Being socialized in Romania

Being socialized in Romania means growing up in a context where democratic institutions function unevenly, trust is limited, and inequalities—especially territorial—shape

opportunities. Traditional family roles remain central, associating authority, financial provision, and emotional restraint with men. Younger cohorts show more inclusive orientations, but structural barriers in employment, services, and education constrain their expression. Digital environments amplify both egalitarian activism and gender-hostile narratives. Consequently, masculine gender norms in Romania emerge through the combination of strong traditional expectations, uneven institutional capacity, and contested ideas about equality.

I.24 SLOVAKIA

I.24.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Slovakia couples mid-level prosperity with comparatively even incomes and a lean welfare state, while facing aging pressures, territorial divides, and persistent gender gaps in paid and unpaid work. The GDP per capita in PPSs places the country below the EU average on material living standards. Inequality is low by EU standards, and the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion is 18%, better than the EU mean but still sizable. The labor market is relatively inclusive for men (76.5% employed, ages 15–64) and somewhat weaker for women (68.3%), leaving a gender gap of roughly eight points (Eurostat 2024b). On EIGE’s index, Slovakia performs solidly in money and work, but the knowledge dimension signals horizontal/vertical segregation across fields and skills (Table 26).

Table 26 Socioeconomic conditions in Slovakia compared with the EU27

	Slovakia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	75.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	23.6	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	18.3	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	74.5	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	72.5	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	66	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	85.5	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Demography and territory shape constraints. The old age dependency ratio is 28, rising but still below the EU average (Eurostat 2024e); about 37% of residents live in rural areas (OECD 2023a), reinforcing access gaps in transport, services, and opportunities between regions.

Migration plays a limited role in the economy and society (foreign-born 4%) (Eurostat 2022), which eases integration demands but narrows labor–supply diversification. Social spending, at roughly 19% of the GDP (OECD 2024b), reflects a comparatively small welfare state that cushions shocks but leaves limited fiscal room to expand long-term care, family support, and work–care reconciliation.

In short, Slovakia combines compressed incomes, low early school leaving, and decent labor market attachment with below-EU productivity, a persistent gender employment gap, pronounced rural–urban disparities, population aging, and a thin safety net. Closing skill segregation, boosting female employment and care infrastructure, and upgrading regional opportunities are pivotal to sustaining inclusive growth.

1.24.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Slovakia is a liberal democracy with functioning institutions and strong formal guarantees of rights, but its value landscape shows clear ambivalence around gender equality, inclusion, and attitudes to European integration. Freedom House classifies the country as “Free” (89/100) (Freedom House 2025), the Economist Intelligence Unit’s Democracy Index rates Slovakia as 7.21/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), the Rule of Law Index is mid-tier (0.66) (World Justice Project 2024), and V-Dem’s civil-liberties measure is comparatively high (0.86) (Varieties of Democracy 2024), together indicating effective electoral competition and protections but uneven institutional performance and enforcement.

On gender equality, Slovakia trails the EU average overall—the Gender Equality Index is 59.9, with time around 61 (care and domestic work remain unequally shared) and a notably weak power score (30.4), reflecting women’s underrepresentation in political and economic decision-making (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Policies of inclusion are mixed. MIPEX suggests a comparatively favorable framework for migrant integration (79) (MIPEX 2023), while the legal environment for LGBTIQI+ people remains among the weakest in the EU (ILGA-Europe Rainbow Europe score 23/100) (ILGA-Europe 2025), pointing to gaps in family recognition and hate crime and hate speech provisions.

Public attitudes toward the EU are cautious. Only 38% of Slovaks report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication.

2024c), signaling stronger Eurosceptic currents. Overall, Slovakia pairs solid democratic standards and civil liberty protections with middling rule-of-law performance, below-average gender equality—especially in access to power—and a restrictive LGBTIQ+ framework. The central challenge is translating formal rights and generally decent integration policies into everyday equality while rebuilding confidence in European institutions.

I.24.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Slovakia reveal a complex landscape in which formal support for equality coexists with persistent traditional expectations regarding family roles, authority, and gender identity. Based on Eurobarometer data, Figure 47 shows that family-role representations are among the domains in which traditional conceptions remain most visible. These figures illustrate enduring cultural scripts that link femininity with caregiving and question the full compatibility between motherhood and paid employment.

Figure 47 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Slovakia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of gender inequality in the labor market confirm this ambivalence. About 38% of respondents believe that men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), indicating a broad recognition of

structural inequality. However, this awareness coexists with traditional beliefs that reproduce gendered hierarchies in leadership and decision-making. In politics, while 65% of Slovaks agree that gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful, a non-negligible share still endorses gendered stereotypes (Figure 47), reflecting the persistence of symbolic biases that continue to limit the legitimacy of women’s authority. (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024).

Cultural norms concerning masculinity display similar contradictions. On the one hand, 73% of Slovaks consider it acceptable for men to cry, suggesting a slow erosion of rigid emotional expectations (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). On the other hand, traditional prescriptive norms remain—41% agree that “men should have the final say in important family decisions”, 41% say that “men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition for their career”, and 63% state that “men are naturally less competent than women in performing household tasks” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These data confirm that although emotional norms around masculinity are softening, social expectations about breadwinning and authority persist.

The broader climate is further shaped by polarization around gender politics. Almost half of Slovaks (49%) agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), a sentiment notably stronger than in most Western European countries and indicative of a defensive stance toward gender-equality policies.

Attitudes toward gender and sexuality in Slovakia show clear generational and gender divides. Support for LGBTQI+ rights is high among the young and declines steadily with age. The agreement that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” reaches 61% of young men and 70% of young women but falls to 41% and 40%, respectively, among those over 56 years old. Within the oldest cohort, only about 22–23% agree, confirming both a sharp generational drop and a persistent gender gap favoring women (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of sexual harassment reveal an unusual pattern—skepticism is strongest among younger respondents. Only 19% of young men and 17% of young women say that exaggeration “never/rarely” occurs, compared with 42% and 49% among the oldest, respectively. Within age groups, women remain consistently less skeptical than men—63% of

young women vs. 37% of young men reject the exaggeration claim, and endorsement of “often/always” is twice as high among young men (22% vs. 11%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Views on whether “women seek to gain power over men” are mixed but clearly generational. Among young respondents, 22% of men and 13% of women say this “never/rarely” happens. Among the oldest, these shares rise to 49% and 53%, respectively. However, across all ages, ambivalence dominates—about half of both men and women choose “sometimes”, while strong endorsement (“often/always”) remains contained (18–27% among men and 12–14% among women) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Benevolent sexism remains visible. The agreement that “women should be protected by men” rises with age—from 24% of young men and 23% of young women to roughly 48% among the oldest. However, the majority still reject this norm—about 71–73% of men and 67–77% of women respond “never/rarely” (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In sum, Slovakia’s cultural landscape is one of transition and tension—strong normative adherence to family-centered and hierarchical gender roles coexists with emerging egalitarian ideals and generational openings toward inclusivity and equality. While attitudes among younger Slovaks—particularly women—signal movement toward more egalitarian norms, persistent skepticism about feminism, enduring stereotypes about leadership and care, and traditional models of masculinity still define the contours within which gender identities and power relations are negotiated.

1.24.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Slovakia remains a serious structural challenge that undermines women’s safety, equality, and full participation in society. Despite the existence of a legal framework aligned with European standards, high prevalence levels, limited awareness of rights, and low knowledge of available services highlight persistent gaps between formal commitments and effective protection.

According to Eurostat and the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (2024), 38% of Slovak women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15—slightly above the EU27 average (31%) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). The prevalence of intimate partner violence is

also high—50.8% of ever-partnered women report having experienced psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence from a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures confirm that gender-based violence in Slovakia is neither marginal nor exceptional but deeply entrenched in social and family relations.

Awareness of rights and access to protection mechanisms remain limited. Only 43.4% of female victims are aware of their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a), and 68% know of the existence of support services for victims (Eurostat 2021b). These shares suggest that even when institutional resources exist, information barriers and low trust in authorities may hinder reporting and access to justice. This gap between formal rights and practical knowledge undermines the effectiveness of the protection system, especially for the most vulnerable groups, such as rural women and those in precarious employment.

The most severe outcomes of violence confirm its gravity. The annual rate of intentional homicides of women by an intimate partner or family member in Slovakia is 0.07 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c). Although this rate is low, its persistence indicates that lethal violence continues to occur in private spaces and remains a major issue for prevention and early intervention policies.

On the institutional front, Slovakia signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, but has not ratified it (Council of Europe 2025). The lack of ratification reflects the political polarization surrounding gender and family policies and has limited the establishment of a comprehensive and enforceable national framework for the prevention of violence and the protection of victims.

Overall, Slovakia's situation depicts a worrying combination of high prevalence, low awareness, and incomplete institutional commitment. Although legislative and service infrastructures exist, they are not fully supported by consistent implementation or broad social legitimacy. Gender-based violence in Slovakia thus continues to test the country's democratic maturity and capacity to translate formal gender-equality principles into effective guarantees of safety, justice, and dignity for all women.

I.24.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Slovakia offers an instructive perspective on the interplay between democracy, representation, and value polarization. The country combines formally stable institutions with a political culture marked by mistrust, polarization, and a fragile relationship between citizens and democratic processes.

Voter turnout represents the first indicator of civic engagement. In the 2024 European elections, Slovakia registered the lowest turnout in the EU, at 34.38%, compared to an EU27 average of 51% (European Parliament 2024). This persistently low participation rate signals widespread detachment from electoral politics and limited confidence in the ability of institutions to address citizens' needs—a longstanding trend that differentiates Slovakia from most Western democracies.

Women's representation in politics remains below European standards. Women currently hold 23% of seats in the national parliament, compared to an EU27 average of 23% (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Despite modest improvements over the past decade, women's access to decision-making positions remains limited, reflecting cultural barriers and the underrepresentation of gender equality priorities in party agendas.

The ideological configuration of the Slovak party system reflects growing polarization and the consolidation of nationalist-conservative forces. According to ParlGov data (ParlGov 2023), the Direction–Social Democracy party secured 22% of the vote in the latest election, while the far-right Republic (Republika) and Slovak National Party together accounted for approximately 10%, confirming the sustained presence of radical-right actors. The Government Coalition Left–Right Index stands at 3.5, indicating a predominantly right-leaning government (V-Dem 2024). This ideological composition has tangible effects on the policy agenda, especially regarding gender equality, minority rights, and international commitments, such as the Istanbul Convention, which Slovakia has signed but has not ratified.

From an institutional standpoint, Slovakia's democracy displays both achievements and vulnerabilities. The Electoral Democracy Index gives the country a score of 0.75, and the Civil Liberties Index stands at 0.86 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), pointing to relatively strong formal guarantees but uneven implementation of democratic rights. Trust in political institutions is markedly low. According to Eurobarometer (2024), 31% trust the government

(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Political engagement follows a similar pattern. Only 32.5% of Slovaks declare being quite interested in politics (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). This low engagement is coupled with a moderate but significant minority expressing openness to illiberal alternatives—35.5% of Slovaks rate “having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections” as a bad idea, while 23% consider it “fairly good” (Haerpfer et al. 2024).

V-Dem’s political polarization index (3.13/4) further confirms the extent of ideological division, while the distribution of power by socioeconomic position (2.27/4) suggests that political influence remains concentrated among economic elites, with limited representation of working and middle-class interests (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

Ideological self-placement in Slovakia shows clear generational and gender differences. Among men, centrism dominates at all ages but sits alongside stronger right-leaning tendencies in youth. Young men (≤ 35) place themselves mainly at the center (43.3%) or the right (33.3%), with 12.2% on the far right, while left positions remain marginal (under 11%). In midlife (36–55), centrism rises to 48.3%, right-wing identification drops to 18.4%, and left-wing orientations gain more space (15.0% left and 12.1% far left). Among older men (>56), centrism weakens slightly (39.2%), and left-wing orientations become more pronounced (23.7% left; 19.9% far left), indicating a generational shift from right-leaning youth to more left-leaning older cohorts (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Women display a more consistent centrist profile. Young women (≤ 35) are mainly centrist (45.2%) or left-leaning (19.0%), with smaller shares on the right (22.6%) or far right (9.5%). Middle-aged women (36–55) are even more centered (54.3%), with limited right identification (13.1%) and stable left shares (19.0%). Among older women (>56), centrism remains strong (39.9%), while left (23.2%) and far-left (17.0%) orientations increase and the far right nearly disappears (3.4%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). In general, men exhibit wider ideological dispersion—right-oriented when young and more left-leaning in later life—while women remain more clustered around the center and the moderate left. Both genders recenter with age, but men stay more polarized,

especially toward the right, whereas women maintain more stable moderate or progressive orientations.

In summary, Slovakia's political landscape combines formal institutional stability with social disaffection, ideological polarization, and weak trust in representation. The low electoral turnout, gender imbalance in political power, and diffusion of illiberal sentiments reflect the challenges facing Slovakia's democratic consolidation. While basic democratic institutions remain intact, the system's legitimacy is weakened by a sense of distance between citizens and politics, amplified by inequalities, cultural conservatism, and the normalization of populist rhetoric.

I.24.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is crucial for political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks tied to disinformation and radicalization. In Slovakia, online news consumption is widespread—about 52% report reading news on the internet with regularity (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a)—underscoring the centrality of digital media in public life. Trust patterns show a clear split—50% say they tend to trust news found on websites, compared with 39% who trust information on social networks (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This asymmetry suggests that professional online outlets retain higher legitimacy, while social feeds are approached more cautiously—even as they remain important gateways to information and debate.

Perceptions of disinformation as a democratic threat are broad. About 89% consider it a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). At the same time, self-assessed skills to spot false content are only moderate—20% feel very confident in recognizing fake news, while the majority report only partial confidence (50%) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and verification skills points to a persistent need for investment in media and digital literacy across age groups.

Overall, Slovakia's digital environment has a dual face. On the one hand are wide access to information and participation online, supported by higher trust in news websites than in social media, and on the other hand are frequent contact with misleading content, only moderate self-efficacy in recognizing it, and the structured presence of misogynist/anti-

democratic niches, factors that pose concrete risks to the quality of public debate and democratic resilience.

I.24.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key indicator of democratic resilience and a country's capacity to secure equal opportunities for new generations. In Slovakia, the picture is mixed—material and relational conditions are broadly adequate, but important bottlenecks persist along the routes to empowerment, education, and socio-economic autonomy.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Slovakia scores 82.8/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This reflects good living conditions and generally positive perceptions of safety and community, alongside areas where the transition to adulthood remains constrained by structural barriers. Openness to diversity is uneven. Youth assessments suggest that 51% regard Slovakia as a good place for immigrants, while acceptance of gays and lesbians is markedly lower (43%) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). In contrast, the relational dimension is stronger. About 87% of young people rate opportunities to make friends and build social networks positively (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)—evidence of comparatively robust youth social capital.

On the educational and economic front, vulnerabilities are clear. Early school leaving remains non-negligible and shows a small gender gap—7.8% among young men versus 7.1% among young women (Eurostat 2024a). These values are close to the EU averages and point to persistent frictions in educational continuity and skill accumulation that can hamper youth entry into quality jobs and long-term autonomy.

Taken together, Slovak youth display solid relational resources but limited cultural openness on some fronts and enduring educational risks. Strengthening targeted support for school-to-work transitions, tackling territorial inequalities, and widening inclusive civic and diversity education would be pivotal to expanding agency and ensuring a more even, resilient pathway to adulthood.

I.24.8 Being socialized in Slovakia

Being socialized in Slovakia means entering a society in which democratic procedures are upheld but public life is marked by mistrust, polarization, and a lean welfare state. Territorial inequalities reinforce the central role of the family as a source of security. Gender norms emphasize male authority and female caregiving, although support for balanced leadership is rising. Younger groups, especially young women, are more willing to challenge established roles. Digital spaces are widely used yet vulnerable to disinformation. Within this context, masculine gender norms in Slovakia form at the intersection of traditional authority expectations and emerging preferences for cooperation, care, and shared responsibility.

I.25 SLOVENIA

I.25.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Slovenia's socioeconomic landscape reflects a balanced combination of macroeconomic stability, moderate inequality, and relatively high social cohesion. Compared to the EU27 average, Slovenia displays a more egalitarian socioeconomic profile. While its level of economic output per capita remains below the EU average, income inequality is markedly lower and the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion is substantially smaller. This combination points to a comparatively inclusive distribution of resources and a welfare system that effectively mitigates social risks despite more moderate economic performance (Table 27).

Table 27 Socioeconomic conditions in Slovenia compared with the EU27

	Slovenia	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	91.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	21.5	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	14.4	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	85.0	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	76.1	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	60.5	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	86.9	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

Income distribution indicators confirm Slovenia's longstanding reputation for equality. With a Gini coefficient of 21.5 (Eurostat 2024d), well below the EU average, Slovenia displays very low

income inequality and ranks among the most egalitarian income distributions in the EU. Only 14.4% of the population is at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f), well below the EU27 average of 21.4%, underscoring a robust welfare model and broad access to social protection.

The labor market presents a favorable picture but retains clear gender asymmetries. Employment among persons aged 15–64 years stands at 76% for men and 70% for women (Eurostat 2024b). While both figures exceed the European averages (75.3% and 66.2%), the 6-point gap reveals persistent gendered divisions in paid work and care responsibilities. The EIGE Gender Equality Index places Slovenia slightly below the EU mean, with a total score of 70.1 against 71 in the EU (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Performance in the money and work dimensions is relatively strong, reflecting decent female employment and earning levels, but the knowledge dimension remains weak, highlighting horizontal segregation across educational fields and persistent barriers (Table 27). Early school leaving affects 6.2% of boys and 3.5% of girls, indicating a generally efficient education system but some gendered pathways that influence later labor outcomes (Eurostat 2024a).

Demographic dynamics show a moderately aging society. The old age dependency ratio of 34.3 (above the EU average of 33.9) signals increasing pressure on pension and health systems (Eurostat 2024e). Approximately 57.93% of the population resides in rural areas, where access to services and opportunities remains more limited than in urban centers (OECD 2023a). The foreign-born population represents 13.6% (Eurostat 2022), a growing share that contributes to demographic renewal and labor market supply but poses integration challenges in some sectors.

Social expenditure, equal to 23% of the GDP, demonstrates Slovenia's commitment to a universal and inclusive welfare state (OECD 2024b). This model has effectively contained inequality and mitigated labor market shocks, although structural reforms will be required to sustain intergenerational equity and improve support for young families and care infrastructures.

In sum, Slovenia combines social cohesion and fiscal prudence with relatively high equality and human development indicators. However, gender and territorial disparities, population aging, and the slow integration of migrants remain structural vulnerabilities. Maintaining a balance between economic competitiveness and social inclusion will be crucial for ensuring sustainable and equitable growth.

I.25.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Slovenia ranks among the Central European countries with the most stable democratic systems and a consistently high level of institutional trust and rule of law. At the same time, the value structure reveals persistent ambivalence regarding gender equality, minority rights, and attitudes toward European integration.

According to Freedom in the World, Slovenia scores 96/100 in 2024 and is classified as “Free”, confirming the solid protection of political rights and civil liberties (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index compiled by the Economist Intelligence Unit assigns the country 7.82/10 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024)—a level that reflects stable democratic procedures and political participation but has some limitations in political culture and media pluralism. The Rule of Law Index (0.69) (World Justice Project 2024) and V-Dem’s Civil Liberties Index (0.89) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) indicate robust institutional performance and high respect for fundamental rights, although with concerns related to judicial efficiency and transparency.

Regarding inclusion and diversity, Slovenia’s policies are moderately developed. MIPEX scores 90/100, reflecting a good level of integration policies (MIPEX 2023). The legal protection framework for LGBTIQ+ people is comparatively advanced but not fully comprehensive. The Rainbow Europe Index ranks Slovenia at 46/100 (ILGA-Europe 2025), showing progress in anti-discrimination legislation but incomplete protection of family rights and gender identity recognition (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Public attitudes mirror these institutional dynamics. In 2024, 47% of Slovenians report trusting the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

In sum, Slovenia presents a mature democratic system with strong institutional foundations and a broad alignment with European democratic values. However, the consolidation of gender equality and the full inclusion of migrants and LGBTIQ+ citizens remain key challenges. Trust in European institutions is sustained, although tempered by moderate Eurosceptic undercurrents. Overall, Slovenia’s value landscape reflects a society anchored in democratic norms but negotiating ongoing tensions between equality principles and social conservatism.

I.25.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Slovenia reveal a pattern of gradual modernization combined with lingering traditional elements that continue to influence both family roles and public life. Family-role representations remain one of the domains in which traditional models persist. According to Eurobarometer data,

Figure 48 shows enduring conceptions of care and motherhood as primarily female responsibilities, suggesting incomplete normalization of dual-earner family models.

Figure 48 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Slovenia

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of workplace inequality show similar ambivalence. About 3.1% of Slovenians believe that men are treated better than women at work, while 52% say that “women are treated less fairly” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). However, this recognition coexists with the persistence of traditional expectations concerning gender roles within household and public life.

When it comes to leadership and politics, attitudes combine support for equality with residual stereotypes. About 74% of Slovenians consider gender-balanced leadership teams to be more successful (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), demonstrating a strong normative endorsement of gender balance. Nevertheless,

Figure 48 shows opinions highlighting symbolic resistance that continues to limit women's perceived legitimacy in power positions despite formal parity commitments.

Cultural understandings of masculinity also oscillate between change and continuity. About 80% of Slovenians find it “acceptable for a man to cry” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), suggesting the slow erosion of rigid emotional stereotypes. However, 13% believe that “men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition”, 18% agree that “men should have the final say in family decisions”, and 36% say that “men are naturally less competent than women” in household tasks (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These contradictions indicate that while emotional openness is gaining ground, traditional divisions of authority and care responsibilities remain culturally reinforced.

A further sign of ambivalence is the perception of feminism and gender-equality policies. About 55% of Slovenians agree that “feminism has gone too far”, revealing a degree of defensive reaction against perceived changes in gender hierarchies (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This sentiment suggests that egalitarian norms coexist with fatigue or backlash attitudes among segments of the population.

In Slovenia, attitudes toward gender and sexuality reveal a mix of generational change and persistent ambivalence. Acceptance of LGBTQI+ rights increases slightly with age among men (from 26% to 40%) and remains high among women (31% to 38%), but strong gender gaps emerge within cohorts—85.9% of young women agree that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish, compared with 55.2% of young men. Disagreement is far more common among men—up to 42% among the oldest—while among older women, it reaches about 16% (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of sexual harassment show deeper divides. The belief that women “often or always” exaggerate harassment rises from 25% to 55% among men and from 18% to 63% among women, indicating a strong generational rather than a purely gendered pattern. However, women across cohorts remain less skeptical than men. Around 58% of young women versus

46% of young men say exaggeration “never or rarely” occurs (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Hostile sexism regarding women “seeking power over men” is persistent but moderate. Across all age groups, about one-third of both men and women endorse the statement, while roughly half respond “sometimes”; fewer than 25% reject it outright. Age effects are small, although older men show slightly higher rejection, suggesting disengagement more than ideological change.

Benevolent sexism is weaker but still present. The rejection of the idea that “women should be protected by men” increases across generations (from 29% to 41% among men and 27% to 45% among women). Overall rejection is high—85–92% among men and 73–80% among women—but small pockets of endorsement persist, especially among young and mid-aged women (4–7%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Overall, Slovenia displays a transitional landscape; younger cohorts—especially women—are more egalitarian, supportive of LGBTQI+ rights, and less accepting of hostile stereotypes, while older generations and men remain more attached to both hostile and benevolent forms of sexism. Progressive and traditional elements therefore coexist, shaping a socialization context in which equality is valued but defensive gender norms continue to surface.

1.25.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Slovenia represents a persistent structural problem that continues to undermine women’s security, equality, and full citizenship. Despite a comprehensive legal framework and relatively strong institutional mechanisms, the prevalence of violence and limited awareness of rights indicate significant gaps between formal commitments and everyday realities.

According to data, 22.5% of Slovenian women aged 18–74 report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15, a figure slightly above the EU27 average of 31% (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). This confirms the structural and widespread nature of gender-based violence in the country. When focusing on intimate partner violence, the prevalence is even higher—27.9% of ever-partnered women report having suffered psychological, physical (including threats), or sexual violence from a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures reveal the deep entrenchment of coercive control and abusive dynamics within intimate

relationships, demonstrating that violence against women is far from an isolated or residual phenomenon.

Awareness of rights and access to protection mechanisms remain uneven. In Slovenia, 97.7% of women who have experienced violence are aware of the existence of support services (Eurostat 2021b), while 50.4% know about their right to free legal aid (Eurostat 2021a). Although these values are slightly better than in several other Central European countries, they suggest that a large share of victims still lack precise information about available resources, which can discourage reporting and reduce access to justice. The gap between general awareness and the effective utilization of services points to the need for more proactive outreach, especially in rural areas and among migrant women.

Lethal violence continues to be a dramatic manifestation of gender inequality. The rate of intentional homicides of female victims by an intimate partner or family member is 0.28 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), one of the lowest in the EU but still indicative of enduring structural risks and insufficient early intervention capacity. These incidents highlight the urgency of improving risk assessment, coordination between law enforcement and social services, and long-term protection measures for survivors.

At the institutional level, Slovenia signed the Istanbul Convention on September 8, 2011, ratified it on February 5, 2015, and entered it into force on June 1, 2015 (Council of Europe 2025). The country has since developed national strategies and specialized support services, including shelters and helplines. However, challenges remain regarding sustainable funding, prevention programs, and the consistent integration of gender-based violence into broader equality and human rights policies.

In sum, the Slovenian context reflects a paradox typical of many advanced welfare states—strong legal and institutional frameworks coexist with persistent high levels of psychological and physical violence, incomplete awareness of rights, and uneven protection capacities. This discrepancy between norms and practices underscores how gender-based violence remains not only a matter of criminal justice but also a key test of democratic quality, social inclusion, and the state's capacity to ensure substantive equality and safety for all women.

1.25.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Slovenia reflects a consolidated democratic system embedded within the European institutional framework but characterized by persistent polarization, low trust in parties, and limited gender parity in representation. Voter turnout in the 2024 European

elections stood at 42.5%, below the EU average but stable compared with previous elections (European Parliament 2024), signaling moderate engagement in supranational politics.

Women's descriptive representation remains significantly constrained. Only about 30% of members of parliament are women (men 70%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), marking an improvement over earlier legislatures but still falling short of parity. This gap mirrors broader gender inequalities in political participation and leadership across public institutions.

In terms of democratic quality, composite indicators portray a picture of relative strength combined with notable vulnerabilities. The Electoral Democracy Index reaches 0.72, indicating competitive elections and effective pluralism (Varieties of Democracy 2024). However, perceptions of fairness and inclusiveness are affected by the concentration of power and perceived favoritism toward higher socioeconomic groups. The “Power distributed by socioeconomic position” score is 3/4, while the polarization index reaches 3.82/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), pointing to a moderately fragmented political environment in which cooperation across ideological lines remains fragile.

In Slovenia's 2022 national elections, the Freedom Movement (GS) achieved a decisive realignment of the country's political landscape. With 34.5% of the vote, GS emerged as the leading political force and the central actor of the new governing majority. The SDS followed in second place with 23.5%, confirming its role as the main opposition party. On the center right, New Slovenia – Christian People's Party secured 6.9%, while among progressive parties, the Social Democrats obtained 6.7% (ParlGov 2023).

Public trust in representative institutions remains limited. Only 17% of citizens express trust in national government and 9% in political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). These figures, slightly below EU averages, underscore a persistent sense of distance between citizens and political elites.

Ideological orientations in Slovenia show clear generational and gender-based divides. Polarization increases with age for men and women, with older cohorts moving away from centrist positions toward the extremes. Among men, the youngest group (≤ 35) is mainly centrist (33.1%) or right-leaning (31.9%), whereas the oldest group (> 56) shows much stronger polarization, with 64.5% identifying with the far left and 68.6% with the far right. Women follow a similar trajectory—younger women combine moderate left (32.6%) and right (32.8%) orientations, while older women display substantially higher shares on the far left

(66.7%) and far right (57.5%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Gender differences further shape these patterns. Centrism is more prevalent among men (72% of young men and around 50–60% of older men) than among women (53–57% across cohorts). Women show stronger left-wing preferences, including among the young (20.9% vs. 6.3% of young men), while far-right identification is slightly higher among older men (10.9%) than among women (10%). Women also show a modestly higher presence on the far left, particularly in older cohorts (up to 14.8%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Slovenia's ideological structure is shaped by generational polarization—driven by older cohorts clustering at both extremes—and gender segmentation, with women leaning more to the left and men showing stronger right-wing and far-right orientations.

Overall, Slovenia's political landscape combines democratic resilience with growing social fragmentation and low institutional trust. Gender representation has improved but remains incomplete, and polarization risks undermining consensus-building on equality and inclusion.

I.25.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital dimension in Slovenia plays a key role in shaping political socialization, public opinion, and exposure to risks associated with disinformation and online radicalization. The country presents a digital ecosystem characterized by high internet use and extensive reliance on social networks for information but also by moderate trust in online content and significant vulnerabilities in media literacy.

According to Eurobarometer data, 38% of Slovenians read news online every day, slightly above the EU average (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a), confirming the centrality of digital media in the country's information landscape. Trust in online content is relatively cautious. About 29% of Slovenians state that they tend to trust news found on the internet, while only 18% trust information disseminated through social media (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). These values, below the EU average, suggest a more critical orientation toward online content but also reflect persistent uncertainty in evaluating information quality.

Perceptions of disinformation as a democratic problem are widespread. About 86% of Slovenians consider disinformation a serious or very serious threat to democracy, a figure aligned with the EU average (81%) (European Commission. Directorate General for

Communication. and Kantar. 2022). However, 37% report having been “often” or “very often” exposed to misleading or false content in the preceding week. Despite this, only 12% feel “very confident” in their ability to recognize disinformation, while 46% say they can do so “only sometimes” (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This gap between awareness and effective critical skills underscores the need for greater investment in digital literacy and media education, especially among youth and older citizens.

The Slovenian digital environment thus presents a dual reality. On the one hand, digital platforms facilitate access to information, civic participation, and transnational communication, reflecting the country’s high connectivity and integration into the European digital sphere. On the other hand, exposure to disinformation and limited critical competences signal risks to democratic resilience.

I.25.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a key indicator of democratic vitality and a country’s capacity to provide equitable opportunities for younger generations. In Slovenia, the overall picture is moderately positive, combining high educational attainment and openness to diversity with structural challenges in employment stability and youth participation in public life.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Slovenia scores 86.9/100, positioning it in the medium–high range of EU countries (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This value reflects both solid material conditions and relatively favorable perceptions of social inclusion while also pointing to persistent barriers in achieving full autonomy and empowerment.

The relational and cultural dimensions are particularly encouraging. Survey data show that 86% of young Slovenians (aged 15–29 years) report good opportunities to make friends and build social networks, suggesting a dense relational fabric and a relatively inclusive social environment (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022).

Openness toward diversity appears moderate among young people—64% consider Slovenia a “good place for immigrants”, and 64% see it as a “good place for gay and lesbian people” (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These figures point to a significant, although not universal, level of acceptance, suggesting that attitudes toward diversity remain somewhat mixed within the younger population.

However, the transition to adulthood remains marked by economic and occupational vulnerability. While educational performance is high—with 3.5% of young women and 6.2% of

young men leaving education or training early (Eurostat 2024a)—the integration into the labor market is often delayed or precarious. Limited access to stable employment and affordable housing constrains young people’s capacity for independent living, reflecting broader structural rigidity in Slovenia’s labor and welfare systems.

In sum, Slovenian youth stand out for their high educational levels, openness to diversity, and inclusive social values but continue to face economic constraints and limited political agency. This duality underscores the potential of young generations as agents of democratic renewal and the need for structural reforms—in labor, housing, and participation policies—to translate inclusive attitudes into concrete opportunities and sustainable autonomy.

I.25.8 Being socialized in Slovenia

Being socialized in Slovenia means growing up in a stable, cohesive democratic system that combines high institutional trust with ambivalence around gender and authority. Equality is widely endorsed in principle, but everyday norms still assign primary care roles to women and link decision-making and provision to men. Younger generations tend to adopt more inclusive and emotionally open attitudes, while older cohorts maintain more conventional orientations. Digital participation is broad but vulnerable to disinformation. As a result, masculine gender norms in Slovenia reflect a layered configuration in which egalitarian ideals coexist with inherited expectations around decisiveness, self-control, and family roles.

I.26 SPAIN

I.26.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Spain’s socioeconomic landscape is marked by a level of economic development below the EU average and by persistent internal disparities, alongside improving macroeconomic stability. In comparison with the EU27 average, Spain combines a level of economic output per capita below the European mean with comparatively higher income inequality. This is reflected in a larger share of the population exposed to poverty or social exclusion. Overall, the Spanish case points to structural vulnerabilities in income distribution and social protection that persist despite moderate levels of economic development (Table 28).

Table 28 Socioeconomic conditions in Spain compared with the EU27

	Spain	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	92.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	33.4	28.7

Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	25.8	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	79.5	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	75.6	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	70.1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	91	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market portrays a mixed picture and a clear gender divide. Among those aged 15–64 years, employment rates are 70.5% for men and 61.6% for women (Eurostat 2024b). Although both rates have risen over the last decade, the gender gap remains sizable and reflects enduring asymmetries in access to stable, well-paid work. These disparities affect women’s economic autonomy and help reproduce traditional models of labor participation. Consistently, early school leaving remains among the highest in the EU—15.8% for boys and 10.0% for girls—constraining social mobility and the quality of labor market entry (Eurostat 2024a).

The EIGE Gender Equality Index confirms areas of strength together with bottlenecks. Spain’s overall score is 76.7, well above the EU average (71) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The money and work dimensions perform strongly, reflecting relatively high female participation and earning capacity. However, imbalances persist in education and in access to decision-making, as indicated by knowledge and by enduring vertical and horizontal segregation that limits women’s presence in top positions (Table 28).

Demography is another crucial factor. The old age dependency ratio is 30.8, slightly below the EU average (33.9) but indicative of a rapidly aging population (Eurostat 2024e). Spain is highly urbanized, with a minority living in rural areas, which translates into uneven access to services, education, and infrastructure between metropolitan cores and low-density regions (OECD 2023a). The foreign-born population accounts for about 18.2%, among the highest shares in the EU—an asset for demographic sustainability and economic dynamism but also a challenge for integration and social cohesion (Eurostat 2022).

Finally, social expenditure amounts to 25.9% of the GDP, signaling a broad and articulated welfare state (OECD 2024b). This system has helped cushion the effects of economic shocks

and labor market dualization; nonetheless, it proves less effective in addressing youth precariousness, territorial divides, and the reconciliation of work and family life.

In sum, Spain's socioeconomic and institutional structure combines moderate material well-being with comparatively high inequality, marked gender gaps in employment, demographic aging, and territorial vulnerabilities. The strengths of the welfare system and advances in gender equality are clear assets, but the country must confront new forms of inequality generated by economic transformation, demographic change, and social diversification to ensure more inclusive and sustainable growth.

I.26.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Spain belongs to the group of EU countries with consolidated democratic institutions, a robust rule-of-law tradition, and broad guarantees of civil and political rights, while its value landscape still shows tensions around gender equality, inclusion, and minority protection. According to Freedom in the World, Spain scores 90/100 (Free) in 2025 (Freedom House 2025), confirming the strong protection of political rights and civil liberties. The Economist Intelligence Unit's Democracy Index 2024 classifies Spain as a "full democracy" with an overall score of 8.1 (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024), signaling pluralism, participation, and institutional stability. The V-Dem dataset likewise registers high levels of civil liberties, in line with Spain's long-standing liberal-democratic profile (0.95) (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

Policies of inclusion and pluralism are comparatively advanced but uneven. On migrant integration, Spain's framework is assessed around the MIPEX 2020 score of 59/100, signaling a generally comprehensive approach with notable strengths (e.g., access to services, political participation) and remaining constraints (e.g., long-term security) (MIPEX 2023). In contrast, the legal environment for LGBTIQ+ people is among the most protective in Europe: 78/100 on the Rainbow Map (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Public attitudes toward the EU are broadly supportive. About 69% of Spaniards report trust in EU institutions (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). In sum, Spain presents itself as a solid liberal democracy with high civil liberty standards, and the rule of law is largely upheld. Its gender-equality record is strong in the comparative EU perspective, but the translation of equality into power and time domains remains an open

challenge. Inclusion policies are broadly favorable—particularly for LGBTIQ+ rights—while migrant integration shows strengths alongside areas to reinforce. Trust in European institutions is relatively high and stable, but the coexistence of progressive legal frameworks with persistent attitudinal and representation gaps reveals a value system still in transition, in which democratic consensus cohabits with tensions over identity, belonging, and rights.

I.26.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Spain reveal a complex dynamic in which clear openings toward equality coexist with resilient stereotypes that still shape women’s and men’s roles in both the public and private spheres. Family-role representations remain an area in which conventional expectations are visible. In Spain, based on Eurobarometer data, Figure 49 suggests that traditional gender role attitudes remain relatively widespread, with a significant share of the population still linking women’s full participation in the labor market to a potential decline in family well-being. These results reveal that although women express slightly more egalitarian views, traditional gender norms around work–family balance remain widespread among both genders, suggesting that the idea of motherhood as inherently in tension with full-time employment continues to shape social attitudes.

Figure 49 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Spain

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality at work point in the same direction. In Spain, 43% of respondents say that men are treated better than women at work (vs. 7% “women treated better” and 47% “treated the same”), signaling broad public recognition of persistent structural disadvantages for women (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This awareness coexists with enduring cultural expectations about the gendered division of labor in families.

The political sphere concentrates on both progress and ambivalence. Support for parity is high—68% judge gender-balanced leadership teams as more successful. At the same time (Figure 49), non-negligible minorities still endorse stereotypes about women’s competence and authority in leadership (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). The coexistence of explicit support for gender balance with lingering symbolic biases indicates a value lag—formal endorsement has advanced faster than the erosion of stereotypes.

Norms around masculinity display a mixed picture. On the one hand, a majority agree that it is acceptable for a man to cry (95%), signaling a gradual softening of traditional emotional norms. On the other hand, smaller but meaningful shares still back rigid expectations—for example, that men should have the final say in important family decisions (11%) or that men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition (12%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These views buttress breadwinner–caregiver models and help sustain the unequal distribution of unpaid work. Finally, the attitudinal climate shows signs of polarization. A majority (53%) agree that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), suggesting that rapid legal and institutional progress can trigger defensive reactions among certain groups.

In Spain, gender norms and attitudes show a generally egalitarian landscape tempered by generational and gender divides. Support for LGBTQI+ rights is extremely high across the population. Among men, the agreement that “gays and lesbians should be free to live their lives as they wish” rises from 28.6% among those under 35 years of age to 39.5% among those over 56 years old. Among women, the percentage rises from 23.8% to 40.7%, respectively. Within cohorts, however, acceptance is overwhelming—over 90% of women and 85–91% of men agree—while disagreement remains marginal (below 3% among women and

2–6% among men). Neutrality increases notably with age (48–61% among older men and 46–61% among older women), suggesting that clear acceptance coexists with more reserved attitudes among the oldest (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Perceptions of sexual harassment reveal sharper divides. Skepticism increases with age, especially among men—“often/always” responses rise from 20.7% of younger men to 40.2% among those over 56 and from 11% to nearly 46%, respectively, among women. Across genders, women remain significantly less skeptical—64–77% of women versus 47–64% of men say exaggeration “never/rarely” occurs, while only 5–11% of women (vs. 8–14% of men) endorse the strongest skeptical view. These patterns indicate that younger Spaniards—especially women—align more closely with feminist understandings of harassment, while older men remain the most distrustful (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Beliefs about women “seeking power by controlling men” reflect persistent ambivalence. Endorsement increases with age. Among men, “often/always” responses rise from 24.6% to 43.2%, and among women, they rise from 15.1% to 42.1%. Only around one-third in either gender reject the statement entirely (“never/rarely”: 27–35% among men and 32–46% among women). Moderate agreement (“sometimes”) is the modal response (around 45% for both), indicating a stable undercurrent of subtle gender distrust that persists even in an otherwise egalitarian context (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Attitudes toward benevolent sexism reveal both traditionalism and polarization, especially among older cohorts. The agreement that women “should be protected by men” increases with age among both sexes (men: 26.7% to 44.6%; women: 26.1% to 38.4%). At the same time, rejection (“never/rarely”) rises with age, particularly among men (22.3% to 48.9%), suggesting that older Spaniards are more internally split between traditional and egalitarian norms. Gender differences are also evident—young women show the strongest endorsement of protection (45.8% vs. 28.4% of men), and even among the oldest, women remain more supportive (39.1% vs. 31.8%). Rejection is consistently lower among women (22–34%) than among men (33–49%), pointing to a lasting symbolic appeal of protection among parts of the

female population (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Taken together, the Spanish landscape of gender norms is marked by a twofold movement. Broad and explicit support for equality—especially for gender-balanced leadership and more expressive masculinities—coexists with resilient family-role traditionalism and leadership stereotypes. Age and gender continue to structure these attitudes, with younger cohorts typically more egalitarian, while residual traditionalism lingers in expectations of care, authority, and men’s roles in the household.

I.26.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Spain is a structural and persistent phenomenon that undermines the quality of democracy and the full exercise of fundamental rights. Despite a comparatively advanced legal framework and a consolidated network of services, prevalence, knowledge of entitlements, and access to protection still leave significant room for improvement.

Drawing on recent EU evidence, around three in ten women in Spain report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since age 15 (28.2%). Violence within intimate relationships remains widespread—ever-partnered women reporting psychological, physical (including threats), and/or sexual violence are 28.6% (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). Although these shares are around or slightly below the EU27 average, they confirm that the problem is systemic and cannot be considered marginal. They may also reflect a greater capacity to identify nonphysical forms of abuse—especially psychological control and coercive behaviors—often normalized in everyday life.

Knowledge and access to support reveal a mixed picture. Awareness of the existence of specialized support services is very high (97.3%) (Eurostat 2021b), indicating that most women—victims and nonvictims—know that help is available. The most extreme outcomes are sobering. The annual rate of intentional homicides of women by an intimate partner or family member stands at 0.28 per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2023c), a value that underscores the persistence of lethal violence rooted in relational and domestic dynamics and the need for earlier risk detection and decisive intervention.

On the legal and institutional front, Spain has long aligned with European standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on April 10, 2014, and entered it into force on August 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). This anchors the Spanish framework in the Council of Europe's reference instrument for preventing and combating violence against women. However, as the indicators above suggest, the implementation gap between formal guarantees and lived protection persists. Overall, Spain's situation is highly ambivalent. A mature legal-institutional architecture and broad awareness of available services coexist with enduring levels of physical and psychological violence, and recurrent lethal cases.

1.26.5 Political dimension

The political dimension provides an essential lens for examining how democracy, gender inequalities, and power relations interact in Spanish society. The emerging picture is that of a consolidated and resilient democracy, supported by high institutional legitimacy and active civic engagement but still marked by political fragmentation, moderate polarization, and uneven gender representation at the top levels of power.

Voter turnout remains a key indicator of democratic vitality. In the 2024 European elections, Spain recorded a turnout of 46.4%, close to the EU average (51%) (European Parliament 2024). Although lower than in national elections, this figure reflects a relatively stable level of civic participation and engagement with the European project, sustained by strong pro-European attitudes in the population.

Regarding gender representation, Spain performs well above the EU27 average. In 2024, women hold 44% of seats in the national parliament (EU: 33%), reflecting one of the most advanced gender-balanced legislatures in Europe (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). This progress is the result of sustained parity measures and an evolving political culture that has normalized women's presence in decision-making positions, both nationally and at the regional level.

According to ParlGov, in the 2019 Spanish general election, the Spanish Socialist Workers' Party (PSOE) emerged as the largest party, obtaining 28.0% of the vote. The People's Party (PP) followed with 20.8% of the vote. The far-right Vox consolidated its position as the third political force, securing 15.1% of the vote, confirming the normalization of radical right-wing politics in Spain's parliamentary landscape. Among regional and centrist forces, the

Republican Left of Catalonia (ERC) gained 3.6% of the vote, while the liberal Citizens (Ciudadanos, Cs) obtained only 6.8% of the vote (ParlGov 2023).

Overall, this distribution illustrates a fragmented yet structured party system, in which two large national parties (PSOE and PP) maintain over half of parliamentary representation, while new and regional actors exert increasing influence. The underrepresentation of centrist forces such as Ciudadanos and the territorial strength of ERC reveal the combined effects of Spain's provincial–district system and d'Hondt allocation method, which favor major and regionally concentrated parties. The resulting parliament reflects a plural and competitive democracy, in which coalition formation and cross-party agreements remain essential for government stability.

Trust in institutions reveals a complex picture. According to Eurobarometer, 27% of Spaniards express trust in the national government and 15% trust political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

Political interest remains substantial but not universal. Around 14.1% of Spaniards report being very interested in politics, while a significant minority remains detached or disenchanted with the political process (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Attitudinal data confirm strong support for democratic norms, but small minorities display tolerance toward illiberal options. According to the World Values Survey, 43.3% of Spaniards consider authoritarian alternatives “very bad”, but about 17.8% see them as “fairly good” (Haerpfer et al. 2024).

Polarization in Spain is moderate but rising. V-Dem assigns a polarization score of 2.45/4, reflecting growing ideological segmentation between left and right blocs and heightened identity-based conflict in political discourse (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Socioeconomic power distribution scores 2.63/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), indicating a concentration of influence in higher-income strata, while middle-class influence remains considerable.

Ideological orientations in Spain reveal a clear interaction between generation and gender, pointing to both age-related polarization and persistent gender asymmetries. Across generations, older cohorts show stronger alignment with the right and far right, while younger groups are more centrist or moderately left-leaning. Among men, identification with the right increases from 33.6% (≤ 35) to 42.5% (56+) and with the far right from 26.3% to

45.6%. Women follow a similar pattern—the right rises from 17.4% to 45.2%, and the far right increases from 22.0% to 46.3%. Younger groups display a more balanced ideological distribution, whereas older cohorts cluster at the extremes (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Across genders, women consistently show stronger identification with the center and the left, while men are more present on the right and the far right. Among Spaniards under 35 years old, the center attracts 52.7% of women and 50.0% of men, the left attracts 20.9% of women and 14.4% of men, and the right attracts 21.6% of men versus 10.0% of women. The far right remains predominantly male (7.2% of young men vs. 4.5% of young women). These gaps persist in older groups. Among those aged 56+, 7.6% of men and 5.0% of women are far right, while 16.5% of men and 14.4% of women identify with the right (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). Data indicate a gendered polarization intensified by age. Men lean more toward conservative and radical-right positions, while women concentrate around centrist and moderately left stances. Younger cohorts of both sexes are more dispersed and less anchored, suggesting that generational renewal may gradually soften ideological divides.

Taken together, these patterns depict Spain as a robust but complex democracy. Formal institutions are strong, and democratic norms enjoy broad support. However, moderate polarization, selective trust, and enduring generational and gender divides in political orientations point to a landscape in transition—one where commitment to democracy coexists with signs of institutional fatigue and ideological fragmentation.

I.26.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere is central to understanding political socialization, opinion formation, and the risks associated with disinformation and online radicalization. In Spain, the online ecosystem combines the widespread use of digital media for news and politics with uneven trust in sources and persistent gaps in media literacy, especially around the ability to recognize false or manipulative content.

The use of digital platforms for news is extensive. A large share of Spaniards report reading news online every day or almost every day (48%) (European Commission. Directorate

General for Communication. 2024a). This confirms the centrality of the internet—alongside television—in everyday news diets and in the formation of political attitudes.

Trust in online sources is mixed. Spaniards show higher trust in news from websites (34%) than from social networks (26%) (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). This distinction suggests that people differentiate between professional outlets and user-generated platforms while still granting notable credibility to online information, which leaves space for misleading content to circulate.

Disinformation is widely perceived as a democratic threat. A large majority (85%) consider false or distorted information a serious problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Self-reported exposure reinforces this perception—most respondents report encountering fake news at least sometimes, with only a small minority describing such exposure as rare or nonexistent (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This pattern points to a general awareness that disinformation is a persistent feature of the media environment.

Confidence in recognizing misleading content is moderate and uneven. Only 14% feel “very confident” in spotting disinformation, while a majority (52%) describe themselves as “somewhat confident”, and a sizable minority express low confidence (26% “not very confident” and 4% “not at all confident”) (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). These figures indicate that while most citizens believe they possess at least some ability to discern disinformation, relatively few feel fully secure in their skills. The high share of respondents expressing only partial or low confidence suggests a population aware of disinformation risks but not entirely equipped to evaluate the credibility of digital content.

Online radicalization and gendered hostility deserve specific attention. As documented for EU countries, Spain registers a nontrivial footprint of users engaging with misogynistic communities associated with the “manosphere” (e.g., incels.is) during 2017–2020 (31 users) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These environments blend anti-feminist narratives with anti-democratic frames, providing a vector for grievance politics, normalizing hostility to gender equality and, in some cases, amplifying offline risks. While the overall audience remains small relative to the population, its intensity and cross-platform diffusion warrant sustained monitoring and targeted prevention.

Taken together, Spain's digital environment has a double face. On the one hand, the internet and social media constitute powerful spaces for information access, participation, and public debate, and most people recognize the threat posed by disinformation. On the other hand, exposure to misleading content, limited detection skills, and the organized presence of misogynistic/anti-egalitarian communities pose concrete risks to the quality of public discussion and democratic resilience.

I.26.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion is a crucial gauge of democratic resilience and of a country's ability to guarantee equal opportunities to new generations. In Spain, the overall picture is broadly favorable in the relational and value dimensions, while structural fragilities persist in the transition to adulthood—in schooling continuity, labor market entry, and economic autonomy above all.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Spain is in the medium–high range among European countries (85.6) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). This reflects a mix of decent material conditions and positive perceptions of social inclusion among young people. A particularly strong point is openness to diversity. Spanish youth report high acceptance of immigrants (around 93%) and of gays and lesbians (around 91%), and they evaluate very positively the opportunity to make friends and build social networks (around 82%) (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022). These attitudes—typically more inclusive than those of the adult population—signal a generational orientation that is compatible with democratic pluralism and respect for rights and may, over time, reinforce civic trust and participation.

On the education–work axis, however, critical issues remain. Spain continues to register one of the highest levels of early school leaving in the EU, with a marked gender gap—in 2024, 15.8% of boys and 10.0% of girls aged 18–24 left education or training early (Eurostat 2024a).

Taken together, Spanish youth display robust social capital and pro-inclusion values, but they face structural constraints in converting these assets into effective agency—that is, the capacity to make consequential life choices with adequate resources and institutional support. Policies that consolidate schooling pathways, improve the quality and stability of first jobs,

and reduce territorial inequalities are therefore pivotal to turning Spain’s positive attitudinal profile into full participation and autonomy for younger generations.

I.26.8 Being socialized in Spain

Being socialized in Spain means growing up in a consolidated liberal democracy with strong gender-equality commitments and broadly inclusive social attitudes. Structural inequalities—especially those related to employment and economic security—continue to influence opportunities. While public support for equality is high, some stereotypes around authority, caregiving, and emotional roles persist. Younger cohorts endorse plural and egalitarian identities, and digital environments amplify both inclusive movements and misogynistic grievance narratives. In this setting, masculine gender norms in Spain develop through a combination of openness to diversity and persistent traces of family-centered and authority-oriented expectations.

I.27 SWEDEN

I.27.1 Socioeconomic structure and governance

Sweden’s socioeconomic and institutional framework is characterized by high levels of prosperity, comparatively low inequality, and a strong welfare system, reinforcing its position as one of Europe’s most socially cohesive contexts. Strong economic conditions coexist with an inclusive distribution of resources and a limited exposure of the population to poverty or social exclusion (Table 29).

Table 29 Socioeconomic conditions in Sweden compared with the EU27

	Sweden	EU27
GDP per capita in PPS	113.00	100.00
Gini coefficient	25.6	28.7
Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	17.5	21.4
Gender Equality Index (Money)	85.7	83.4
Gender Equality Index (Work)	85.0	74.2
Gender Equality Index (Knowledge)	76,1	64.2
Gender Equality Index (Health)	93.8	88.6

Source: GDP per Capita in PPS (Eurostat 2024c); Gini index (Eurostat 2024d); Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (Eurostat 2024f); Gender Equality Index dimension (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)

The labor market is characterized by high employment and narrow gender gaps. Among people aged 15–64 years, employment rates are 78.1% for men and 75.2% for women, both above EU averages (75.3% and 66.2%) (Eurostat 2024b). These figures underline Sweden’s success in integrating women into the labor force through extensive family support policies and flexible working arrangements.

Sweden ranks among the most gender-equal countries in Europe. It consistently performs very strongly across all dimensions of the Gender Equality Index, particularly in work, knowledge, and health (Table 29). The early school-leaving rate stands at 8.4% for men and 5.9% for women, indicating effective retention, but some gender variations could influence long-term labor participation.

The demographic structure is stable but aging. The old age dependency ratio (33.1) is close to the European average (33.9) (Eurostat 2024e), highlighting the gradual demographic transition typical of Nordic societies. The rural population accounts for 8.9%, reflecting Sweden’s high urbanization and strong concentration of economic activity in metropolitan regions (OECD 2023a). At the same time, the foreign-born population (20.6%) (Eurostat 2022) contributes significantly to demographic sustainability but also challenges social cohesion and labor market integration.

Welfare and social protection remain core pillars of Sweden’s institutional model. Social expenditure equals 26.1% of the GDP, ensuring broad access to education, healthcare, and income support (OECD 2024b). In sum, Sweden’s socioeconomic structure combines high living standards, strong gender equality, and institutional trust within a comprehensive welfare system.

I.27.2 European values and attitudes toward Europe

Sweden stands out in Europe for its deeply rooted democratic tradition, strong rule of law, and broad social consensus around equality, inclusion, and human rights. The country’s value framework reflects high institutional trust and social progress, combined with a firm commitment to gender equality and minority protection.

According to Freedom in the World, Sweden scores 93/100 in 2024, maintaining its classification as “Free” and confirming one of the highest levels of political and civil liberties worldwide (Freedom House 2025). The Democracy Index produced by the Economist

Intelligence Unit assigns 9.39/10, placing Sweden among the most advanced “full democracies” (Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024). The Rule of Law Index (0.96) (World Justice Project 2024) and Civil Liberties Index (0.86) (Varieties of Democracy 2024) attest to a political culture grounded in transparency, independence of the judiciary, and accountability. Together, these indicators portray a mature and resilient democracy in which the state and citizens maintain a high level of mutual trust.

Gender equality represents a cornerstone of Swedish society and policy. With an overall score of 82 on the Gender Equality Index—far above the EU average of 71—Sweden remains among Europe’s top performers (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). The country performs exceptionally well in time (85.8 vs. 68.5 for EU), reflecting a relatively balanced distribution of unpaid care work, and in power (85.0 vs. 61.4 for EU), demonstrating strong female representation in politics and decision-making (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Sweden also ranks among the most progressive European countries in terms of inclusiveness and minority rights. MIPEX assigns a score of 100, among the highest in the EU, reflecting comprehensive integration policies and equal access to education, employment, and health services (MIPEX 2023). The Rainbow Europe Index positions Sweden at the top of the EU ranking with 66/100, indicating a legislative framework protecting LGBTQI+ rights, including recognition of same-sex couples and protection against hate crimes (ILGA-Europe 2025).

Attitudes toward the EU are generally positive and consistent with Sweden’s internationalist orientation. About 53% of Swedes express trust in the European Parliament (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c). Overall, Sweden’s value landscape reflects one of the most consolidated democratic systems in Europe—characterized by equality, pluralism, and institutional trust. Gender equality and minority inclusion are not only formal principles but also central components of civic identity. The remaining challenges concern the integration of migrant populations and the persistence of subtle inequalities in power and representation. Nevertheless, Sweden continues to embody a model of democratic resilience and social cohesion grounded in freedom, equality, and shared responsibility.

I.27.3 Gender norms

Gender norms and cultural attitudes in Sweden display one of the most progressive profiles in Europe, marked by widespread support for equality, inclusive conceptions of gender roles, and a sustained rejection of traditional hierarchies between men and women. However, even in this highly egalitarian context, subtle ambivalence persists, particularly regarding the distribution of care work and perceptions of feminism.

Based on Eurobarometer data, Figure 50 shows family-role attitudes with a strong cultural consensus in favor of dual-earner, dual-carer models (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This indicates a broad normalization of women’s full participation in the labor market and the near-complete erosion of traditional gender expectations in family life.

Figure 50 Agreement with gender norm statements (%) in Sweden

Source: Eurobarometer (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)

Perceptions of inequality in the workplace point to an awareness of structural discrimination—59% of Swedes believe that men are treated better than women at work (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). This acknowledgment of persistent inequality coexists with high expectations of gender balance in

decision-making—83% consider that gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful. Symbolic stereotypes have been largely eroded but not entirely eliminated. These figures, among the lowest in the EU, nevertheless indicate that cultural biases concerning women’s leadership capacity endure in a minority segment of the population (Figure 50).

Norms related to masculinity reveal Sweden’s exceptional degree of cultural liberalization—98% of respondents agree that “it is acceptable for a man to cry” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). Similarly, only 4% maintain that “men taking parental leave show a lack of ambition”, while 2% think that “men should have the final say in important family decisions” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024). These very low figures signal that hegemonic masculinity models emphasizing control and authority have lost much of their normative force. Still, 34% of respondents consider that “feminism has gone too far” (European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024), showing that egalitarian consensus occasionally triggers defensive reactions, particularly among men.

In Sweden, attitudes toward sexual and gender equality are among the most egalitarian in Europe, with minimal generational conflict. Support for the statement that gays and lesbians should be free to live as they wish exceeds 93% among men and 95–98% among women in all age groups, and disagreement is virtually absent. In the cohort-based tables, older respondents appear more neutral (up to 69% of men and 76% of women over 56), suggesting disengagement rather than opposition (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

More variation appears in perceptions of sexual harassment. When viewed across cohorts, men and women show increased polarization with age. Among men, “never/rarely” rises from 22.9% (≤ 35) to 43.3% (> 56) but “often/always” also grows dramatically (15.2% to 60.6%). Women follow a similar pattern (20% to 60%). However, the gender comparison table shows that skepticism is actually very low among younger Swedes, with 74% of young men and 83% of young women rejecting exaggeration, and only 4–7% endorsing “often/always”. This confirms that distrust toward harassment claims is confined to a small older minority (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Attitudes toward female power show similar age-related ambivalence rather than widespread hostility. Among men, “never/rarely” rises from 23.8% to 45.8% across age groups, but “often/always” also increases (23.3% to 56.7%). Women show parallel trends. However, among the youngest, most respondents reject the stereotype—54.6% of young men and 60.2% of young women say it “never/rarely” happens, and only 6–12% say “often/always” (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

The strongest traditionalism emerges around paternalistic protection. Among men, endorsement of “often/always” rises from 14.5% (≤ 35) to 54.0% (> 56), and among women, it rises from 19.2% to 45.7%. At the same time, rejection also increases with age, showing clear polarization. Gender differences are notable—younger women are more likely than men to endorse protection (46.2% vs. 33.6%), while men are consistently more likely to reject it (“never/rarely”: 19–23% vs. 8–14%) (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025). These figures suggest that some women interpret protection as care rather than hierarchy, even in an otherwise highly egalitarian context.

Taken together, these patterns portray Sweden as a country in which support for gender and sexual equality is exceptionally high, although not entirely uniform across age and gender. Support for same-sex rights is nearly universal, while beliefs about gender dynamics—especially regarding power and protection—retain some generational nuances. Younger respondents tend to express more individualistic and egalitarian attitudes, whereas older respondents combine egalitarianism with traces of traditional values. Gender differences, although limited, remain meaningful. Women consistently display stronger trust and solidarity toward other women, particularly concerning sexual harassment, while men express slightly more ambivalence about issues of power and protection. Overall, the findings reflect a society in which overt prejudice is rare, but the legacies of gendered expectations persist subtly, especially among older generations.

I.27.4 Gender-based violence and institutional response

Gender-based violence in Sweden remains a structural problem that affects democratic quality and the full enjoyment of fundamental rights, even in a country with one of Europe’s most advanced legal and institutional frameworks. Prevalence data indicate that the phenomenon is neither marginal nor confined to isolated cases. According to recent EU

surveys, 52.5% of Swedish women report having experienced physical and/or sexual violence by any perpetrator since the age of 15, while 48.2% of ever-partnered women report psychological, physical (including threats) and/or sexual violence by a current or former partner (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024). These figures, among the highest reported in Europe, suggest both a broad diffusion of abusive dynamics and a comparatively high ability to recognize and name non-physical forms of violence.

Knowledge of rights and access to support are comparatively strong but not complete. Awareness of the existence of support services is extremely high—around 89.7% of women (Eurostat 2021b)—but awareness of the right to free legal aid is much lower (about 52.5%) (Eurostat 2021a). This gap points to a translation problem between the general knowledge that “help exists” and concrete awareness of specific entitlements, with potential consequences for victims’ willingness and ability to seek remedies, particularly among the most vulnerable.

Sweden’s Gender Equality Index score is quite low (37.4), reflecting elevated self-reported prevalence, which indicates that policy capacity and social norms do not always translate into effective prevention in everyday life (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). Legally and institutionally, Sweden is fully aligned with European standards. It signed the Istanbul Convention on May 11, 2011, ratified it on July 1, 2014, and entered it into force nationally on November 1, 2014 (Council of Europe 2025). Despite this advanced framework—and extensive welfare and criminal justice support—the persistence of high prevalence and the information gap on legal entitlements show that implementation remains the key challenge.

Overall, Sweden presents a paradoxical configuration—strong institutions, high service awareness, and robust equality norms coexist with enduring levels of partner and non-partner violence. Closing the gap between rights on paper and effective protection requires sustained investments in early prevention, systematic risk assessment, and rights communication strategies that make concrete entitlements (such as free legal aid) visible and usable for all survivors.

1.27.5 Political dimension

The political dimension in Sweden offers a clear window into how strong democratic institutions, high civic trust, and gender equality interact within one of Europe’s most stable

political systems. Sweden's democracy combines formal robustness with extensive citizen participation, high institutional legitimacy, and comparatively low polarization—even though challenges related to political fragmentation and the rise of populist movements have emerged in recent years.

Voter turnout remains one of the highest in Europe. In the 2024 European elections, participation has reached 53.39%, above the EU average of 51% (European Parliament 2024). In terms of gender representation, Sweden continues to rank among the top performers globally—47% of the members of parliament are women, far surpassing the EU average (33%) (European Institute for Gender Equality 2024), and gender parity is a longstanding structural feature of Swedish political life.

In the 2022 national elections, Sweden's political landscape reflected both stability and fragmentation within its mature democratic system. The Social Democrats remained the largest political force, securing 30.3% of the vote. The Sweden Democrats consolidated its position as the country's main right-wing populist party, capturing 20.5% of the vote—a historic result confirming their transformation from a marginal to a mainstream political actor. The Moderate Party followed closely with 19.1% of the vote, maintaining its role as a central force within the traditional right (ParlGov 2023).

This configuration produced a highly competitive and polarized parliament, with the center-left bloc led by the Social Democrats narrowly losing ground to a right-wing coalition, including the Moderates and the Sweden Democrats. The results underscore Sweden's transition toward a more fragmented party system, in which coalition-building and ideological negotiation are increasingly required to ensure stable governance.

Institutional indicators confirm the exceptional quality of Swedish democracy. The V-Dem Electoral Democracy Index assigns Sweden 0.88 (Varieties of Democracy 2024). Levels of trust in political institutions are strikingly high according to international standards. According to recent surveys, 45% of Swedes express trust in the national government, whereas 37% show trust in political parties (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c).

When asked about the idea of “having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections”, a clear majority of respondents in Sweden expressed rejection of

such an undemocratic model—54.1% considered it very bad and 24.4% thought it was fairly bad, while only a small minority viewed it positively (4.6% very good and 14.3% fairly good) (Haerpfer et al. 2024). These figures point to a strong attachment to parliamentary democracy and widespread resistance to authoritarian alternatives, confirming Sweden’s deeply rooted democratic culture and institutional trust. Interest in politics is relatively high in Sweden. In 2023, 21.8% of respondents described themselves as very interested and 47.3% as quite interested in politics, while only 25.4% were hardly interested, and 5.5% were not at all interested (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Sweden also stands out for low levels of political polarization and violence. The V-Dem Political Polarization Index places it at 1.83/4 (Varieties of Democracy 2024), among the least polarized democracies in Europe, and tolerance for political violence is minimal. Power distribution across social classes is more balanced than elsewhere in Europe. With a score of 2.85/4, socioeconomic power is relatively dispersed, reflecting Sweden’s egalitarian legacy and strong welfare institutions (Varieties of Democracy 2024).

Ideological orientations in Sweden show consistent generational and gender differences. Across cohorts, alignment with the center grows steadily with age for both sexes, reaching around 45–48% among older respondents. Younger men are more evenly distributed, with a stronger inclination toward the right (28%) and far right (5.7%), while younger women lean more toward the left (28%) and far left (14%). Among older cohorts, both men and women display higher levels of identification with the center and left, but men remain more concentrated on the right (26–27%), whereas women are more evenly split between the left (25%) and center (45%). In sum, men are more likely to identify with conservative and radical right positions, while women consistently align with progressive and egalitarian positions. The center remains the largest ideological cluster in Sweden for both genders, but gendered polarization persists—men lean rightward, women leftward, and the generational divide suggests that younger Swedes are slightly more dispersed ideologically, reflecting a plural and fluid political landscape (European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025).

Overall, Sweden’s political landscape embodies a mature and inclusive democracy characterized by strong participation, institutional stability, and high trust in governance. Gender equality is fully integrated into political life, and polarization remains low. However,

the gradual normalization of nationalist discourse and the growing complexity of coalition politics suggest emerging challenges.

I.27.6 Digitalization and online behavior

The digital sphere in Sweden represents a cornerstone of social life, political communication, and civic engagement, reflecting one of the most technologically advanced and interconnected societies in Europe. Sweden's high levels of internet penetration, digital literacy, and institutional transparency provide a favorable environment for democratic participation and informed debate. At the same time, these conditions coexist with new challenges linked to disinformation, online polarization, and the spread of gendered or extremist narratives.

The Swedish digital environment is characterized by widespread engagement with online information, high awareness of disinformation risks, and moderate levels of trust in digital media.

According to recent Eurobarometer data, 69% of Swedes read online news daily or almost daily, and another 10% do so several times a week, confirming the centrality of digital platforms in Sweden's information ecosystem (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a). Trust, however, remains limited—only 28% tend to trust news websites, and just 9% trust information found on social networks.

Awareness of online manipulation is nearly universal. About 94% agree that false or misleading information is a problem for democracy (European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022). Perceived exposure is lower—only 5% feel they encounter fake news very often, 12% encounter it often, and 35% are faced with fake news sometimes (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This suggests that while Swedes recognize disinformation as a systemic threat, many underestimate their personal exposure.

Confidence in identifying misleading content is moderate but comparatively strong—15% feel very confident, 56% feel somewhat confident, 20% are not very confident, and 5% are not at all confident (European Parliament, Brussels 2022). This combination of high awareness, intensive digital use, and moderate critical confidence portrays a population engaged with online information but still facing challenges in navigating manipulative content.

Sweden's digital sphere combines high usage, cautious trust, and broad recognition of disinformation risks, reinforcing the need for continued investment in media literacy and critical digital competences.

The Swedish online environment is also affected by the dynamics of gendered hostility and digital extremism, although at lower levels than in most EU countries. Between 2017 and 2020, users based in Sweden were identified on misogynist forums, such as incels.is (51 users), a key node of the transnational “manosphere” (European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021). These online communities disseminate anti-feminist, homophobic, and anti-democratic rhetoric, often blending narratives of male victimization with broader distrust toward institutions and liberal values. Although their absolute size remains limited, their visibility illustrates the potential for online radicalization to infiltrate even highly egalitarian societies. In sum, Sweden stands as a model of digital modernity and participatory communication, but it faces the same structural tensions that mark advanced democracies—balancing openness and freedom with the protection of truth, equality, and democratic integrity in the digital public sphere.

I.27.7 Youth agency

Youth inclusion in Sweden represents a central pillar of democratic resilience and social cohesion. The country's longstanding investments in equality, education, and welfare translate into high levels of youth well-being and participation, while new challenges emerge concerning socioeconomic independence, mental health, and political engagement.

According to the Youth Progress Index, Sweden ranks among the top performers in Europe, with a score of 89.59/100 (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022), reflecting advanced material conditions, robust institutional inclusion, and strong civic participation. Swedish youth benefit from one of the most comprehensive welfare and educational systems globally, ensuring broad access to education, healthcare, and social rights. However, inequalities persist between native-born and foreign-born youth, particularly in labor market entry and long-term economic security.

Openness and inclusion are defining features of Sweden's younger generations. Data indicate that 90% of young Swedes consider their country a “good place for immigrants”, and 94% say the same for gay and lesbian people (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum

2022). These scores, among the highest in Europe, reveal a markedly cosmopolitan orientation and a strong commitment to diversity, tolerance, and equal treatment. Likewise, 82% of young people report having good opportunities to make friends, reflecting dense social networks and a positive relational climate that fosters trust and collective belonging (Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022).

In terms of education and training, Sweden performs well above the European average. The share of early school leavers stands at 8.4% among boys and 5.9% among girls, confirming both the effectiveness of the educational system and the relatively small gender gap (Eurostat 2024a).

Overall, Swedish youth are among the most socially integrated and equality-oriented in Europe. They combine high levels of openness to diversity and strong social capital with ongoing struggles related to material autonomy and long-term economic stability.

1.27.8 Being socialized in Sweden

Being socialized in Sweden means growing up in one of the most egalitarian and institutionally robust societies in Europe, where democratic values and gender equality are deeply internalized. Shared caregiving, gender-balanced leadership, and emotional openness form part of everyday expectations. Nonetheless, demographic diversification and digital polarization introduce new sources of tension, and pockets of defensive reactions to feminism still appear. Young people grow up with strong normative expectations of autonomy and inclusion but face pressures related to economic security and mental health. Consequently, masculine gender norms in Sweden reflect deeply rooted egalitarian ideals while still negotiating identity, vulnerability, and authority in a rapidly evolving social landscape.

APPENDIX I. LIST OF INDICATORS BY DIMENSION

Table 30 List of Indicators by Dimension

Dimension	Sub-Dimension	Indicator	Unit of measure	Source	Note
Socioeconomic Structure and Inequalities	Economic Structure and Inequality	GDP per capita (PPS, volume index, EU=100)	Index (EU=100)	(Eurostat 2024c)	Volume index of GDP per capita in Purchasing Power Standards. >100 above EU average; <100 below.
		Gini coefficient (equivalised disposable income)	Index (0-100)	(Eurostat 2024d)	The Gini coefficient measures the inequality among the values of the frequency distribution of income levels. Higher values indicate more inequality.
		Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (AROPE)	% of population	(Eurostat 2024f)	Refers to individuals who are at risk of poverty, severely materially and socially deprived, or living in households with very low work intensity.
		Employment rate (15-64)	% of population 15-64	(Eurostat 2024b)	Share of the population of the same age group (15–64) who are employed
		Gender Equality Index - Money	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in financial resources.
		Gender Equality Index - Work	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in work participation/segregation/quality.
	Education and Human Capital	Gender Equality Index - Knowledge	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in education & training.
		Gender Equality Index - Time	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in care, domestic work, and social activities.
		Gender Equality Index - Power	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in decision-making across political/economic/social domains.
		Gender Equality Index - Health	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality in health status, behaviours, access.
		Gender Equality Index - Total	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Overall score across domains. Higher scores indicate higher levels of gender equality.
		Tertiary field segregation (Education);	%	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Sex segregation among tertiary students; can compute a segregation index or report % distribution.

	Health & Welfare; Humanities & Arts)	Graduates in tertiary education (STEM+ related), by sex	Per 1,000 population aged 20-29	(Eurostat 2023b)	Science, mathematics, computing, engineering, manufacturing & construction.	
		Graduates in tertiary education by level - women per 100 men	Women per 100 men	(Eurostat 2023a)	Female graduates relative to male graduates at specified ISCED level.	
		Early leavers from education and training	% of 18-24	(Eurostat 2024a)	Percentage of the population aged 18 to 24 having attained at most lower secondary education and not being involved in further education or training.	
		Demography and Spatial Distribution	Population by urban-rural typology - Rural	% of population	(OECD 2023)	Share living in rural areas.
	Welfare and Access to Social Services	Old-age dependency ratio	% (65+ as % of 15-64)	(Eurostat 2024e)	Population aged 65+ relative to working age (15-64).	
		Foreign-born population	% of population	(Eurostat 2022)	Residents born outside the reporting country.	
		Social protection expenditure	% of GDP	(OECD 2024b)	Total social protection expenditure as a share of GDP.	
	European Values	Governance, Rights, and Freedoms	Paternal leave, length	Number of days or weeks	(OECD 2024a)	Statutory length of paternity/paternal leave.
			Paternal leave, average payment	% of previous earnings	(OECD 2024a)	Average payment rate or replacement rate for paternal leave.
			Freedom in the World Index	Index (0-100)	(Freedom House 2025)	Aggregate score of political rights & civil liberties. Higher scores indicate greater freedom.
Democracy Index (EIU)			Index (0-10)	(Economist Intelligence Unit; processed by Our World in Data 2024)	Overall democracy score and regime type. Higher scores indicate greater democracy.	
		Rule of Law Index	Index (0-1)	(World Justice Project 2024)	Perceptions & experiences across eight factors of rule of law.	
		Civil Liberties	Index (0-100)	(Varieties of Democracy 2024)	Civil Liberties sub-score; higher = more liberties.	

	Pluralism and Inclusion	Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI)	Index (0-100)	(OECD 2023b)	Measures discriminatory social institutions in four dimensions: discrimination in the family; restricted physical integrity; restricted access to productive and financial resources; restricted civil liberties.. Higher scores indicate more social and institutional discrimination.
		Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) - Measures policies to integrate migrants	Index (0-100)	(MIPEX 2023)	Measures government policies to integrate migrants. Higher scores indicate more inclusive policies.
		Hate speech/hate crime laws	Index (0-100)	(OECD 2023b)	Existence/scope of hate speech & hate crime provisions covering sexual orientation and/or gender identity. The index ranges from 0 to 100, where 0 indicates no discrimination and 100 indicates absolute discrimination.
		Rainbow Europe Index	Index (0-100)	(ILGA-Europe 2025)	Legal & policy benchmarking on LGBTI equality. Higher scores indicate more equality.
	Trust in European Institutions and Democratic Legitimacy	Trust in the European Parliament- trust	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
		European unification - go further vs gone too far	%	(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
	Gender norms	Domestic Sphere	Women should prioritise family over career - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)
Family life suffers when mother has a full-time job - agree			%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
Perceived unequal treatment of women vs men at work			% è	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	Share saying women and men are treated differently at work.

	Public Sphere	Gender-balanced leadership teams are more successful - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Women exaggerate claims of sexual harassment	%	(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% distribution by age group and gender (“never/rarely, “sometimes”, “often/always”).
		How often women seek to gain power by getting control over men	%	(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% distribution by age group and gender (“never/rarely, “sometimes”, “often/always”).
		How often women should be protected by men	%	(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% distribution by age group and gender (“never/rarely, “sometimes”, “often/always”).
		Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish	%	(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% distribution by age group and gender (“never/rarely, “sometimes”, “often/always”).
		Prefer male or female political leader	%	(King’s Global Institute for Women’s Leadership and Ipsos 2024)	Prefer male / female / no preference.
		Men make better leaders than women - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Women are too emotional to be good leaders - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Women in leadership lack authority to be taken seriously - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).

		Unattractive for women to express strong opinions in public - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
Masculine gender norms / belief		It is acceptable for men to cry - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		For important family decisions men should have final say - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Men naturally less competent at household tasks - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Men taking parental leave show lack of ambition - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		If father earns less, he should be the one to stop working to care - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Men more ambitious than women in politics - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
	anti-gender equality views	Feminism has gone too far - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Justice and Consumers. 2024)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
Gender-Based Violence and	Gender-Based Violence	Ever-partnered women experiencing IPV	% of women 18-74 (by type)	(European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024)	Experience of violence by intimate partners.

Institutional Response	(Experience & Awareness)	(psychological/physical/sexual)			
		Women experiencing violence by any perpetrator (any type)	% of women 18-74	(European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. et al. 2024)	Any psychological, physical or sexual violence.
		Awareness of free legal aid among victims/non-victims	% Aware	(Eurostat 2021a)	Awareness of legal aid availability.
		Awareness of support services among victims/non-victims	% Aware	(Eurostat 2021b)	Awareness of support services for GBV.
		Female homicide rate by intimate partner/family member	Per 100,000 women	Eurostat crime statistics / UNODC	Annual intentional homicide rate of female victims by IP/family.
		Gender Equality Index - Violence	Index (0-100)	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Measures violence against women; not aggregated into the overall EGEI score.
	Institutional Legal Framework	Ratification of the Istanbul Convention	Status (Yes/No/Year)	(Council of Europe 2025)	Ratification and entry-into-force status.
Political Dimension	Electoral Participation and Behavior	European Parliament elections 2024 - turnout	% of registered voters	(European Parliament 2024)	Official turnout by country.
		Share of female members of parliament	% of MPs	(European Institute for Gender Equality 2024)	Share of female members of parliament.
		Share of far-right party (vote or seats)	% vote / % seats	(ParlGov 2023)	The Parliaments and Governments Database (ParlGov) is a data infrastructure with information about EU and OECD democracies (1900–2023). 1700 parties, 1000 elections (9800 results), and 1600 cabinets (4000 parties).
		Electoral democracy index	Index (0-1)	(Varieties of Democracy 2024)	Captures the extent to which the ideal of electoral democracy is achieved. The index combines measures of freedom of expression, association, suffrage, clean elections, and elected officials. Scores range from 0 (no electoral democracy) to 1 (fully achieved electoral democracy). Computed as the mean between a weighted additive and a multiplicative aggregation, balancing partial compensation among components and the “weakest link”

					principle. High values indicate competitive, free, and fair elections, broad suffrage, and free media and civil society.
	Trust in political parties - trust	%		(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
	Trust in national government - trust	%		(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024c)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
Trust in Political Institutions	Interest in politics	%		(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% of people expressing interest (“very interested” + “fairly interested”).
	Strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections - agree	% good/very good		(Haerpfer et al. 2024)	% of people reporting “good” or “very good”.
Interest and Attitudes toward Politics	Placement on left-right scale (self-placement)	0-10		(European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC) 2025)	% distribution by age group and gender (“far left” 0–1, “left” 2–3, “center” 4–6, “right” 7–8, “far right” 9–10).
	Political violence	Index (0-4)		(Varieties of Democracy 2024)	Measures the extent to which non-state actors (individuals or groups not formally part of the state) use physical force to achieve political objectives. Excludes profit-driven or crime-related violence. Includes militias and politically oriented youth groups, even if informally linked to ruling parties. Psychological or symbolic violence (e.g. destruction of objects) is not included. Higher values indicate more frequent or severe political violence.
	Power distributed by socioeconomic position	Index (0-4)		(Varieties of Democracy 2024)	Captures the extent to which economic inequality (wealth and income) translates into political power. Focuses not on the degree of inequality itself but on its political effects, i.e. how much wealth and income influence political decision-making and access to power. Higher scores indicate stronger influence of wealth on politics.
Polarization and Political Violence	Political polarization	Index (0-4)		(Varieties of Democracy 2024)	Measures the extent to which political differences affect social relationships beyond political discussions. Societies are

					considered highly polarized when supporters of opposing political camps avoid friendly or cooperative interactions (e.g. in families, associations, leisure, or workplaces). Higher values indicate stronger social segregation along political lines.
Digitalization and Online Behavior	Internet Use, Trust in Digital Media, and Disinformation	Trust in websites as a news source - trust	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
		Trust in online social networks - tend to trust	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a)	% of people expressing total trust (“tend to trust” + “trust completely”).
		Read news on the Internet	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. 2024a)	% distribution (“Everyday/Almost everyday”, “Two or three times a week”, “About once a week”, “Two or three times a month”, “Less often”, “Never”).
		Disinformation is a problem for democracy - agree	%	(European Commission. Directorate General for Communication. and Kantar. 2022)	% of people expressing agreement (“agree”+“strongly agree”).
		Self-reported exposure to disinformation (last 7 days)	%	(European Parliament, Brussels 2022)	% distribution (“Very often”, “Often”, “Sometimes”, “Rarely”, “Never”).
		Confidence in recognising disinformation	%	(European Parliament, Brussels 2022)	% distribution (“Very confident”, “Somewhat confident”, “Not very confident”, “Not at all confident”).
	Manosphere spread	Number of incels.is users (by country)	Count	(European Commission, Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs 2021)	Data was collected by Moonshot from incels.is (formerly incels.co), the largest anglophone incel online community, from October 2017 to October2020. Demographic information was not available for users. Instead, keyword selectors such as “I live in” or “I am from” were used and paired with European countries to identify comments from the incels.co data set that mentioned both a location indicator phrase and a European country name.
Youth Agency	Structural Dimension	Young women 25-29 with 12-18 years of education	%	(Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)	% of young women aged 25-29 who have attained 12-18 years of education.

Perceptual Dimension	Openness towards immigrants (youth 15-29)	%	(Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)	Based on the percentage of respondents aged 15–29 answering “good place” to the question: “Is the city or area where you live a good place or not a good place to live for immigrants from other countries?” Higher values indicate stronger perceived inclusiveness toward immigrants.
	Opportunity to make friends (youth 15-29)	%	(Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)	Based on the percentage of respondents aged 15–29 answering “satisfied” to the question: “In the city or area where you live, are you satisfied or dissatisfied with the opportunities to meet people and make friends?” Higher values indicate stronger perceived social connectedness.
	Youth Index	0-100	(Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)	Measure of the quality of life of young people around the world.
	Acceptance of gays and lesbians (youth 15-29)	%	(Social Progress Imperative; European Youth Forum 2022)	Based on the percentage of respondents aged 15–29 answering “yes” to the question: “Is the city or area where you live a good place or not a good place to live for gay or lesbian people?” Higher values indicate greater local acceptance and perceived inclusiveness.

